

**Young adults' Mental health experiences in different cultures in
the digital age: Case of Algeria and the United Kingdom**

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of the West of Scotland for Doctorate degree in Psychology.**

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Declaration

I certify that this thesis has been written by me and is my own work except where explicitly stated otherwise. I further declare that it has not been submitted for any other degree or professional qualification.

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Abstract

Young adults globally are encountering various mental health challenges during the transition from adolescence to young adulthood. Their perceptions and experiences of mental health within diverse cultural contexts influence their understanding of cultural factors effects on mental health, the use of services, and their views on optimal mental health and quality of life within the context of their wider social environment. This study aimed to compare the mental health experiences of young adults in different cultures in the digital age, exploring cultural factors that impact the understanding, management, and treatment of mental health. A qualitative research framework was implemented, incorporating semi-structured interviews and qualitative surveys with 12 young adult participants and 30 religious' leaders from Algeria and the United Kingdom. Participants were recruited through in-person and via social media platforms. Data were analysed using thematic analysis, leading to the identification of several key themes.

Results highlighted the importance of mental health literacy within Algerian society, elucidating factors that facilitate or impede mental health in both cultural settings, including the influence of social media on the mental well-being of young adults. This primary investigation led to a subsequent study focusing on the Islamic therapeutic perspectives of imams regarding mental health and their roles within Muslim communities across different cultural contexts. This follow-up study examined the involvement of imams in advancing mental health awareness among Muslims in both cultures, their preparedness when community members seek their assistance, their approach to addressing mental health concerns, and their collaboration with professionals in critical situations to develop suitable mental health interventions tailored to young adults from varied cultural backgrounds

Chapter 01: Overview

1.1 Introduction

This chapter begins with a brief overview of the motivation and purpose of this study, which provides information on different social and cultural backgrounds concerning the symptoms of young adults' mental health and a summary of known linkages between using digital technology and mental health of young people. The rationale for the study comprises of explaining the reasons for poor mental health and how to communicate emotions during late adolescence. The chapter ends with a summary of the following chapter.

1.2 Motivation of the research study

This research is motivated by the growing prevalence of mental health problems among teenagers and young adults in Arab countries particularly in Algerian society. Many young people are struggling with mental health difficulties since talking about them in Algerian culture is still primarily a taboo topic. The dominant Arab Islamic research suggests individual's attitudes toward formal mental health services are negative (Aloud & Rathur, 2009). This is particularly relevant in the Arab countries, where psychological problems are not considered to require professional help, and people who seek help are often not representative of wider society and they tend to be more seriously affected and often have comorbid diagnosis (Dardas and Simmons, 2015). Engaging with religious and community leaders or traditional healers is frequently the first step taken to help individuals experiencing mental health challenges (Youssef and Deane, 2006; Aloud and Rathur, 2009). Religious leaders are usually more readily available and willing to help individuals experiencing a crisis, and seeking their assistance is considered a less stigmatising and shameful action compared to

seeking professional help (Youssef & Deane 2006). There hasn't been a lot of research conducted on mental health in the Arab world, particularly in Algeria. According to Maalouf et al. (2019) although mental disorders are a predominant contributor to disability in the Arab region, encompassing 5.54% of the global population, it is noteworthy that Arab nations contribute merely 1.0% to the worldwide production of peer-reviewed publications in the field of mental health research. In this regard, this work sought to better understand the factors contributing to positive or negative outcomes in mental health between Western (United Kingdom) and Arab (Algeria) cultural expectations and norms in this specific age group (18-24). By exploring how individuals from these regions reflect on and express their mental health within their cultural frameworks, the study seeks to uncover the cultural mechanisms that influence perceptions and behaviours surrounding mental health. Such insights may inform strategies for improving interventions by recognizing how mental health is understood and managed across different cultural norms and expectations (Jang et al., 2007). While mental health issues may be diagnosed and experienced differently across cultures, this research prioritizes cultural and societal factors over racial or ethnic distinctions, ensuring a more inclusive examination of mental health perceptions and practices.

The rationale for comparing these two cultures centres on the cultural aspects of western attitudes. These may play a significant role in developing a stronger approach in overcoming mental health challenges in Algeria. In addition, the significance of social media in expressing and supporting their mental health concerns is discussed. The Islamic perspective of mental health gives significance to understanding the overriding patterns of behaviour, goals, feelings, intellect, emotions, thoughts, spiritual values, human conflict, and mental anguish as a whole lifestyle of an individual (Farooqi, 2006). A common misconception in Western societies is that Muslims believe mental illnesses are caused by demons or bad spirits. While such beliefs were historically prevalent in many cultures, including medieval Europe, Islamic scholars such

as Ibn Sina (Avicenna) rejected supernatural explanations for mental disorders. In contrast, they viewed mental health issues as primarily stemming from physiological and psychological factors (Youssef & Youssef, 1996; Haque, 2004). While traditional beliefs in demonic influences are no longer widely held, some individuals within Muslim communities may still adhere to cultural superstitions that complicate their understanding of mental health.

Understanding both Islamic and Western psychology allows the researcher to explore the similarities and differences between the Western evidence-based modern scientific methods of treatment for mental health issues and religious-cultural traditional methods of the Muslim world (Farooqi, 2006). In this study, the terms 'Muslim' and 'Islamic' refer to individuals who identify with the Islamic faith. However, it is important to note that the Muslim world is diverse, encompassing a wide range of cultural practices, beliefs, and interpretations of Islam. 'Islamic psychology' refers to the body of thought rooted in Islamic principles. It represents a dynamic and evolving field that integrates spiritual, moral, and cognitive dimensions of human experience, drawing from Islamic teachings. This study emphasizes the well-being of the soul, or 'ruh', and personal growth aligned with ethical values derived from the Qur'an and Hadith. In the context of mental health, Islamic counselling, a psychosocial model, shares similarities with Western counselling in that individuals seek assistance from qualified professionals to address psychological concerns. However, in Islamic contexts, such support may also be effectively provided by religious leaders, such as Imams (Ali et al., 2005). This research focuses on exploring the broader Islamic cultural framework rather than examining specific denominations, aiming to capture a more holistic understanding of how Islamic principles and practices influence mental health across diverse Muslim communities. Islam is practiced in various ways across different regions and cultures, and this study acknowledges the diversity within the Muslim world. It avoids overgeneralization by recognizing that mental health

practices may differ, for instance, between Muslims in Algeria and those in other parts of the world

Conversely, 'Western psychology' generally refers to psychological theories and practices that have developed within predominantly Western, secular contexts, often focusing on individualism, cognitive-behavioural therapy, and evidence-based methods. Farooqi (2006) stated that the Western culture favours individualism, materialism, change, and competition, whereas the Islamic perspective favours collectivism, spirituality, religion, stability, morality, sharing, and caring for the development of well-adjusted individuals and healthy societies (Farooqi, 1983; Iqbal, 1984; Rizvi, 1994; Moghaddam & Marsella, 2004). More broadly, valid psychology will develop through understanding what is culturally distinctive in mainstream psychology and adopting new concepts from other cultures that have broader applicability (Azuma, 2007). In addition, the significance of social media in expressing and supporting young adults' mental health concerns is discussed.

1.3 Purpose of the study

Every culture has its own way of understanding mental health based on a set of beliefs and practices, such as expressing, experiencing, coping, seeking treatment and dealing with stigma and discrimination. Understanding mental health issues in different cultures can play a key role in terms of how mental health problems are managed started from the implications for mental health practices, the ways people view health and illness, to treatment seeking patterns. The proposed study aims to explore the cultural differences in experiencing and expressing mental health issues among Algerian and UK's young adults. Moreover, this research project seeks to gain a better understanding of the role social media plays as a potentially viable intervention for those struggling with poor mental health by understanding how young people talk about their mental health through social media. In addition, how they might use social media as a

means of peer support that could provide significant input into developing tools to improve mental health outcomes in this population. Social media is often seen as a safe place for young people to voice concerns about their health potentially removing the stigma talking about these issues. Boyd (2014) reported that they frequently turning to sites such as Facebook and Twitter to escape from the external pressures threatening their mental health. Although social media may be facilitating new forms of communication and social connection (Baker & Moore, 2008), there were always fears about the negative effects on young people.

The research reported primarily began with study 1, which investigated young adults' mental health experiences in Algeria and the UK in the digital age. Following study 1, a second follow-up study, study 2, was conducted to address research questions arising from the first study.

1.4 Research questions

Study 1

This research discussed the following research questions:

1. How do young adults experience and express mental health challenges in Algeria and United Kingdom.
2. How do cultural and societal factors affect young people's mental health.
3. What role social media can play in communicating mental health challenges of young people.

Study 2

1. What is the imam's role in counselling Muslims with mental health issues?
2. What types of referrals do imams offer to Muslims suffering from mental illnesses and how do they provide support?

1.5 Rationale of the study

Many mental health issues emerge adolescent period and young adulthood between the ages of 14-24. Globally, 20% of young people experience mental disorders (Gaiha et al., 2020). 50% of mental health issues are established by the age of 14, and 75% by age 24 (Polaris Teen Centre, 2018). Mental health problems remain prevalent in the younger population (Jurewicz, 2015). Young people are more vulnerable to acquiring vulnerabilities or mental health difficulties since they are frequently exposed to new experiences and challenges in their daily lives. However, these life experiences are not determinative, and the flexibility of adolescence defines it as a window of opportunity for change, within which processes of resilience, recovery, and growth are achievable (The National Academy of Science, 2019). Identifying and diagnosing a mental illness in young adults in different cultures can be difficult since adolescents and young adults go through a variety of behavioural, social, and physical changes. Increasing focus is given to this important age of transition from adolescence to adulthood, as the ways in which this psychological and social transition may affect current and future well-being. Culture encompasses the shared beliefs, values, and practices that define social behaviours and norms within a society. It plays a crucial role in shaping individuals' perceptions of mental health, influencing how mental illnesses are understood, diagnosed, and treated (Gogineni, 2023). Culture is central to interpreting human psychological and psychosocial development, contributing to diversity in human thought and societal structures. Understanding and interventions in mental health must ultimately consider cultural contexts. Cultural norms shape perceptions of normal and abnormal behaviour, influencing the recognition, expression, and stigma of mental illness (Heather et al., 2022). They also guide pathways to care, determining whether individuals seek medical treatment or prefer traditional and spiritual healing methods (Bhugra et al., 2022; Kohrt & Patel, 2020). The value system within a culture

can either encourage or discourage individuals from pursuing mental health treatment (Naibili & Rochmawati, 2019).

In Western countries, mental health is often medicalized, relying on standardized frameworks for diagnosis and a focus on pharmacological treatments (Gogineni et al., 2023). This approach, while offering structured care, can overlook cultural factors that shape mental health experiences and outcomes (Karthick & Sangita, 2017). Many studies related to mental health and well-being have been conducted in Western countries, which refer to nations primarily located in Europe and North America, such as the United States, Canada, the United Kingdom, and Germany. These countries often share cultural, historical, and societal frameworks influenced by industrialization, secularism, and individualism. In the context of mental health research, Western countries typically emphasize biomedical approaches, evidence-based therapies, and open discussions about mental health challenges. Western mental health research frequently employs evidence-based therapies, such as cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) and mindfulness, which have shown medium to strong effects on well-being (Blodgett et al., 2022). Conversely, in many Muslim societies, mental health is closely tied to religious beliefs, with spiritual guidance and community support playing significant roles (Grenier & Ojembre, 2020). Religious institutions often provide alternative frameworks for understanding and addressing mental health, which can differ markedly from Western medical practices (Bhugra et al., 2022). However, this focus has resulted in limited research on mental health in Arab countries, such as Algeria, where cultural norms, religious values, and societal stigmas significantly shape perceptions of mental health. Cultural beliefs often associate mental illness with personal failure or moral weakness, leading to stigma that discourages individuals from seeking help (Musa, 2024). Jaalouk et al (2012) and Karam and Itani (2015) recommended there should be an increase in mental health research in the Arab world due to the substantial gap in research in this field compared to other countries and regions. Among them a relative

lack of national data, studies on cultural differences in risk factors, prognosis, and treatment behaviours (Jaalouk et al., 2012). Similarly, Karam et al. (2006) and Karam et al. (2008) stated that epidemiological studies that allow for cross-country comparisons are needed. This comparison highlights the need for culturally informed approaches to mental health care, integrating both medical and cultural dimensions to address diverse needs globally.

In many cultures, mental health remains a taboo subject, largely due to factors rooted in one's social and cultural background. These factors include stigma, cultural norms equating mental health struggles with weakness, specific beliefs about mental health, limited awareness of mental health issues, and insufficient access to mental health resources. These elements collectively contribute to a reluctance to openly discuss mental health, shaping how individuals describe and address their mental health challenges or physical symptoms within diverse cultural contexts. Cultural differences have a wide range of implications for mental health practise, ranging from how people view health and illness to treatment seeking patterns, the nature of the therapeutic relationship, and issues of racism and discrimination (Gopalkrishnan, 2018). Culture plays a vital role in directing, shaping, and modelling social behaviour at both individual and group levels (Pandey, 1988). It can be challenging to convey a message to express one's mental health status, especially when social norms make discussing mental health concerns a barrier and a source of shame. Bicchieri (2006) highlighted these issues by stating that social norms are behavioural rules shaped and supported by the community's accepted and expected social expectations. People diagnosed with mental illnesses often experience a sense of shame, brought on by stigma and prejudice in society, which causes marginalisation, exclusion, and a lack of social opportunities (Carr & Ashby, 2020). Stigma can be understood as a combination of problems of knowledge (ignorance), attitudes (prejudice) and behaviour (discrimination) (Thornicroft et al., 2008). It can cause people to feel so ashamed that they hide their symptoms and do not seek treatment until the issues becomes acute (Shrivastava et al., 2012). Expressing

emotions is just as powerful when it comes to mental health, it can be instrumental to make progress also, and it can be an obstacle for adolescents and young adults who have mental health problems.

Different studies revealed different views about mental health. According to Arabic culture, the importance of communicating mental health issues is still considered a topic that is not spoken about openly. In the Arab world, mental illness has been viewed as a curse from the “evil eye” or a “Jinn” possession for Muslim believers (Ahmad et al., 2016), a “devil-possession” for Christian believers (Waldmeier, 1897) and it is perceived in a similar way as supernatural or parapsychological phenomenon in some Western cultures. This process can have detrimental effects on the mental health of young individuals, prompting them to turn to social media platforms as a means of seeking help and finding solutions for their mental health concerns.

Seeking help is an important first step in improving one's mental health and getting access to suitable treatment options. Seeking help is defined as “the process of actively seeking out and utilizing social relationships, either formal or informal, to help with personal problems” (Rickwood, 2005). In modern society, the internet has become a primary source of health information (Eysenbach et al., 2002), particularly among young people, who frequently utilise online services to seek support and information about mental health issues (Kauer et al., 2014). Similarly, many exploratory studies have found that many of these individuals with mental health issues appear to turn to social media to share their personal experiences, seek information about their mental health and treatment options, give and receive support from others facing similar mental health challenges (Naslund et al., 2016; Bucci et al., 2019). There are various online services readily available for young people including self-directed, low intensity web-based mental health support (e.g. ReachOut), national online counselling services (e.g. Eheadspace), repositories for information and resources concerning

mental health (e.g. Somazone), and structured self-directed online therapy (e.g. MoodGym) (Christensen et al., 2002). Social media facilitates the creative display of information, while simultaneously influencing, motivating, and engaging individuals on important health issues (Maher et al., 2014). A potential explanation is that the widespread use of online social networks allows individuals to connect on a global scale to locate others dealing with similar issues. It is identified by Hampton et al. (2014) that social media use can increase users' awareness of stressful events in others' lives, and this awareness can lead to higher levels of stress.

Despite recent advancements in mental health research in Western cultures, there remains a significant gap in understanding the perspectives and lived experiences of young adults, particularly in non-Western contexts like Algeria. Young adults' subjective experiences and interpretations of mental health are deeply shaped by their social and cultural backgrounds such as their personal beliefs, cultural influences, and social contexts. Amplifying the voices of young Algerian adults can provide valuable insights into their unique understandings, attitudes, and preferences regarding mental health and support. While much research has been done to examine the barriers to service access, few studies have explored unbiased accounts of young adults' experiences with mental health issues (Marcus et al., 2012). The literature appears to focus more on Western and East Asian contexts, leaving a significant gap in understanding the unique experiences and views of young people in the Arab world. (see Yu-Wen, 1995; Hasset, 2006; Ngai et al., 2014; Furnham & Hamid, 2014; Navaneetham & Kanth, 2022). It is important to recognize mental health difficulties among adolescents and young people from various cultural origins to better understand how mental health is experienced in different cultures and if cultural/traditional beliefs influence their help-seeking behaviours. In other words, to find out what should be regarded culturally relevant when dealing with mental

health in both Algerian and British cultures, as well as to comprehend more about mental health support in real life and on social media?

1.6 The main definitions relevant to this study

1.6.1 Young adulthood

It is understood that young adulthood is a transitional stage period between adolescence and mature adulthood that occurs between ages 18 to 25 and it can extend to as late as 30 years of age. the United Nations has identified youth as the period from 15 to 24 years of age, a period of vulnerability worldwide and has made it a priority for multiple interventions (UNESCO 2013) whereas the African Union refers to those aged 15 to 35 in acknowledgment of the age range where life changes take place" (UNECA 2009). It is the period in which young adults become more economically independent by training and/or education (Hochberg and Konner, 2020). Youth has been defined as a time when there is the most valuable opportunity to acquire life skills and consolidate one's identity (Perret-Clermont, 2004), for a number of reasons, young people's ability to take advantage of these chances is limited (Bernhart & Medel-Añonuevo, 2014).

It is understood that difficulties associated with anxiety and depression are the most prevalent types of mental illness found amongst young people and in the last 25 years, rates have increased by 70% (Halliwell et al., 2007). It is a distinct stage of development where young people face tremendous changes in biology, neuropathy, psychology, and their wider societal perspectives, indicating a time of increased strain and struggle for youth. The linkages between these changes have been theorized by life course researchers through a focus on age grading; as biological age marks different stages in human development, 'social age' denotes expected roles and transitions at various periods of life (Elder and Rockwell 1979; Hogan and Stone 1986). Individuals in this transition period are more vulnerable to mental health issue and that through the multiple experiences and expectations that they may pass through. this

phase is distinguished by the emergence of noteworthy psychological issues and related dysfunction, hindering individuals from effectively accomplishing these developmental milestones (Taliercio et al., 2023). Coping with mental health problems at this age may be difficult for them because of the lack of acknowledgment or awareness. Struggling with mental health and remaining silent further elevates the risk on the physical health.

Young adults may be more informed about mental health in modern times. Research highlights that younger generations exhibit higher mental health literacy (Jumbe et al., 2023). Cultural differences, gaps in mental health literacy, intergenerational value conflicts, and the lasting impacts of major life events can still make it difficult for them to openly talk about and share their mental health experiences. This can result a complex issue in terms of communicating poor mental health, which may be due to personal or social issues. Notably, this period is often made more challenging due to the high prevalence of poor mental health (Burns et al., 2009). Many diagnoses are detected for the first-time during adolescence (Patel et al, 2007). Half of all mental health problems have been established by the age of 14, rising to 75% by age (Office for Health improvements and Disparities, 2022). However, despite the relative importance of protecting mental health and emotional wellbeing, adolescents tend to have a limited knowledge of what it means to be mentally healthy or how to maintain this level of wellbeing (Dogra et al., 2012). It is believed that mental health difficulties can have a significant impact upon the lives of young people affecting their academic achievement, self-esteem, and personal relationships (Zins et al., 2004). Mental health issues among adolescents and young people are common and account for a significant proportion of the burden of ill health in this age range. Rates of depression, suicidal behaviours, eating disorders and substance abuse have increased steadily among young people in recent decades (Jurewicz, 2015). A summary of young people's wellbeing produced a national report (Office for National Statistics, 2014), noted the following: one in five young adults had symptoms of depression or anxiety, 2.2% of 16–24

year olds in Great Britain experienced a depressive episode, 6.2% of 16–24 year olds have attempted suicide in their lifetime, 8.9% of 16–24 year olds have self-harmed in their lifetime, 194 15–19 year olds and 427 20–24 year olds committed suicide in 2011 (Office for National Statistics, 2014). It seems that a considerable proportion of adolescents and young adults aged 16 to 24 may have symptoms of depression or anxiety at some point throughout these years. While in recent years within the rise of social media and the COVID-19 pandemic have significantly impacted the mental health of young adults more. Isolation in the time of the pandemic allowed young adults greater access to social media, leading to a deterioration in young adults' mental health. Studies have shown that the increased use of social media during the pandemic has led to negative effects on mental health such as anxiety, depression, and stress (Titisuk et al., 2023; Draženović et al., 2023). As a result, the perception of social isolation among young adults has increased during the pandemic, leading to an increased risk of depressive symptoms (Bak et al., 2023)

1.6.2 Islamic psychology

In recent years a growing body of research has explored the relation between religiosity and mental health and psychopathology, including anxiety (Seybold and Hill, 2001), and this association has attracted considerable attention (Koenig et al., 2012). Religious practices and beliefs are widespread in different parts around the globe and are linked to indices of well-being (Koenig and Larson, 2001). Research indicates that religion can provide a sense of meaning and purpose in life, as well as promote mental health (Papaleontiou, 2020). Further, Novak (1998) stated that the twenty-first century will be “the most religious century” in recent times. There are many research studies show that there is a close connection between religiosity and positive indicators of mental health, this relationship is present in studies of Christians, Hindus, and Muslims (Koenig et al., 2001). For example, Islamic tradition emphasizes the link

between religious dedication and overall human well-being, including happiness. Qur'anic verses like:

"For those who believe and do righteous deeds—for them is happiness and a beautiful return"

(Ra'd 13, 29)

And

"As for those who are happy, they will be in Paradise, remaining therein for as long as the heavens and the earth endure, except as your Lord wills—a reward without end" (Hud 11, 108).

These align with claims made in other Abrahamic religious traditions. claims consistent with those made within other Abrahamic religious traditions. (Tekke, Francis & Robbins, 2018).

Furthermore, religious involvement plays an important role in helping people cope with the effects of stressful life circumstances (Koenig et al., 2001). Regarding religiosity and happiness or well-being, extensive literature has demonstrated an apparent connection between them (see Argyle, 2002; Francis, Jones, & Wilcox, 2000; French & Joseph, 1999; Myers and Diener, 1995). Koenig et al (2001) reviewed studies that have examined the relationship between religious involvement and measures of well-being, happiness, and life satisfaction. Few studies have explored how individuals of different religious affiliations (for example, Christianity, Hindu, and Islamic faith) perform on measures of positive mental health.

1.6.3 Western psychology

Western Europe comprises a huge diversity of lifestyles, social determinants of health such as housing and income, mental health services and health data (Rutz, 2001). In the second part of the 20th century the development of mental health services in Western Europe was characterized by dramatic conceptual and structural changes (Becker, Vázquez-Barquero,

2001), Yet mental health services are frequently held to be insensitive to culture, psychiatrists and psychologists are said to be culturally incompetent and psychiatric and psychological therapies appear to be inappropriate for many people from non-western cultural backgrounds (Fernando, 2004). Psychology in a less privileged society (developing countries) is treated as a discipline of second choice because priority is given to providing bare necessities (Smith and Bond, 1998). The transfer of knowledge and information technologies from the Western countries to the rest of the world lead to the domination of scientifically based Western worldviews, philosophies, and theories of understanding human behaviour (Mkhize, 2006). Ganga and Kutty (2013) found that devotion to religion among Christians translated to higher levels of subjective wellbeing, when compared to Muslims and Hindus. Contrary to the materialistic culture and philosophy of the West, the focus of Islamic philosophy is that people are holistic, social, goal-directed, belonging, creative and responsible.

1.6.4 Quran

The Quran is considered sacred and vital in Islam because it is the actual word of God (Allah) given to Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) during a 23-year period by the angel Gabriel. The Quran is a comprehensive handbook that addresses many parts of life, including laws, ethical behaviour, social relationships, and religious philosophy. The Holy Quran is divided into 114 chapters, known as Surahs, and contains 6,348 verses. The verses are arranged thematically, with the largest chapter, Surah al-Baqarah, having 287 verses. Each chapter addresses religion, guidance, and morality. The arrangement makes it easier for Muslims to reference and memorize the holy scripture, ensuring ease and accessibility in reading and reciting it.

The Quran is not only the holy book of Islam but also serves as a profound source of knowledge, guidance, and law. It encompasses teachings that influence multiple academic

disciplines and encourages critical thinking and the pursuit of knowledge. The Quran invites individuals to reason, reflect, observe, listen, explore, and innovate (Rahman, 2021). Beyond its role as a sacred text, the Quran is central to everyday Muslim practices, including recitation, memorization, and contemplation (Che Wan Mohd Rozali et al., 2022). Its verses are not only a source of spiritual enlightenment but also provide moral principles, wisdom, and divine teachings to guide believers in navigating personal and communal challenges.

Muslims view the Quran as a comprehensive source of support for life's struggles. It is believed to offer guidance for spiritual, psychological, and physical well-being. The therapeutic effects of listening to Quranic verses also highlight its psycho-spiritual benefits, promoting mental well-being (Kannan et al., 2022). The traditions of Prophet Muhammad (SAW) provide evidence for the use of Quranic verses in healing practices, encompassing spiritual, psychological, and physical illnesses (Adu-Gyamfi, 2014). Written in Arabic, the Quran's recitation is a key element of Islamic worship, and many Muslims aspire to memorize it fully, incorporating its teachings into daily prayers and rituals. The Quran integrates ethical and spiritual dimensions into critical thinking, advocating for a holistic approach that includes moral reasoning and character-building (Hashi, 2024). It encourages the use of intellect alongside divine revelation, emphasizing contemplation and deliberation in understanding its teachings (Zahra & Ghayas, 2023).

Philosophical Christology emphasizes the centrality of Christ in modern philosophical discourse, asserting that both Christ and the Qur'an are instrumental in shaping philosophical thought. This perspective explores the intersection of religious belief and philosophical inquiry, suggesting that understanding Christ can lead to deeper insights into human existence and morality. In this context, the Qur'an occupies a similarly important place alongside Christ in philosophical reflection (Campanini, 2018). Christ is a key figure in Christian philosophy, influencing ethical frameworks and existential questions (Stachewicz, 2020).

The historical context of Christ's life and teachings is crucial for understanding his impact on philosophical thought, as it serves as the foundation for theological discourse (Oduor, 2022). Philosophical Christology fosters dialogue between different religious perspectives, including Islamic views on Jesus, which emphasize his humanity (Mathew, 2022). In Islam, the Qur'an is regarded as the ultimate source of truth and guidance, much as Christ is in Christian philosophy. It holds the highest authority in Islam, representing divine wisdom and offering key insights into the nature of God. The Qur'an presents a distinct understanding of Jesus, focusing on his prophetic role rather than his divinity, which invites philosophical exploration of religious truths (Mathew, 2022).

Both Christology and the Qur'an significantly shape philosophical and theological thinking, providing believers with a framework for comprehending and interpreting the world. Additionally, the Qur'an addresses not only the Muslim community but also non-Islamic cultures, transcending any specific national or sectarian context.

1.6.5 Roqya

Roqya is a traditional Islamic practice focused on spiritual healing and protection. It entails reciting specific Quranic verses and supplications to seek protection against the evil eye, black magic, and other spiritual issues. Rooted in the sunnah, it involves imploring Allah for assistance in healing and is typically performed by knowledgeable individuals well-versed in the Quran. The roqya, a means for extracting djinns and demons associated to sorcery via the evil eye, is becoming part of the religious leaders offering. According to Abdul-Rahman and Hussin (2021) ruqyah, a therapeutic approach, is founded on Islamic epistemology and ontology. Islamic epistemology focuses on two primary sources of knowledge. The first source employs logical, intellectual, and scientific evidence, similar to Western epistemological techniques. The second form of knowledge is gained from divine revelation, giving birth to beliefs in diverse ontological elements, including the existence of invisible creatures like angels

and jinn. Ruqya, the practice of spiritual healing through the recitation of Quranic verses and Hadith, varies significantly across the Muslim world, reflecting diverse cultural interpretations and practices influenced by local traditions, understandings of spiritual ailments, and the role of religious authorities. In the Middle East, particularly in countries like Saudi Arabia, Ruqya is typically performed by trained practitioners who adhere strictly to Quranic texts and Hadith, emphasizing authenticity in the recitations (Syarifuddin & Rosyid, 2019). In Southeast Asia, particularly in Indonesia and Malaysia, Ruqya often incorporates local healing traditions, blending Islamic texts with indigenous practices to create a more holistic approach to healing (Zainol et al., 2016). In North Africa, such as Morocco, Ruqya is sometimes performed in communal settings, where the recitation is accompanied by traditional music and rituals, highlighting a collective and communal aspect of healing ("Riba dalam pandangan al-qur'an dan hadist", 2023). These regional variations demonstrate the dynamic interplay between Islamic principles and cultural contexts in shaping the practice of Ruqya.

The therapists, known as "Raqi ", advocate reverting to a cleansed exorcism focused on Koranic verses and therapy with Quranized water (Touag, 2014). There are various types of Ruqyah treatment, such as reciting Quranic verses or praying, but different Ruqyah treatment centres employ different methods, procedures, or approaches (Eneborg, 2013) for example Khedimellah (2007) describes how his Raqī uses mostly blessed water, fortified with basic prophetic medicine (olive oil, honey, etc.) to assist the healing process after the ruqya has been performed. The Raqī method of healing emphasizes the spiritual and physical well-being of an individual, employing Quranic water and prophetic remedies to restore equilibrium and enhance overall healing. This approach addresses both physical and spiritual ailments, aiming to strengthen faith and find comfort in Allah's guidance within the Islamic belief system. It's essential to recognize that roqya and its concepts are culturally and religiously specific, not

universally acknowledged. Those interested in this practice should seek guidance from qualified authorities.

1.6.6 Hadith

The Quran and Hadith together form the foundation of Islamic teachings and law (Sharia). While the Quran is considered the unchanged, direct word of God, the Hadith comprises the sayings and actions of the Prophet Muhammad, providing practical guidance for implementing Islamic principles (Kesgin, 2012; Saeed et al., 2023). The Hadith also aids in interpreting Quranic verses, enabling the adaptation of Islamic law to diverse cultural and societal contexts (Fadholi, 2022). Hadiths such as "Shame is a sign of faith" (الحياء من الإيمان) and "If you are shameless, do whatever you want" (إذا لم تستحي فاصنع ما شئت) emphasize the moral value of shame (hayaa) as an aspect of faith in God (Batyrgyzhan et al., 2014). These proverbs and sayings, integral to Islamic ethics, embody deeper meanings and spiritual values. However, some scholars caution that excessive reliance on Hadith may lead to over-interpretation, potentially distorting the Quran's original message and causing divisions within the Muslim community (Kesgin, 2012). Without the Hadith, the application of Islamic law—whether in personal or social matters—would be challenging, as the Hadith elaborates on the Quran's meanings and provides essential details for practice (Rasyid et al., 2021)

1.7 Overview of the chapters

Chapter One: Introduction

This chapter includes an introduction to the study's background, motivation for the research study, purpose, rationale, and research questions.

Chapter Two: Literature review

Chapter two addresses and synthesizes relevant international literature associated with the present study and upon which this study is based by defining key concepts and highlighting the existing gap in the literature review.

Chapter Three: Methodology

Chapter three's methodology chapter describes the methodological context of the study, providing a detailed outline of the research design and qualitative research. It focuses on the qualitative approach and describes the data collection process, ethical considerations, and data analysis.

Chapter Four: Study 1 findings and discussion

This chapter presents the findings of the first research study, answering the research questions, and provides an interpretation of these findings. The study focuses on the experiences of mental health issues in different cultures in the digital age. Additionally, it lays the groundwork for another research study exploring the roles and experiences of imams in supporting Muslims facing mental health issues across diverse cultural contexts.

Chapter 5: Study 2 findings and discussion:

This chapter presents the findings of the second research study, answering the research questions, and discusses and interprets these findings. It also includes a discussion about the comparison of how imams deal with mental health issues in Algeria and the United Kingdom, including their referral programs.

Chapter six: Conclusion

this Chapter concludes both research studies, connecting them with each other. It discusses the major contributions, limitations of the study, and provides recommendations for future studies.

Chapter 02: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the various cultural intricacies pertaining to mental health challenges among young adults in Algerian and British societies. It outlines the distinct cultural and societal factors that potentially contribute to these challenges. An examination of both Arab and Western literature reveals a scarcity of studies concerning mental health in Algeria and mental health care within Muslim communities in Western contexts. It is imperative to acknowledge the intricate relationship between mental health, young adults, and their respective cultures, given that the experiences of mental health issues may vary between young individuals in different cultures. Numerous research studies utilize the term "young adults" to denote individuals aged between 18 and 24 years when discussing mental health concerns (Perlis et al, 2023; Burnett et al, 2023; Sabella et al, 2022, Sawyer et al, 2012; Gore et al, 2011). This age group is often described as being in the phase of late adolescence or emerging adulthood. The concepts "young adults" or "young people" is employed in this study to denote individuals within this age period.

Cultural beliefs, values, and practices significantly shape how individuals perceive and construe mental health conditions. In certain cultural contexts, mental health issues may be seen as spiritual or supernatural phenomena rather than medical issue (Sodi & Bojuwove, 2014). Cultural viewpoints also influence help-seeking behaviours and treatment preferences. The literature extensively discusses psychological Western therapy and Islamic traditional healing therapy, aiming to discern the disparities in therapeutic approaches globally across Western and Muslim communities. Subsequently, the literature touches upon Arab and Western cultures in a broader context due to the dearth of research studies in Algeria and the United Kingdom on this subject matter. The chapter highlights specific challenges related to

mental health service accessibility in both regions, as well as a comparison between traditional and professional treatments in Algeria and the United Kingdom. Furthermore, it mentions the involvement of religious leaders in Islamic psychotherapy. The chapter concludes emphasizing on the necessity of collaboration and the integration of religious and spiritual dimensions into mental health practices and treatments.

2-2 Mental health and wellbeing

Before providing a definition for mental health, it's crucial to establish a definition for health and well-being. Well-being, as described by Kononenko and Grigoraschenko (2021) is a subjective measure of life quality shaped by various factors such as life events, individual attitudes, and tolerance. This systemic quality is influenced by a meta-implicative model that considers cultural, social, psychological, physical, economic, and spiritual variables. It stands in contrast to common mental illnesses like depression and anxiety (Huppert & So, 2013). Well-being is often conceptualized as evaluations of individual life satisfaction (Carlsson & Hamrin, 2002), encompassing a person's ability to recognize their capacities, manage life stresses, work productively, contribute to their community (WHO, 2022), and make judgments about the meaning and purpose of life (Zika & Chamberlain, 1992). In simpler terms, well-being integrates mental and physical health, socioeconomics, and the environment, providing a holistic approach to disease prevention, health promotion, and positive life outcomes.

However, the academic community experiences disagreement on well-being's definition due to its subjective nature, and the influence of social and environmental factors. Different domains, such as emotional, physical, or economic well-being, have distinct definitions (Butista et al., 2023). Though aspects of well-being may seem universal, its depiction in the literature exhibits substantial variation in definition and even greater diversity in measurement (Sunday Idemudia & Adedeji, 2023). Researchers use burnout measures to assess wellbeing because it is easily

quantifiable but has no universal definition, resulting in interchangeable synonyms, descriptions, and lists that make comparing research difficult (Smons & Baldwin, 2021). The development of well-being measures and their use in different cultures assumes a shared understanding of well-being across cultures, implying that it can be captured using the same measures (Butista et al., 2023). This recognition underscores the challenges in creating a universally accepted definition of well-being and emphasizes the importance of considering cultural variations when addressing this complex and nuanced concept.

Health is dynamic, influenced by social and environmental challenges, prone to change over time. Reference to the WHO (1946, p 100) another definition of health can be seen as not the absence of diseases but a state of well-being (The WHOQOL Group, 1998). Individuals can maintain well-being by effectively adjusting to illness and engaging in various social activities. (Keyes & Simoes, 2012). In contrast, terms like disease and illness are used literally to describe physical states, rather than as metaphors that draw attention to similarities between mental and physical dysfunction. Troublesome thoughts, feelings, and actions are viewed as indicators of underlying pathology (Aneshensel et al., 2013). Health and wellbeing are interconnected concepts, referring to an individual's ability to achieve and maintain optimal health. Understanding the connection between these concepts helps us appreciate the significance of experiences in personal development and societal contributions.

Mental health is one important marker, given its impact on one's capacity to effectively interact with others, make decisions, relate to others and cope with social challenges (shepherd et al., 2021). Keyes and Simoes (2012) argued that mental health is operationalized within subjective well-being, which refers to individuals' evaluations of their lives' quality. this can be understood through how one equates well-being with positive emotions which highlight the importance of experiencing contentment in one's life and as an individual's ability to function

effectively in various domains. These approaches, known as the hedonic and eudemonic perspectives, respectively, both emphasize on positive feelings, and a fulfilling existence as individuals as well as their contributions to society. Individuals with low hedonic and eudemonic well-being experience limited positive emotions and self-perception. Moderate mental health individuals have moderate levels of both, highlighting the importance of mental health in overall well-being. (Keyes & Anas, 2009). Another shift in attention is towards positive components of mental health which represents an approach which not only focuses on the treatment or prevention of mental health disorders, but also emphasises the importance of feeling good and functioning effectively (Huppert & So, 2013). It is becoming obvious that good and positive mental wellbeing is necessary in overall individuals' overall wellbeing.

Mental health refers to an individual's balanced psychological constitution, promoting harmony with themselves and their environment, preventing mental problems, and promoting overall well-being. The definition of mental health, according to the World Health Organization (2001) Mental health is a state of thriving where people acknowledge their abilities, handle life's challenges well, operate efficiently, and play a positive role in society. Maintaining a balanced, healthy lifestyle requires mental, physical, and societal well-being, which highlights the importance of finding a sense of equilibrium. Mental health issues can have significant implications on individuals' lives when considering their emotional and physical experiences. On the other hand, severe mental disorders like depression, schizophrenia, and bipolar disorder can be debilitating if left untreated. These diseases have the potential to be catastrophic. There are various factors that can impact our mental health. These factors, including physical, emotional, intellectual, and social changes, can increase the risk of mental health problems (Penzes et al., 2020). These risk factors can vary across different age groups, from childhood to adolescence to adulthood. However, it is possible to improve mental health by reducing or building protective measures against these risk factors.

Huber et al. (2011) argue that health should prioritize an individual's ability to adapt and self-manage in the face of challenges, contrasting with the World Health Organization's (WHO) definition (2001, 2022) of complete well-being. The WHO's broad use of the term "complete" is criticized for potentially leading to the medicalization of society, categorizing most individuals as unhealthy for significant portions of their lives if complete health were a requirement. According to Machteld Huber et al. (2011) the focus should shift towards one's ability to adapt and self-care amid social, physical, and emotional challenges. The relationship between mental health and well-being can be viewed from a nuanced perspective, potentially leading to positive changes in the mental health system. This approach could improve mental health assessments and enhance the design and implementation of interventions aimed at improving mental health symptoms. Recognizing the complex interplay between mental health and well-being promotes a holistic approach, promoting inclusivity in/ health understanding (Huber et al., 2011). Consequently, good mental health can be viewed as being essential for individuals' overall wellbeing. The field of mental health encompasses two distinct paradigms: the medical model and the psychological model. The medical model focuses on assessing psychopathology of disorders such as depression and anxiety, to determine overall well-being and mental health (Zabo et al., 2023; Bicknell, 2023). In contrast, the psychological or traditional model emphasizes an individual's life satisfaction and subjective evaluation of positive emotions (Gonzalez et al., 2023). These paradigms offer different perspectives on mental health, with the medical model prioritizing the identification and treatment of mental disorders, while the psychological model emphasizes subjective well-being and positive psychological functioning. Both paradigms contribute to a comprehensive understanding of mental health, considering both psychopathology and positive aspects of mental well-being. It is crucial to incorporate both aspects of mental well-being for individuals to attain a harmonious state of mental health, which, in turn, positively influences their social lives.

Mental health is difficult to define precisely because it differs across individuals and cultures. The variability of values across different cultures and even within specific groups and individuals in a culture precludes the possibility of a universally agreed upon definition of "mental health," rendering it a mere illusion. (Cowen, 1994). Recognizing the differences in values, cultures, and socioeconomic backgrounds between nations may impede the development of a broad consensus on the notion of mental health, developing an inclusive definition while avoiding as many restrictive and culture-bound statements as possible (Galderisi et al., 2015). Galderisi et al. (2015) pointing out that it is influenced by hedonic and eudemonic traditions and additionally, that it is influenced by cultural values without being culture sensitive. Further, the authors mention that universal mental health elements need to be identified while culture-specific elements also need to be catered for. According to them, while representing a substantial progress with respect to moving away from the conceptualization of mental health as a state of absence of mental illness, raises several concerns and lends itself to potential misunderstandings when it identifies positive feelings and positive functioning as key factors for mental health. Mental health is largely shaped by the daily environments in which people live their lives, with positive components of mental health emphasising the importance of feeling good and functioning effectively (Cresswell et al., 2022). Recognizing that variations in values, cultures backgrounds between countries may impede the development of a broad consensus on the notion of mental health.

There are significant treatment gaps and a lack of understanding of mental illness in the public healthcare system. Individual and societal mental health can only be improved by ensuring the rights and care of those suffering from mental illnesses, as well as by promoting mental wellness and preventing mental illnesses from occurring (Mishra et al., 2022). A as a result understanding the meaning and definitions of mental health and its relation to culture and that to recognise the risk factors that can be identified in different cultures such as social and

psychological factors (social support, education, awareness, coping strategies, help seeking behaviours and barriers that may be an obstacle for individuals to seek help). Cultural norms have a substantial impact on how individuals manifest their symptoms, encompassing not only subtle variations in communication but also the potential omission of certain symptoms. Each cultural group possesses its own unique system of beliefs, traditions, and practices concerning mental health. This emphasizes the criticality of acknowledging the influence of these cultural factors on an individual's overall attitude towards seeking treatment.

2.3 The relationship between culture and mental wellbeing

The intricate connection between culture and mental well-being significantly influences human psychological and psychosocial development (Gogineni et al., 2023). The cultural disparities in self-concept, emotions, values, and religion impact individuals' perceptions and experiences of mental health. Notably, western cultures prioritize individual autonomy, while Arab cultures underscore the importance of relationships and community (Markus & Kitayama, 1991; Realo et al., 2002, Basurrah et al., 2022; Vicman et al., 2022). This cultural distinction is of utmost importance in the assessment and treatment of mental health issues, necessitating culturally sensitive interventions (Summerton & Blunden, 2022). Culture significantly impacts mental health through biological, developmental, social, and environmental factors, shaping values, beliefs, and behaviours in minds and society. In the other hand, Arab cultures place significant value on family and community, exerting a profound impact on an individual's life. Loyalty to family and the importance of friendships are central to an Arab's existence, suggesting potential for group-oriented interventions that focus on relationships (Basurrah et al., 2022). Traditionally, the family and community environment in Arab societies are regarded positively, with a perceived therapeutic role in resolving conflicts and stresses (Basurrah et al., 2022). In contrast, the prioritization of group cohesion and social relationships can sometimes lead to

lower happiness indices due to the pressure of social conformity (Jasielska et al., 2018). The emphasis on community can create a sense of belonging, yet it may also result in individuals sacrificing personal desires for the sake of group harmony (Zayani & Khalil, 2023).

However, opposing views within Arab collectivist cultures emerge, with modernists advocating for individual freedom, conflicting with traditionalists who prioritize the positive therapeutic role of family and community (Sohail et al., 2017). The shift from Western individualist to Arab collectivist cultures becomes evident in the valuation of happiness. Individualist cultures prioritize happiness, whereas collective cultures place value on low arousal and positive emotions (Leu et al., 2011). In individualist societies, happiness is frequently associated with personal success and autonomy, leading to higher reported happiness levels (Jasielska et al., 2018). The focus on self-expression and personal goals fosters a sense of fulfilment, which is often reflected in positive emotional states (Svoray et al., 2022).

The narratives surrounding the social environment become a battleground for conflict between modernists and traditionalists, reflecting divergent views on individual freedom and familial/community values (Sohail et al., 2017). Overall, culture is not just an adjunct to mental health, but an inseparable aspect deeply intertwined with it. Understanding cultural influences is essential for effective mental health interventions, as it shapes symptom expression, help-seeking behaviours, and the meanings individuals attribute to their mental health conditions.

2.4 The Importance of understanding mental Health among Young Adults in different cultures.

Understanding mental health during young adulthood is crucial because individuals at this stage are particularly vulnerable and often experience the onset of mental health issues. Analysing this stage in different cultural contexts provides a comprehensive understanding of the prevalence and severity of mental health problems across societies. This understanding is

essential for developing culturally sensitive and effective interventions tailored to each unique culture. One way to shed light on the challenges faced by young adults with mental health problems is to use a lived experience paradigm (Neubauer et al., 2019) to examine their subjective experiences. The concept of lived experience falls within a phenomenological or 'emic' framework, seeking to grasp "what was experienced and how it was experienced. While many studies have used the lived experience paradigm in developed countries such as the United States, Canada, the United Kingdom, and some countries in Western Europe and the Pacific Rim, there have been very few investigations using this paradigm in emerging economies (Palinkas, 2014).

Young adulthood is a critical phase for establishing the foundations of mental and physical health. Many mental health issues arise during adolescence and young adulthood, emphasizing the importance of early interventions to promote mental health and prevent illness. By capturing the perspectives of adolescents and young adults on their own experiences, we can identify the essential skills and abilities needed for adaptive and positive behaviour. These skills empower young individuals to effectively navigate the challenges of everyday life (Hellstrom & Beckman, 2021). Understanding mental health challenges among young adults in different cultures is crucial for providing effective support and interventions. Mental ill-health can hinder an individual's ability to engage with others and cope with social difficulties, particularly for culturally and linguistically diverse (CALD) individuals going through acculturation (Shepherd et al., 2021). Inclusivity and cultural competence play pivotal roles in supporting the mental health of young individuals because culture significantly impacts mental well-being, both positively and negatively (Srivastava & Srivastava, 2018).

Mental and behavioural disorders are highly prevalent, affecting over 25% of individuals at some point in their lives (Mahto et al., 2009). By listening to the experiences and viewpoints of adolescents and young adults, we can identify important skills and abilities that promote

adaptive and positive behaviour, enabling them to effectively cope with the challenges of daily life (Hellstrom and Beckman, 2021). Understanding young people's perspectives on mental health in different cultures is crucial for several reasons, as these perspectives can shape future beliefs and attitudes (Secker & Armstrong, 1999). This comprehensive approach promotes a more inclusive and effective approach to mental health care, ultimately leading to better outcomes and improved overall societal well-being.

Many young adults worldwide suffer from diagnosed and/or undiagnosed mental health problems (Gulliver et al., 2012). Young adults have further been identified as a high-risk group as they show elevated levels of anxiety and depression. For example, nearly one-third of 16–24-year-olds in the UK (31%) reported some evidence of depression or anxiety in 2017 to 2018. This is up from the previous year (26%) and the same period five years earlier (26%) (Office for National Statistics, 2021). Young adults in the UK have been found to have high rates of mental health problems, including anxiety and depression (Syed et al., 2021). Another study in Norway examined mental health problems in adolescents and young adults with persistent health challenges, including disabilities. (Fekih-Romdhane et al., 2020). While in Arab North African countries such as Morocco, one study conducted during the Covid-19 pandemic found a high prevalence of anxiety (40.5%) and depression (28.9%) among adults aged 18 to 63 years (Khalki et al., 2022). However, there is limited information available regarding mental health problems in young adults in Arab culture, including Algeria.

Listening to the narratives of adolescents and young adults about their lived experiences can aid in identifying crucial skills and capabilities for adaptive and positive behaviour (Hellstrom & Beckman, 2021). This comprehension empowers the youth to effectively cope with the demands and challenges of daily life. Regrettably, there is a dearth of studies focusing on individuals grappling with severe mental health issues from a salutogenic health-promotion perspective (Langeland & Vinje, 2013). The salutogenic theory becomes pertinent,

highlighting the interplay between an individual and their environment in promoting mental health and fostering recovery. The significance of comprehending young people's perspectives on mental health across diverse cultures cannot be overstated. Each segment of society possesses a distinctive outlook on mental illness, particularly among the younger generation and college students (Mahto, 2009). Understanding these perspectives is crucial for multiple reasons, serving, to some extent, as precursors to future beliefs and attitudes (Armstrong, 2000). Such insights contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the origins of mental health challenges among young adults, considering both social and medical lenses.

Understanding mental health concerns among young adults within Arab and Western cultures holds significant importance for multiple reasons. Individuals construct perceptions regarding mental illness and those affected by it, influencing their conduct. Thus, public education becomes imperative to instigate positive changes in attitudes (Song et al., 2005). For instance, the concept of personal recovery in mental illness, predominantly formulated in Western contexts, may not be entirely applicable in non-Western settings such as Arab culture (Hickey et al., 2017). Furthermore, life challenges, encompassing perspectives on mental health sources, strategies for managing various relationships, and acceptable modes of expressing mental health concerns, underscore critical considerations. Notably, seeking help involves the expressed need for acknowledgement and engagement by adults, including parents, school staff, and other professionals, necessitating increased adult availability (Hellstrom & Beckman, 2021).

Religious dimensions significantly influence mental health perceptions across cultures, with notable variations between Islamic and Western traditions. Religion is generally understood as a system of recognized rules and beliefs shared by a group, while spirituality is often viewed as an individualized experience that seeks to address profound questions about life and its meaning (Astrow et al., 2001; Lucchetti et al., 2021). These distinctions highlight the diverse

ways in which religious and spiritual beliefs shape mental health understanding and practices across different cultural contexts. In Arab cultures, mental health is often intertwined with religious beliefs, emphasizing spiritual well-being as integral to psychological health. Cultural attributes influenced by Arab Muslim traditions, the significance of family, and the impact of socio-economic and religious realities collectively contribute to the conceptualization of mental illness in Arab contexts (Barbato et al., 2021). For instance, Islamic teachings emphasize mental health through principles found in the Quran and Hadith, promoting feelings of security and balance (Yuliharti et al., 2024). Islamic education, as articulated by Zakiah Daradjat, focuses on moral development and mental well-being, advocating for worship and community support as means to enhance mental health (Uswatun & Aulia, 2024; Putri & Ridlwan, 2024). Conversely, Western contexts exhibit a more diverse relationship between religion and mental health, shaped by individual beliefs and cultural settings. Mental health approaches in the West often adopt a biopsychosocial-spiritual model, recognizing the influence of spirituality alongside biological, psychological, and social factors (Ghuloum et al., 2024). While religion can provide emotional support and resilience, stigma surrounding mental illness remains prevalent and continues to affect help-seeking behaviours across various communities (Musa, 2024). This research identifies a distinct gap in mental health studies within Arab contexts, particularly regarding explanatory models of mental illness and the experiences of young adults. It seeks to explore and compare the mental health experiences of young adults in Algeria and the United Kingdom, highlighting cultural influences that shape mental health perceptions and the similarities and differences in how young adults from these two cultures navigate mental health challenges

2.4.1 Young adults Knowledge about mental health issues

Young adults globally, including those in Arab cultures and the United Kingdom, show a deficit in knowledge about mental health issues, encompassing conditions like depression, anxiety, and stress disorders (Izzah et al., 2022). Significant obstacle being insufficient knowledge about their conditions, leading to unwarranted delays in seeking treatment. Despite this, knowledge about mental health demonstrates a weak negative relationship with stigmatizing attitudes toward mental illness. However, it does not consistently translate into intentions to seek help for mental health problems (Safira, 2022). Recognizing the importance of mental health literacy becomes crucial for identifying gaps in knowledge and shaping interventions to enhance mental health awareness among young people.

Studies reveal a lack of awareness and understanding of mental health problems among young adults (Ahmed, 2018). In Arab cultures, young adults often have a limited understanding of mental health challenges, accompanied by negative attitudes and a reluctance to seek professional help (Al-Yateem et al., 2022; Al-Omari et al., 2020). Studies in Saudi Arabia indicate a moderately negative attitude toward mental illness, reflecting a lack of awareness and understanding (Al-Omari et al., 2023). However, experiences with mental illness seem to foster more positive attitudes, suggesting higher levels of mental health literacy among Arabs (Mahsoon et al., 2020). Unfortunately, there is a lack of specific studies addressing the knowledge of mental health among Algerian young adults. Contrastingly, in the United Kingdom, despite ongoing commitments to improving the mental health and well-being of young people, the incidence of mental health issues continues to rise (Holding et al., 2022). In the UK, evidence suggests that knowledge of mental health and illness among young people is low (Pinfold et al., 2003) and that there is both factual ignorance and emotionally charged prejudice against mentally ill people (Rose et al., 2007). Importantly, the experiences and approaches of young adults in the UK toward mental health remain less explored. The research should focus more on the link between culture and mental health on British and Algerian

populations, necessitating indigenous studies before implementing Western conceptions of good functioning to Muslims. There was a lack of investigation concerning level of knowledge and awareness of young adults in western and Arab cultures. As most researchers did not assess the kind of knowledge young adults have about the symptoms causes and consequences of mental health issues which this research did.

2.5 Mental health in Algeria and United Kingdom

The Arab world comprises a diverse population of Arabic-speaking individuals from 22 countries in North Africa and the Middle East. This group has a combined population exceeding 380 million (The World Bank, 2014), Not everyone who lives in the Middle East and Northern Africa is considered an Arab. However, the ethnic and religious makeup of Arab countries varies widely, and this has repercussions for any conclusions or implications that can be drawn from research with this population. The Arab world, consisting of 22 countries (Algeria, Bahrain, Comoros, Djibouti, Egypt, Iraq, Jordan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Libya, Morocco, Mauritania, Oman, Palestine, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Somalia, Sudan, Syria, Tunisia, United Arab Emirates, and Yemen), is home to roughly 5% of the world's population, with 60% being under the age of 25 years. The area has a high burden of mental health disorders (GBD, 2015). It is a multi-ethnic and multi-religious community with a shared language and cultural values and beliefs. Given underfunded health systems, mental health stigma, insufficient research capacity and training, sociocultural changes, political instability and conflict, and economic inequalities as contributors (Alzahrani, 2020; Maalouf et al., 2019), such a high burden will require ongoing efforts towards the development of effective and culturally congruent psychological interventions in response.

Algeria is a north African developing country with a predominantly Muslim population adhering to a traditional collectivistic culture. In examining the mental health of Arab people,

including those in Algeria, it becomes evident that this field is under-researched. The Arab world is not immune to the high prevalence of mental disorders. However, a lack of information about mental health statistics in the region can present a barrier to mental health research (Ghanem et al., 2009). Limited research has been conducted on mental health in Arab countries, with only five countries having some studies (Daouk et al., 2023) which are Egypt (Ghanem et al., 2009), Iraq (Alhasnawi et al., 2009), Lebanon (Karam et al., 2008), Morocco (Kadri et al. 2010), and Qatar (Bener et al., 2015). However, these studies also indicate substantial delays in treatment initiation and highlight that only a minority of Arabs with mental disorders ever received professional treatment (Karam et al., 2008). The mental health human resources and the attention devoted to mental health issues are still insufficient in the Arab world.

Furthermore, In Algeria, mental health issues among young adults are a growing concern, with surveys highlighting the increasing prevalence of mental disorders and the demand for mental health care (Seridi & Belaadi, 2022). Algeria has undertaken several actions and devoted various resources to improve mental health services in the prevention and management of mental disorders. Indeed, the increase in mental disorders and the demand for care make mental health a major social issue (Seridi & Berlaadi, 2022). However, the coverage and supply of mental health care remain insufficient and unevenly distributed (Seridi & Belaadi, 2022). The current mental health law in Algeria, originating from the French colonial era, needs amendments to improve care and protect those with mental disorders from abuse (Estingoy et al., 2013). Public health policies in Algeria should allocate more resources to enhance mental health services (Benmebarek, 2017). Despite the implementation of an ambitious mental health promotion plan in Algeria since 2017, its effectiveness in improving mental health services, preventing mental disorders, and safeguarding patient rights is yet to be determined (Seridi & Belaadi, 2022). Comparing Algeria to other Arab and Western cultures reveals a significant

gap in understanding the mental health experiences of young adults. Lack of data, statistics, or research in this area hinders comprehensive comparisons.

Mental disorders, despite being a leading cause of disability in the Arab region, receive only few global outputs in mental health research. In the other hand Mental health research in the United Kingdom has been more extensive compared to Arab countries. The UK has a higher research output, with a greater number of publications and higher quality studies (Hassan et al.,2022). In the past decade, mental health research output in the Arab region has increased, but it still lags behind the UK (Karam & Itani, 2015). The UK has a higher number of articles per capita and a wider range of research topics. the requirement for highly trained researchers in mental health domain in Arab countries including Algeria and professionals, a frequent weakness in the mental health sector of developing countries, and challenges faced by health professionals in these regions.

In recent years, Western culture has witnessed a significant focus on and acknowledgment of mental health. This is reflected in the increased accessibility of mental health services, the implementation of campaigns to diminish stigma, and the incorporation of mental health support across various sectors, including education, workplaces, and healthcare systems (Zolezzi et al., 2018; Al-Krenawi, 2005). However, the typical psychiatric and psychological approaches applied in high-income western countries may not translate well to the underdeveloped world. The realm of mental health in Arab culture poses distinctive challenges and considerations (Al-Krenawi, 2005). While progress has been made in promoting mental health awareness in Western culture, evident through the widespread availability of mental health services across sectors, there is still much work to be done in Algeria to enhance understanding and support for mental health issues. Achieving a comprehensive understanding of mental health in both Western (UK) and Arab cultures (Algeria) necessitate recognizing the unique cultural factors that shape attitudes, beliefs, and practices surrounding mental health.

2.6 Western psychotherapy versus Arab traditional healing

Understanding the cultural influences on mental health experiences and attitudes is critical to bridging this gap. Cultural factors can alter response patterns, resulting in psychiatric problems. Viswanath and Chaturvedi (2012) found that mental illness has a significant influence on symptoms, behaviour, frequency, perception, and responses. Even willingness to accept psychotherapy is culturally influenced (Yalvac et al., 2015). Cultures have a huge impact on healing and therapeutic methods.

The Perceptions of mental illnesses in Arab and Western cultures significantly Mold experiences and understandings of mental health issues (Islam, 2008). Altweck et al. (2015) highlight that knowledge and positive beliefs about mental disorders are more prevalent in European and North American cultures compared to Asian and African cultures. Pedersen and Pope (2016) emphasized on these diverse perspectives, that require heightened awareness, knowledge, and skills to prevent misconceptions and foster a comprehensive understanding while promoting appropriate actions. This suggests that mental health experiences are not universally understood but are shaped by cultural contexts.

Comparing Western cultures like the UK and Arab cultures like Algeria reveals significant differences in mental health perception and approach. When talking about mental health and psychotherapy in the west most researchers focus on three main western concepts and mainly focus on the ideas provided by Sigmund Freud (1856-1939) from psychoanalysis, J.B. Watson (1879-1958) and Skinner (1904-1990) from behaviourism and Abraham Maslow (1908-1970) and Carl Rogers (1902-1987) from humanistic psychology (Abdulrazak et al., 2019). for example, Psychotherapy in humanistic psychology is based on client-centred therapy. It invites individuals to discover their real selves (Abdul Razak et al., 2019). Psychotherapy generally involves sessions with a psychologist aimed at helping patients with mental health issues

explore their inner selves and providing guidance to address their problems or cope with them in a more positive manner. This differs from traditional healing methods.

Psychotherapy may not be universally applicable across all cultures and countries, as each culture has its own perspectives and views regarding the appropriate treatment of mental health issues. Orlinsky et al. (1999) note that a few theoretical orientations of Western origin tend to dominate psychotherapy practice, raising questions about their universal applicability. This is particularly relevant given the cultural reflection inherent in each psychotherapy model. Mishu, Tindal, and Gega (2023) point out that many psychological interventions are shaped by Western cultural environments, posing uncertainties about their relevance to populations from Arab societies. In the United Kingdom, mental health is predominantly considered a medical issue, with professional aid being the primary point of contact (Ayub & Macaulay, 2023) which is largely based on verbalization that may pose challenges for noncommunicative individuals from cultures where verbalization is less reinforced (Uzoka, 1983). In contrast, Islamic psychology, which is rooted in the Islamic tradition, offers a "science of the soul" and its own treatment modalities. Traditionalist Muslims may view psychotherapy as a threat to Islam and prefer religious remedies such as Qur'anic recitation and prayer (Akwash, 2017). However, there is a need for integration between Islamic spirituality and psychotherapy, as some Muslim clinicians are synthesizing Islam with Western therapeutic approaches. The concept of mental health and psychotherapy in Islamic psychology is being explored and compared with Western mainstream psychology. In most Arab cultures traditional healing considered as the first point of treatments of the mental health issues. The WHO (2008) defines traditional medicine as "the sum total of the knowledge, skills, and practices based on the theories, beliefs, and experiences indigenous to different cultures, whether explicable or not, used in the maintenance of health as well as in the prevention, diagnosis, improvement, or treatment of physical and mental illness." Traditional medical systems, influenced by social, religious, and spiritual concepts,

classify mental distress based on their cultural understanding of suffering. Muslims may express reservations about psychology due to its perceived secular nature (Haque & Masuan, 2002). For Example, In Algeria, cultural factors, including the Muslim religion and social changes, are associated with mental illness rates and symptoms (Al-Issa, 1990). In terms of religion, Arab culture has a rich culture rooted in values and beliefs, with an exceptional focus on spirituality. Religion stands out as the most important and distinguishing component of Arab society. It is vital to highlight that Arab nations differ in terms of religion, with Islam dominating the area (Basurah et al., 2022). In many other Arab societies, spiritual or religious healing plays a significant role in treating mental health issues among young adults (Mou and Albagmi, 2022). Traditional Arabic and Islamic medicines are based on the concept of restoring bodily balance through diet, lifestyle, exercise, body cleansing, and mental, physical, and spiritual health (Al-Rawi et al., 2017). In Algeria, alternative medicine incorporates practices and beliefs from the Holy Quran and Hadith to prevent and treat health problems. This comprises herbal medications, spiritual treatments, dietary habits, mind-body practices, and manual techniques for treating, diagnosing, and preventing illness (Al-Rawi et al., 2017). Algerian society faces significant controversy regarding psychotherapy and medical remedies for mental health illnesses, despite the prevalence of traditional and spiritual healing practices. This gap suggests a need for future research and integration into the wider healthcare system. Nevertheless, some negative attitudes associate religious involvement with worse outcomes, creating a separation between religion and medicine (Almeida et al., 2014; Levin, 2010). This has resulted in negative perceptions of addressing spiritual and religious beliefs in clinical practice (Levin, 2010). The integration of spirituality and religion into therapy remains an understudied area, particularly in the UK (Baheretibeb et al., 2021). The lack of information underscores the need for a systematic approach, feasible in resource-constrained settings, addressing cultural attitudes for effective mental health interventions and service engagement.

Disparities in seeking professional versus informal support for mental health issues highlight the nuanced influence of cultural and religious beliefs. Badu, Mitchell et al. (2023) emphasize that decisions regarding treatment pathways are shaped by belief systems, attitudes, and acceptability. This raises questions about the applicability of both UK's and Algerian psychotherapy and traditional healing interventions, considering their cultural origins. little information exists on the provision of culturally competent mental health services that take faith seriously.

The separation between religion and psychotherapy in treating mental health varies between Arab and Western cultures. In Western cultures, there has been a historical divide between religion and psychotherapy, with modern Western psychology often seen as antithetical to religious beliefs (Sotillos, 2021). This has led to stigma and misunderstanding about participating in therapy within the Muslim community (Carle, 2019). However, there is a growing recognition of the need for cultural and spiritual competencies within the field of mental health (Abdul Razak et al., 2019). There is also a growing trend to seek religious healing and alternative therapies that integrate the mind and spirit. Overall, the integration of religion and psychotherapy in treating mental health varies between Arab and Western cultures, with efforts being made to bridge the gap and provide culturally competent mental health services.

2.7 Multicultural beliefs and attitudes towards mental health

The influence of cultural background on mental illness can be observed in various aspects, including the conception, perception, experience of symptoms, recognition and labelling, classification, treatment, and course of mental illness (Kleinman, 1977; Ng, 1997). This interplay between cultural elements and mental health is derived from unobserved causes

leading to observable behaviours, resulting in a profound connection between mental health issues and cultural attitudes and beliefs.

The recognition of mental disorders on a global scale, acknowledged across diverse cultures, emphasizes the importance of cultural elements in shaping individuals' attitudes and beliefs towards mental health. The attitudes of lay individuals towards mental illness, as described by Choudhry et al. (2016) are shaped by personal knowledge, interactions with individuals experiencing mental illness, and cultural stereotypes. This emphasizes the pervasive impact on one's perceptions of mental health. Burns (1982) further highlights the importance of an individual's beliefs and self-assessments in determining their behaviours, which ultimately affect their self-esteem. Importantly, this effect is linked with cultural and societal reactions to mental health problems. to determine responsibility for behaviour by distinguishing between internal factors (such as character, ability, personality) and external factors (such as environment, social situations) (Heider ,1958). This explores the potential for individuals to change social structures that affect their lives, highlight the fundamental relationship between an individual and society (Spencer & Doull, 2015) as psychological processes and culture both influence each other, with individual thoughts and actions influencing cultural norms and practices, and cultural norms and practices influencing individual thoughts and actions (Lehman et al., 2004). This emphasizes the significance of understanding the impact of cultural background on mental illness.

Many research studies acknowledge that there is a greater knowledge, positive attitudes, and high level of awareness about mental health in western societies compared to Arab or non-western societies. Positive attitudes toward mental health in the United Kingdom indicate an increase in acceptance and understanding of mental health concerns (Liimatainen & Gabriel, 2000) for example in England, despite having unfavourable attitudes about the causes of

mental disorders, the general population views mental illness positively and believes that people with mental health difficulties should be integrated into society (Kotera et al., 2023), with these attitudes significantly influencing their acceptance and social integration, possibly influenced by their mental illness knowledge (Wolf et al., 1996). Efforts have been made to improve access and support for individuals experiencing mental health issues, aiming for a pluralist, integrated, and well-funded reform led by joint professional and patient interests (Ikkos et al., 2022). This assertion finds support in the work of other researchers who have noted heightened awareness not only within society but also with government initiatives specifically targeting the reduction of stigma and enhancement of access to mental health treatments (Okasha et al., 2012). Anti-stigma endeavours have been implemented in the UK to diminish prejudice and foster positive treatment for individuals grappling with mental illnesses (Rossetto et al., 2019). In Somerset, a radical redesign of mental health services aimed to deliver an experience of "no wrong door" and bridge the gap between secondary and primary care (Yeandle et al., 2022). Additionally, the implementation of Peer Supported Open Dialogue (POD) teams in the NHS has shown significant improvements in clinical outcomes and experiences for service users and their families (Yip, 2022). The availability of mental health services and the multifaceted strategy to reduce stigma in the United Kingdom foster a more supportive environment for those with mental health challenges.

Despite efforts to reduce stigma and improve mental health services, there still exists a significant level of stigma in the British society. Various sources highlight the persistence of mental health stigma in the UK. Research published on PMC indicates that while there have been improvements in knowledge, attitudes, and desire for social distance regarding mental health stigma, there are still inequalities that need further improvement (Henderson et al., 2020) and despite initiatives like Time to change in England, there are still significant levels of mental illness stigma, with variations across regions and age groups (Henderson et al., 2020)

such as the regional differences in mental health stigma have been observed, with areas like London and southern regions tending to exhibit more negative attitudes towards mental illness (Bhavsar et al., 2019). Despite progress made by campaigns, the persistence of mental health stigma in the UK necessitates continued efforts to analyse its effects and implement targeted interventions at societal and personal levels. Addressing these barriers is essential to ensure improved access to mental health care and support for individuals dealing with mental health challenges.

In contrast, within the Arab world, cultural norms, governed by unwritten rules deeply rooted in religion, history, and tradition, heavily influenced by traditional values and Islam, shape perspectives on mental health. Arab-Islamic culture plays a pivotal role in shaping understanding and treatment preferences in the realm of mental health, presenting significant barriers to professional help-seeking. The absence of formal mental health treatment concepts, coupled with perceived stigma, limited-service availability, cultural dissonance, restricted budget allocation, and deficits in health system functioning, collectively hinder the utilization of mental health services and negative community judgments further compound these challenges, fostering a reliance on Arabic resources (Edlund et al., 2008; Okasha et al., 2012; Elqasir & Ohtsuka, 2023). Consequently, mental health discussions are considered taboo in Arab societies, discouraging open conversations (Jallad, 2024). A longitudinal study by Link and colleagues, involving participants previously diagnosed with a mental illness, explored aspects such as self-esteem, perception of potential devaluation or discrimination, and the extent of social withdrawal to avoid rejection due to stigma (Link et al., 2001). Having a mental illness in Arab cultures can be perceived as violating cultural norms, posing particular challenges.

Beliefs attributing mental health disorders to spiritual causes are prevalent (Al-Habeeb, 2003). For example, Algerian culture, characterized by diverse beliefs, reflects in its approach to mental health (Seridi & Belaadi, 2022). It is often associated with beliefs in Jinn spirits, external factors like persecution and sorcery, and the evil eye. The term "Jinnoon," meaning crazy, originates from the word Jinn, reflecting the cultural understanding of mental health issues. The evil eye, a common belief causing physical and mental sickness, is believed to be driven by envy, jealousy, or admiration. In Algerian society, the evil eye is seen as a punishment for individuals who exceed certain limits (Al-Issa, 1989; Al-Issa, 1990). The role of supernatural, religious, and magical approaches to mental illness in Algeria is prevailing. Because the Qur'an (Islamic sacred book) speaks about mental health in spiritual terms, physical illness, on top of mental illness, is also seen as a spiritual disease (Islam & Campbell, 2014). Even though no connection between spirit-possession and madness or mental illness was found (Islam & Campbell, 2014). Regardless of the physical or mental illness, Algerian Muslims do not view these as a medical connection but rather a spiritual one. This view could impact the pathway to care, leading to scepticism towards mental health services and treatments offered (Al-Issa, 1989). There is a research gap regarding mental health beliefs, treatments, and service utilization in Algerian and Arab Muslim communities.

In Summary, cultural attitudes and beliefs significantly impact mental health processes, affecting aetiology, causes, cultural meanings, distress expression, diagnostics, assessment, prevalence, help-seeking, coping styles, treatment, and policy (Hwang, 2016). The acceptance and acknowledgment of mental health concerns in British and Algerian societies are influenced by cultural distinctions between individualistic Western cultures and collectivist Arab cultures. The degree to which cultures are individualistic versus collectivistic may moderate the association between wellbeing and health (Okley et al., 2018). This spectrum of individualism

versus collectivism plays a role in shaping perceptions of mental health and attitudes toward accepting, understanding, and seeking help. In more individualistic cultures, such as those in the UK and other Western societies, there is a prioritization of individual autonomy, independence, and personal achievement, promoting self-reliance and seeking personal fulfilment, including the management of mental health issues. This shows the biomedical lens of the western culture, with an emphasis on the individual's experience and autonomy in seeking help. This perspective can lead to greater openness and acceptance of mental health issues and a willingness to access mental health services (U.S Department of Health and Human services. 2001). On the other hand, Arab countries, including Algeria, are often classified as collectivist cultures, where social systems heavily influence identity and decisions. in collectivist cultures, mental health is attributed to supernatural forces or as a spiritual issue, and there is a strong emphasis on the family and community's role in an individual's life (Krstanoska-Blazeska et al., 2021). In individualistic British culture, wellbeing is primarily related to self-esteem and personal achievement, while in collectivistic Algerian culture, it is primarily about interpersonal goals and avoiding social conflict. These cultural differences may be attributed to cultural factors rather than country-specific factors. This cultural framework can impact how mental health issues are perceived and addressed that potentially accompanied by a higher degree of stigma and social rejection for those facing mental health problems (Wahass & Kent, 1997). This can result in mental health issues being seen as a source of shame or stigma, not just for the individual but for their family and community as well. Despite changes in social perceptions and attitudes toward mental illness, restrictive cultural beliefs and social norms continue to shape Arab societies.

2.8 Mental health issues Coping strategies among young adults.

Lazarus (1993) defined coping as a response to “*ongoing cognitive and behavioural demands that are taxing or exceeding the resources of the person*” (p. 237). The way one deals with stress is an important component to protect individuals from psychological and physiological harm (Pearlin & Schooler, 1978; Thome & Espelage, 2004,). There are four main approaches to dealing with stress: approach (vigilant) coping, avoidant coping, problem-focused coping, and emotion-focused coping (Straub, 2014). Approach (vigilant) coping is attempting to deal with the problem by directly confronting the stressor. Problem-oriented coping is doing something constructive to problem solve. Emotion-oriented coping is managing the uncomfortable effect associated with a stressor, and avoidance-oriented coping is seeking a distraction or social diversion. However, there is little agreement as to the structure of coping, with at least 100 coping taxonomies and 400 lower-order categories proposed in the literature (Skinner et al., 2003).

The transactional theory of Coping (TTC) acknowledges that coping is a complex process influenced by various factors and is subject to change over time. Contributing to its complex nature, coping is strategies are both specific to situation and individual (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Lazarus and Folkman's stress and coping theory is a critical psychological framework that distinguishes two types of coping strategies: problem-focused coping, which addresses the source of distress, and emotion-focused coping, which regulates the emotion caused by the distress. (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). The first category addresses stress by providing information, making plans, or confronting it, whereas the second category addresses emotional distress by denying, avoiding, or seeking help. The TTC proposes that individuals continuously appraise the demands of their environment in relation to their coping abilities, and stress and negative emotions occur when the environment exceeds perceived coping abilities (Kaveh et al., 2023). Additionally, it highlights the role of cognitive, emotional, and behavioural processes in response to stressful stimuli, emphasizing the importance of appraisal in shaping

coping responses (Genoese, Harkey & Baez, 2023). The theory also recognizes the impact of social support and positive reappraisal in enhancing coping skills and reducing perceived stress (Wolf & Fisher, 2022). The TTC provides a comprehensive understanding of coping, considering individual differences, situational factors, and the dynamic nature of the process.

However, the research of TTC theory of Lazarus and Folkman has identified several gaps and areas that require further empirical investigation. Skinner et al. (2003) criticised the study by Lazarus and Folkman. They said that TTC theory suggests that coping strategies can serve both functions, such as problem-solving and emotional calm, and that the binary classification may not fully capture the nuanced ways people cope with stress. They only highlighted the importance of self-solving problems and did not consider the cultural values and social structures that might shape individuals' coping mechanisms. Carver et al. (1989) support Skinner's idea that problem-focused and emotion-focused coping are useful but insufficient. A Multidimensional Coping Inventory (MCI) was developed by Carver et al, (1989) to assess different ways people respond to stress. Five scales (of four items each) measure conceptually distinct aspects of problem-focused coping (active coping, planning, suppression of competing activities, restraint coping, seeking of instrumental social support); five scales measure aspects of what could be viewed as emotional-focused coping (seeking of emotional social support, positive reinterpretation, acceptance, denial, turning to religion); and three scales measure coping responses that arguably are less useful. Coping mechanisms are diverse and influenced by individual and cultural factors. The effectiveness of these strategies is closely tied to cultural norms, beliefs, and societal expectations. MCI acknowledges the importance of understanding both personal and cultural coping mechanisms. It is essential to recognize that the interpretation and success of coping strategies can vary due to cultural influences. Researchers should consider coping mechanisms in different cultural context to gain a comprehensive understanding of how individuals cope with stress and challenges across different cultural

backgrounds. Olah (1995) stated Coping culture is a crucial factor that influences the type of coping adopted, acting as both an internal, value-laden variable and an external variable that encourages conformity in habits and attitudes.

2.8.1 Western Self Reliance coping strategy

Culture influences the development of various coping strategies, while individual experiences shape the chosen coping strategy. Stressful experiences and efforts to cope with mental health issues are central to understanding psychological distress and psychopathology during the period between adolescence and young adulthood. Mental health issues during adolescence offer a particularly interesting opportunity for understanding the role of stress and coping processes in adolescent psychopathology (Compas et al., 1993) An understanding of young adults coping structure is crucial to explaining the impact of mental health challenges as individuals progress towards an adult life (Compas et al., 2001). There are numerous coping strategies that differ among young adults in various cultures. In the United Kingdom, young adults hold stigmatizing beliefs about mental health, acting as a barrier to seeking help for emotional or mental health difficulties (Gagne et al., 2022). These beliefs contribute to a preference for self-reliance and a reluctance to approach others for help. Mitchel et al. (2017) stated that 35% of young adults in the UK experiencing emotional difficulties did not seek help due to perceived stigma, difficulty expressing concerns, and a preference for self-reliance. Social attitudes towards mental illness can influence their self-reporting of mental health problems. According to them, total self-reliance is an unrealistic goal for any adult; we are all social beings and in need of support. There is a growing body of evidence relating to the resilience of young people that identifies fundamental building blocks: a secure base, self-esteem from being valued, and being enabled to exercise control in their lives. Reaching out to young people who are more likely to be experiencing mental health difficulties, especially

where the aforementioned factors do not apply or have been lost, for example during transitions, should be a collective societal goal (Mitchel et al., 2017). Difficulty in identifying or expressing concerns and limited awareness of available social or professional support hinder expressing mental health problems among young adults. In Arab cultures, the research has not sufficiently addressed self-reliance coping strategies specifically among young adults facing mental health issue. Understanding the similarities and differences in coping strategies among young adults within the same age range is crucial. Existing research has not adequately explored cultural factors shaping coping strategies among young adults and whether these strategies alleviate or exacerbate mental health challenges. It is unclear whether self-reliance is a cultural choice or a personal choice (a consequence of an introverted nature). Understanding these factors is essential for developing effective interventions. Exploring coping strategies in Arab and Western cultures offers valuable insights for developing culturally sensitive and effective mental health support systems.

2.8.2 Arab Religious coping: Self Control

Another significant area of research that has been explored is the role of self-control among young adults in Muslim or Arab cultures. Existing research presents strong evidence linking self-control to positive mental health outcomes, with an association between spirituality and mental health potentially mediated through one's self-control. This proposition is rooted in the theory that the evolution of religion and spirituality is related to cultural adaptations aimed at promoting self-control. Several possible explanations suggest that spiritual individuals may engage in self-monitoring due to a fear of a higher power (Shroff et al., 2023). Religious practices, a significant aspect of coping in Arab cultures, play a crucial role in providing solace to individuals facing negative experiences or emotional distress. Muslims employ various religious practices, such as belief, trust in God, prayer, forbearance, supplication, recitation of

the Quran, remembrance of God, patience, thankfulness, and seeking guidance from religious leaders, to cope with life stressors (Krenawi, 2005; Achour et al., 2016; Adam & Ward, 2016). The multi-faceted nature of Muslim religious coping has been emphasized, with specific attention to both inner aspects (personal relationship with God) and outer aspects (religious rituals and interactions with others) as crucial components of faith (Khan & Watson, 2006; Abu Raiya et al., 2008). This diversity in religious coping strategies suggests varying effects on mental well-being outcomes.

The relationship between spirituality and psychological well-being requires a distinction between institutional religion and spirituality. Spirituality can exist both within and outside religious frameworks, while religion is a systematic set of ideas, rituals, and worship, with some focusing on traditions and social relationships (Woods et al., 1999; Nelson et al., 2002). The effects of religion and spirituality on youth are historically understudied but an emerging area of research (Johnson, 2008). This emerging field has been galvanized by findings relating religious or spiritual variables to many positive outcomes (Eisenberg et al., 2011). Research on spirituality, religiosity, and psychological well-being is extensive, but the mechanisms behind these associations remain unclear, particularly regarding religious coping and their impact on adolescents and young adults.

The findings of several research studies have yielded diverse perspectives on the impact of religion as a coping strategy for well-being. Krägeloh et al. (2012) posits that religion plays a positive role in enhancing psychological well-being by serving as a valuable resource for managing stress. Several studies have identified a correlation between religious engagement and reduced risk of depression and suicidality in both the general population and medical samples (Miller et al., 1997; Koenig et al., 1998; Rasic et al., 2009). Furthermore, Religious, and spiritual coping not only reduces substance abuse and delinquency but also enhances well-being, hope, purpose, meaning, educational attainment, and treatment outcomes. (Johnson,

2008; Rosmarin et al., 2013). These capacities are thought to assist individuals in coping and fostering positive development. However, religious coping may also have adverse effects, as indicated by various research studies that highlight a complex link between spirituality/religious and mental health issues. Individuals identifying as spiritual or religious often face higher odds of mental health illnesses (Baetz et al., 2004, 2006) such as suicidal ideation, depression, anxiety and less wellbeing (Rosmarin et al., 2013). Despite the existence of studies highlighting both positive and negative effects of religious coping strategies, others have failed to establish or have found negative relationships between religiosity and mental health (Fitchett et al., 1999; Woods et al., 1999; Nelson et al., 2002). While others such as researcher McClain-Jacobson et al. (2004) find no association between spirituality and mental illness. It is crucial to recognize that religious coping strategies' affiliation is not uniformly damaging to mental health, nor does it consistently predict better mental health outcomes.

Research on religious coping strategies among young Muslim Arabs and other Western religions is limited, with little exploration of faith-based coping. This approach uses religious and spiritual beliefs to interpret stressful events or mental health challenges. Understanding how these individuals use faith-based coping mechanisms can provide insight into their mental health outcomes and overall well-being. This knowledge can inform culturally sensitive interventions and support systems that cater to the diverse religious backgrounds of these populations, ultimately improving their mental health outcomes.

2.8.3 Physical activity

Unfortunately, not all coping mechanisms are effective. In fact, using sleep to cope with stress is deemed a dysfunctional strategy (Carver et al., 1989). According to Bland et al. (2014), activities such as listening to music, sleeping, and surfing the Internet do not alleviate stress; instead, they may exacerbate it. On the contrary, seeking social support, engaging in social

interactions, and participating in vigorous physical activity, stretching exercises, and strength training have proven to be more effective in dealing with stress. Exercise has been recognized as a beneficial coping mechanism. Røset (2019) emphasizes the significance of regular physical activity from a young age. It is considered an effective self-help method managing worrying in stressed young adults (Bruin et al., 2016). Numerous studies have found that exercise is beneficial in reducing depression and anxiety, enhancing mood states, fostering appreciative thinking, cognitive performance, academic achievement and instilling a sense of normalcy (Thome and Espelage, 2004; Biddle & Asare, 2011; Rastad, Martin & Asenlöf, 2014; Hargreaves et al., 2017). For example, Activities with low to moderate intensity, like walking, have been shown to be useful for increased social engagement, working through thoughts, and reducing perceived stress levels. Walking in nature has been particularly effective in promoting realistic and constructive reflections (Hargreaves et al., 2017; Rastad et al., 2014). The role of physical activity as a coping style is a crucial component of psychological well-being, and exercise behaviour not only enhances physical health but also contributes to psychological well-being.

Cultural differences in attitudes towards physical activity and mental health can be observed between Western and Arab cultures. In Western cultures, physical activity to cope with mental health issues is commonly accepted and practiced (Netz et al, 2011). However, social support and encouragement were identified as crucial factors in overcoming barriers to engaging in physical activity. Several barriers preventing people from being physically active have been identified in studies, with one major obstacle being the lack of someone to exercise with (Firth et al., 2018). Additionally, social anxiety, the influence of symptoms, low motivation, low self-confidence, and anxiety about utilizing facilities alongside others have frequently been found in studies (Soundy et al., 2014; Firth et al., 2016).

While Others cope with their emotions in healthier ways, such as through exercise, which can increase stress tolerance (Bland et al., 2014). Many turn to social supports, such as religious communities (Bland et al, 2014). in Arab culture, there may be lower adherence to physical activity recommendations for coping with mental health issues. Cultural beliefs can limit physical activities to cope with mental health issues (Bahroon & King, 2022). Some religious or cultural beliefs may act as barriers to practicing physical activity (Zolezzi et al., 2018). These barriers may be further exacerbated by acculturative stress (Slewa-Younan et al., 2020). However, it is important to note that religiosity, can indirectly play a role in managing stress through socialization, family support, and the adoption of coping strategies (El Halabi et al., 2020). Interestingly, individuals in Arabic communities tend to exhibit flexibility in addressing these religious and cultural issues. Although the use of religious coping strategies is evident from research, the precise reasons behind the impact of cultural beliefs on physical activity as a coping mechanism remain unclear. Nevertheless, it is recognized that self-stigma or social stigma may be linked to this phenomenon. It is essential to consider the complex interplay between cultural norms, religiosity, social support structures, and individual coping strategies when addressing the impact of cultural beliefs on physical activity engagement among individuals with mental health issues. Research on coping mechanisms across various cultures, particularly among young adults, plays a crucial role in understanding stress reduction strategies and enhancing daily well-being. The importance of exploring how self-reliance, religious coping methods, and participation in physical activities are connected to enhanced emotional and behavioural well-being in Western and Arab cultures cannot be overstated; however, there exists a significant gap in the literature regarding the comparison of coping strategies across diverse cultural backgrounds. Previous studies have identified techniques that are generally viewed as "adaptive" without considering the cultural context. Nevertheless, this research demonstrates how cultural variations influence preferences for coping strategies -

emphasizing the need to acknowledge that the efficacy of these strategies may be shaped by cultural beliefs, norms, and societal influences. A comparative study provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of these strategies and their implications for stress management techniques.

2.9 Multicultural Help seeking behaviours.

Mental health help-seeking behaviours among young adults in both Algerian and British cultures encompass a spectrum of formal and informal sources of support. Rickwood and Thomas (2012) define help-seeking for mental health problems as an adaptive coping process, denoting the attempt to seek external assistance in addressing mental health concerns. The inclination towards seeking help is influenced by the presence of a perceived need, while attitudes reflect a general inclination, where acculturation significantly shapes both behaviour and attitude (Ying & Miller, 1992). The pathways to seeking help are intricately structured by the convergence of psychosocial and cultural factors, serving as a framework that integrates knowledge about mental health care use and accessibility (Rogler & Cortes, 1993). The process of help-seeking for mental health problems can indeed be categorized into formal and informal pathways. Formal help-seeking involves turning to credentialed health and mental health professionals such as doctors, psychiatrists, counsellors, psychologists, teachers, and youth workers. Informal help-seeking, on the other hand, involves seeking support from non-professional sources such as family, friends, and community members, including religious leaders (Brown et al., 2014; Lynch et al., 2023). This The dynamics of formal and informal help vary, with individuals in recovery actively choosing their roles and maintaining a complementary approach (Lauzier-Jobin & Houle, 2021). which entails interpersonal interactions aimed at gaining relevant understanding, advice, and supportive action in response to problems or distressing experiences (Rickwood et al., 2005).

Despite the persistent global public health challenges concerning the underdiagnosis and treatment of mental health conditions in young people (Polanczyk et al., 2015), the rate of formal help-seeking among young adults remains alarmingly low. Shockingly, one in four young individuals grappling with mental health difficulties has no contact with either formal or informal support systems (Sadler et al., 2018). This reluctance to seek help is further intensified by the discouragement of seeking treatment for mental health issues among young adults, even though alternative coping mechanisms could offer potential benefits. Accordingly, Understanding the factors that influence youth mental health help-seeking processes is critical for providing timely and appropriate interventions that can lead to better outcomes for young people (WHO, 2021).

2.9.1 Barriers accessing Formal mental health support among young adults.

Access to timely care is a quality standard underpinning many international healthcare models, especially for the treatment of mental health problems in young people, as prolonged absences can lead to chronic issues due to their complexity and potential for recurrence (Patton et al., 2014; Collizzi et al., 2020). Despite the expectation of seeking aid, few seek professional care, highlighting the need for more effective mental health support. This is concerning as it can lead to a treatment gap and further distress and impairment in their lives (Sanghvi et al., 2023). Examining the barriers to accessing mental health services for young adults, studies consistently report poor rates of treatment access. Approximately 18 to 34% of young people with high levels of depression or anxiety symptoms actively seek professional help (Gulliver et al., 2010). National surveys in the UK, Australia, and the USA estimate that only 25–56% of young people with mental health disorders access specialist mental health services (Green et al., 2005; Merinkangas et al., 2011). In Arab countries such as Lebanon, the number of individuals with mental disorders not receiving treatment is significantly higher than in

Western countries (Karam et al., 2006). The reason might be that the discrepancy in seeking assistance for personal mental health issues is partially due to the perception that consulting a mental health professional is a Western cultural concept of mental health care (Pheko et al., 2013; Mbutia et al. 2018) or they have the perspective of encompassing practices such as traditional medicine and religion (Dogra et al., 2012; Pheko et al., 2013; Mbutia et al., 2018). Additionally, in certain regions, seeking professional help for mental health concerns may be considered taboo (Al-Krenawi et al., 2009; Bilican, 2013). Notably, there are particularly low rates of access for internalizing compared to externalizing problems (Green et al., 2005; Merikangas et al., 2011).

Numerous barriers surround accessing mental health support for young people, with studies examining the reasons for this reluctance to seek help. These barriers are divided between personal beliefs about mental health issues and social beliefs. A systematic review conducted by Radez et al. (2021) highlighted the main reasons young adults do not seek professional help, including negative perceptions of help-seeking, a lack of mental health knowledge, and mental health stigma and embarrassment. Young people reported problems with committing to the process of professional help-seeking, mostly preferring to rely on themselves when facing difficulties. Unfavourable attitudes towards mental illness and self-stigma of help-seeking, particularly related to viewing people with mental disorders as different and fearing a decrease in their own worth if they seek help (Harvey & White, 2023). Another study emphasized the role of emotion self-stigma, referring to the belief that experiencing and expressing negative emotions is unacceptable, in predicting help-seeking intentions among young adults (Samari et al., 2022). Another systematic review of parent-reported barriers to accessing professional help for their child's mental health problems identified barriers related to systemic/structural obstacles (e.g., costs, waiting times), attitudes towards service providers and psychological treatment (e.g., trust and confidence in professionals, perceived effectiveness of treatment),

knowledge and understanding of mental health problems and the help-seeking process (e.g., recognition of the problem, knowing where to get help), and family circumstances (e.g., other responsibilities and family's support network) (Readon et al., 2017). To bridge the gap between the high prevalence of mental health disorders in young people and the low utilization of professional help, it's essential to understand why young individuals, rather than parents or professionals, often refrain from seeking assistance. This highlights the intrinsic relationship between humans and culture. Culture is not just a part of human existence; it's integral, shaping beliefs, behaviours, and expressions of creativity. Each person has a unique cultural identity that influences their perceptions and responses to mental health issues. Therefore, comprehending the cultural context is crucial for understanding help-seeking behaviours and addressing barriers to accessing mental health services.

2.9.2 Mental health services Access in the United Kingdom and Arab countries

Mental illness, and specifically accessibility to adequate care, is manifested differently in various parts of the world. For instance, about 42% of the individuals coping with mental illnesses in Western countries receive no formal treatment, while this figure is nearly double in non-Western countries (Bedi, 2018). considerations of access to mental healthcare for people with common mental health disorders have largely been restricted to concerns about recognition of mental health disorders by primary care 'gatekeepers' and the difficulties of training professionals to improve recognition and referral (National Collaborating Centre for Mental Health UK, 2011). Mental health concerns provide substantial obstacles for individuals, caregivers, and healthcare systems. While treatments have been shown to be beneficial, many people are still disadvantaged because they lack access to basic care or receive inadequate assistance (Dowrick et al., 2009). New approaches are required to comprehend these difficulties and provide answers.

In the United Kingdom, efforts have been made to improve and embed mental health support within schools and colleges through initiatives outlined in the 2018 Green Paper on YP's mental health. These measures include introducing a designated lead for mental health support, funding new mental health support teams, and piloting a four-week waiting time for access to specialist support (Department of Health and Social Care & Department of Education, 2018). The NHS Long Term Plan (NHS England, 2019) also proposed funding community-based mental health services for young people. However, these policies have faced criticism for focusing on joined up working rather than increasing service capacity (Griffin et al., 2022). The strain on specialist service provision is exacerbated by continued funding cuts (Edbrooke-Childs & Deighton, 2020). These research studies on mental health services in the UK are lacking in focus on improving service quality, cultural competency, cost reduction, and technology use. These aspects are crucial for healthcare practitioners to meet diverse needs and provide accessible treatment. A holistic approach addressing quantity, quality, and accessibility of mental health services is needed to create a comprehensive and effective support system.

In contrast to Arab countries, young adults with mental health issues face challenges in accessing mental health services due to various factors. The availability of mental health services in the Arab world is limited, with disparities among different countries. Mental health services in the Arab world are insufficient, with some improvement in recent years, but human resources and attention to mental health issues remain insufficient (Okasha et al., 1999). There is a scarcity of studies on the working conditions for mental health professionals and mental health services in Arab countries. Research in Arab countries, underscores the need for continued efforts to address mental health challenges, improve access to services, and enhance cultural understanding of mental illness for better care outcomes. Appropriate help-seeking from a professional source is particularly important for the prevention, early detection, and treatment of, and recovery from mental disorders. However, there have been no systematic

reviews of the efficacy or effectiveness of these interventions in promoting help-seeking (Gulliver et al., 2012). To meet the need for early intervention into young adulthood mental health difficulties, it is imperative to parallel redesign prevention and early intervention services for young populations by promoting multidisciplinary collaborations between different specialized professionals in an enhanced and integrated service of extended primary care (Allen et al., 2009). Thus, resourcing support without improving accessibility and acceptability for young people may be a redundant approach. Considering these issues, it is vital to explore the perspectives and experiences of young people around mental health support and service provision so that policies can be developed to better meet their needs.

2.9.3 Informal help seeking behaviour

Research suggests that informal help-seeking behaviour is more acceptable among young adults. Young people tend to prefer utilizing informal help-seeking behaviours when facing mental health issues, influenced by various factors. One such reason is that informal sources of help are often more accessible and familiar to young individuals, creating a greater sense of comfort when seeking support (Goktas & Buldukoglu, 2022; Lynch et al., 2023; Syakarofath & Widyasaru, 2023). Additionally, many young people report a lack of willingness and knowledge about where to seek help when needed (Hellstrom and Beckman, 2021). Research emphasizes that individuals with high levels of mental health literacy are more likely to engage in help-seeking for mental health issues compared to those with lower mental health literacy. Hence, it is crucial to ensure that young people can recognize signs of psychological distress and identify appropriate supports and resources when necessary (Ratnayake & Hyde, 2019). For those confronted with symptoms of mental illness, whether through developing a disorder themselves or encountering someone who has, their approach depends on their mental health literacy. Evaluating the effectiveness of informal help poses a crucial question. Defining

informal help proves challenging, given its variable nature and irregularity in seeking assistance, making it challenging for researchers to assess, as they are rarely present when individuals with mental health problems initially approach friends or family (Brown et al., 2014). The role of informal help from friends, families, or other non-medical sources has been less frequently researched.

2.9.3.1 Friends and family roles

Social relationships and networks play a crucial role in protecting against emerging mental health conditions and promoting recovery (Byrom, 2017). However, the role of friends and family in supporting young adults' mental health remains less explored. It is widely acknowledged that social support is valuable in safeguarding against mental health difficulties and enhancing overall well-being (Berkman & Glass, 2000). To comprehend the influences of network structure and function on social and interpersonal behaviour, it is argued that networks operate at the behavioural level through four primary pathways: (1) provision of social support; (2) social influence; (3) impact on social engagement and attachment; and (4) access to resources and material goods (Berkman & Glass, 2000). Social support is believed to have a protective effect by enhancing coping abilities (Davis & Brekke, 2014), reducing stigma around seeking help, and decreasing isolation (Gulliver et al., 2010; Saltzman et al., 2020). The complex context of help-seeking, influenced by strong emotions and challenging life circumstances, revealed that despite seeking advice or support through traditional avenues, friends and family encountered professionals and a health/mental health system that exacerbated their distress (Migliorini et al., 2023).

Consequently, while informal sources of assistance can act as supportive intermediaries, they also have the potential for obstructive influences in this process (Goldstein et al., 2023). Two main themes emerge from existing literature regarding the role of informal helpers: 1) Informal

helpers can act as supportive intermediaries, aiding young people in accessing and engaging with professional mental health care (Lynch et al., 2023). Conversely, they can also function as obstructive factors, impeding young people's access to and engagement with professional mental health care (Markiewitz & Jungblut, 2023). A thorough exploration of young people's real help-seeking experiences and their interactions with informal sources of help is essential for gaining a comprehensive understanding of how these relationships operate within the help-seeking process (Mackenzie et al., 2023). Understanding the role of informal help sources in youth mental health help-seeking is crucial for engaging with professional mental health care. While studies have discussed the positive and negative effects of informal help seeking behaviour from family and friends, there is a lack of research on the similarities and differences of informal help-seeking behaviours in different cultures. This raises the question of why knowledge documented elsewhere may not be adequate to address challenges specific to a country like Algeria. More research is needed to determine if the same help-seeking behaviours are effective and desirable in different cultural settings.

2.9.3.2 The role of social media

Digital media, encompassing various electronic platforms like social media, websites, mobile apps, and more, is reshaping society through its pervasive influence. With the rise of digitalization, daily activities are increasingly mediated by computers and algorithms, yet understanding its full impact remains challenging due to the complex and fragmented digital landscape (Dufva & Dufva, 2019). Social media, a subset of digital media, plays a crucial role in this transformation, providing internet-based platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram for personal and public communication (Miekle, 2016). As social media usage continues to surge, with an estimated 3 billion users by 2021, it has garnered significant attention for its mobile, immersive, and ever-evolving nature (Clement, 2018; Orben, 2020). The dynamic nature of social media content, tailored to individual preferences and constantly

evolving, makes it particularly appealing to younger generations who have grown up in a digitalized environment (Orben, 2020). Young adults were among the earliest adopters of social media and continue to be heavy users of these platforms. Numerous studies have documented the widespread use of social media among young adults, highlighting its global reach and ubiquity (Lenhart et al., 2015; Abi-Jaoude et al., 2020). They are deeply immersed in digital culture, with a significant percentage accessing multiple social media platforms and spending considerable time online, facilitated by the accessibility of smartphones (Lenhart et al., 2015).

This demographic, often referred to as digital natives, has seamlessly integrated digital technology into their daily lives, relying heavily on digital screens for communication, entertainment, and information (Prensky, 2001; Roberts & Foehr, 2008). As online activity among youth continues to surge, there is growing interest in understanding the impact of social media use on their health and well-being, especially during critical developmental stages (Best et al., 2014). Digital applications have significantly impacted adolescents' social relationships, access to information, and social interactions. They have also significantly impacted their health, including their sleep-waking cycle and cognitive development, such as attention levels during tasks. This has led to a shift in their social interactions (Benvenuti et al., 2023). However, characterizing the overall effect of social media on youth remains a complex challenge. It is essential to recognize the individual differences in strengths and vulnerabilities that influence how adolescents engage with and respond to social media (Nesi, 2020). Social media has become a powerful tool for connecting, sharing information, and engaging people of all ages. However, its influence on young adults and communities is increasingly complex, necessitating a deeper understanding of its complexity. Identifying specific social media behaviours and experiences posing risks to adolescents is crucial for developing effective interventions.

Social media's significance is underscored in young people daily life by its role as a vital platform for social interaction and communication (Khalaf et al., 2023). They actively engage with social media platforms for various purposes, including communication, content sharing, and social connection (Khalaf et al., 2023). Davis, Anthony, and Pauls (2015) highlight the unique environment provided by online support conversations for exploring social dynamics. Furthermore, studies have shown positive effects on mental well-being, such as enhanced social connections and networks (Ellison et al., 2007). Raise awareness about mental health issues and facilitate mental health promotion efforts (Yonker et al., 2015) and promising solutions by empowering individuals to gain better insight into their symptoms and providing accessible support to those awaiting professional assistance (El Asmar et al., 2023). In contrast, Nie (2001) contended that excessive Internet use can detract from face-to-face interactions, potentially diminishing an individual's social capital. However, this perspective has been criticized by many researchers noting that the Internet can both increase and decrease social capital and depression may stem from the tendency for unflattering social comparisons on platforms like Facebook, where likes serve as a measure of social acceptance (Bargh & McKenna, 2004; Rosenthal-von der Pütten et al., 2019). As a result, excessive consumption of social media may lead to poor well-being, influenced by upward and downward social comparisons (Vogel et al., 2014). Although some studies have highlighted online risks such as cyber-bullying and social isolation, others acknowledge a middle ground between the positives and negatives (Bryant et al., 2006). Orben (2020) suggests that while conventional wisdom suggests less screen time is healthier, longitudinal evidence correlating high screen use with negative mental health outcomes is lacking. The individual nature of social media's effects on youth complicates any broad generalizations, underscoring the need for nuanced understanding (Orben & Przybylski, 2019).

Researchers have not extensively investigated the fundamental processes and variables that influence the advantages and drawbacks of digital technology, and there is a lack of discourse on possible strategies to alleviate its adverse impact on mental health. This research endeavour elucidated these mechanisms and scrutinized favourable online mental health interventions utilized by young adults in both Algeria and the United Kingdom, delineating the optimum digital milieu for their well-being. By attaining a more profound comprehension of these mechanisms, efforts can be directed towards formulating efficacious approaches to foster positive mental health in the era of digitalization. Furthermore, this study extensively examines the detrimental effects of social media on the mental health of young adults. Consequently, this segment of the research strives to ascertain whether young adults exhibit similar accessibility, attitudes, and behaviours concerning the utilization of social media to protect their mental well-being.

2.10 The role of religion in seeking help.

Religion and spirituality are becoming increasingly recognized as important constructs in assessing and treating mental illness because they are deeply ingrained in many cultures (Oxhandler et al., 2018). Understanding the impact of religious beliefs on mental health is essential for promoting overall well-being. Multiple studies have consistently shown that religiosity can profoundly influence a person's willingness to seek help for their mental health challenges (Milner et al., 2019). This reliance on religious support is deeply ingrained in their theological beliefs, with many perceiving religious assistances as more comforting and supportive than secular alternatives (Chen, 2021). Religion fosters a sense of purpose, belonging, structure, discipline, and entitlement, making individuals feel empowered and gratified. This approach is often more effective than conventional psychotherapy, family, and social organizations, enhancing self-esteem, alleviating despair, and fostering renewed hope (Gopaul-McNicol, 1997). As a result, religious individuals often find themselves struggling

with their mental health conditions and may hesitate to seek both formal (professional) and informal help (friends and family).

Numerous research studies have demonstrated that in Western cultures, religiosity is not commonly utilized for the treatment or management of mental health issues. Oxhandler et al. (2018) conducted a study examining young adults experiencing mental health challenges within Western communities. The research investigated the importance of religion/spirituality (RS) in the narratives shared by these individuals regarding their perceptions and management of mental health issues. The findings indicated that RS was perceived as a multifaceted and intricate component within this specific cohort. This observation may have contributed to the enduring tensions between religion and mental health care in Western societies, where mental health professionals frequently disregarded or criticized religious beliefs (Oxhandler et al., 2018). Another study carried out in Spain by Torralba, Oveido and Canteras (2021) revealed a significant decline in religious practices among young people in Western societies, with religious coping being a less common choice. This suggests a diminishing trust in religious approaches among this demographic, leading them to explore alternative coping mechanisms. Another study shows that there has been a noticeable decrease in religiosity among young adults in the United Kingdom. Research has shown that 70% of individuals aged 16-29 do not affiliate with any religion (Bullivant, 2018). Similarly, data from the British Social Attitudes Survey has highlighted that 71% of 18-24-year-olds do not identify with any religious group (Bullivant, 2018). Consequently, these research studies illustrate traditional religious practices or faith healing may no longer serve as the primary avenue for young adults seeking mental health support. This indicates that they do not view religiosity as a reliable resource for addressing their mental health concerns and seeking assistance from a higher power (God) or religious figures are not perceived as a favourable help-seeking behaviour this outcome may be related to the cultural effects or uncontrolled factors on help seeking behaviours. This invite

researchers to look for the reasons and factors that discourage using religiosity in the western communities to develop a positive view on the benefits of using religion among young adults.

The Arab context demonstrates a strong connection between religious healing and psychological well-being, which may not be maintained in Western settings. The notion of 'healing' within an Islamic context is perceived as a holistic conceptualisation of health wherein spiritual, physical, emotional, and mental wellness is regarded as inseparable (Rassool, 2015). Faith healing is a traditional Arab method involving spiritual practices by a faith healer, used to treat various mental disorders, and is widely practiced in the Arab world (Al-Shelali et al., 2023). According to them there are seven distinct aspects of faith healing include the characteristics of individuals seeking healing, the frequency of visits, the symptoms they treat, the treatment methods, the stigma, and attitudes towards mental disorders in the Arab world, and the perceived effectiveness of faith healing in treating mental disorders (Al-Shelali et al., 2023).

Research shows that religious service attendance positively impacts mental health care use for those in distress, emphasizing the crucial role of imams in providing mental health support. Religious leaders are one group of people who may be uniquely positioned to promote community change but have been largely ignored in the literature on applied health and consulting psychology (Anshel & Smith, 2014). Religious leaders are individuals who have unique position to promote community change, but frequently have been forgotten in health programs (Anshel & Smith, 2014). In many Arab communities, seeking guidance from religious figures like Imams, Sheikhs, or spiritual leaders is a prevalent practice (Al-Harbi et al., 2023). Religious leaders in faith communities form lasting relationships with members, supporting health issues and promoting health behaviours due to shared worldview and traditions (Cornish, 2021). These influential figures, with extensive knowledge in Islam, often

guide decisions regarding mental health care, contributing to mental health awareness and practices within their communities (Hasan & Tanjung, 2017), as they offer a range of help, such as lay counselling, forming supportive communities, leading prayer, and spiritual healing, extending social support, and instilling hope in those facing crises. They play a crucial role in enhancing social connection, aiding individuals in coping with challenges, and reinforcing personal identity through meaningful beliefs and values (Paloutzian & Park, 2014; Meran & Mason, 2019). As a result, Faith-based support, a culturally sensitive service, can significantly improve mental health outcomes in vulnerable communities by providing necessary resources to community members who maintain their religious beliefs.

However, it's essential to acknowledge the potential negative implications of religiosity. A recent comprehensive review of literature highlighted mental illness conceptualization, stigma, traditional healing methods, and the influence of religious leaders as significant contributors to negative attitudes towards seeking help among citizens of the Arab region (Al-Horany, 2019). Additionally, religion and spirituality can sometimes serve as sources of struggle, confusion, or act as defences against unresolved psychological conflicts (e.g., Exline & Rose, 2014). Moreover, other research indicates that excessive religiosity can lead to feelings of guilt, fear, shame, and death anxiety (Koenig et al., 2012; Oman, 2018). Clinical studies in Southeast Asia show that Islamic religiousness has a negative impact on clinical service preferences because it contradicts medical professionals' biological beliefs about mental health and treatment options (Phang et al., 2010; Razali et al., 2018), similarly to another research, heightened levels of religiosity may deter individuals from seeking assistance from mental health professionals, as some religious leaders may assert their expertise in diagnosing and treating distress (El-Islam, 2008). This can result in mental illnesses being inaccurately attributed to spiritual deficiencies or supernatural causes, leading to practices such as exorcism and discouraging the use of mental health services (El-Islam, 2008; Weatherhead & Daiches, 2010).

Thus, it's evident that attitudes towards seeking help for mental health issues are complex and influenced by various factors, including religiosity. Religion and religious leaders significantly impact mental health in young adults in Muslim Arab communities, but understanding cultural barriers in Muslim communities is lacking. Emerging research aims to identify the barriers and the ways to create effective interventions catering to the diverse needs of Muslims in Western and Arab cultures.

2.11 Religious practices and mental health

Various research has linked religious practices with self-reported enhanced overall health and an improved quality of life, covering both mental and physical well-being. Multiple studies have highlighted the positive results of incorporating religious practices into psychological therapy. The advantages of religious practice on mental well-being stem from different sources and aspects, including religious teachings for resilience, meditation, and social backing. Additionally, within Islamic history, mental health has received significant attention from Muslim scholars like Avicenna, Ghazali, and Al-Balkhi, who have authored papers on the subject (Bonelli & Koenig, 2013). Larson et al. (1986) conducted thorough reviews of quantitative studies on religion in psychiatry. Their analysis in 1986 revealed that merely 2.5% of psychiatric literature examined included a religious factor. Six years later, they evaluated all indicators of religious dedication discussed in studies published in two prominent psychiatric research journals from 1978 to 1989, identifying 139 religious indicators scrutinized in 35 research projects. In contrast to Sanua's findings, they observed that 72% of the studies indicated a positive link between religious engagement and improved mental well-being, while 16% suggested worse mental health, and 12% showed no correlation (Larson et al., 1992). Larson and colleagues' work long served as a leading review on the connections between religion and mental health. Nonetheless, research on this subject has significantly expanded

across various health fields since then. Nevertheless, these studies frequently fail to consider the significance of such beliefs and practices within the therapeutic procedure.

2.11.1 Prayers

Research has shown the effectiveness of traditional healing modalities, particularly concerning their capacity to address emotional states during therapy. Prayers have emerged as a prominent form of traditional healing, offering psychological comfort. Spiritual practices such as prayer have been used by individuals for every type of illness and across all age groups, cultures, and religions (Lindquist et al., 2018). Within the Islamic faith, the Salah prayer holds particular significance, encompassing components such as dhikr (Remembrance of Allah), involving the repetition of Quranic verses. Indeed, prayer, a fundamental aspect of Islamic worship, serves as a means for individuals to seek solace, inner peace, and closeness to the divine (Sayeed & Prakash, 2013). Prayer, according to Islamic belief, can be either a formal prayer, which one performs (recites) five times daily as compulsory, or an optional prayer, which is mainly performed before and after a formal prayers and night prayers in the very early morning as well as morning prayers after sunrise. (Rezaei et al., 2008). Such practices foster mindfulness and deepen one's spiritual connection that improves mental health wellbeing (Kocak et al., 2012; Saniotis, 2018).

Studies have consistently demonstrated the positive impact of religious practices, highlighting their role in both addressing and preventing mental health concerns (Sayeed & Prakash, 2013; Keshavarzi et al., 2020). The repetitive motions, recitations, and focus on divine connection inherent in Islamic prayers facilitate stress reduction, relaxation, and enhanced emotional regulation (Saged et al., 2022). Moreover, religiosity and regular prayer attendance have been identified as predictive factors for improved well-being (Sayeed & Prakash, 2013). The efficacy of prayers can be comprehended through two distinct mechanisms. Primarily, there

exists a profound connection to the divine, facilitating individuals with a sense of autonomy, consciousness, and emotional/motivational reinforcement. Secondly, there is the enhancement of spiritual energy via one's religiosity and steadfast faith, resulting in transformative healing outcomes (Jones, 1922; Levin, 1993; Shafranske, 1996; Stenger, 2001; Ladd & McIntosh, 2008). The advantages offered by prayers contribute to community cohesion, the promotion of general well-being, the reinforcement of faith, and the cultivation of deliberate mindfulness (Callender et al., 2022). The impact of prayers on mental well-being is intricately linked to individuals' personal convictions, faith, and the importance they place on the ritual. Often characterized as sustenance for the spirit and remedy for the psyche, prayers are perceived as capable of enhancing both spiritual and psychological welfare.

Modern research suggests that Salah have healing potential among Muslims, but there's little discussion about how today's Muslim professionals use them in their therapies. Also, it's hard to study their effectiveness scientifically due to theological and methodological challenges (Andrade & Radhakrishnan, 2009; Al-Rawi & Fetters, 2012). Although prayer plays a significant role in the Islamic belief system and rituals, it is essential to supplement it with expert mental health assistance whenever needed, rather than regarding it as an independent remedy. Prayers should not be seen as a substitute for professional mental health treatment, but rather as a complementary practice that can be integrated with appropriate clinical interventions (Upenieks, 2023). Consequently, relying on prayers without seeking necessary medical or psychological support can be detrimental, as mental illness requires proper diagnosis and treatment, just like physical illnesses. Integrating a balanced approach based on both religious practices and psychological treatment can lead to a most effective strategy to deal and treat mental health issues.

2.11.2 The healing power of Qur'an

The Quran is revered as a miraculous text, intricately tailored to the societal context of Arab culture. It stands out for its unparalleled style, profound wisdom, and miraculous attributes (Nakhavali & Seyedi, 2013). Each verse contains literary treasures that surpass classical Arabic eloquence. The Quran's unique style, layout, features, and powerful message have the potential to inspire profound lifestyle changes. Its language is clear, and its spiritual essence serves as a soothing balm for the human soul, resonating with both readers and listeners. It's worth noting that non-Muslims also have the right to engage with and interpret the Quran's teachings (Joseph, 2012). The Quran elucidates the understanding of its verses and distinguishes itself from Hadith, the sayings of the Prophet Muhammad (Joseph, 2012). Moreover, the Quran is not merely a religious scripture but also encompasses scientific miracles, providing insights into cosmic phenomena such as the universe's expansion and human anatomy. It also contains predictions about future events and historical occurrences (Yahya, 2001).

Al-Banna (2010) underscores the Quran's significance in treating diseases, drawing from verses like (Fusilat 41:44) and (al-Isra' 17:82). According to these verses, Allah has depicted the entire Quran as a remedy (Shifa') for all physical and spiritual ailments. Certain chapters and verses, such as Yasin, al-Maryam, and al-Rahman, have been shown to induce greater calm and peace in patients (Alhouseini et al., 2014; Jabbari et al., 2020; Raduan et al., 2018; Rafique et al., 2019). These specific surahs and verses mark the starting point of discussions linking the Quran with medical sciences. This dialogue highlights the Quran's miraculous nature and its intersection with scientific medicine, paving the way for a broader integration of medical science with an Islamic perspective that traditionally leaned towards Western perspectives.

The Quran outlines three states of the self: commanding self, accusatory self, and peaceful self, which govern our psyche and behaviours' (Frankie, 2018). Quranic guidance offers strategies to weaken the influence of the commanding self, promoting contentment and peace. In Muslim culture, Quranic guidance and Islam-based psychotherapy are utilized for therapeutic purposes

(Rafique et al., 2019). Various Quranic verses are employed for alternative treatment among Islamic practitioners (Zulkurnaini et al., 2012). Research indicates the Quran's effective healing power for both physical and mental health. However, in Muslim countries, traditional methodologies for treating mental ailments often overshadow the simple efficacy of Quranic guidance (Tabatabai, 1987; Nelson, 2001). Quranic verses are explained to address faith-related issues, leaving no room for doubt (Yahya, 2002). The Quran provides guidance on relaxation exercises to mitigate the influence of negative self-states, fostering mental well-being (Ahsan & Khan, 2013). The Quran's therapeutic effects include alleviating stress, anxiety, depression, and pain through listening and recitation (Kannan et al., 2022). Quranic therapy is viewed as a form of unconventional melodic vocals among Muslims, often resulting in a pleasing effect termed "Quranic chills" (Kannan et al., 2022). As a result, Reciting Quranic verses induces a sense of pleasantness and relaxation, akin to music therapy, by stimulating the release of endorphins (Ghiasi & Keramat, 2018).

Listening to, reciting, or memorizing the Quran can reduce anxiety and improve physical and mental health among Muslims (Rozali et al., 2022). It fosters a connection with God and provides relief from stress, activating and enhancing memory capacity and ensuring mental health (Hojjati et al., 2014). Muslims are encouraged to prioritize listening to the Quran over music for relaxation and stress reduction due to its positive effects on the soul. However, while both music and the Quran can have beneficial effects on mental health, the Quran is considered more suitable for Muslims. Nonetheless, further exploration of the neural basis of the Quran's healing effects remains largely unexplored compared to other therapies such as music and meditation.

2.11.3 Ruqyah Shar'iyah: Quran Recitation

While medical disciplines have contributed to the development of treatments for many diseases and disorders, there are still those for which cures have yet to be found. In recent years, there has been a growing understanding of the role of cultural and religious values in mental health care. For example, Quranic ruqyah permits Muslim believers to heal ailments using Allah's words and duas given by the prophet (Pbuh.), in addition to medical treatments. Recent studies have demonstrated that the scholarly comprehension of Ruqya shari'yya exhibits variations, with merely a restricted number acknowledging it as a distinctive tradition. As posited by Salah et al. (2022), Ruqyah is delineated as a form of psycho spiritual therapy grounded in Islamic doctrines, offering a comprehensive approach to tackling psychological issues, well-suited for aiding individuals grappling with such challenges by drawing upon the teachings of Quran and Sunnah. emerges as a cultural and historical therapeutic practice, free from cultural influences (Eneborg, 2013). This method of Ruqyah is based on the recommendations and practices carried out by the Prophet (Peace be upon him) for self-treatment or to help his Sahabah and others. (Ahmad et al., 2016). Cherak (2019) delineated Roqyah within three discrete communities. In nations like Algeria, Egypt, and France, Ruqyah has been employed as a method of self-medication since the 1990s. This approach entails the utilization of botanicals and substances to counteract possession and sorcery, emphasizing purification and the eradication of malevolent forces. The healing aspect of Ruqyah encompasses both communal and individual rituals, integrating purgatives, emetics, bodily purification, physiological fluids, and cupping to tackle malevolence and administer targeted therapy. The Ruqyah encounter is assimilated into the therapeutic journey and conveyed to the patient's social circle (relatives and other individuals with similar issues). Similarly, there are scholarly writings that equate ruqyah shar'iyyah exclusively to spiritual Islamic exorcism although it can be applied for physical illness as well (Philips, 2007).

Academic researchers have identified the steps for performing Roqya, a religious treatment, and the ideal conditions for both the religious leader (Raqi) and the patient. According to Al-Jeraisy (2004), the Raqi must be righteous, have a good command of relevant Quranic ruqyas, and the patient must be a committed Muslim and pious righteous person who avoids sins and forbidden activities. Roqyas may not produce desired effects in cases of habitual sinners and those who commit abominable acts. Patients must also believe the Quran is a healing and mercy, and the treatment should be beneficial once the requirements are fulfilled. Adynata and Idris (2016) and Khaleel (2006) outlined the essential steps to be followed in compliance with the correct roqya procedures. In preparation for the initiation of roqya, it is necessary to follow a series of preliminary measures to begin this longstanding healing tradition. Roqya is a traditional healing practice that involves a series of steps to initiate the process. The first step involves preparing the patient in a clean, quiet environment. The practitioner, known as a Raqi, conducts counselling or diagnosis, gathering information about the patient's complaints and background to understand the underlying causes of their issues. This includes identifying the cause, such as jinn possession, witchcraft, or magic, and determining the appropriate treatment approach. The practitioner then begins the Qur'anic treatments, reciting specific Quranic verses and prophetic prayers aloud. For jinn possession, these verses are referred to as Ruqyah, while for witchcraft, verses against magic are recited. If the cause is uncertain, general Ruqyah is recited as the first step. The practitioner then handles any physical or emotional reactions the patient may exhibit during the session. The practitioner then assesses the effects of the Ruqyah treatment on the patient before concluding the session. The recitation of the roqya is always be done on a clean water or oil (olive oil) to be drunk or to be rubbed onto the body or honey to be eaten (Al- Jeraisy, 2004). The implementation of Psycho Spiritual Therapy not only presents an additional dimension but also provides a substitute to the established contemporary treatments. This therapeutic modality also serves to reinstate the adherence to Islamic

principles in assisting individuals afflicted with mental health disorders, emphasizing faith and devotion to Allah as a fundamental means to surmount psychological adversities (Saleh et al., 2022). Roqya shari'yyaa is not only for jinn and exorcism, but there are also few studies that tackle this subject that it treats psychological issues as an alternative method (Afifuddin & Nooraini, 2016; Arifuddin & Pamungkas, 2018).

While researchers have outlined the steps of Roqya, they have yet to specifically address whether the same procedure is employed for mental health issues as for spiritual concerns. It emphasizes the necessity for further investigation to ascertain potential differences in performing Roqya for mental health compared to spiritual issues. Additionally, the statement highlights the importance of further research to explore any distinctions or similarities in the approach to Roqya for spiritual versus mental health issues. This study explored the attitudes and practices of religious leaders in treating mental health issues, including the response of imams in performing Roqya. By determining whether differences and similarities exist in performing Roqya for mental health issues across different cultures, the study considers both cultural and religious perspectives.

Roqyah therapy, rooted in Islamic traditions, extends beyond Arab cultures such as North Africa (including Algeria) and the Middle East, finding its way into Western cultures as well. This practice, encouraged by the Prophet Muhammad, is believed to offer therapeutic remedies for various disorders and can be used as a complementary spiritual-based treatment alongside mainstream psychiatry, providing multiple benefits across various cultural groups of Muslims (Razali et al., 2018). For example, in his study of Ruqya Sharia practices in East London, Yusuf Muslim Eneborg explains the popularity and ramifications of such a phenomenon as healing with Qur'anic texts in terms of the globalizing trends and attitudes present in Muslim society, especially among Muslims living in the West (Eneborg, 2013). Although researchers have

inadvertently touched upon this trend, studies on Ruqya in Europe have been published focusing on various demographics, including Bangladeshi Muslims in London (Dein et al., 2008), Muslims in France (Khedimellah, 2007), Somali Muslims in Finland (Molsa et al., 2010), Netherlands (Hoffer, 1992). Central Asian Muslims in Russia (Oparin, 2020), Denmark (Suhr, 2019), and Sweden (Johnsdotter et al., 2011). As Roqya gains popularity, there is a growing need to understand its implications and effects on individuals seeking this alternative form of healing in Western communities.

The traditional healing practice of Ruqyah Shari'yya has gained significant popularity among young adult Muslims not only in Arab communities but also in Western cultures. In Western communities, some young Muslims, feeling excluded from Western healthcare systems, turn to Ruqyah as an alternative (Adynata & Idris, 2016). Ruqyah Shari'yya integrates elements of Islam and science in a manner that resonates with younger generations of Muslims (Marlow, 2022; Mayberry, 2022). its strong association with the younger generation has received serious attention from Spadola (2009). As the younger generation becomes more cultivated and educated about this topic, particularly with the rise of technology and the availability of social media, the use of Roqya as a new form of treatment among them has increased (Spadola, 2009). Emilio Spadola (2009) extensively discusses the rise of this traditional treatment among young adults in Morocco. He notes that young Muslims, often secondary school graduates, practice al-ruqiya al-shar 'iyya, or Islamic curing, which involves exorcising jinns, often learning from mass-market Islamic books, audio- and videocassettes, CD-ROMs, and websites. Academic Research on Roqya among young adult Muslims in Western cultures is limited. The literature lacks sufficient information to confidently assess the prevalence or popularity of the traditional healing practice of Ruqyah Shari'yya among Muslims in Western communities. Further targeted research is needed to fully understand the extent of its adoption in Western context.

The academic research addressed a significant gap in existing research by exploring the utilization of traditional Islamic healing practices, including Roqyah Shari'yya, as potential treatments for mental health issues among young Muslim adults. It notes that prior literature has predominantly focused on Ruqya's role in addressing spiritual concerns like jinn possession rather than its application in mental health treatment. This underscores the necessity for further investigation into the potential therapeutic benefits of Roqyah Shari'yya for mental health problems among young Muslims. This study identifies various factors contributing to the adoption of traditional Islamic healing practices, particularly among more religiously young adults' Muslim generations. These factors encompass guidance from religious leaders, personal experiences, and cultural/community influences. Understanding these factors can inform culturally sensitive approaches to mental health care that respect individuals' religious beliefs and cultural backgrounds. By examining the use of Roqyah Shariya in both Algeria and the United Kingdom, the study acknowledges the diversity within Muslim communities and the significance of cultural context in shaping beliefs and practices related to mental health. This comparative approach allows for a more nuanced understanding of how traditional healing methods are integrated into mental health care across different cultural settings. Overall, the research contributes to the development of holistic and effective mental health care practices by recognizing the role of traditional Islamic healing practices like Roqyah Shari'yya and considering their integration into culturally responsive care approaches.

2.12 Recognition of religion in professional setting: imams and professional collaboration

Understanding the psycho-spiritual development of individuals through the perspective of religious leaders and professionals is essential. They can play a central role in integrating Islamic principles, beliefs, and practices into psychotherapeutic approaches by utilizing the

Islamic sources to help clients reframe their challenges, develop spiritual coping mechanisms, and find meaning and purpose in both religious and non-religious settings. Faith healers as ‘a key player in the mental health care system are widely promoted within universal mental health’ (Widodo & Suryosukmono, 2021) Their deep understanding of Islamic teachings, combined with religious authority and community influence, enables them to offer culturally-sensitive and spiritually-integrated psychotherapeutic support within Islamic contexts (Rozario, 2009; Eneborg, 2012) that can greatly improve the therapeutic relationship

2.12.1 Imams Integrating of religious healing to professional healing: the effect of knowledge and training on mental health counselling.

Imams can significantly contribute to local health promotion initiatives, potentially reducing existing health disparities in their communities. Several studies advocate further exploration of this effective method for health promotion (Grace et al., 2008). In settings with limited access to formal mental health care, reliance on informal support networks is common, creating an opportunity for imams to facilitate access to evidence-based care (Girma & Tesfaye, 2011; Menberu et al., 2018). However, enhancing the capacity of informal support networks, including imams, through evidence-based psychoeducation could further improve access to mental health care (Filiatreau et al., 2021). Providing imams with proper training and education is crucial to address the existing gap in mental health support within their congregations and broader communities.

Few researchers oppose the fact that clergy counsel individuals frequently. Minimal discussion exists in the literature, however, about how clergy’s views shape their decisions about mental health referral and intervention (Payne, 2009). It is obvious that religious leaders that counselling they give will be related to their knowledge of the situation and it depends here on

the situation if it is spiritual knowledge or mental health knowledge or both. Robert Taylor et al., in their article on the role of clergy in African American churches, noted that behaviours' may be defined differently by clergy. In turn, these definitions shape beliefs about the best solutions to address the behaviours' (Taylor et al. 2000). studies conducted among these influencers revealed poor mental health literacy and referral linkages (Jang et al., 2017; Slewa-Younan et al., 2020). The qualitative study conducted among Korean American clergy revealed that the religious leaders acknowledged the need to address depression among their community members and believe they have responsibilities for the well-being of their circle of influence, however, there was a need for their capacity to be built in the identification and support on depression (Jang et al., 2017). There are variations in the knowledge of mental disorders aetiology among religious leaders based on race and denominational affiliation (Payne, 2009).

Imams in Muslim majority countries typically require profound knowledge of Islamic traditions, legal-ethical traditions, and ritual guidance. However, in European secular contexts, imams face new challenges and may require additional skills to address the diverse issues facing Muslim communities. Establishing publicly funded teaching and training facilities involving collaboration between Muslim organizations, the state, and educational institutes could be challenging (Boender, 2021). Imams' knowledge of the pathway models for recognizing symptoms, beliefs about treatment, decision-making, medical encounters, and evaluation of outcomes is essential for determining appropriate therapy paths (Alem et al., 1993; Jorm, 2000; Isaac, 2003). The training and education of imams have been subjects of discussion in Western European societies for decades, with stakeholders from both Muslim and non-Muslim communities expressing concerns. Research projects like 'Imams of the West' have explored the authority and roles of imams, proposing typologies based on religious-organizational fields' authority dynamics (El-Yousfi, 2019). However, there's ongoing debate

about the sufficiency of imam training and mosque funding, indicating a need for continued discussion and action in this area.

Recognizing the importance of religion and spirituality in the mental health field, collaboration between imams and mental health professionals can enhance the provision of culturally sensitive and integrated care for Muslim individuals. Psychologists can benefit from the knowledge and expertise of imams in understanding the intersection between religion, spirituality, and mental health. Peck (1993) assert that ignoring spirituality is a significant oversight for mental health workers. To address this, psychologists should inquire about clients' religious beliefs and practices, as well as their conceptualization of God, upbringing, and spiritual experiences (Peck, 1993).

Insufficient knowledge and training among imams can lead to gaps in mental health treatment and hinder collaboration between individuals with mental health issues and professionals. Addressing these gaps necessitates comprehensive training initiatives aimed at providing imams with evidence-based psychoeducation and a deeper understanding of mental health disorders, care, and management. Recognizing imams' evolving role in addressing broader societal issues in both Western and Arab secular contexts underscore the importance of equipping them with proper training and education to enhance their support for mental health issues within their communities. Collaboration between religious leaders and mental health professionals is essential for providing culturally sensitive and effective support to diverse populations, emphasizing the need for understanding across cultural and religious boundaries. This study aims to fill the gap in the literature by investigating the role of imams in counselling Muslims with mental health issues in Algeria and the United Kingdom. It seeks to understand their position in Islamic psychotherapy and their function as spiritual healers or mental health counsellors. The ongoing debate regarding whether religion should be considered in

psychotherapy persists in this research. The study also explores whether these differences persist when considering education level, religious adherence, and cultural background.

2.12.2 Professional religious integration into therapy

Understanding the stages of spiritual development is crucial in psychotherapy to prevent misdiagnosis and mistreatment of clients (Gopaul-McNicol, 1997). Psychologists must be trained to differentiate between healthy and unhealthy spirituality and to support clients in their spiritual development. Integrating Islamic perspectives into Western therapeutic techniques can enhance their acceptability among Muslim societies. The biomedical field has not effectively integrated Islamic faith healing, leading to perceived shortcomings and disparities in healthcare provision (Mateo-Dieste, 2021). The neglect of religion in psychotherapy can lead to harm, as psychologists may dismiss or pathologize patients' religious beliefs, hindering effective treatment (Trusty et al., 2022). To provide effective and comprehensive mental health care, it is crucial for professionals to embrace an inclusive approach to psychotherapy that values Islamic religious principles.

Professional counselling and psychotherapy are not widely recognized interventions within the Islamic context. Studies have proposed models to foster active collaboration between mental health professionals and religious and spiritual leaders. (e.g., Thomas, 2012; Breuninger et al., 2014; Janse Van Rensburg, et al., 2014). These studies emphasize the importance of a healthy relationship between the two, as they strengthen each other and enhance therapeutic interventions for culturally competent and effective treatment for religious individuals. According to Pargament (2011), people bring their spiritual beliefs, practices, experiences, values, relationships, and struggles with them when they go to therapist. It has been observed through research that a significant number of psychologists feel less prepared to address matters related to religion and spirituality, highlighting a deficiency in their training and expertise

(Vieten et al., 2016). A survey examining the attitudes of mental health professionals towards integrating spirituality and religion into therapy revealed that many practitioners admitted to feeling uneasy about discussing such topics of a spiritual or religious nature with their clients, often opting to avoid them (Ho et al., 2016; Neathery et al., 2020). And that may be a result of the lack the confidence to engage with spiritual or religious concerns during therapy sessions due to insufficient training and resources (Captari et al., 2018). Perhaps psychologists advocate for the separation of psychology from religious roots because psychology is a scientific discipline that studies human behaviour systematically, while religiosity and spirituality are entirely subjective experiences unrelated to scientific methods. This is why some believe that the psychology discipline should be distinct from religious influences. On the other hand, certain religious topics have been confused with spiritual beliefs. Additionally, two major clinical paradigms, psychoanalysis, and behaviourism, tended to overlook religion and spirituality when explaining human behaviour (Wulff, 1991; Coon, 1992; Rajaei, 2010). The comprehension of the spiritual of the spiritual aspect among individuals facing mental health difficulties is often hindered by the existence of positive and negative symptoms, which limit their capacity to express their spiritual requirements and shift the focus of mental health experts from spiritual assistance to symptom control. Divergences in the understanding of spirituality between patients and healthcare providers may result in different anticipations and additionally obstruct the provision of thorough and all-encompassing care.

The misinterpretation of spiritual aspects by mental health practitioners and the absence of cooperation between religious figures and secular therapists can impede comprehensive care (Kumar, 2023). Frictions between religious guidance and mental health interventions might impede the timely access to suitable treatment (Freire et al., 2019). To overcome these challenges, it is imperative to implement interventions aimed at enhancing mental health

awareness among religious leaders and fostering partnerships with mental health experts (Vaidyanathan et al., 2021; Ojelade et al., 2023) to promote awareness and leverage local knowledge to tackle diverse health issues (Songwathana, 2009). Religious leaders may have the ability to positively facilitate local health promotion campaigns and thereby reduce existing health inequalities within this population. Given the accessibility and established relationships within religious leaders possess a unique ability to identify behavioural changes that could signal early indications of distress. Leveraging this understanding, religious leaders can effectively link individuals in crisis with mental health professionals specializing in preventative measures. This collaborative approach, marked by their high level of religious involvement, serves to enhance the accessibility and acceptance of mental health support services (Weaver et al., 2003). Through close collaboration with religious leaders, professionals can ensure that the spiritual and cultural beliefs of individuals are respected and integrated into their treatment strategies. However, Therapists who wish to integrate spirituality into their clinical work with religious Muslim clients need to do that in a professional manner that does not violate professional and ethical standards (Henry, 2015). Therefore, several studies are calling for this potentially very effective method for health promotion to be further explored (Grace et al., 2008). Consequently, health professionals need to be properly trained to consider patients' beliefs, attitudes, and particular needs based on their cultural background (Ridley et al., 2021). Culturally competent professionals should understand the concept of culture and how it affects individuals' feelings and interactions (Zartaloudi, 2022). They should also choose appropriate collaboration strategies with people from different cultural backgrounds. Accepting diversity, respecting patients' differences, and providing proper care without criticism are essential (Ladegard et al., 2022). Mental healthcare professionals should familiarize themselves with issues related to mental health and illness and encourage patients to explain how their illness affects their lives (Wedding et al., 2015). Cultural competence can

help professionals understand and provide adequate services to patients from different cultural backgrounds.

The development of three approaches involving religious leaders, mental health professionals, and individuals with mental health issues, and establishing a common understanding of spirituality's role in rehabilitation, is crucial for supporting individuals' mental health. Integrating Islamic therapy into psychotherapy can be advantageous for Muslim communities across various cultures. Understanding the impact of this integration on religious leaders and professionals is essential. This research explores the perspective of imams and their methods in guiding their communities, particularly individuals with mental health issues, in both Algeria and the United Kingdom. It aims to contribute authentically to existing knowledge by collaborating with mental health services and professionals in both countries, examining potential challenges faced by imams in this endeavour. Additionally, it will address these challenges and propose suggestions for establishing Islamic psychotherapy systems.

2.13 Conclusion

The present study highlights disparities in the management of mental health between Western and Arab societies, including countries like Algeria and the UK. It demonstrates that young adults encounter comparable mental health issues but employ distinct approaches influenced by cultural, social, and religious factors. Western communities primarily utilize medical or professional measures, shaped by factors such as accessibility and societal attitudes towards mental health issues. Conversely, Arab cultures perceive mental health concerns as spiritual matters necessitating religious remedies, despite available services. Comprehending these cultural variations is imperative for delivering efficient assistance and interventions to individuals grappling with diverse mental health challenges. Western individuals typically address mental health issues within a medical framework and an individualistic standpoint,

whereas non-Western individuals embrace a collectivist outlook, heavily moulded by their cultural and social backgrounds. It is crucial to acknowledge these cultural complexities for effective support and interventions. The comparison of mental health experiences between Western and Arab populations sheds light on the traditional healing approach for mental health issues from a religious leader's viewpoint; however, further examination is essential to elucidate viewpoints regarding medical or professional interventions from a professional standpoint concerning individuals with religious and non-religious backgrounds in both Western and non-Western settings contending with mental health difficulties.

Chapter 3: Methods

3.1 Introduction

The current chapter describes the research methods needed to complete the experimentation portion of the research study. Qualitative research is valuable in this study for gaining insights into the real world by exploring the perspectives of practitioners. This helps formulate relevant research questions and address immediate needs. Solutions derived from qualitative research are more likely to be applicable, effective, and easily implemented in practice. This chapter justifies the use of this method by starting with an introduction to the research paradigm and then delving into the research philosophy chosen, which includes ontology and epistemology. The Chapter also describes the various stages of the research, such as the research approach employed, the data collection processes, and data analysis research methodology, concludes with the ethical considerations which play important role in conducting and gathering data, additionally to the steps taken to ensure collection of reliable and valid data. As a result, this methodology is therefore intended to meet the research plan and the research objectives set by the researcher.

3.2 Research paradigm

Good research required making research paradigms and philosophical assumptions because they influence the conduct of inquiry. Research is a systematic inquiry into the study or discovery of a social science phenomenon, moving from the known to the unknown to understand, describe, predict, or control specific issues or concerns through objective and systematic analysis to find a solution. It is a search for facts or knowledge; knowledge in this context refers to information about the research subject. The information collected could come

from a variety of sources, including books, journals, personal experiences, and so on. Creswell (2012) defines research as “a process of steps used to collect and analysis information to increase our understanding of a topic or issue”. There are many different types of research, but it depends on the mode of inquiry Quantitative and qualitative research. It can take many forms such as pure theoretical research, applied research, exploratory or grounded research, explanatory research, quantitative research, qualitative research, empirical research, desk research, field research, and mixed research or triangulation, among many other methods of research (Bhattacharjee, 2012). It is very important to state the paradigm in any research study to shed the light on the researchers’ philosophical orientation; because once the paradigm is chosen, it will be easier for the researcher to remain within it as it is planned.

The word paradigm first used by The Structure of Scientific Revolutions American philosopher Thomas Kuhn (1962) to mean a philosophical way of thinking. The term paradigm is used to describe a researcher’s ‘worldview’ (Mackenzie & Knipe, 2006). Lindlof and Taylor (2019) have argued that paradigms are relatively more abstract, and they exist above and behind theories and methodologies. They are so intrinsic to our way of thinking and acting that they are often not fully recognized until they challenged by some unexpected development. In addition, they added that scholars who orient to the same paradigm see each other as collaborators in the normal progress of related research (Lindlof, Taylor 2019).

The Structure of Scientific Revolutions (1962/1996) by Thomas Kuhn is responsible for the popularity of paradigms as a way of summarising researchers' beliefs about how they create knowledge. Consequently, the research paradigm is used to justify the researcher’s decision to conducting the research study. It aids the researcher in illuminating the quality of the results and guides the scientific research study via its assumptions and principles.

Most research paradigms emerge from one of two research approaches: positivist and interpretivism. Because of advancements in human thinking and various ways of explaining

the occurrence and implications of the world's phenomena, there are many philosophical paradigms in existence today. The positivist focuses on strictly scientific empiricist method designed to yield pure data and facts uninfluenced by human interpretation or bias (Kitokivi & Mantere, 2010). The positivist paradigm of social reality exploration is based on the idea that observation and reason are the best ways to understand of human behaviour. Positivism is compatible with the hypothetic-deductive scientific model, which is based on testing a priori hypotheses and experimentation by operationalizing variables and measures; the results of hypothesis testing are used to inform and advance science (Park, Konge, Artino, 2020). positivists believe in empirical hypothesis testing; quantitative research always takes a positivist approach. On the other hand. Interpretivism is a relatively new paradigm that assumes knowledge is subjective that is based on qualitative research. It is opposed the traditional objectivist view of knowledge which is positivism. Researchers within the interpretivist paradigm are naturalistic since they study real-world situations as they unfold naturally. More specifically, they tend to be non-manipulative, unobtrusive, and no controlling (Tuli, 2010). According to Collins (2010) “interpretivism is associated with the philosophical position of idealism, and is used to group together diverse approaches, including social constructivism, phenomenology and hermeneutics; approaches that reject the objectivist view that meaning resides within the world independently of consciousness”. As a result, positivism is more concerned with objectivity and statistical generalisation, with the goal of developing general truth through theory testing. Interpretivism, on the other hand, is concerned with comprehending the context through the construction of social aspects.

3.3 Research philosophy

Research philosophy is defined as “the development of knowledge and the nature of knowledge” (Saunders, et al., 2009). Research philosophy guides a researcher to determine the

most suitable approach that should be applied to conduct a research work. Research philosophy is defined as the belief and assumptions pertaining to knowledge expansion (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2009). This belief is also known as worldview or paradigms, wherein a researcher must decide either quantitative, qualitative, or mixed methods as the research approach (Creswell, 2009). Guetterman et al (2015) points out that a clearer way of viewing gradations of differences between the approaches is to examine the basic philosophical assumptions that are brought to the study, the kinds of research strategies used, and the methods that are implemented in conducting the strategies. Although philosophical ideas remain largely hidden in research (Slife & Williams, 1995), they still influence the practice of research and need to be identified. There are various important reasons why researchers need to comprehend philosophical issues before starting any research investigation. The researcher should first identify the method, select the technique and the strategy that are best suited to the research topic and then explore and develop new research concepts. The aims and philosophical assumptions of the researcher are intrinsically related to the research project investigated. Creswell and Poth (2018), and Grix (2004) highlights the need to comprehend the philosophical foundations guiding research questions, methodology, and intentions to prevent bias and guarantee the validity and reliability of findings for those conducting clear, precise research and evaluating the work of others. The creation and construction of knowledge through scientific research study cannot be accomplished without the knowledge-building principles of ontology and epistemology philosophies.

3.4 Ontology

To understand the type of ontology used in this study, it is necessary to first define ontology. The term ontology is composed of two Greek words: 'ontos' and 'logos. The former refers to being, whereas the latter refers to theory or knowledge. Ontology is a branch of philosophy which deals with the nature of existence. Therefore, to question about the

ontological existence of anything is often to ask whether it is real or illusionary (Symon, Cassel, 2012). Ontology is defined by (Crotty, 2003) as “the study of being.” Which means the philosophical study of the nature of being existence or reality. Hence, the term 'ontology' concerns what is said to exist in the world. For Richards (2003) ontology is the assumptions we make about the kind and nature of reality and what exists. Similarly, Ormiston et al (2014) argue that ontology is concerned with the question of whether there is a social reality that exists independently of human conceptions and interpretations, as well as whether there is a shared social reality or only multiple, context-specific ones. It classically tells the researcher the fundamental categories of the basic conceptual dimension of reality.

Constructivist ontology posits that there is no objective reality. A constructive ontological position recognising that social phenomena are dynamic and realised through social interaction, usually linked to qualitative approach (Dainty 2008). As Bryman and Bell (2011: 21) purport “Constructivism is an ontological position that asserts that social actors are continually accomplishing social phenomena and their meanings”. This implies that social phenomena and categories are not only produced through social interaction but are in a constant state of revision.

The researcher employs constructivist ontology to investigate the social world by using interpretive design techniques such as interviews to analyse the sensations, emotions, and thoughts of young people. This study does not dismiss the presence of a real world just by creating the models to simplify its complexity. The researcher defines and puts its aspects into practise in the social environment to correspond with reality. The researcher in this position can be viewed as part of the reality and can determine how reality is simultaneously explored and affected.

3.5 Epistemology

The term epistemology comes from a Greek word *episteme*, which means knowledge. In simple term, Epistemology is understood as the scientific production of knowledge. It concerned with its nature, forms, and limitations in a particular area of study by providing a truthful information for specific purposes. In other words, how knowledge can be investigated and apprehended. Cooksey and McDonald (2011) posit that the essence of knowledge in the world is encapsulated by a concentration on elucidating the fundamental underpinnings of knowledge, with a particular focus on the experiences tied to human nature. This assertion suggests that knowledge is moulded by individual experiences and the intrinsic nature of humanity. Furthermore, Maynard (1994) as cited by Crotty (1998) Epistemology addresses the philosophical foundation of what types of knowledge are achievable and how we can ensure that they are both sufficient and valid.

To describe the knowledge acquired in a research study. The researcher should pose the following questions: how knowledge can be acquired and experienced. What is the relationship between the knower and what is known? How do we know what we know? What counts as knowledge? If the researcher relies on forms of knowledge such as beliefs, faith, and intuition, then the epistemological basis of research study is intuitive knowledge. If it is data gathered from people in the know, books, leaders in organisations, then epistemology is grounded on authoritative knowledge. If the emphasis was on reason as the surest path to knowing the truth, then it is called rationalist epistemology or logical knowledge. On the other hand, if there is an emphasis on the understanding that knowledge is best derived from sense experiences, and demonstrable, objective facts, it is an empirical epistemology (Kivunja & Kuyini, 2017). To understand the purpose of using a qualitative data the researcher should examine the philosophical views, especially from an epistemological perspective, as it helps uncovering the nature of knowledge investigated in the social context.

The researcher and the researched are independent entities. Meaning solely resides in objects, not in the conscience of the researcher, and it is the aim of the researcher to obtain this meaning. where meaning is inherent in objects and not dependent on the researcher's awareness. The researcher's goal is to extract this meaning. The credible knowledge is derived from direct observation or manipulation of natural phenomena through empirical, often experimental, methods (Lincoln & Guba, 2000, 2005; Neuman, 2003). The naturalist or constructivist view says that knowledge is established through the meanings attached to the phenomena studied; researchers interact with the subjects of study to obtain data; inquiry changes both researcher and subject; and knowledge is context and time dependent (Krauss, 2005). This study elucidates the concept of constructivist epistemology, asserting that knowledge is shaped by individual and collective worldviews rather than being objective. The researcher aimed to explore how subjective experiences and societal contexts influence individuals' perceptions of reality, highlighting the intricate connection between personal beliefs, social structures, and the formation of knowledge.

The researcher adopted an interpretivist view to identify the interactive relationship between the researcher and participants, which necessitates a level of trust and understanding from both sides, i.e., the researcher and participants can remain independent of each other by not influencing one another. Likewise, the researcher cannot distance him/herself from the research process. Conversely, they are constantly constructing the interpretations depends on the context based on their own experiences and reflections as well as those of their participants. The interpretation of the participants will be varied and yield different viewpoints. The researcher believes that acknowledging, comprehending, and explaining the social phenomenon is preferable to observing it. as a result, experiencing and the way expressing mental health issues is challenging and does not consider an objective phenomenon; however,

expressing and sharing these experiences with others may reduce the false perception of an individual with mental issues.

3.6 Phenomenology

The term "phenomenology" derives from the Greek phenomenon, which means "Philosophy.". Phenomenology has been practised in various forms for centuries, but it became popular in the early twentieth century in the work of Edmund Husserl. The phenomenological discussion of Husserl was the first who gave major attention to the topic in his two-volume work, logical investigations. In simple terms, phenomenology can be defined as an approach to research that seeks to describe the essence of a phenomenon by exploring it from the perspective of those who have experienced it (Teherani et al., 2015). Saunders et al. (2009) said that in symbolic interactionism we are in continual process of interpreting the social world around us in that we interpret the actions of others with whom we interact, and this interpretation leads adjustment of our own meaning and actions. Phenomenology does not consider the researcher as external and unbiased to the research process (Neubauer et al., 2019) but it requires the researcher to understand the world with the point of view of those having lived experience of the phenomena (Creswell, 2014).

The philosophies that underlie phenomenology need to be understood by the researcher because the significance of human experience is theorised by these philosophies. In other words, the researcher needs to be familiarised with the philosophical basis of the interpretations of individual experiences to conduct a phenomenological study. Phenomenological researchers must thoroughly evaluate the philosophical foundation of their methodology, ensuring consistent and coherent procedures, despite ongoing concerns about the usefulness of thematic analysis within the descriptive phenomenological framework (Saundler et al., 2019). In Such

detailed study often requires understanding the experiences of others so that the researcher can glean new insights about a particular phenomenon (Neubauer et al., 2019).

Phenomenology consists of a complex philosophical tradition in human science, containing different concepts interpreted in various ways. One main theme among phenomenological methods is the diversity between descriptive versus interpretive phenomenology (Norlyk & Harder, 2010). The descriptive tradition of phenomenology originated from the writings of Husserl that was further developed by Merleau-Ponty, while the interpretive approach was developed mainly from Heidegger and Gadamer (Sundler et al., 2019). The aim of descriptive phenomenology is to describe a phenomenon's general characteristics rather than the individual's experiences (Malterud et al., 2016). Husserl believed that subjective information should be important to scientists seeking to understand human motivation because human actions are influenced by what people perceive to be real (Lopez & Willis, 2004). Dahlberg et al. (2008) stated that according to Heidegger, human existence is a fundamental idea, and our understanding of the world is interpretive. He expanded the realm of hermeneutics by investigating being in the world rather than just knowledge of the world, uncovering the significance present in everyday occurrences, going beyond simple explanations and basic principles. Based on Heidegger, consequently, hermeneutic phenomenological methods have been developed in both philosophy and psychology (Giorgi et al., 2017). Husserl and Heidegger disagreed in this exploration of the experience.

One of qualitative research's major strengths is its emphasis on understanding the phenomenon of interest holistically and in its context. This qualitative study employs hermeneutical or interpretive phenomenology, which focuses on uncovering hidden meaning in the phenomenon under investigation. As a result, the phenomenon can be described in the manner in which the participants first experience it. The rationale behind the choice of

phenomenological research is that it will help to elicit the truth from young adults about their experiences and feelings by producing a detailed description of the phenomenon.

3.7 The relationship between phenomenology, epistemology, and ontology

Phenomenology, epistemology, and ontology each fulfil various interconnected roles in the realm of research. Epistemology is focused on the process of knowledge acquisition and its origins, while ontology delves into the fundamental essence of reality and the state of being. Conversely, phenomenology places significant emphasis on the analysis of human experiences and perceptions. These three fundamental components of philosophy collaborate synergistically and complement each other in shaping research paradigms and methodologies, thereby impacting how researchers interact with and interpret data. Epistemology functions as a guide for defining the limits of knowledge and truth (Perotta, 2021), while ontology examines the framework of reality and the relationships among entities (Buriro et al., 2021). Phenomenology, by concentrating on individuals' firsthand experiences and perceptions, provides a valuable methodological approach for qualitative research endeavours, especially in exploring human existence and experiences (Marsonet, 2022). The integration of phenomenology, epistemology, and ontology is conspicuous as phenomenology influences epistemology, which subsequently dictates ontology. Through the synthesis of these three conceptual frameworks, scientists can formulate a comprehensive insight into the world and human cognition, involving how individuals perceive, comprehend, and coexist within their environment.

3.8 Research design

Scientific research is designed to solve a particular problem of a specific phenomenon. The research design process is intended to provide significant research approach to provide an

accurate test and relevant interpretation of the results obtained from the collected data in line with meeting the objectives of the study. There are two main approaches in research method design, which are qualitative and quantitative research methods.

Qualitative research explores how individuals create significance and understand their environment, focusing on the underlying meanings and motivations behind their experiences and perspectives. According to Al-Busaidi (2008) Traditional quantitative methods, such as randomized controlled trials, are appropriate for assessing the efficacy of interventions or treatments, whereas qualitative exploration of beliefs and understandings is required to understand why research findings are not widely implemented in clinical practice. Qualitative research is a broad generic naturalistic approach in social sciences research that is used to understand the non-numerical data that seeks to understand the intersubjectivity of people which usually refers to their experiences, attitudes, behaviour, interaction in a natural setting. Denzin and Lincoln (2005) define qualitative researchers as people who usually work in the 'real' world of lived experience, often in a natural setting, rather than a laboratory based experimental approach. Qualitative research is a situated activity that locates the observer in the world. It consists of a set of interpretive, material practices that makes the world visible. These practices transform the world. They turn the world into a series of representations, including field notes, interviews, conversations, photographs, recordings, and memos to the self. At this level, qualitative research involves an interpretive, naturalistic approach to the world. This means that qualitative researchers study things in their natural settings, attempting to make sense of, or to interpret, phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them. (Denzin & Lincoln, 2005).

The qualitative researcher provides real information to make sense of social phenomena in the real environment. Saumure and Given (2008) stated that Qualitative research is designed to explore the human elements of a given topic, where specific methods are used to examine

how individuals see and experience the world. It encompasses a range of methods, including logic, ethnography, discourse analysis, case study, open-ended interview, participant observation, counselling, therapy, grounded theory, biography, comparative method, introspection, casuistry, focus group, literary criticism, meditation practice, historical research, and others (Cibangu, 2012). Qualitative research aims to explore new phenomena and captures what has happened during the experiments to test interventions, which leads to explanation rather than generalization. Qualitative research typically leads to explanation rather than generalization (Payne & Williams, 2005). In other words, qualitative research is typically concerned more about describing the social reality. It tries to help us to understand the social world in which we live, and why things are the way, they are (Polkinghorne, 2005). A good qualitative research design should apply and tests trustworthiness via credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability for more explained and justified data result. The trustworthiness or rigor of a study is determined by the confidence one has in the data, interpretation, and methods utilized to uphold the quality of the study (Pilot & Beck, 2014). Today, qualitative research methods are valid techniques for conducting research (Taylor, 2005). The researcher can "see" the research problem through the eyes of practitioners rather than a gap-spotting analysis of the literature, resulting in more practical and focused solutions (Makri & Neely, 2021).

Moreover, it takes a more exploratory, less pre-defined approach, by asking open-ended questions that allow greater freedom and scope in the response (Biggerstaff, 2012). As cited by Haradhan (2018) Qualitative research is inductive in nature, and the researcher generally explores meanings and insights in each situation (Strauss & Corbin, 2008; Levitt et al., 2017). It refers to a range of data collection and analysis techniques that use purposive sampling and semi-structured, open-ended interviews (Dudwick et al., 2006; Gopaldas, 2016). Applying a constructivist approach within this qualitative method of inquiry allows for the study to

Describe how and sometimes why individuals form understandings and behaviours in particular circumstances (Charmaz, 2006). Qualitative methods may, therefore, encourage participants to give rich responses and facilitate a deeper understanding of an issue (Queirós et al., 2017).

In this research study, the researcher chose not to use Quantitative method because it has been criticised for oversimplifying individual experience in the name of generalisation, researchers' prejudice, expectations have not been taken into consideration, and that it is necessary for the researcher to comprehend the human significance of aggregates data (Hammarberg et al., 2015). In other words, in quantitative method more control and objectivity can be exercised.

Since this study is exploratory in its nature. Qualitative inquiry and analysis fit this this study. Qualitative data helped to develop arguments through the whole process of data and make sense of the total experience of which it is the key ingredient of the study, that centred upon how individuals construct their reality based on their interactions with the social world (Merriam & Tisdell, 2009). This type of study was suitable to reflect experiences of social worlds through capturing the subjective views and perspectives of participants. The applicability of qualitative data would allow readers of the study and future researchers to identify pieces of the data that may create an interest or spark the development of questions within the contexts of their own lives or future research.

Qualitative research was therefore the optimal method for this investigation as it provided intricate and rich inquiry into real-life situations (Warren, 2002). Patton (2012) argues that the strength of qualitative research is its engagement with natural settings and its interactive data collection process. There are multiple methodological approaches in qualitative research; this

research paper operationalizes semi structured in-depth interviews. Brenner et al. (1985) argued that interviews offer an opportunity for both parties to delve into the significance of the questions and the responses provided. By adopting the Qualitative methodology, this research has an "empathetic stance" (Saunders et al., 2006). To comprehend the cultural variations among respondents in how they approach, perceive, and address mental health concerns from their point of view. This is especially useful for this study because it allows us to understand the perspectives of the target population.

3.9 Data Collection: Interviews and semi structured Questionnaires

Interviews and qualitative questionnaires were selected to collect the data to address the gap of this research study. Semi-structured individual interview is considered to collect the data as it provides focused, reliable, and comparable qualitative data (Stuckey, 2013). Conducting interviews in mental health topics cross-culturally is crucial due to the significant impact of culture on how psychological symptoms are expressed and perceived, as well as on interactions with the healthcare system (Aggarwal et al., 2023) and exploring sensitive topics like mental health, allowing participants to express their real experiences. Interviews can provide rich data on sensitive topics (Indah, 2022; Arthur et al., 2021). This requires researchers to conduct research in a manner that provides a more nuanced understanding of these sensitivities, helps address potential concerns, facilitates the development of research relationships to promote ethical conduct of research (Powell et al., 2018). Possess the necessary skills and strategies to effectively overcome potential challenges.

Interviews hold significant value across various fields. They are powerful tools for collecting qualitative data, allowing researchers to determine the depth, richness and gain new understanding of participants' perspectives and experiences by emphasizing the importance of effective interview skills for quality data collection (Mitchell, 2015; Utibe, 2020). Interviews

go beyond mere question-and-answer sessions, allowing for the observation of behaviours, personalities, and beliefs, aiding in securing accurate information and detecting contradictions (Sachan et., 2011). as they add analytical value by elucidating tacit knowledge and enhancing the credibility of research findings, especially in studying complex cultural practices like health coping and seeking help strategies. Elicitation techniques within qualitative interviews help reveal unarticulated informant knowledge, emotions, and needs, providing a significant advantage in data collection (Sade et al., 2013). Interview offer a clearer interpretation of the experiences.

However, recent research challenges the traditional belief in the effectiveness of interviews, suggesting that they may lead to biased judgments and inaccurate predictions (Staloff & Akula, 2020). The weaknesses of interviews include issues related to the reliability and validity of the information obtained (Nunkoosing, 2005). The problems include resistance, distinguishing truth from authenticity, the possibility of consent if knowing is a problem for both the interviewer and the interviewee, and the nature and significance of stories and the self.

Furthermore, a semi-structured questionnaire was employed to facilitate the exploration of in-depth inquiries within a structured framework, with the aim of enriching the understanding of the perspectives expressed by the participants. The utilization of a semi-structured questionnaire, as a qualitative research tool, enables a more profound exploration through open-ended inquiries in contrast to a purely quantitative questionnaire (Adejimi et al., 2011) semi-structured questionnaires involve asking in-depth questions using a structured guide to better understand the individual's points of view (Aung et al., 2021). Content validity is the degree to which items of a questionnaire are relevant to and representative of the targeted construct for a particular assessment purpose (McKenna et al., 2004). It highlights the advantages of the study in conducting qualitative research. This method allowed for more open-ended, in-depth responses and captured nuanced responses, especially for participants

from different cultural backgrounds. Experts recommend using qualitative methods involving members of the population of interest to ensure that the questionnaire fully reflects their perspective and that items are relevant, comprehensive, and acceptable (McKenna et al., 2003). Interviews and semi-structured questionnaires are better suited for capturing these responses. While interviews are more open-ended and flexible, semi-structured questionnaires have a more defined set of guiding questions, but both have similarities in their qualitative approach, flexibility, and potential for integration with quantitative methods. Therefore, combining both qualitative and semi-structured questionnaire, is an effective way to achieve content validity and ensure that the research results are meaningful and relevant.

The data was collected both online and in person. Online is a practical and convenient means to connect and interact with study participants (Mann and Steward, 2000). The online space offers a secure and emotionally supportive venue for individuals to openly express their feelings and exchange personal experiences. Indeed, the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly altered the research methodologies, prompting numerous researchers to adjust and introduce new approaches in their data collection techniques (Azhari et al., 2022). This transition from in-person data collection to remote methods like Zoom meetings was indeed crucial for maintaining research continuity during the COVID-19 pandemic. These remote techniques became indispensable tools for researchers striving to adhere to social distancing protocols and other restrictions.

Online data gathering proved advantageous as it enabled researchers to engage with a broader and more diverse range of participants spanning various geographical regions (Wilt & Revelle, 2012), particularly those who may be challenging to reach through traditional in-person means (Azhari et al., 2022), thereby granting increased flexibility in scheduling and accessibility for both researchers and participants (Zboun & Farrah, 2021). Furthermore, conducting in-person data collection presented benefits such as fostering stronger relationships with participants,

receiving immediate feedback, and establishing a more controlled experimental setting (Staggs & Mills-Finnerty, 2023). In-person interviews were conducive to physical assessments, thereby implying a more controlled experimental environment (Rahman, 2015), consequently enabling real-time feedback that aids researchers in comprehending participants' experiences and responding appropriately (Staggs & Mills-Finnerty, 2023).

Establishing a conducive research environment involves creating a comfortable space and undertaking a thorough walkthrough of the setting's procedures, including security measures where applicable. This includes considering timing, minimizing potential distractions, and organizing materials or equipment. Adequate preparedness not only reduces the likelihood of disruptions but also lessens both physical and psychological strain, fostering familiarity with the research setting (Selverio et al., 2022).

The recruitment of participants from Algeria and the United Kingdom involved a comprehensive approach encompassing both online and offline methods. To spread awareness of the study, posts detailing its purpose and objectives were disseminated across various social media platforms, including targeted Facebook groups and Instagram pages dedicated to mental health advocacy and support. In addition to leveraging the broad reach of social media, targeted emails were sent to university communities, capitalizing on the diverse demographics and potential interest in research among students and faculty. Moreover, recognizing the importance of inclusivity, in-person data collection efforts were undertaken by visiting different locations to engage individuals who may not have access to or prefer online participation methods. This multifaceted recruitment strategy aimed to cast a wide net, ensuring the representation of diverse perspectives and experiences within the study's participants from both Algeria and the United Kingdom.

3.10 Sampling and saturation

In the present study, the non-probability 'Purposeful' sampling is adopted in the qualitative research to identify and select the information-rich cases linked to the phenomenon of interest. It is selected because it meets the criteria that have been presented as key to address the research questions. Non-probability sampling involves non-random selection of the population. This involves identifying and selecting individuals or groups of individuals that are especially knowledgeable about or experienced with a phenomenon of interest (Cresswell, Clark, 2011), i.e. individuals with special knowledge and experience related to the investigated topic which is the case of this research study.

3.11 Data Analyses: Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis is a widely used method and one of the most important types of analysis used for qualitative data. Braun and Clarke (2006) and King (2004) argued that thematic analysis is a useful method for examining the perspectives of different research participants, highlighting similarities and differences, and generating unanticipated insights. It has been poorly branded, yet widely used in qualitative research (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Thematic analysis is an ideal method to deal with such rich data as it is exploratory and can be used to structure the data. It helps the researcher explore explicit and implicit meanings in the individual interviews in recognizing the mental health issues faced by young adults through themes that should be categorized based on the codes.

Braun and Clarke (2006) argue that a rigorous thematic approach can produce insightful analysis. It produces an account of lived experience in its terms rather than one prescribed by pre-existing theoretical preconceptions and it recognises that this is an interpretative endeavour as humans are sense-making organisms (Smith & Osborn, 2015). This allows data

categorization by witnessing the experience in its natural setting, disallowing preconceived hypotheses, and using critical researcher judgment (Berrios & Lucca, 2006).

Braun and Clarke have admitted that their 2006 paper left a few aspects of their method somewhat vague and open to interpretation. This study used reflexive thematic analysis using inductive approach. In fact, the term 'reflexive thematic analyses only emerged recently to address these misunderstandings (Braun & Clarke, 2019). Reflexive thematic analysis offers an accessible and flexible way to interpret qualitative data, helping researchers identify and analyse patterns or themes within their dataset (Braun & Clarke, 2012). This method highlights the active and reflective role of the researcher in spotting themes, rather than waiting for them to simply "emerge" from the data. (Braun & Clarke, 2013). There are some Potential for researcher bias and subjectivity, it Can be time-consuming compared to more structured approaches and it Requires strong interpretive and reflexive skills from the researcher (Byrne, 2022)

The data collected transcribed into written form to conduct a thematic analysis through six steps. Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-step approach to thematic analysis involves the following key stages. The first step is 'Familiarizing Yourself with the Data,' where the researcher immerses herself in the dataset to gain a deep understanding by reading and re-reading the data. The second step is 'Generating Initial Codes,' during which the researcher systematically codes interesting features of the data, assigning short labels or tags to represent meaningful patterns. Following this, the third step is 'Searching for Themes,' where potential themes are identified by collating related codes. The fourth step is 'Reviewing Themes,' involving a careful examination and refinement of themes to ensure accuracy in representation. Moving on to the fifth step, 'Defining and Naming Themes,' the researcher provides clear definitions and names for each theme. Finally, the sixth step is 'Writing Up,' where the analysis is documented in a

detailed report or article, outlining the research process, presenting findings, and discussing the implications of the identified themes.

Thematic analysis gained deeper understandings of the subject matter and focus on reviewing the main ideas and perform critical thinking about them to identify themes by describing, illustrating, and examining the meaning each time. The data analysis involves coding responses of the participants into categories along with emergent themes. Sometimes a theme may include more than one main idea and different codes. These themes were transcribed and followed by an item analysis concerning the frequency with each code surfaced in the context of the study (Whiffin, et al., 2011; Levkov et al., 2023; Groner-Richardson et al., 2023)

Braun and Clarke's reflexive thematic analysis approach is well-suited to a phenomenological epistemology and ontology within a qualitative research method by recognizing and allowing for the exploration of personal perceptions, interpretations and acknowledges the complexities of reality and multiple perspectives, enables researchers to delve into the essence of experiences and phenomena (Campbell et al., 2021; Drinkwater et al., 2022). The researcher has chosen Braun and Clarke's RTA is a flexible, theoretically flexible approach that can be used across different research paradigms and with a range of data types. This aligns well with the exploratory, interpretive nature of study's research question. The emphasis on co-construction of meaning, researcher reflexivity, and exploration of lived experiences make RTA a robust and flexible analytical approach for phenomenological inquiry.

3.12 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approvals were granted by the Ethical Review Committee of the University of the West of Scotland's School of Education and Social Sciences for both research studies (no. 13922/on 04 /08/2021) and (no. 16234/ on 27/01/2023).

Moreover, participants were residents of Algeria and the United Kingdom. Meeting these specified criteria qualifies individuals for inclusion in this research. Before conducting interviews, and semi-structured questionnaires the researcher ensured that participants were fully informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any point. It is emphasized that there will be no negative consequences or repercussions for their refusal to participate. These ethical considerations underscore the importance of respecting participants' autonomy and well-being throughout the research process. Ensuring the well-being and protection of participants, particularly when discussing sensitive topics like mental health, is paramount. Adhering to ethical guidelines, such as those outlined by the British Psychological Society (BPS), is essential in this regard.

For participants from the United Kingdom, the researcher followed the BPS Code, which emphasizes the importance of informed consent, confidentiality, and minimizing harm to participants. This included obtaining informed consent from participants before the study, ensuring the confidentiality of their responses, and providing them with information about available support services. For participants from Algeria, the researcher adapted their approach to align with cultural norms and ethical guidelines specific to the culture. This involved obtaining informed consent in a culturally appropriate manner, respecting participants' privacy and confidentiality within the context of their cultural beliefs and providing support resources such as accessible and relevant mental health services.

Overall, regardless of the participants' geographic location, the researcher took proactive measures to ensure their protection and well-being in accordance with ethical guidelines and cultural sensitivity. These measures included providing thorough debriefing and offering access to mental health support services for participants to contact if they experienced any concerns or distress.

Only the primary researcher and the supervision team had access to participant's information (identities, audio records) and the data collected was anonymised and be on a secure server (UWS) one-drive password protected. This code was not linked to any identifying information. Participants were referred to by pseudonyms at the point of transcription, so they cannot be identified by anyone except the research team and any identifiable features from the data collection were left out of the transcript (for instance, if they mentioned what town they lived in, it has been out of transcripts). After the collection of the data, all the data in any form, e.g., printed transcripts or audio recordings, and kept in a locked filing cabinet in the researcher's office and UWS secure systems any stored were stored in password-protected computers.

3.13 Reflexivity and positionality

Reflexivity is a vital aspect of qualitative research, acknowledging the researcher's subjectivity as influencing the research process. Unlike in quantitative studies, where subjectivity is often seen as a bias, qualitative research embraces reflexivity to explore how the researcher's background, values, and experiences shape data interpretation (Olmos-Vega et al., 2022). As Finlay (2002) highlights, subjectivity can enrich the research by providing context and deeper insight into the studied phenomenon. In my research, reflexivity meant critically reflecting on how my cultural background, personal beliefs, and experiences could influence my understanding of the data, particularly in a sensitive study exploring mental health across cultural and religious contexts in Algeria and the UK.

My positionality stems from a personal and professional connection to the topic. As an Algerian with an Islamic faith, I share a cultural and religious background with my Algerian participants, offering me unique insights into their experiences. This shared identity allowed me to build

rapport and establish trust, facilitating a deeper understanding of their views on mental health, particularly regarding religion and cultural values. However, I remained aware of the potential for bias and actively ensured that my interpretations stayed grounded in the participants' perspectives.

Conversely, my positionality with UK participants required me to approach their experiences with curiosity and respect, given the differing cultural context and secular approach to mental health. This insider-outsider perspective allowed me to critically examine the intersections of culture, religion, and mental health across both contexts.

Academically, my background in psychology and interest in integrating Islamic perspectives into mental health care shaped the study's focus and methodology. Recognizing the research gap on mental health literacy and culturally sensitive care in the Arab world, I was motivated to explore these issues in Algeria and contrast them with a Western framework in the UK. Throughout the process, I ensured cultural sensitivity by aligning my ethical considerations with the specific norms of each participant group.

To minimize bias, I made a conscious effort to avoid imposing my personal beliefs on my Algerian participants. Similarly, I remained open and receptive to the experiences of UK participants, recognizing potential cultural differences. I deepened my understanding of both cultural contexts by reviewing literature on mental health in Arab and Western cultures, critically comparing participants' experiences while considering their cultural influences.

During data collection, I was mindful of how my thoughts and biases might affect the interviews. I practiced active listening, confirmed understanding, and maintained a neutral stance, especially on sensitive topics like mental health. I refrained from expressing personal opinions, allowing participants to share their experiences freely. I regularly reflected on my role in the research and sought feedback to ensure my interpretations remained grounded in the

data. By using these strategies, I aimed to produce research that is valid and reliable, ensuring that my proximity to the subject did not distort the findings.

3.14 Conclusion

Choosing qualitative methods provides an opportunity for a more profound exploration of the topic. By embracing qualitative method, participants can openly express diverse perspectives and experiences, thereby facilitating a thorough comparative analysis between the two cultures under study. Within this chapter, insights into participant recruitment strategies are offered, along with a detailed examination of both online and in-person data collection methods. These approaches are adept at handling substantial qualitative data efficiently, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. Subsequently, elucidating how the methodological choice was beneficial in influenced and shaped these significant outcomes, offering valuable insights about the study.

Chapter 4: Findings and discussion of Study 01

4.1 Introduction

This section examines the research and draws conclusions based on the findings. It is divided into two key areas: mental health, culture, and social media. The first study is divided into two sections. The first part addresses the initial two research questions: "How do young adults experience and express mental health challenges in Algeria and the United Kingdom?" and how do cultural and societal factors affect young adults' mental health? This part focuses on the interplay between culture and mental health, examining how cultural factors influence coping strategies, help-seeking behaviours, societal perceptions of mental health, and the level

of acceptance of mental health issues. The second part of the study, which responds to the third research question (What role social media can play in communicating mental health challenges of young people?), explores the relationship between social media and mental health. Specifically, it examines how young adults utilize social media for seeking help and the positive and negative impacts of social media on their mental well-being. As digital natives born in a modern society, young adults are particularly susceptible to these influences, which can have both positive and negative effects on mental health. Further research is necessary to gain a deeper understanding of these relationships and to develop effective interventions and support for young adults grappling with mental health challenges.

4.2 Methods

4.2.1 Participants

More recently, it has shown in several research studies that sample size can be determined in relation to what they refer to as the ‘information power’ that a given sample holds. It has previously been recommended that qualitative studies require a minimum sample size of at least 12 to reach data saturation (Clarke and Braun, 2013; Fugard and Potts, 2015; Guest, Bunce, & Johnson, 2006). According to Burmeister and Aitken (2012) sufficient sample size is the minimum number of participants required to identify a statistically significant difference if a difference truly exists. It is often justified by interviewing participants until reaching ‘data saturation’ (Francis, et Al 2010). In this study, choosing 12 participants (6 from Algeria and from 6 the UK) gives the researcher the experience of planning, structuring, conducting and partially transcribing the interviews within the customary time constraints. The participants invited in the study are not diagnosed mental health problems. When the data is saturated, i.e. no new themes emerge; the researcher can conclude that no additional interviews are required.

The target population of the current study consisted of young adults from Algeria and the United Kingdom, with data collected from a total of 12 participants, aged between 18 and 24. The participants in Algeria were all Arab, while those in the United Kingdom were British born. The UK participants were non-religious, with none identifying with a specific religious belief. According to Morse (2000), numerous interconnecting variables should be considered; these include the scope of the research, and the quality of the information obtained from participants. Braun and Clarke's (2013) suggested sample size was used to ensure there was sufficient and rich data to aid the development of the themes. The participants recruited in this study were 6 females (3 Algerians/ 3 British) and 6 males (3 Algerians/ 3 British). This research study investigated how young adults in Algeria and the United Kingdom experience symptoms of poor mental health without having a diagnosis. The participants experienced mental health challenges, but they did not receive an official diagnosis from psychologists. Their mental health issues were consistent with their individual experiences and self-diagnosis methods, which underscores the importance of how they communicate their symptoms and the level of support from their social networks and seeking treatment. Furthermore, researchers gained a deeper understanding of the role of social media in providing insight into the ways participants use it to improve their mental well-being and the potential benefits it can have on overall life satisfaction.

4.2.2 Data collection

The data were collected through two methods: online and in person. Recruiting participants online posed some challenges, as not all individuals who contacted the researcher expressed interest in or had relevant knowledge about the study. The researcher selected participants based on their demonstration of knowledge about the topic and a genuine interest in actively

participating. Recruiting British participants in person also presented difficulties, as not everyone who agreed to participate responded to the researcher's emails, with only a few providing suitable interview times.

The recruitment process involved writing posts on various social media platforms, outlining the project's aims, and providing contact information. Interested participants reached out to the researcher for more details, and upon contact, the researcher sent them an information sheet offering a comprehensive overview of the research. Following the participants' review of the information sheet, consent forms were emailed to confirm their understanding and willingness to participate. To expedite the process, the researcher-initiated contact through interview request emails, considering email as a quick and cost-effective means of communication. Once consent was obtained, interview times were scheduled according to the participants' availability.

Furthermore, the researcher distributed participant information sheets by printing them and promoted the study among undergraduate students at the university. The researcher explained the study's aims orally and invited students to participate; some accepted and provided their emails for further communication. While some participants responded to the emails, others did not. Out of the six British young adults, the researcher conducted one in-person interview, while all six Algerian participants were interviewed online.

The researcher proposed doing interviews throughout zoom meeting or Skype. The data is supposed to be gathered through 12 semi-structured interviews. the researcher has obtained 12 semi structured interviews with open-ended questions enabling study of young adults' mental health experiences. The individual interviews questions were divided in to two parts which are culture and mental health, social media, and mental health. The questions were organised round three core issues that reflected the scope of the main project, including

opinions and experiences of mental health challenges and issues, cultural beliefs and perception about mental health, and the potential of social media as a source of mental health support and intervention. It took a place at the time that suits the participants. Interviews lasted between 20 and 60 minutes.

The interviews were audio and video recorded by the researcher. Seale and Silverman (1997: 380) list among the strategies required to ensure 'rigour and validity' in qualitative research: 'Recording data objectively and comprehensively, including the use of audiotapes, videotapes and different levels of details in the transcription of data'. The researcher focused on the verbal content of the interaction with the participants. All the gathered data, including the observational notes and the audio and video recordings, chronologically reflected the date, time, and the place where the actions took place (Neuman, 2011). The interviews conducted by the researcher were written in two languages, which are English and Arabic. By conducting the interviews in English, the researcher was able to transcribe the interviews without having to translate them. However, when conducting interviews with Algerian participants, they expressed themselves in a language other than English. During the transcription stage, the researcher translates the information into English. The researcher made notes after each interview. All authors will review the transcripts at different time points and conclude if the sampling adequacy was achieved through the process of saturation.

4.2.3 Data Analysis

Thematic analysis, which is highly applicable in this research study, offers a flexible yet rigorous approach to young adults' subjective experiences. The report of the result should weave a narrative that provides a clear, concise, and logical account not only how a researcher interprets the data, but also why his or her selection of themes and interpretation of the data are important and accurate (Braun & Clarke 2006, 2012). Using both narrative descriptions and

representative data extracts (e.g., direct quotations from participants), the analysis should describe the data and provide an argument for why the researcher's explanation richly and fully answers the research question (Braun & Clarke 2006). To become acquainted with the codes, the researcher listened several times to all the audio-recorded interviews, wrote the transcriptions, and manually translated the Arabic transcriptions into English. Since the Algerian dialect is a mixture of both Arabic and French, the researcher translated the transcripts for meaning, rather than providing a word-for-word translation, as it would not be understandable and clear otherwise. The translated transcripts were then typed into the laptop to find the codes. All codes and themes were extracted using pen and paper and verified as data driven. The codes were then condensed into two main categories, also done using pen and paper. The results are divided into two basic categories, with themes and subthemes found in each category. These categories are based on repeated themes in the interviews of the participants. Before settling on the final themes, the researcher thoroughly reviewed the themes several times.

In brief, eleven of the twelve participants self-identified as having mental health issues and actively engaged in coping mechanisms, help-seeking, and treatment of their mental health issues. They also made recommendations for ways to assist those who are experiencing mental health issues, as well as explanations of how each society views and treats those who are experiencing mental health issues. The following chapter presents a detailed examination of the findings of the thematic analysis to capture young adults' diverse experiences of mental health issues in their societies in the digital era. Before describing major themes, the following table will outline the demographic information about the sample gathered as well as participants' mental health experiences. Assigning labels to participants based on their nationality and gender, such as AM/AF for Algerian Male/Female and BM/BF for British

Male/Female, along with numbering them, enhances clarity and ensures a clear understanding of each participant's identity within the study.

Table 1: Participants demographics

Participants	Gender	Age	Ethnic Groups	M.H. I
AM1	Male	19	Algerian	Worrying/ fear sad/low/mood changes
AF2	Female	23	Algerian	Overthinking/ Anxiety
AM3	Male	24	Algerian	Unsociable/ Loneliness/Lack of self Confidence
AF4	Female	24	Algerian	Psychological Distress
AF5	Female	19	Algerian	Stress/ Sleeping and eating difficulties
AM6	Male	21	Algerian	Loss of self-esteem/ Anxiety
BM1	Male	18	British	Mood and behaviour changes
BM2	Male	24	British	Struggling doing daily tasks
BF3	Female	24	British	Mood changes
BF1	Female	21	British	Loss of interest
BF2	Female	22	British	Stress/ Anxiety
BM6	Male	24	British	No M.H. I

4.3 Section 1: Culture and young adults mental health experiences

The data collection was framed around two focuses: culture and mental health and social media usage and mental health, and the table above relates to the first focus. Participants in both Algeria and the United Kingdom described the many indications they saw, which included emotional, behavioural, and physical aspects of mental health issues. They demonstrated how they deal with mental health issues in their communities by emphasising the varied cultural viewpoints and beliefs of each society. There is a notable difference in how each theme and subtheme relate to each other.

Table 2: Themes identified for each research question of the first section.

Research questions	Themes
RSQ1: How do young adults experience and express mental health challenges in Algeria and United Kingdom?	1. Mental health acknowledgment 2. Treatments for mental health contributors (coping behaviours) 3. British and Algerian community attitudes towards M.H
RSQ2: How do cultural and societal factors affect young adults' mental health?	4. Preferred support and help seeking behaviour

The outcomes are the result of interactions between the researcher's and the participants' realities. To minimise the potential effects of their preconceptions or viewpoints, which could misrepresent interpretation, the researcher must remain consciously reflexive throughout the production process. The research themes, as well as their subthemes, are discussed below. They were chosen because of their exceptional and realistic contribution.

Research Question 1

In answer to the research question *How do young adults experience and express mental health challenges in Algeria and United Kingdom?* the following table refers to the first research question:

Table 3: Young adults mental health experiences

Themes	Subthemes
1/ Mental Health acknowledgment	1a-Mental stability
	1b- Mental health Signs
2/ Treatments for mental health contributors (Coping Behaviour)	2a-Reliance on self
	2b-Active coping
	2c-Spiritual versus Professional help

This section is a detailed explanation of each of the discovered themes and subthemes, with quotes used as supporting evidence. Themes that highlight the intertwined cross-cultural journey of young adults' mental health experiences

Theme 1: Mental health acknowledgment

The first theme delves into participants' understanding of mental health, including symptoms accompanying challenges, and their general comprehension of related issues. This demonstrates their awareness and education on mental health, enabling effective communication and clearer understanding of mental health challenges. Both participant groups possess a solid understanding, aiding in diagnosis, treatment, or prevention efforts.

Sub-theme 1a: Mental health stability

Some of the participants described mental health as mental stability, which allows a person to be peaceful and think, feel, and behave in the ways that they need and desire to live their lives.

As it is stated by (BM2):

I think it just means you are being stable in your thoughts and feelings and making sure that you feel consistently well enough to perform. You know, the sort of expectations of how you live in the society, and if you do not have that, then you know, your mental health would be bad. Moreover, if you have that, you will have a good mental health and it is just about you, feeling good or bad depends on how you feel.

Similarly to an Algerian Imam:

I believe that this concept is summed up in the person's psychological internal peace, so that he does not suffer from psychological problems in the long term. (AF4)

The participants highlighted the connection between mental health and one's capacity to interact effectively with society. They suggested that mental health is connected to mental stability and emphasized the significance of having positive relationships in the society for overall well-being. They explained that persistent negative emotions could be a sign of underlying mental health issues. This observation highlights the importance of recognizing and addressing mental health challenges early. The participants appear to recognize the interconnectedness of mental health with social engagement and emotional well-being. They imply that maintaining a balance of positive emotions and effective social interactions is essential for promoting and maintaining mental health. This perspective aligns with the holistic

understanding of mental health, which considers various factors, including social, emotional, and psychological aspects, in assessing and supporting individuals' well-being.

Another respondent had a different perspective on what mental health entailed.

It means being subjected to mental distress because of society. (AM6)

the participant believes that mental health is primarily associated with distress and that this association is deeply ingrained in societal perceptions. Their emphasis on the influence of society on the meaning of mental health suggests they see the definition of mental health as intricately linked to societal understanding.

The responses demonstrated by the participants highlight that mental health is characterized by the presence of positive emotions, enabling individuals to achieve their desired life goals while maintaining a stable mental well-being and a favourable psychological state. The concept described by the participants was intricately interconnected and influenced by the prevailing societal values and standards. This standpoint suggests that societal viewpoints not only mirror but also contribute to the definition and comprehension of mental health. thus, any shifts in societal perceptions could potentially impact how mental health is conceptualized and addressed among young adults. Awareness of the participants' mental health makes them more aware of the indications and symptoms of their mental health challenges. Participants who are educated and aware of mental health concerns can better understand their own mental health and help create a more helpful and understanding atmosphere for those in need.

Sub-theme 1b: Mental health Signs

When asked about the signs of mental health issues participants dealt with, Participants highlighted anxiety, panic attacks, stress, depression, fear, overthinking, emotions and mood swings, as most common mental health issues they know. This is to illustrate that the most prevalent mental health symptoms they discussed may have been experienced or witnessed in family and friends, or they may have searched for and learned about it. Participants (AF2), shared these signs by stating:

I might say I have experienced overthinking. (AF2)

Not being able to share. (AM6)

Loss of self-esteem. (BF2)

Inability to control anxiety. (BM2)

Anxiety could be a sign of a mental health disorder if it is constant and interferes with daily life, which was the most reported symptom of mental health difficulties among most participants. AM6, BF2, and BM2 shared same point of view that it had a significant impact on their daily life activities. While AM1 discussed the three struggles of mental health issues that have been linked to negative effects on physical health:

Excessive worrying or fear. (The first sign is very visible). The second sign is very excessively sad or low (most of the time you see these people always lovely, but they lack energy). the third sign is the most common one which is extremely mood changes, or someone can be very nice with you then he can flip and switch his entirely mood.

The signs of poor mental wellbeing addressed by the participants are broken down into three distinct categories. The first category is characterized by observable manifestations of worry and fear, which may manifest internally but exhibit clear outward features. Additionally, there are physical symptoms such as self-talk, anger, isolation, heart problems, insomnia, and eating issues. These symptoms resemble a mental illness with physical repercussions, impacting one's ability to be active and leading to a lack of energy. Lastly, the third category involves mood changes that can affect individuals' interactions within their community. These changes are particularly evident in communication patterns and social interactions.

Some participants from both cultures described the painful of mental health effects on their physical health including changes in their mood and behaviours as well as decreasing the daily activities such as:

Hard to socialise with other people. (BM1)

Laziness. (BM6)

Do not do your daily activities...feeling your mood down and not talking to many people or not letting people into what is going on. (BF3)

Many of them provide evidence that most mental health symptoms are related to and as significant as physical illness. AF5 explains how challenging it is to deal with mental health issues as at the physical level:

You do bizarre things at home, such as breaking things, being much stressed, and attacking people for no apparent reason. Speak to yourself loudly at times, harm

yourself; when you do these things, you feel as though you are removing negative energy from yourself. I feel stressed, I do not feel comfortable in doing my daily activities, I cannot eat or sleep, my sleeping has been irregular. (AF5)

As a result, the longer a person suffers from mental health issues such as restlessness, difficulty concentrating on normal daily activities, violent behaviour, and aggression, the more their body suffers. Recognizing mental health issues, on the other hand, can help in their management and reduction of all negative emotions.

While (BF1) stated that people sometimes avoid discussing and sharing their mental health experiences with others:

When you ask people if they are okay, they just say "well," "I am just tired," people reflecting the question, which means they do not want to talk about it. (BF1)

BF1 indicates a reluctance to discuss mental health and showed that when asked how they are, people react with an option that does not directly address their mental state: they are just fatigued. This unwillingness to address mental health might indicate that there is an issue. Some participants may be hesitant how to address the topic of mental health, but being straightforward and sympathetic may go a long way.

It is through hearing these experiences and gaining an in-depth understanding of what is being said about mental health problems among young adults has resulted in increased awareness of mental health and its symptoms, as well as increased concern and intention about the relationship between mental health issues and physical health problems, and how mental health can worsen symptoms of physical health problems.

This theme indicated that recognizing mental health and its symptoms affects how young adults think, feel, and act to cope with negative emotions. It also has an impact on how they handle stress in social life, interact with others.

Theme 2: Treatments for mental health contributors (Coping Behaviours)

The next theme will highlight a variety of coping mechanisms and help comprehend how young adults use them in various situations to achieve positive mental health and wellbeing. To help oneself function well despite the challenges, one must first recognise mental health issues and consider solutions. Coping skills in this following theme do not necessarily mean removing anxiety or eradicating mental health challenges.

Participants tended to respond to this part by reporting the different emotions and feelings they experienced when dealing with their mental health challenges. When asked participants how they would recognise if they had a mental health condition, how they would deal with it, and what they would do to cope.

Participants indicated that if they encounter the previously described symptoms, they would be aware that they have a problem with their mental health and they explained their concerns in detail, with replies varying from one to the other from both groups. According to BF2:

You don't feel well, and you have the feeling that you are missing something and that something is wrong with you, but you don't really understand what is wrong with you since it isn't really impacting your body; rather, it is more about your mind and how it works.

BF2 highlights the complexity of mental well-being, suggesting that discomfort is rooted in the mind's workings rather than physical symptoms. It resonates with those experiencing mental

health challenges or a general sense of unease without a clear cause. Recognizing and addressing mental well-being is crucial, even when issues may not be visible as physical symptoms.

The major difference between participants who know they have mental health issues is that they lose interest in things they used to enjoy doing in their daily lives. This loss of interest can be accompanied by feelings of sadness, hopelessness, and isolation. Reliance on oneself was one of the primary strategies that young adults used to solve their mental health issues. The self-solving problem approach was effective in some cases. Young adults need to recognise when they may be experiencing mental health issues, and any efforts to solve mental health problems are needed in this case to improve their overall well-being.

Sub-theme 2a: Reliance on self

The first coping sub-theme was clearly apparent in most young adult narratives. The participants used the self-solving problem coping theme by coming up with their own solutions to their negative thoughts and feelings. One commonly reported reason for not sharing mental health problems is youths' belief that they should solve problems on their own because they are introverts when it comes to their mental health issues. As it has been stated by AM1:

I am an introvert I solve things alone. I would like to think about my problems alone. I do not like bothering people with my issues.... I would love to solve it myself because there is no one knows you better than yourself... That is why helping your self is better. I will not seek help from anyone.

The preference for independent problem-solving and self-reliance among the participant is deeply rooted in their introverted nature. The way the participant tackles problems alone underscore their belief in the value of personal growth and resilience through self-reliance. The

participant asserts that confronting challenges independently fosters the development of character. This perspective reflects a desire for autonomy and confidence in personal resilience, challenging societal norms that promote dependency on others. Furthermore, the decision not to share problems with others is a vital aspect of the participant's coping mechanisms for managing mental health issues. The participant expresses that nobody knows their issues better than themselves, elucidating their reasoning by choosing to confront and address issues independently, the participant demonstrates a commitment to personal agency and self-discovery, ultimately seeking to cultivate resilience and autonomy in their journey towards mental well-being.

While not everyone may possess the capability to solve problems independently, the satisfaction and effectiveness found in this approach are emphasized. This mindset is characterized by a strong sense of self-awareness, reluctance to burden others with personal issues, and the belief that confronting challenges alone is an empowering and character-building method of coping. This suggests that participants view themselves as their own best source of support when it comes to managing mental health problems. As a result, they develop self-solving problem coping skills to attempt to cope with their mental health issues. This attitude of self-reliance has both positive and negative implications for young adults, as it can lead to a sense of resilience and independence but can also cause them to avoid reaching out for help when necessary.

Although awareness of a problem by oneself is a starting point, symptoms of mental health play a minor role than might be expected in prompting help-seeking. Being in a situation where discussing or displaying difficult emotions is not always the best solution for some participants, as BF1 asserted:

I am more of a bottled-up feelings' kind of person rather than a sharer. It has major negative repercussions I know but I think that honestly my first reaction is to try to figure out why I had that certain anxious feelings or why I feel bad about something. I will try to address it by my own, but if I couldn't do it, I would like to go to a charity camp for young people, I would probably go that route to see any resources that could help me in that before going to GP or something like that.

Participants initially sought help from informal sources before turning to formal channels for more specific advice. While informal sources have the potential to offer valuable support and guidance to individuals in need, relying exclusively on these avenues can be detrimental. Active coping, identified as an informal strategy suggested by young adults from both Algerian and British cultures, was found to be an effective source of assistance. This commonality in informal coping strategies between the two cultures may be attributed to the shared period of age participants are navigating, which could present universal challenges for young adults worldwide. The experiences shared by participants from Algeria and the United Kingdom during this stage of life appear to be remarkably similar.

Sub-Theme 2b: Active coping

Active coping strategies are approaches that young adults used to manage stress and cope with difficult situations in a proactive and constructive manner. These strategies were typically characterized by behaviours and attitudes that involve acting and making changes to the situation or one's response to it. The examples of active coping strategies for mental health challenges mentioned by young adults includes listening to music, practising sports, meditation, and journaling, going on vacation, or going for a walk-in nature. When addressing active coping, the participants discussed the obstacles they experienced when they realised,

they had mental health issues, how tough it was to cope with it on their own, and what activities they did to overcome. It is stated by AF2:

So, my first step was to Google anxiety, depression, and mental health issues, and from there I started reading until I discovered meditation, which was the best thing in my life and saved my life. I started meditating regularly, and in 2020, I started journaling, which turned up to be a good habit. I listened to music, painted, and did all I could to keep myself distracted and focused on something else. Those are my coping strategies for my mental health issues. (AF2)

AF2 found that mindfulness practices like searching for information, meditation, and journaling can help alleviate stress and promote emotional well-being. Engaging in these practices can help feel more connected to themselves and their experiences, fostering a sense of understanding. The research also emphasizes the importance of a "multi-faceted approach to coping" to ensure mental well-being is not a one-size-fits-all concept, allowing individuals to tailor their strategies based on their personal preferences and needs. This comprehensive approach to coping is crucial for managing and improving mental well-being on multiple levels.

Moreover, narratives assert that nature and sports are good for one's mental health. Taking a walk-in nature or engaging in any sport activity, such as going to the gym, assisted participants in relaxing and improving their mood, resulting in improved mental health. AF5 said:

I help myself by going to calm places and reviewing the things that have made my mental health bad...go to the gym and try to be active. (AF5)

Stay social and try to stay positive as well. (BM2)

Going for walks is very therapeutic for me. (BM6)

Therefore, it is possible to draw the conclusion that the therapeutic benefits of nature and physical activity can have a positive effect on mental health. Overall, incorporating outdoor activities and spending time in nature can be a valuable tool in promoting mental well-being and should be considered as part of a holistic approach to mental health treatment. The effectiveness of strategies for young adults may differ from one person to another, and what works for one individual may not work for another. Therefore, it is essential to try out different strategies and determine the ones that are most suitable for each person's specific needs preferences.

Sub-theme 2c: Spiritual practices versus professional help

Spirituality, religion, and faith (prayer, Quran reading, and Roqya) continue to be incredibly important coping strategies and a guiding source of comfort for Algerian participants. According to AF5

Since we are Muslims, the first thing I do is praying and reading Quran, and I do anything to make me attached to God to feel comfortable. Especially when I pray at night, I feel all the negative energy gone. In addition, I used Roqya to relax mentally, and I still drink Roqya water.

These practises provide them with an important source of control and agency to deal with their mental health issues, as AM1 stated.

I have my faith since 90% of the Algerian society is Muslim and do believe in God and I think this is very helpful because we can always reach a higher being than us that could help us with our mental health issues.

The involvement of spiritual and religious factors shown to be associated with better mental health outcomes, such as a reduction of feelings of stress and anxiety which was also confirmed by participant AM3:

The second thing you should do is have a strong relationship with God, which includes praying 5 times a day. You may feel low in between prayers, but after you pray, you will feel better because you are attached to God.

Algerian participants have shown praying and reading the Quran is more than simply a religious requirement; it is a deliberate and necessary reaction to life's challenges, offering comfort and a connection to God. The inclusion of evening prayer is noteworthy, meaning that this specific religious practice has a substantial impact on Algerian young adults' mental health. Praying at night is described as changing, eradicating negativity, and increasing a sense of purification and tranquillity. Furthermore, the usage of Roqya, both as a mental relaxation technique and as Roqya water, signifies a holistic approach to well-being. This highlights the belief in the therapeutic and spiritually based aspects of Islamic rituals, which extend beyond daily prayers to encompass certain sorts of spiritual participation. demonstrates a key relationship between religious faith and mental well-being, demonstrating how this Algerian participant finds consolation, calm, and mental relaxation via their adherence to Islamic rites and activities. This is not to say that mental health issues are solely spiritual and religious

matters, however, the presence of such practises allows participants to make sense of their difficulties in a meaningful way. The primary sources of guidance for Algerian participants' coping strategies are largely derived from their religious and cultural beliefs. As a result, there is a positive correlation between psychological health and religious belief. These beliefs and practises provide a sense of connection with something greater than oneself and encourage an individual to look at life from a different perspective.

Despite the cultural differences between the British and Algerian participants, visiting a therapist or a professional was seen by many of them as an important step.

Definitely go to a medical professional, possibly a counsellor, to work out any issues you have. (BM2)

AM6 said:

Addressing mental problems begins with contacting a psychologist.

It is evident from BM2 and AM6's statements that seeking out professional help can provide those suffering from mental health issues with much needed support and guidance. A therapist visit is an important component of their mental health and wellbeing because it allows them to gain insight into their own thought processes and understand how to better manage their emotions. In a therapeutic setting, these individuals can share their feelings, fears, and hopes in a secure and safe space, which can help them receive valuable advice from them on how to better cope with stress or other difficult situations, allowing them to develop healthier ways of dealing with issues that arise.

Many participants choose to use a combination of the above-mentioned coping strategies, as different tactics work for different individuals, which demonstrates the

importance of understanding their unique needs and preferences. It has been discovered that while there were similarities in the way Algerian and British participants coped with mental health issues, there were also distinct differences. It has been demonstrated that when it comes to understanding how Algerians cope with mental health issues, it is critical to understand their unique cultural context, including the significant role of religion. Whereas British participants appeared to prefer a more secular approach, seeking support from professionals, which was Algerians' second-most preferred option. It is evident that in order to provide adequate care for participants from both countries, it is important to take into consideration the cultural and religious influences that may shape their attitude toward mental health.

The difference between coping strategies was obvious between the two cultures. In the first culture (Algerian), a more traditional approach was adopted, using spiritual and religious practises as coping strategies, while in the second culture (UK), a more modern approach was adopted, such as engaging in physical activities or talking to professionals. Coping strategies therefore encompass a variety of methods, and the key is to identify the ones that work best for one's individual needs.

Research question 02:

In answer to the second research question, *how do cultural and societal factors affect young people's mental health?* The following themes and subthemes were identified:

Table 4: the effect of cultural and societal factors on young adults' mental health

Themes	Subthemes
3/ British and Algerian Community attitudes towards mental health	3a- Mental health Acceptance
	3b- Stigma
	3c- Cultural diversity and knowledge about mental health practices in Algeria and UK

**4/ Preferred support and help seeking
behaviour**

4a- Different avenues of mental health
support

4b- Religiosity

4c- Support those who exhibit symptoms

Theme 3: British and Algerian communities' attitudes toward mental health

This theme Examining the attitudes toward mental health within British and Algerian communities reveals a nuanced interplay between cultural, religious, and societal factors. In both contexts, perceptions and approaches to mental health are shaped by a variety of influences, including cultural norms, religious beliefs, stigma, and access to mental health services.

Sub-theme 3a: Mental health acceptance

British participants believe that cultural views around mental health are changing for the better. Initially, mental health concerns were taboo and kept hidden from the public. However, based on the opinions of these individuals, there has been a significant shift in recent years. People are becoming more open about discussing and expressing their mental health difficulties. This movement implies an increasing readiness to confront and handle mental health difficulties, which contrasts with the past inclination to conceal such issues. The participants' observations mirror the changing public viewpoint on mental health, indicating a good trend toward more openness and acceptance in British culture. According to BF2:

It is only recently that it has been talked about, most likely because mental health was not regarded as important. I believe that society is dealing with it much better now by talking about it, attempting to pinpoint the cause of it, and advising people to seek help if they need it. Additionally, to try to do something about it, implying that having a mental health problem is not the end of the world and that you can still do something to improve your situation.

This shift in attitude has enabled British society to openly discuss mental health issues, as well as foster a more inclusive environment in which individuals feel comfortable discussing their personal experiences with mental health. Another British participant addressed the availability of mental health services and campaigns, as well as online facilities such as help lines, which allow individuals suffering from mental illnesses to easily obtain assistance.

There are many people who hide mental health issues but here in the UK, people are more open about mental health issues, and they can deal with it easily because of the availability of online services and mental health services. (BF3)

The availability of mental health services is a positive indicator of the advancements being made in understanding mental health in British society and in normalising the conversation about it. This is a noticeable attitude change, especially when compared to previous decades when mental health was somewhat of a taboo subject and access to services was constrained.

In contrast to the comments of Algerian participants, discussing mental health issues is still considered taboo in the Algerian community and is seldom mentioned, and there is a significant ignorance on the subject. The community commonly neglects mental health issues.

Individuals suffering from mental illnesses may be regarded differently, rejected in social settings, or isolated or ostracised by community members. As it is stated by AM1:

In the Algerian society, I am going to be very critical of it. It is very rare where I used to see the country pushing for mental health help. I think the idea of mental health in here is very taboo and unheard in my opinion... Therefore, it is very unheard-of people talk about their mental health issues and secondly, I feel like it seen as a sign of weakness and many people has this mind-set that if you complain to this guy, he is going to think that I am a weak person. Therefore, I should not talk about it at all. Then, they will keep it themselves.

This Algerian participant has shown a critical perspective on the state of mental health awareness and discourse in Algerian society. It has been emphasized on the rarity of initiatives or efforts in the country to promote mental health support. The prevailing sentiment is described as one where mental health is considered taboo and largely unheard of, leading to a lack of openness, and understanding. It is also has been pointed out that discussing mental health is often perceived negatively in Algerian society. There's a prevailing belief that acknowledging mental health struggles may be interpreted as a sign of weakness. This perceived stigma creates a reluctance among Algerian to open about their mental health issues, contributing to a culture of silence and self-isolation.

The consequence of this lack of understanding and openness is highlighted by AM1, suggesting that it may exacerbate mental health issues within the Algerian community. The fear of judgment and the societal mindset around mental health may prevent individuals from seeking the help they need. Moreover, this collective silence hinders the broader society from

addressing the root causes of mental health conditions, perpetuating a cycle of stigma and limited awareness. AM6 said,

When society notices that the individual is suffering from mental health issues, it begins to insult him and call him insane, and the majority of society treats him negatively because of a lack of information and culture in this domain. Only a small group can support you, but society and bullying on persons with mental health difficulties might bring you more problems than your actual one.

Other participant pointed to this point of view AF2:

it is unspoken topic in the society, and I never heard anyone said that they have mental health issues in Algeria because they always hide it for the reason of the people who think they are crazy just because of mental health issues.

AM1, AM6, and AF2's statements highlighted the widespread stigma and lack of understanding around mental health in Algerian culture. The participants depict a disturbing situation in which people suffering from mental illnesses encounter insults and discrimination from society. The use of disparaging terminology, such as "insane," demonstrates a serious lack of understanding and empathy. The participant emphasizes that this bad treatment stems from society's general lack of information and cultural awareness regarding mental health. Furthermore, the participants believe that when someone is thought to have mental health issues, society's response might worsen the situation rather than help. Individuals who are afraid of society's criticism and potential bullying are less likely to seek assistance, which contributes to the maintenance of mental health issues. Participants explained that this stigma

is a significant barrier in Algerian society when it comes to addressing mental health concerns, as it may make Algerians feel that expressing their feelings is something to be ashamed of and should remain hidden, which can lead to more serious issues later. This, unfortunately, creates a negative spiral where people become more isolated, feel even worse, and can no longer properly cope with their problems.

Sub-theme 3b: Stigma

Despite the progress made in the UK towards a more open attitude towards mental health issues, a key barrier identified by participants concerning the stigma that still present in their culture. BM2:

I think there is a lot of stigmas for example if you break your leg, you are going to get sympathy... I think people have many of these defensive mechanisms. Maybe because they do not have mental health issues, or they have mental health issues, but they do not want to deal with it.

BM2 in discussion about mental health stigma in the United Kingdom revealed a significant level of misunderstanding and diverse perceptions compared to physical health issues. There were varying perspectives and conceptualizations of mental health, indicating the presence of numerous misconceptions and stigmas. The participant noted a tendency in society to discuss physical health more openly than mental health, attributing this difference to the visibility and tangibility of physical health issues and that mental health struggles often go unnoticed due to ignorance and a lack of understanding, contributing to a serious gap in awareness. BM6 gave an example of how stigma could be dangerous for people with mental health issues:

I think it is from the most dangerous things that can happen if you are already suffering from mental health. I have always held the belief that stigma can kill people through many ways. I feel like it is something you can see in high school where there is this view of mental health. So, in high school, I feel like you are very likely to have mental health issues just because of all the stress of everything going on at home, school. It is a very weird time in your life as well. Especially physiologically. I feel like stigma does kill because it stops you from getting help.

This example provided an illustration of how stigmatising those with mental health issues can be harmful, especially in the teenage years, which are considered the most sensitive period in people's life. Participant continued by describing the extreme negative stigma that are frequently shown toward those who have mental health issues and how this discrimination can make people reluctant to seek treatment or even recognise that treatment is necessary.

Similarly, Algerian participants identified how persons with mental illnesses are typically the target of gossip and severe judgement from their society. AF5 stated that:

The Algerian community stigmatizes people with mental health.... Algerian culture believes that if you go to a psychologist and he gives you medications, you would be regarded as a crazy person. At this point, people in Algeria are afraid of being stigmatized if they claimed to have mental health issues or that they had seen a psychologist.

Participants overwhelmingly demonstrated their society's negative associations with people who have mental health issues, this is why it has always gone unheard because people were expected to deal with and treat it themselves. Participants explained that mental health issues were always associated with craziness and madness.

People with mental health issues are characterised in society in a variety of ways, the most prevalent of which is "crazy". (AM3)

Algerian participants demonstrate how widespread the stigma associated with mental health issues is in Algerian culture and how individuals fear judgement and social exclusion if they seek help from a psychologist to address their psychological issues. This problem is compounded by the fact that mental health is often not seen as an important or serious issue in Algerian society, and the pervasive stigma can create significant barriers for those who are seeking professional help. Participants were opposed to these stigmatising beliefs, claiming that people with mental illnesses can behave normally and like everyone else.

Sub-theme 3c: Mental health literacy and lack of awareness

Some Algerian participants stated that people in villages and rural areas face stigma, and many confirmed that there is a lack of awareness and ignorance. This can be attributed to the cultural belief that mental health issues are caused not by biological or psychological factors but rather by spiritual or supernatural forces. As opposed to those in big cities, who are more educated and aware of mental health issues. AF4 said:

Algerian society has not yet reached that level, particularly in my region. They completely ignore the existence of psychological and mental disorders. Rather, they say, maybe it is magic, the evil eye, or jealousy, so we return to a religious man (Raque), rather than going to a psychologist or a psychiatrist.

Participants shared their views about the differing beliefs about mental health make people in urban areas go to religious leaders which have been found to play a prominent role in

maintaining mental health more than those in rural areas, who are more likely to visit professionals for mental health advice and support. AM6 gave the following example of a person who has been stigmatised due to lack of awareness and has suffered as a result:

There was a girl in our neighbourhood who was a young girl dealing with mental health difficulties; thus, society began stigmatising her (children and adults) by treating her as if she were insane...Until she went so insane, she had no idea what she was doing and began repeating the words people told her outside until she lost her mind. These traditions know no bounds, especially in rural villages, but when we travel to big cities, for example, we see that there are conscious people and that people can recognise the symptoms of psychological problems and that it is not something shameful, whereas in villages, people do have negative thoughts.

The example mentioned by the Algerian participant demonstrated how stigma can harm and worsen mental health, particularly in villages and rural areas where there is a lack of mental health literacy. Stigma can become internalised, threatening the quality of life, disrupting social connections, and decreasing the probability of people with mental illnesses seeking mental health care. The Algerian participant's narrative highlights the cultural attitudes and practices in rural villages, particularly rural areas. The narrative compares rural villages to urban areas, where society recognizes psychological symptoms and perceives mental health issues without shame. However, negative thoughts persist in rural villages, contributing to the stigmatization of mental health difficulties. The narrative emphasizes the negative impact of societal stigma on mental health, especially in traditional settings, and suggests increased awareness and understanding in urban areas.

According to participants' experiences, when it comes to dealing with mental health issues, the UK's people are more open. This makes for an interesting cultural comparison between Algeria and the United Kingdom, as Algerian society tends to be more closed off when it comes to mental health issues. Therefore, when it comes to stigmatising mental health, they have the same attitudes. Algerians and the UK's community both have a propensity to stigmatise mental illness in similar ways, with comparable degrees of preconceptions about mental illness. Despite this shared attitude, there is a marked difference in the way that both societies treat individuals with mental health problems.

Sub-theme 3d: Cultural diversity and knowledge about mental health practises

In terms of understanding mental health concerns in Arab and western cultures and the differences between them, British participants demonstrate that they lack knowledge about mental health concerns in Arab countries because they have never visited Arab. As stated by BF1:

Honestly, I would never know how mental health are experienced in Arab countries but if I would guess potentially in European or western countries people were more liberal, we don't live as much of regimented life and maybe we are more open in that sense. Maybe mental health in Arab countries is not that accepted, maybe people feel more comfortable speaking about it in European cultures than Arab cultures.

Although the British participants are unfamiliar with how Arab countries deal with mental health issues, they believe that Western or European countries are more expressive and open in comparison to Arab countries.

I think mental health is more accepted in Western countries as it is an actual disorder, but not in Arab countries. BM1

It was pointed out by them that Arab and Western cultures approach mental health differently.

In my opinion, Arab culture is more family oriented. I believe they are also reserved in this regard since they do not approach their families about it. It is not difficult to communicate mental health difficulties in Western culture because it is not family oriented due to the diversity of what is part of Western culture. However, I believe that it is much easier to discuss in Western society. (BM6)

According to participants' explanations, in Arab countries, mental health is more family-oriented, making it difficult to express mental health issues due to their reserved nature, while in Western countries, there is a greater emphasis on individualism and openness when it comes to mental health discussions. This contrast can have an impact on how each culture views and deals with mental health.

According to Algerian participants, there are significant cultural disparities in this area, illustrating the variability in how societies are dealing with mental health problems. In comparison to the Algerian community, they believe that western societies are more receptive to treating mental health problems and offering a wide range of mental health services in all sectors, including schools and universities. AF2 stated:

I started having a glance on mental health issues on European countries, the way it was dealt with is different, even in universities they have different office dealing with students with mental health issues, and it is very confidential. When I started googling

about it, I saw that they had some appointments with psychiatrists and that in western countries people are more open to talk about mental health issues and it is very normal, they do not minimize the issue and they take it very seriously. In Algeria, they will always tell you "You will go out of it" "it is just a phase" "it is just in your head". These are all the phrases I heard but in western countries, they face the problem with you and help you to get out of it.

This Algerian participant made a notable disparity in the treatment of mental health issues between European countries and Algeria. In European countries, particularly within university settings, there is a distinct and supportive approach to mental health, marked by confidentiality, specialized offices, and normalized conversations. Mental health issues are addressed seriously, with access to appointments with psychiatrists indicating a proactive stance. Conversely, the participant's experience in Algeria reveals a contrasting scenario. Cultural attitudes seem to dismiss mental health concerns, using phrases like "you will go out of it," "it is just a phase," and "it is just in your head." Confronting the Algerian society with the fact that it will be solved without treatment can make the situation worse, indicating a lack of understanding or willingness to encourage them to solve the problem or seek help rather than ignoring it. This can be damaging in a multitude of ways, as it is an act of avoidance and reinforces the notion that suffering in silence is the best way to cope with the issue. Overall, it has been highlighted that there are cultural differences in how mental health is perceived and managed, with implications for support systems and societal attitudes. The comparison underscores the importance of understanding cultural contexts in shaping mental health practices and the potential impact on individuals seeking assistance for mental health issues. Furthermore, even though psychologists exist in Algeria, Algerian participants expressed a preference for religious healers due to their cultural background and the belief that imams could

provide more culturally appropriate advice than psychologists, which shows another major difference between the two cultures:

Of course, there is a major difference between the two. As Muslims, we seek guidance from our religion, whereas in Western culture, people prefer to consult professionals like psychologists. There are psychologists in Algeria, but we choose to address mental health issues through the religious community. For example, in Algeria, we have the Imam, a religious man who understands religion better than we do, and we can seek advice from him. AM3

Therefore, in the Algerian context, the religious community is more trustworthy and helpful than psychologists in tackling mental health issues because of the belief that they understand religious matters more deeply and can provide insights into their faith-based perspective on mental health.

In the other hand, Algerian participants felt that young people are not exposed to the same levels of mental health issues in their culture due to a greater emphasis on family unity, in contrast to Western cultures where independence is encouraged from an early age, which makes them vulnerable to mental health issues because of their independence.

There is a huge difference. If you can somehow express yourself in this Arabic country, there is going to be many helps because instant societies like Algeria are built on union and family. In western societies that is not present at all, as the idea of being pushed to do your goals alone is very common in western countries. Some people reach the age of 18 years old and abandon their families to reach their goals. To reach these goals

they will find themselves empty, they have no one to talk which they find themselves in a very difficult situation where there is no help presented to them. (AM1)

There was one notable difference of Algerian culture over western culture: it is family oriented, which protects and lessens the impact of mental health problems on young Algerians. This is largely due to the strong family ties that Algerian youth frequently have access to when times are tough, which is not the case in western or European countries.

The study reveals significant cultural differences in mental health perception, treatment, and handling. Western countries are more accepting of mental health, while Arab cultures like Algeria are family-oriented and reserved. Algerian participants agree, highlighting cultural differences in mental health treatment. Western countries, particularly Europe, provide comprehensive treatments and discreet assistance in educational settings. Algerian society lacks understanding and acceptance of mental health concerns. Additionally, cultural preference for religious people over psychologists is noted. Family unity is emphasized as a preventive measure against mental health disorders, unlike Western cultures that promote independence from an early age.

Theme 04: Preferred mental health support and help seeking behaviour.

Participants' cultural beliefs, values, practises, families, and communities have a profound influence on how they perceive their mental health, how they manage mental illness, who they seek out for treatment, and how they respond to treatments. Professional medical advice and treatment are still necessary for proper diagnosis and care, but it is important to understand and respect the influence of cultural beliefs and values on mental health perceptions to provide culturally sensitive care. The following subthemes will discuss the different avenues used by young adults in different cultures to support their mental health issues.

Subtheme 4a: Different avenues of mental health support

Participants' responses illustrate selectivity in their personal decisions about when and how much they share information about their mental health experiences.

First, I would like to phone a doctor or GP and tell them the problem, and I am sure that they are always able to refer me to a psychologist. (BF3)

The most important details are that few British participants prefer to seek support from psychologists, seeking support from a professional can provide a unique and valuable perspective on one's mental health. Psychologists are trained to provide evidence-based interventions and can help individuals develop coping strategies and tools to manage their mental health. Additionally, seeking support from a professional can provide a safe and confidential space to discuss sensitive topics and work through difficult emotions. It is important to remember that it is a brave and proactive step towards prioritising one's mental health. While some believe it is important to speak to a trusted friend or family member. It is up to the individual to decide what works best for them and prioritise their mental health by seeking help when needed.

Few respondents from the UK shared a variety of etiological factors for mental health issues, including consulting with and sharing problems with relatives. BM1 stated,

I guess probably speak to my siblings, maybe my sister. I tried to talk to her for advice...I've heard people advise me to see a psychologist and mental health services... but the best option is to talk to family.

Most of Algerian participants' experiences seeking help benefits for family and friends' involvement in supporting their loved one can include decreased stress and burden of care, improved wellbeing, and a greater understanding of treatment. AM6, AF2, and AF5 shared the same idea of disclosing their mental health issues to their families, as it has been stated:

I began talking about my issues with family members such as my mother and sister and telling them all about my problems. (AM6).

In general, I do not share my difficulties with my friends, but I do share them with my grandmother and mother. I do it if I appear emotional. (AF2)

My sister is familiar with my habits and behaviours; thus, she is the person with whom I choose to discuss my mental health issues among family and friends. (AF5)

The scenarios described by the participants shed light on the importance of receiving support from family members. The support provided by them was the most meaningful and comprehensive, as family members are in a better position to understand how their behaviours related to their mental health experiences. Talking to family first when dealing with mental health concerns indicates a preference for seeking assistance and understanding from close relatives as an initial step in coping with emotional challenges. This attitude might come from a belief in the value of familial relationships and the assumption that family members can provide comfort, empathy, and a sense of security. Furthermore, reaching out to family members may be viewed as a natural and culturally entrenched response, indicating the importance put on interpersonal interactions within the family unit. This decision might also

be affected by the belief that family members are more likely to give unconditional support and a nonjudgmental atmosphere, laying the basis for treating mental health issues.

In contrast, according to most of British participants, requesting help from relatives is not always helpful; rather, it puts pressure to you in your worst-case scenario. They feel that they should choose their words carefully since it is difficult to persuade someone not to do what he should do in such a difficult situation or to compare it to the experiences of others.

BF1:

I think people like to compare scenarios a lot. So, they will say that there are people out there that are worse than you, which doesn't always help.... Well, there are people out there starving and you have everything to start asking yourself why I am sad I shouldn't be sad when there are people worse than me, but the relatives do not know why or how you are experiencing it. However, I think the comparison thing that people think resolve it because they think it will make someone better in to put their pain a perspective, but I don't think it always works like that.

BF1 highlights that everyone's experiences and feelings are unique, and pointing out the difficulties of others does not always give comfort or solutions. In summary, BF1 emphasizes the significance of identifying and comprehending one's emotions without invalidating them through comparisons or dismissing remarks. It advocates for a more compassionate and nuanced approach to assisting someone suffering from emotional issues, acknowledging the complexities of unique feelings and experiences.

British participants focused also on Parents' understanding of mental health issues is not always correct, and their attitudes can have a negative impact on how their children

approach mental health topics for example the use of the social comparison behaviour is always associated with negative outcomes impacting mental health and relationship satisfaction.

Especially parents may not understand your mental health issues because it is not the same as when they were growing up. Society is totally different. So, they might not deal with it that way and they are passing on the same advice which is not a good advice. I think any one given advice need to try and put themselves in that person's shoes. (BM2)

Compassion and understanding were two of the key ingredients identified by participants as necessary when attempting to better understand mental health issues. British participants felt that parents were often not the best resource to turn to when trying to navigate mental health problems, as their perspectives and experiences may be rooted in different times. Participants wished for openness in discussing their mental health experiences and understanding their growing problem.

In summary, a small number of British participants view professional help as the preferred option, whereas most Algerian participants show little inclination towards seeking assistance from professionals. This inclination is likely influenced by cultural values in both contexts, with an emphasis on family support and the associated benefits of stress reduction and improved mental health in Algerian culture. Nonetheless, British participants express concerns about the common tendency to compare situations and emphasize deficiencies. They also underscore gaps in parental awareness of mental health issues, underscoring the importance of compassion and empathy. The perception and attitude towards seeking professional help appear to be shaped by cultural norms and the accessibility of mental health treatments in each country. Additionally, variations in how family members are perceived in providing assistance and the level of trust placed in relatives contribute to these differences.

This underscores the critical need for culturally sensitive approaches to mental health that consider diverse perspectives and beliefs in the development of treatments and intervention programs.

Sub-theme 4b: Religiosity

Religious values are important in mental health care for Algerian participants since one of the fundamental objectives of religion is to recover from suffering, seek peace and closeness to God, and achieve life transformation.

Since my country is religion oriented, we rely a lot on religion, and this is a good thing to me because they tell you just read the Quran and pray, and praying is good to me to help me because it calms you and makes you focused on. Focus on religion, study religion, read Quran or even listen to it; because everything is in our holy Quran, we rely a lot on the Holy book of Quran. (AF2)

Algerian participants note that it might be comforting for those who are suffering to remember that Allah is always there and can help those who put their confidence in Him. AM3 said:

I do not believe in the concept of "helping," but I do ask God for help. God created this problem, and I think that God has a solution; thus, I seek therapy from God rather than others who do nothing or are unaware of my situation.

Participants emphasised on the effectiveness of the integration of spirituality and religiosity into psychotherapy and how religious beliefs could affect their mental wellbeing. Besides seeking the help of imams or religious leaders, the Qur'an and prayers have the potential to alleviate psychological distress by providing spiritual direction and comfort.

As opposed to some British participants who acknowledge the changing cultural landscape in the UK and the decreasing significance of religious beliefs in addressing mental health issues, most British participants share this perspective. They emphasize that religious beliefs are not considered significant when dealing with mental health problems. BF1 stated:

I would say religion is not resorted as much in the UK because we moved away from being a religious country in the last 30 years maybe even more than that. Yet, I don't really know in my circle of friends, in my generation either me as well as many people I know do not go to the church regularly at many more my parents' generations and above like my grandparents. I think that they would go to the church for something like that. To may ask questions and feel that they are connected to something bigger than themselves, but I think for younger people that really creep mechanism. I think they would much rather write it down or talk about it with a friend rather than going to church.

Participants explained that the United Kingdom is characterized as a secular nation, with a declining prevalence of religious adherence. Historically, the country exhibited strong religious ties, however, participants explained that the newer generation suggests a decline in traditional religious practices among. The participants tend to prioritize alternative methods for preserving their mental well-being, instead of finding comfort in religious establishments like the ancient generation used to. While the older generations found significance in their affiliation with churches and other religious establishments as a means of connecting to a higher power, the younger generation perceives social interactions and conversations with peers as more conducive to their well-being than engaging in religious activities.

The idea of relying on one's social circle rather than a higher power is shared by many British participants. Therefore, they rely on their connections with friends for support, believing it is a more reliable form of assistance than religion. BF2:

I tried to switch off and concentrate on my energy and something else, like meeting with friends and having chats with them or just going out and seeing some places or walking in nature and just trying to make my mind focus on anything else other than the reason of my mental health problem... Therefore, I was brought up as orthodox Christian and I have of course some kind of religious belief, but I am not a practicing, so I do not actually go to the church or follow what is religion says. I really do not have insight about my religion says about mental health.

There were important differences between Western and Islamic understandings of mental distress, which manifested in the different ways participants sought help. Participants' beliefs, perceptions, and attitudes toward mental illness and mental health treatment showed that they affected their help-seeking behaviour. Western participants were more likely to see mental illness as an individual problem and seek professional, family, or friends' help. In contrast, Algerian participants were more likely to view mental illness as part of their greater cultural context, perceiving it as a spiritual issue requiring religious healing rather than professional intervention, and thus put more emphasis on the involvement of family members in the mental health healing process. The next theme explains how participants support people with mental health issues in their societies.

Sub-theme 4c: Support those who exhibit symptoms.

The British participants suggested that having meaningful conversations is essential in helping people who are dealing with mental health issues, as this enables them to express how they feel and makes it easier for others to provide the necessary support. BF1 said:

Being careful what you say to them and not including like don't cry be happy or think about other people because these words do not help them in that situation and do not help them to be away better so try to choose you words carefully in that situation because you never know that it will make them feel worse.

They reported that understanding the situation and recognising the feelings of the person they support without passing judgement are crucial. In addition to seeking professional help, which is widely regarded as the best advice anyone can give to someone suffering from mental illness:

I would comfort the person and understand what is actually happening. I would advise them to seek help elsewhere rather than coming to me. Going to someone professional because I am not professional yet, so I will not be able to help him or her. (BF3)

The same idea was shared by BM1:

I would like to ask them to talk to me if they can first. If they cannot, I would advise speaking to a professional.

According to them, getting professional assistance is frequently the best course of action because it enables a skilled expert to evaluate the situation, assess one's unique circumstances, and develop a personalised strategy to address their issues.

In contrast, the advice that Algerian participants often offer or receive from their community is to visit religious leader (Al-Raqi) to be healed. AF4 stated that:

A person should choose people who can understand him for the sake of containment, because the most difficult thing for a person when he suffers from a psychological problem is a lack of support or the absence of someone to support you at least to understand the psychology state you are going through. As a result, the healing process is affected. Most people believe that if you have any type of mental health problem, you should go to Al-Raqi.

The Algerian participants believe that a holistic approach integrating religious guidance and traditional healing methods is the most effective way to become cured.

I would advise them to recognise their mistakes, repair them, and return to God and pray, especially the night prayers. (AF5)

Similarly, AM1 stated that:

Well, as I previously stated, 90% of the country is Islamic, and most people would not tell you to accept yourself. He would usually tell you to reach out to God, which is a good thing if you are a faithful person because you can find something to do to fill the hole you had inside your heart. Also, you can reach out to God, who can really help you with your issues, and I believe that is the perception we had.

According to Algerian participants the role of God is considered paramount to Muslim life, and this is essential in understanding the prism through which a Muslim understands and responds to their difficulties. God is seen as the sole sustainer and provider, so it would make sense that during times of difficulty, a Muslim might turn to Him for strength and comfort. This explains why participants might focus on strengthening their relationship with God and returning to Him in remembrance during periods of illness.

To conclude this section, Algerian young adults' mental health experiences were not at the same levels of severity as British young adults' mental health experiences, owing to a societal lack of awareness and a high level of stigma. Young adults from both cultures were educated and made aware of how to cope with and treat mental health difficulties, as well as how to help others suffering from mental health concerns.

This part of the study answered the research question: How do young adults experience and express mental health challenges in Algeria and the United Kingdom? Understanding why there are such large differences in the rates of dealing with mental health issues is dependent on understanding the differences in cultural beliefs, attitudes, and knowledge about mental health in Algeria and the United Kingdom. Participants' experiences and knowledge showed that cultural factors influence the aetiology and progression of mental health challenges, as well as how they define their symptoms and illnesses. This indicates that, when it comes to mental health treatment, cultural norms and values play a major role in determining what is considered an acceptable form of treatment.

Participants claimed that religion has a strong influence on Algerian culture, whereas a more secular perspective on mental health is more prevalent in the UK. This means that while formal mental health treatments are frequently viewed as more appropriate for addressing psychological issues in the United Kingdom, religious or spiritual healing is frequently the main source of healing in Algeria. This part of the research answered the second research

question about how cultural and societal factors affect young adults' mental health. Furthermore, coping with and seeking help for mental health issues has changed with the evolution of technology and social media. They have made it much easier to communicate and share experiences with others across the globe, which is especially beneficial for those struggling with mental health issues. The next section will explain how social media could be used to support participants' mental health.

4.4 Section 2: Social media usage and mental health

The development of modern technology has facilitated interactions among people from different cultures and countries, allowing them to exchange ideas and find solace in each other's experiences while dealing with mental health struggles. This has revolutionized the treatment of mental health, leading to increased access to support and understanding across cultures. Social media plays a significant role in this shift, as young adults across cultures increasingly turn to platforms like social media for mental health support. This reflects a global trend in coping mechanisms, highlighting the interconnectedness of cultural diversity and technological advancement. This section is related to the first section, as it explores how young adults utilize different methods and strategies to cope with and treat mental health issues within their respective cultures. Social media and technology have become integral parts of young adults' daily lives, providing open spaces for sharing experiences, seeking advice, and finding help for mental health concerns. In addition, the challenges presented by the COVID-19 pandemic have further emphasized the role of social media as a source of comfort during difficult times. The discussion on social media's impact on young adults' mental health expands the scope of the study to include modern technological influences. This aligns with the evolving nature of mental health support, where technology bridges cultural gaps and offers accessible resources. By integrating these themes, the study provides a comprehensive understanding of young adults' mental health experiences. Rather than conducting separate studies, the integration

allows researchers to identify connections and disparities between traditional and modern avenues of support.

This section of themes presents the second theme category which is based on participants' narratives that shows the relationship between young adults' mental health and social media usage and explain the role social media play in supporting their mental health. To address the second research question of this study, *what role can social media play in communicating mental health challenges of young adults?* the following themes were identified:

- Theme 1: Mental health challenges sharing online.
- Theme 2: Impact of social media
- Theme 3: Online Activities
- Theme 4: Online Mental health influence and Support

Theme 1: Mental health challenges sharing online.

Each participant had a unique approach to managing their mental health struggles and determined the best course of action based on personal preference. As a result, instead of turning to social media for support, the participants had to rely solely on self-care and their social networks, which included close supportive relationships with family and friends, to manage their mental health. AF2:

I do not share my mental health difficulties on social media, but I do share them with my family (mother and sister), as well as my best friend. I frequently call my family to tell them about my problems: How I feel, the symptoms I've been struggling with recently, crying... I just follow people but do not post my issues on social media I make

some videos for myself because I have mental health issues, but I never share them with others on social media.

AF2's mental health management approach prioritizes privacy and personal support networks. These values keeping a close-knit group above broadcasting their difficulties on social media. AF2 also makes personal videos that show a self-reflective and therapeutic approach, emphasizing personal expression and healing over seeking external acceptance or attention on social media. This method promotes personal development and healing.

Some Participants choose to exhibit only their positive sides on social media because they think that mental health is a private matter that should not be shared publicly. BF2 said:

I usually use social media to show the positive aspects of my life, such as how I prefer to keep any issues that I encounter during my journey private because they are more personal and aren't something that I want to share with people on social media.

This decision is understandable to participants, as mental health issues can be sensitive, and many of them are not yet comfortable talking openly about such matters on social media platforms. This idea was also confirmed by BM6:

If I were going through a permanent mental health problem, I am likely to just not contribute anything on social media. I guess I am introverted and reserved when I do have bad mental health.

Participants asserted that they do not make their mental health difficulties visible online. Even though they do not share their experiences, they have friends who find it helpful to share their

healing process by sharing their experiences with mental health professionals and posting solutions that have helped them.

I do not share my feelings with others in real or virtual life; Nonetheless, I have friends that use social media platforms to post stories, comments, and emoji's that explain how they are feeling. (AF5)

Yet, for many, the concept of openly talking about mental health online can be an open choice for them to help themselves and connect with others who may have had similar experiences.

BF1:

As I said already, I am not more and as much of sharer person when it comes my feeling. I think I attend push down my feelings until I reach a breaking point...I do not feel like I would necessarily share my feeling or mental health issues I face.... For me, I do not have a problem to share my experiences online if it would help others.

BF1 initially hesitant about expressing emotions, is resolute in undergoing a transformation and grasping the significance of sharing personal experiences. BF1 is prepared to openly discuss her struggles online, indicating a shift towards increased acknowledgment of mental health issues and support. This personal evolution not only aids this participant in personal growth and healing but also plays a part in a broader movement aimed at destigmatizing mental health and cultivating a more compassionate and understanding society. Online help-seeking has the potential to meet the needs of participants with a preference for self-reliance or act as a gateway to further help-seeking.

On the other hand, some participants believe that social media is an important aspect of dealing with mental health issues by getting professional advice and learning from others' experiences. AM6:

I share my mental health struggles on various social media platforms groups related to mental health where I know I may receive support from psychologists or others who have had similar experiences as me and have overcome all their mental health challenges on their own. I seek guidance on Instagram, Facebook, and YouTube.... yet, social media allows you to share your thoughts, and your problems may have solutions.

The participant recognizes the significance of social media in connecting with diverse individuals and fostering a sense of belonging in their mental health journey. They take a proactive approach to seeking guidance and support, highlighting the positive impact of online interactions on their well-being. Their positive experiences with online communities have reinforced their belief in social media's power as a supportive and empowering tool. Since the participant's acknowledgment of the significance of social media suggests that it may have a transformative effect on their overall social experience, the following subtheme examines the intricate relationship between participating in online mental health discussions and social interaction.

Sub-theme 1a: Online mental health communications' impact on social interaction

This subtheme was developed based on participant responses and presented their opinions regarding using online communication to talk about their issues and whether it truly affects their social interaction with others. Few participants demonstrates that when communicating

online, there is a lack of accountability and a greater chance to 'fake' mental health issues to gain attention. AF4:

There is even a difference between the terms virtual and real. I see that communication through social networking sites is that some people seek attention, and I, as a virtual person, will believe him. For example, claiming that he is mentally ill to get attention, there are people who are sick with superiority, and as a result, they may resort to some strategies in order to attract attention. In this case, what is virtual remains virtual and thus fake? As a result, in the real world, when someone who suffers from a mental health problem comes to us, the conscious person who is aware of some symptoms or signs of mental health issues may be able to recognise whether this person truly suffers from a specific mental illness or not, unlike social media.

Participants believe that discussing mental health issues online increases the likelihood of stigma, which makes things worse. Participants believe that expressing their mental health issues in person instead of online is a more beneficial method of receiving support from those around them unlike social media, which they assume cannot be trusted AM1:

it might be problematic because you cannot really trust everyone online, so someone can really use anything against you if you have serious mental health issues and the person exposes you and makes fun of you, which could lead to a very bad thing. In person, it is harder but if you do it. Most of the time, doing it in person is beneficial because if you do it with a friend, you can truly comprehend the connection of the other people when they listen to you. I believe it is a way to cope with the mental health issues you are experiencing on your own, but online cannot be trusted.

This demonstrate that in person communication provides a more secure environment and allows for easier interpretation of body language and facial expressions, creating a sense of trust and understanding. AF5:

To understand someone who has mental health difficulties, you must have suffered mental health issues yourself. or at least, you are aware of the signs of mental health issues, because if someone comes up to you and tells you about his mental health problems, you will be able to recognize whether he is telling the truth or not based on the way he speaks to find a solution for him. I regularly chat with my friends while crying, but when I text them, I speak normally and send funny emoji's without even showing that I am crying, and they have no idea what is wrong with me, so you can pretend to everyone that you are Okay when you are not. In the virtual world, you may do whatever you want. That is why I prefer to chat with them face to face rather than through social media platforms. Maybe I will cry and relieve all the negative energy. However, they will not feel you on social media, and even if you were exhausted, they will not know or see your face expressions.

the complexity of managing mental health difficulties and the challenge of others understanding an individual's experience, especially in virtual interactions where physical cues may be less discernible, is a notable concern. While those with personal mental health histories may grasp others' struggles better, it's essential to recognize that empathy and aid can stem from diverse sources beyond direct encounters. Articulating one's emotions openly, whether in face-to-face interactions or online conversations, can help others understand the situation more effectively. While it's true that people might not pick up on subtle cues in text-based

communication, expressing yourself honestly can still lead to meaningful connections and support. It's crucial to identify the most effective method for seeking help and expressing emotions, whether through in-person meetings, online communication, or a combination of both. Moreover, it's important to acknowledge that seeking assistance when necessary is acceptable, even if others may not immediately perceive the challenges faced.

On the other side, some participants mentioned that online communication was seen as beneficial, allowing participants to reach out and share experiences in a way that is not always possible offline, particularly for those suffering from mental health issues that are commonly considered too sensitive to discuss face-to-face. BF1:

I would say people who already feel less pressure to share online, because behind the screen, it is quite easy to type away and you do not really think about it.... In a fore sense where people sharing their own experiences as it could be nice to release for people who may be like myself find it difficult to share in real life.

The participant emphasized the importance of online communication for sharing ideas, addressing mental health issues, and reducing isolation. It helps individuals feel less isolated and normalize their experiences, fostering resilience and stronger relationships. This approach is crucial for individuals to build resilience and strengthen their relationships with others, reducing the pressure of in-person communication.

Theme 2: Impact of social media

This theme provides insight into how participants are emotionally attached to social media use. Narratives show results regarding social media's impacts on mental health have, in fact, been mixed. Many participants described how they evaluated the value of social media in their lives.

It appeared to be separated into two categories: highly significant and not at all significant. These categories were associated with positive and negative impacts on the participants' mental health. A few participants found that social media enabled the spread of positive thinking and allowed people to learn more about different topics. AF4 stated,

As a student, I previously studied the specialty of automated media, which is related to social networking sites. It aided me in getting educational news as well as conversing and exchanging ideas with others.

Examining automated media in the context of social networking allows the participant to grasp its practical benefits and social relationships. This participant noted that the abundance of information available on social media platforms provided an opportunity to explore different perspectives and expand one's knowledge. Similarly, to AM6:

I believe social media is essential in my life because it simplifies everything. I have learned many new ideas that have changed a lot of my thinking. I had many false ideas, but it expanded my positive thinking.

The participant sees social media as an important part of their lives, highlighting its simplifying impact. The participant indicates that using social media has been an excellent source of learning, introducing them to fresh ideas that have considerably affected their viewpoint. The remark of having "many false ideas" denotes a transformational component, indicating that social media has helped to dispel misunderstandings and broaden the participant's positive attitude in numerous parts of life. Overall, this may be seen as the participant's conviction in

the importance of social media as a tool for simplifying knowledge, increasing learning, and encouraging positive thinking.

While others, whose highly significant use is often referred to as "addiction," were connected to feelings of depression. BF2 said,

It was quite important a few months ago, but then I felt it was kind of oppressing me in a way, and I felt like I had to be on social media. I did not like that feeling, so I felt depressed in a way. So, I decided to just delete my social media for a while and take some time off.

Similarly, BM1 says:

I deleted most of the social media platforms like Snapchat and Facebook because they take so much time.

Deleted platforms would help participants take some time away from all the stress and worry, allowing them to focus on more important things. As much as social media can provide opportunities to connect and express oneself, it can also become a source of stress for many participants.

Theme 3: Online activities

This theme contained comments that related to participants' online activities to support their mental health. Facebook, Instagram, Tik-Tok, Snapchat, and Twitter are the most popular social media platforms used by Algerians and British participants. Apart from staying in touch with family and friends, participants also use these platforms to learn educational, religious, and cultural aspects, watch motivational videos about improving mental health, and participate in stress-reduction challenges. The various activities they do while using social media are

record books and novels, education, entertainment, scrawling, post photos, and videos, contact family, meditation, music, learn new languages., watch movies., sport, seek professional help. motivation videos, share challenges, pass time.

As a result, participants are turning to online streaming platforms to find accessible and calming activities like meditation, which has been useful in providing relief from mental health issues.

AF2:

I started meditating after discovering a meditation staff app on social media platforms. They help you in breathing properly. I started with 10 minutes and worked my way up to 25 minutes. It made me feel more comfortable and relaxed, and it helped me cleanse my mind of all the negativity, making my ideas clearer.

Listening to music and watching motivational videos proved effective in helping the participants by providing them with much-needed support and understanding. AF5:

I use TikTok. I have a specific time at night when I enter the platform and watch music or motivational videos or participate in challenges that all Tik-Tokers do to reduce stress and anxiety. I have created several videos, but I have never made them public. These types of challenges help me get away of the stress of the day.

Similarly, to AM1 who find listening to music in online platforms helpful in dealing with mental health issues.

I have many activities. I would say that the most common thing I do when I want to be alone is listen to music, since music can really describe other people's problems or private cases that you are experiencing. It helps me feel better since music shows that you are not alone in your feelings. The sad singer who is talking about this subject is also dealing with sad problems or mental health issues, which helps you feel better knowing that you are not alone or crazy.

These activities gave them a sense of understanding that there were others with similar experiences and that they were not alone. Others said that the content enabled them to actively engage and stay occupied, diverting them from negativity. These activities provided a sense of normalcy and allowed them to cope, rest, and recharge. AM6:

Instagram and Facebook are the two main sites I use daily, along with Twitter. Facebook is related to family and my studies since it allows me to contact family members and my friends, and Instagram provides me with useful recommendations such as how to build your sports life, how to have a good mental health state, and many professionals give advice that I am currently following. The feeling changes with usage.

Other participants have different perspectives on the bad habits that have resulted from online activities. They indicated how their use of social media could make them feel bad. BM6 said:

Scrolling, I think just scrolling through Instagram. TikTok seeing what other people do. I would say probably get me a bit of frustration, jealousy, obviously people are living their best lives, and I am working on ethical applications. As for the most part, I

feel like emotions that you do feel in general is negative ones are covered by frustration, jealousy, and comparison. I would say 70% of it negative.

They noted that the pressure to constantly maintain their online presence could lead them to compare themselves to others and damage their self-esteem. BF2:

I used to it for hours for day just scrawling through it and seeing what other people were posting. This kind of made me feel inadequate and feel oppressed like I had something to show off and I had to like posts, or I had to look in a certain way or how to act in a certain way, that is what should social media be about.

This sentiment was echoed by several other participants, who all described feeling overwhelmed and stressed by the demands of being constantly connected and trying to maintain a "perfect" persona online. Participants highlight a similar theme of negative emotions and pressure caused using social media. Participants exhibit irritation, jealousy, and feelings of inadequacy because of their frequent access to curated material on sites such as Instagram and TikTok. The pressure to meet cultural norms, create a polished online presence, and compare oneself to others can have a negative influence on mental health. These observations highlight the importance of individuals being careful of their online behaviours and prioritizing authenticity over pursuing an idealized image on social media.

Theme 4: Online mental health influence and support

Narratives shows results regarding social media impacts on mental health have, in fact, been mixed. There are many aspects to social media use, and each is crucial to mental health in different ways based on participant viewpoints. Tik-Tok, YouTube and Instagram are the most

popular platforms that appear to be very useful, being most often chosen by participants in both cultures for mental health support. The participants were encouraged to watch videos by professionals and those with mental issues to enhance their psychological resilience. AF2:

TikTok, I follow several accounts that discuss mental health issues. They gave me some tips. They discuss their personal experiences. I also follow a lot of individuals on YouTube who are dealing with mental health concerns, whether they are students or professionals; they have inspired me since I have been there and learnt a lot of lessons. Many platforms are helpful, especially for mental health issues. People are receiving information about their issues and how to deal with it, because at the end of the day is just "you against you.

This view was shared by other participants that one should not ignore their feelings but rather learn to cope with them and use the power of videos to help them understand themselves better and develop strategies for improving their mental health BF1:

I usually use YouTube of people talking about their mental health even I read comments of YouTube videos talking about their experiences, feelings and this help me to change my mentality, and it really helped me. Even two short sentences comment will help me to find that I am not alone.

Participants shared that, by providing an avenue for communication that does not involve the fear of judgement or rejection, social media has allowed people to interact and communicate more freely. AM1:

Finding foreigners, people who are not from your society and do not think in the same manner as your society, could be very helpful, because you do not feel alone and insane, even though the idea is widely rejected in Algerian culture. The way you find people who are open to talking about your case. For example, you can talk with people who have the same mental health problems as you, but they will be too shy, because you are from a society that is against talking about mental health. In contrary, if you use to discover people from other countries who have the same issues as you, you will feel very comfortable because you are not alone. I watch videos and learn because I do learn many things from YouTube. If I want to do a search on any topic, I can do it online since information is everywhere on the internet, and knowledge is the strongest thing you can do in life because it makes you very mentally strong.

This participant expressed the view that forming friendships with people from different cultures could be beneficial, as it might offer a sense of relief from potential judgment by Algerian society, particularly from those who are not acquainted with them. They highlighted the importance of being open about sharing mental health issues. However, within Algeria, discussing mental health issues with individuals who have similar experiences was seen as advantageous, yet hindered by the prevailing social stigma surrounding mental health. Consequently, participants found solace in sharing their mental health struggles with individuals from other cultures and countries, despite them being strangers. Moreover, they noted that engaging with mental health content on social media platforms was another beneficial strategy, contributing to improved mental health literacy and providing valuable support.

Social media platforms make it easy for young adults to seek mental health support, raise awareness, identify any mental health issues they might be dealing with, gain access to mental health services, and keep up to date on different treatments. BM6:

I think social media has made it easier now to seek mental health support. So, I think it is easier to access now and easier to see what is going on with you and to get a defect and know how to get an assessment.

The participant highlighted the pivotal role of social media platforms in providing mental health support. They emphasized how these platforms streamline access to mental health services, assessments, and guidance on seeking support. Furthermore, social media serves as a means for connecting with mental health professionals and supportive communities. Through a diverse array of resources and tools, these platforms empower individuals to proactively address their mental health challenges and seek out effective solutions.

The responses were similar in terms of the positive influence of social media on their mental health. Both participant groups indicated that it helped those overcome issues or worries that they were unable to express in person, and that it provided both informational and emotional support.

Even though several participants acknowledged the potential benefits of social media, it is also said that it is accountable for exacerbating mental health problems. They stated that browsing social media can have negative feelings but at the same time if they do not use it, they fear of missing out something. After witnessing the detrimental effects of social media platforms on them, several of the participants displayed self-control in their usage of social media. BF3:

I felt tired when I had the Instagram on my phone, I used to stay days and days scrawling in it without doing something important or much better in my life. Nevertheless, I attempt to feel tired after going on social media, I feel like my whole day gone. As I said before, it has a very negative impact on me. It makes me feel very bad scrawling all day and watching everybody lives, and I believe not everything on social media is true. But when I see their lives, I always say “oh my god, they are having such a happy life than me” that’s what I didn’t like It.

BF3 spends long periods scrolling on social media, recognizing the lack of value and development in their lives. Despite limiting usage to avoid fatigue, BF3 understands the negative impact on their well-being. The constant scrolling creates dissatisfaction and disconnects them from the real world, highlighting the emotional cost and feelings of inadequacy associated with social media use. This highlights the common experience of social media addiction.

Another participant agreed that encountering negative content on social media had an adverse effect on their mood BF1:

I investigate body image category on TikTok with people who are showing their weight lost or main habits such as how they are doing makeup and plastic surgery and stuff like that. I think that moment I started stop following them because they get a bit toxic because if you are looking at all these people who they are not sharing that they had work done or that they have done an extreme diet of food to lose weight, but you see people think that is realistic. I think when I across that point of seeing a negative thing like that, it is a time when you realise that is not real life. I think it is that time and point to move away from that.

To summarise, following the participants' points of view, social media can be an effective tool for enhancing mental health and giving support to young adults who might not have access to more formal help. Social media can offer them a distinctive forum to comprehend and discuss mental health issues by giving them, as users, access to a wide range of resources and allowing them to share their experiences. On the other hand, it can also cause them to feel anxious and compare themselves to others. Social media, however, can be a significant source of support for those dealing with mental health issues, despite its potential drawbacks. This part of the research answered the research question, "What role can social media play in communicating the mental health challenges of young adults?" that social media can promote young adults' mental health experiences both positively and negatively, but it ultimately depends on how it is used. It can provide a valuable platform for individuals to connect with others and access resources, but it can also contribute to feelings of anxiety and depression. Despite these potential drawbacks, social media can still be a valuable tool for those dealing with mental health issues, and it should be approached with caution and mindfulness.

4.5 Conclusion

Finally, this component of the study offered insight into the influence of cultural and societal variables on the experiences of young adults encountering mental health difficulties in Algeria and the United Kingdom. The findings imply that cultural variations in mental health beliefs, attitudes, and knowledge have a substantial impact on the aetiology, development, and treatment of mental health difficulties. Religion was discovered to maintain a strong position in Algerian society, while a more secular approach to mental health was observed in the UK. Additionally, the section has highlighted the significance of social media in discussing and addressing mental health concerns among young adults. While social networking may be a useful tool for improving mental health and delivering support to those in need. Overall, these

findings underscore the significance of cultural and societal factors in shaping mental health experiences among young adults in Algeria and the United Kingdom. Additionally, they emphasise the need for tailored approaches to addressing mental health challenges that consider the unique cultural contexts and beliefs of the individuals seeking help. Further research in this area can help inform the development of culturally sensitive interventions aimed at improving mental health outcomes for young adults. This section's findings will guide a thorough analysis of the impact of cultural and societal factors on young adults' mental health, offering recommendations and potential research areas.

4.6 Discussion of Study 01: Section 1

In this study, the researcher was interested in investigating mental health experiences among Algerian and British young adults in the digital age. This qualitative study offers insights into young adults' mental health experiences across cultures, examining their knowledge, coping strategies, cultural practices, and attitudes. It also highlights the role of digital media in supporting mental health. Understanding these experiences is vital for recognizing mental health importance globally. The study focuses on two areas: how cultural values shape mental health experiences among young adults, and the role of social media in supporting their mental health. This research aims to inform tailored interventions for better mental health outcomes.

Theme 1: Mental health Acknowledgment

The present study's results reveal that young adults from both Algerian and British cultures exhibit a commendable level of knowledge about mental health, demonstrating an awareness of various mental health symptoms. This discovery assumes paramount significance, as it underscores the potential benefits of instilling mental health education among young adults.

By possessing an understanding of mental health concepts individuals are better equipped to foster positive mental health outcomes and aver the progression of mental health disorders. The implication resonates with prior research, such as that conducted by Rusch et al. (2011), wherein enhanced knowledge about mental health and disorders correlated with improved awareness regarding help-seeking strategies and treatment options. Consequently, the augmented awareness ascertained among these cohorts stands poised to positively influence mental health outcomes and ultimately underscoring the pivotal role of comprehensive mental health education.

Acknowledging the study's focus solely on perceptions and definitions of mental health among young adults in Algeria and the UK, rather than measuring their actual knowledge, is important. It highlights the lack of previous research in this area, especially within the Algerian context. In a review of MHL measurement tools, O'Connor et al. revealed that the most assessed domain was recognition of mental disorders. No studies assessed either knowledge of how to seek information or knowledge of self-help interventions (O'Connor et al., 2014). When young adults have knowledge about mental health and its symptoms, they are better equipped to recognise and address any mental health issues that may arise.

Sub-theme 1a: Mental health stability

Participants in this study have a shared definition of mental health as a state of stability, indicating a comprehensive knowledge of numerous characteristics associated with mental health stability. In young adults understanding, mental health stability refers to the stability of ideas and feelings, which is defined by emotional and mental balance. It entails psychological peace and the lack of discomfort. the nuanced comprehension displayed by these young adults, wherein they depict mental health as a peaceful journey between oneself and his/her psychological wellbeing. Similarly to a previous research studies it is considered as an integral

and essential part of overall health, which can be defined in at least three ways – as the absence of disease, as a state of the organism that allows the full performance of all its functions or as a state of balance within oneself and between oneself and one’s physical and social environment (Sartorius, 2002). The holistic approach emphasizes the interconnectedness of mental, physical, and social dimensions in shaping an individual's overall health, emphasizing the importance of balance for optimal well-being.

Sub-theme 1b: Mental health signs

Young adults openly shared their knowledge about mental health symptoms, providing valuable insights into their personal experiences. In doing so, they highlighted specific symptoms they themselves had encountered, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of these manifestations.

This result indicate that young adults have shown an increased ability to recognize symptoms associated with mental health issues that often drawing from their own experiences. This aligns with prior research of (Jurecwicz, 2015) that mental health issues continue to be prevalent in the younger population. These issues typically manifest as anxiety, panic attacks, stress, depression, fear, and overthinking. Aligned with a previous research, one possible explanation for this phenomenon is that adolescence and early adulthood are critical times marked by accepting obligations while occasionally rebelling against them. Young people are gaining freedom, which exposes them to the consequences of their behaviour (Jurewicz, 2015). Their willingness to discuss personal experiences not only enriches the discourse on mental health symptoms but also fosters a sense of openness and empathy, which are crucial for destigmatizing mental health challenges and promoting a culture of support among young adults’ generation.

In addition, it is noteworthy that young adults from both cultural backgrounds consistently highlighted the existence of the relationship between mental and physical health, citing various manifestations such as laziness, anger problems, violent behaviours, eating issues, and insomnia. This highlights the profound impact of mental health on physical well-being and vice versa, a finding that resonates with previous research. It is essential to recognize that mental and physical health are not discrete domains but rather intertwined facets of overall well-being (WHO, 2004). This assertion gains further support from the work of Ohrnberger, Fichera, and Sutton (2017) who have empirically demonstrated a robust correlation between mental health and physical health. As a result, it is critical to prioritize the promotion of both mental and physical health to achieve holistic well-being.

Theme 2: Treatments for mental health contributors (coping behaviours)

The young adults' participants used both introverted and positive approach coping strategies to deal with previous adversity and current challenges. Three coping sub-themes were identified, which differed depending on the challenges and stages of life of the participants. Pervaded most young adult life experiences.

Sub-theme 2a: Reliance on self

Young people very rarely seek help from formal mental health services without the involvement of others and are very unlikely to refer themselves for treatment (Costello et al., 1998). Self-reliance was an important factor in the youths' perception of their situation. A previous research study aligns with this result shows that young people are less likely to seek help if they are experiencing suicidal thoughts and depressive symptoms; have negative attitudes toward seeking help or have had negative past experiences with sources of help; or believe they should be able to solve their own mental health problems (Rickwood, 2007). For example, a possible explanation for this is that the youths do not want to disturb their families

with their problems, primarily because their main sources of emotional support (their parents) are already in difficult situations, or they are unaware of mental health issues due to cultural beliefs or literacy. Another possibility is that the youths believe they cannot be understood or helped by others because they are not experiencing the same emotions.

Although individuals who offer advice or support aren't professionals, young people don't see them as reliable sources of help and prefer to be independent. Adolescents and young adults opt to depend on themselves rather than seeking outside assistance for their issues, which is a common obstacle to seeking help (Gulliver et al., 2010). Another explanation is that this aligns with the concept that young adults have trust in themselves and wish to take on more responsibility for their health concerns, enabling them to manage their mental health challenges. High self-trust fosters self-reliance, while high level of trust in others encourages seeking help. This indicates that self-reliance stems from believing in one's ability to handle problems independently (Meadley et al., 2024)

In this way, the preference for self-reliance could be seen as a positive sign of maturity, allowing young adults to actively take ownership of their mental health and work towards improved outcomes. On the other side, self-reliance can be a barrier to seeking help. Taken as a whole, the present results are consistent with the findings of previous research on young adults' mental health attitudes (Rickwood et al., 2005) and coping strategies (Pimenta et al., 2021). For example, previous studies found that young adults, in contrast to other age groups, do not believe that it will be helpful to seek care for their mental health concerns (Gonzales et al., 2005), and the One appraisal that can influence their coping process is self-efficacy (Bandura, 1999). If a young person believes they are well equipped to deal with their symptoms, they are less likely to seek help and more likely to try to cope on their own, as described by some of the young adults in the current study.

By not engaging with services in a timely manner, mental health problems may increase in severity and have ongoing detrimental impacts as they persist into adulthood. While self-reliance may provide a sense of independence and control, it is important for young adults to understand that seeking help does not diminish their strength or ability to manage their mental health. Overall, while self-reliance can be a positive trait in young adults, it is important for individuals to be aware of the potential negative impacts of relying solely on this approach.

Sub-theme 2b: Active coping

Another piece of evidence demonstrates meditation's magical effect in dealing with mental health issues. Many young adults from both cultures discovered that meditation, as a different therapeutic technique, had a significant impact on their mental health issues. This study result has shown that regular practise of meditation can improve overall mental health and reduce anxiety, depression, and stress levels. This finding corresponds with a previous research study that addressed meditation as a non-stigmatizing alternative to traditional mental health support. It is regarded as one of the most popular techniques in tertiary education institutes, where it is utilized to reduce stress, increase productivity, and improve overall mental health (Breedvelt et al., 2019). To some participants, it is the best way to achieve a calm and peaceful state of mind to relieve such stress. Consequently, meditation is very powerful technique for personal development such as physical and mental health, which helps to vividly imagine positive experiences that represent, either directly or symbolically.

A variety of participants identified sport as a powerful tool to help them cope with mental health issues. Regular participation in physical activity is imperative for good health as it provide the opportunity to let go of negative energy as well as creating positive energy through physical activity, being outdoors, and connecting with nature, which can help to provide a sense of peace. Aligned with this research result. World health Organisation (2019)

asserted that regular physical activity (PA) can both prevent and treat noncommunicable illnesses. Furthermore, physical activity promotes mental health, quality of life, and well-being. Similarly, to another research study physical activity enhance mental health and quality of life (Gualdi-Russo & Zaccagni.,2021). In addition, connecting with nature which can be explained as a reminder of the beauty in life and can provide an escape from the difficulties of everyday life. In accordance with a recent research study by Pascoe et al. (2020) physical activity is a non-stigmatizing intervention with few side effects and is seen as helpful in promoting mental health and treating mental health problems. Participation in physical activities, such as walking or sports, not only improves physical health but also incorporates mental components.

Sub-theme 2c: Spiritual versus Professional help

Algerian participants reported different facets of belonging to the Islamic faith, which examined the role and meaning of faith. Islamic religion provides Algerian young adults with a code of behaviour, ethics, and social values, which helps them in tolerating and developing adaptive coping strategies to deal with stressful life events. Faith-related aspects relate to a sense of belonging to the Muslim community. Religious practises played an important role in coping with mental health issues among young adults in Algeria. Aligned with a previous research study, The extant and rapidly expanding literature on religion and mental health provides support for the beneficial effects of religious involvement on mental health and well-being (Dein, 2020). The most effective coping strategies for dealing with mental health issues were mentioned as reading Qur'an, praying, and Roqia.

Numerous psychological, religious, and spiritual research studies have aligned with the Holy Quran as a source of healing, calmness, and comfort for human mental well-being. this alignment in accordance with the work of Abdekhoda and Ranjbaran (2022), who reference verses such as those from the Quran. For example,

(Qur'an 17:82) *وَنَزَّلْنَا مِنَ الْقُرْآنِ مَا هُوَ شِفَاءٌ وَرَحْمَةٌ لِّلْمُؤْمِنِينَ وَلَا يَزِيدُ الظَّالِمِينَ إِلَّا خَسَارًا*

Translation: *We send down (stage by stage) in the Qur'an that which is a healing and a mercy to those who believe: to the unjust it causes nothing but loss after loss.*

and,

(Qur'an 10:57; Talayeh Afagh Edition) *يَا أَيُّهَا النَّاسُ قَدْ جَاءَكُم مَّوْعِظَةٌ مِّن رَّبِّكُمْ وَشِفَاءٌ لِّمَا فِي الصُّدُورِ وَهُدًى وَرَحْمَةٌ لِّلْمُؤْمِنِينَ*

Translation: *O mankind! there hath come to you a direction from your Lord and a healing for the (diseases) in your hearts, and for those who believe, a guidance and mercy.*

The study's result reveals that reading the Quran can provide healing, mental health protection, and spiritual connection. It also offers guidance, inner peace, and strength in times of adversity, allowing individuals to find resilience and find inner peace.

Prayers (Salah) were also seen as a comfort and a way of helping to reduce stress. A previous research study reported that prayer is a complex and variegated phenomenon, it can function as a source of meaning, purpose and coping in a person's life and may facilitate social bonding (Koenig et al., 1997). What appears to be understood from the result is the value of fostering a deeper understanding behind the worship, which can help individuals develop a more insightful level of spirituality and connection to Allah (God).as a result, having a "healthy attachment" to God would also be linked to better psychological functioning: "... And whosoever puts his trust in Allah, then He will suffice him..." (Quran, 65:3). Since the studied participants were Algerian Muslims, it is not surprising that the Islamic beliefs, which encourage people to be optimistic, consider God's mercy, and have endurance in dealing with adverse events in life, had a high influence on the coping mechanisms adopted by the participants. Whenever there

were mental health challenges in life, they sought comfort through prayers and the recitation of their holy book as strategies to cope with stressors in life. In detail, praying may help someone to feel an extreme connection with God (who is the only one that has the power to control the world) and believe that God is the one who can provide maximum support. As a result, Algerian young adults explained the effectiveness of the integration of the spirituality and religiosity into psychotherapy. This study result of Mental Health, Religion, and Culture addresses the gap in academic attention by examining the psychological consequences of religious healing and its impact on mental well-being.

In comparing the preferences of Algerian and UK participants, it is evident that cultural distinctions influence their choices in addressing mental health concerns. Algerian participants display a strong inclination towards spiritual treatments, notably through engagement with the spiritual treatments, as a primary means to heal their mental health issues. To answer the first study question, how do young adults experience and express mental health challenges in Algeria and the United Kingdom? The section stresses the importance of culture and cultural values. Algerians are more reliant on spiritual treatments, but they also recognize the worth of professional interventions, whereas UK participants prioritize professional treatment alternatives. This cultural divide illustrates the complex interplay of social norms, belief systems, and individual choices in determining reactions to mental health issues.

After answering the first research question, attention moves to the second: how do cultural and societal factors affect young people's mental health? Themes three and four, which will be discussed in the next section, are intended to shed light on new elements of how young adults in Algeria and the United Kingdom view and deal with mental health difficulties in their societies.

Theme 3: British and Algerian communities' attitudes towards mental health

The research examines cultural variations in how Algerian and British society approach mental health concerns, with a particular emphasis on religious inclusion. Cultural differences emphasize the role of religious beliefs and practices in affecting attitudes toward mental health among countries.

Sub-theme 3a: Mental health Acceptance

The social acceptability of mental illness is viewed differently by people from various cultural backgrounds. Results showed that participants from the United Kingdom indicated that their society is more open to discussing mental health issues and that the availability of mental health services and online helplines makes it simple for them to access support. In accordance with this result, BACP's (2021) research about mental health acceptance in British society found that 83% of people think it's more socially acceptable to discuss mental health than five years ago, and 69% of people are more aware of mental health issues themselves than five years ago. Which is not the case in the Algerian community, which still views mental health issues as a private matter. Linked to this result, a previous research study has shown that personal knowledge about mental illness, knowing and interacting with someone living with mental illness, cultural stereotypes about mental illness, media stories, and familiarity with institutional practices and past restrictions all shape attitudes and beliefs about mental illness (Corrigan et al, 2004; Wahl, 2003). Participants claim that discussing mental health is taboo. Most people who bring up this subject are bullied because it is taboo in society and seen as a sign of weakness and shame. As a result, The Arab sociocultural context may therefore have an impact on their decisions, use of, and attitudes towards mental health services. The responses from the participants demonstrated that Arabs in Algeria share a common set of values, beliefs, and traditions that are very dissimilar from those of Westerners in the United

Kingdom. These cultural variations have a significant impact on how mental illness is perceived and handled.

Sub-theme 3b: Stigma

According to the Algerian participants' experiences and views about how their society perceives and treats people with mental health issues, the majority declared that Algerian society holds negative attitudes towards people with mental health issues. Several studies have shown that mental illness is largely surrounded by stigmatizing attitudes in Arab communities (Zolezzi et al 2018). As a result, there is a stigma attached to mental illness that leads to a feeling of shame and social exclusion, whereby people with mental health issues are seen as "vulnerable" or "weak." Previous studies have consistently found that the public has negative attitudes toward people who have been identified as having mental illness and often describes these people in negative terms (Angermeyer & Dietrich, 2006). Mental health is diagnosed by deviations from societal or behavioural standards.

Sub-theme 3c: Mental health literacy and lack of awareness

Some Algerian participants emphasised the notion that one of the primary causes of stigma was a general lack of knowledge and ignorance about mental health issues. Which was previously mentioned in a research study that the misunderstandings of society about the various mental disorders result in stigma (Rusch et al2005). Algerian participants emphasized the connection between these two variables. As a result, mental illness is a cultural construct, and the stigma associated with it is likely to vary between countries. For example, in Algeria, some participants emphasise that many Algerian people strongly believe in the existence of supernatural forces such as Jinn, black magic (*Sehr*), and the evil eye (*Hasad*). It is common among Arabs to relate the symptoms of mental illnesses to these supernatural reasons. The

previous research holds by the Algerian researcher Ihsan El Issa (1989) explained the situation that In Algeria and many other parts of the Arab world, a common belief system attributes mental illness to the influence of spirits called Jinn, with 'Jinnoon,' meaning madness, originating from this term.). The results of this study demonstrate the importance of religious beliefs in shaping attitudes toward mental illness in the Algerian community. Many religions, including Islam, encourage witchcraft and spirit possession, both of which are supposed to change a person's behaviour to resemble that of a mentally ill person (Ally and Laher, 2008). As a result, these ideas discourage people from seeking treatment for mental health problems. When we compared the experiences and viewpoints of the two cultural groups, this became abundantly clear. This result is in line with their traditional and cultural reliance on other sources of assistance, such as religious figures and traditional healers. Stigmatizing beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours are all considered unacceptable in Islam, and Arabs can be informed that doing so is considered a breach of their Islamic teachings. A verse in the Holy Quran says:

If ye realise this not, ask of those who possess the Message (Quran, Al-Nahl, 43).

This verse asks people who do not have answers in certain topic to go and ask those who are specialist in that topic which reflects the guidance of the Quran in advocating for seeking appropriate help, including for mental health concerns.

Like western society, participants from the UK agreed that stigma still exists in their culture even though mental health issues are widely accepted. There was a similar point view shared between the two groups that Mental illness is frequently viewed as being less significant than physical illness. For example, in a systematic reviews of mental health practices in the Arab world, Al-Krenawi (2005) stated that In Arab countries, individuals with mental health challenges tend to convey their psychological issues through physical symptoms, thus avoiding

the associated social stigma. Because of this attitude, mental illnesses are not given the same level of seriousness as physical illnesses. Due to the stigma, there is a culture of silence that discourages people from asking for help or advice for fear of being judged and this was highly emphasised by Algerian participants.

Sub-theme 3d: Cultural diversity and knowledge about mental health practises in Algeria and United Kingdom.

There are clear cultural differences between young adults from Algeria and the UK regarding their knowledge of mental health practises in both cultures. Algerian and UK participants stressed the importance of psychosocial factors, particularly family structure, and its detrimental effects on promoting people's mental wellbeing. The cultural differences in mental health awareness are evident, with western societies displaying a more open and accepting attitude towards mental health issues, according to both groups' participants' points of view. British young adults emphasised on the point that Arab communities, on the other hand, tend to keep mental health discussions private or within the family, which can make it challenging to seek help. This highlights the need for more education and awareness about mental health in Arab communities, as well as promoting mental health practises that align with cultural values. Creating safe spaces for young adults to discuss their mental health and connecting them with culturally sensitive healthcare providers can also help bridge this knowledge gap. Nonetheless, some other Algerian young adults had opposing views and acknowledged the crucial role of family in supporting and dealing with individuals with mental health conditions in Arab communities. For example, as cited by Ibrahim (2006) research has shown that in Saudi Arabia, where the culture encourages strong family ties and kinship, respondents avoided expressing feelings of hostility or aggression towards others. Instead of feelings of hostility being disguised by niceties of behaviour (*mujamala*) and conformity (*musayara*), *musayara* means to get along with others' attitudes, wishes, and expectations through conformity and

hiding one's real feelings, thoughts, and attitudes (Dwairy, 1998). Algerian young adults mentioned that western countries do not depend on their families, which makes them more independent. Being independent at an early age in the western community will lead to conflict, loneliness, guilt, loss, and loss of self-esteem, which result in the manifestation of mental health illnesses. Being far from family unity can make mental health worse.

Furthermore, Algerian young adults shed light on the fact that religious leaders in the Arab community are recognised as key figures in promoting mental health awareness and offering counsel and assistance to people suffering from mental illnesses. Due to their strong religious orientation, Algerian patients seek professional mental health care only after they have tried all other forms of healing, both traditional and religious. This frequently includes seeking religious leaders' counsel, visiting sacred sites, praying, and conducting religious rituals. Algerian young adults believe religion may be a powerful instrument for fostering mental well-being. Young adults in Algeria stressed the significance of the role played by the religious leader in helping them deal with their mental health issues. Religious leaders were identified as important sources of help for mental-health problems. Religious leaders can play an important role in treating mental health concerns in Algeria and should be considered when implementing mental health treatments in rural or urban regions.

Their involvement and advocacy can help reduce stigma and improve access to mental health services. The result shows that family structure, social context, the role of religions, and other belief systems were important in shaping the perception of young adults about mental health in different societies.

Theme 4: Preferred mental health support and help seeking behaviour.

This part of the research delves into the most preferable support plans for young adults and how they aid in managing mental health issues by selecting the most appropriate help-seeking

strategy. It offers a comparative analysis of informal and formal help-seeking behaviours, as well as religious and non-religious seeking behaviours, within the cultural contexts of Algerian and British societies.

Sub-theme 4a: Different avenues of mental health support

Seeking assistance is a significant step in accessing appropriate mental health support and enhancing one's quality of life. Participants from the UK demonstrated a strong inclination towards seeking professional help, which contributes to managing symptoms, developing coping skills, and overall well-being. This preference may be attributed to the increased availability and efficiency of mental health services in the country. Moreover, the United Kingdom has made notable progress towards achieving the mental health goals outlined by the World Health Organization. These goals emphasize the provision of comprehensive physical and mental health care for all individuals, collaboration between mental health systems and other sectors, and the improvement of mental health governance and service delivery through accurate information dissemination (Chen & Cardinal, 2021).

The result shows that most Algerian young adult participants were not interested in seeking help from professionals, despite their availability in Algerian society. This is due to various reasons that have already been mentioned, such as a lack of awareness about the importance of seeking professional help, the stigma surrounding mental health, self-reliance, or a preference for traditional healing methods. Cultural and religious formation, attribution, and conceptualization all play essential roles in diagnosing one's mental health or psychological illness and selecting appropriate therapies. It is crucial to highlight, however, that seeking professional aid should not be an open choice for both cultures. It's worth noting that seeking help can also come in the form of talking to friends or family members, joining support groups, or practising self-care techniques. In line with this study result, a previous research study stated

that social support from family and friends, as well as professional assistance, may all aid in rehabilitation in various ways. Attesting to the agency of those in recovery, the two types of assistance are not only regarded as complimentary but are intentionally kept so (Lauzier-Jobin & Houle., 2022). It's important to find what works best for each individual and to not hesitate to reach out for help when needed. More resources and education should be provided to increase awareness of the various options for seeking mental health support and create a healthier society by promoting a culture of openness and understanding towards mental health. The result shows that informal support from family can positively and negatively impact the mental health outcomes of young adults with mental health challenges in Algeria and the United Kingdom. This highlights the important role that social support can play in the treatment and management of mental health issues in youth. young people very rarely seek help from formal mental health services without the involvement of others and are very unlikely to refer themselves for treatment (Costello et al., 1998). previous research has shown that young adults are significantly less likely to report interest in receiving professional care (Wilson et al ,2005; Boyd et al; 2007). Rather they prefer Interpersonal relationships that are indispensable in helping adolescents cope with stressors, acting as social support sources that protect them from psychological distress (Camara et al, 2017), young adults prefer to handle their concerns on their own or with the support of friends and family (Schonert et al, 1996). Adolescents and young adults suffering from a mental health disorder often seek out their parents as their primary source of support and often request their assistance in the process of seeking professional help. The result of this study shows that young adults and adolescents suffering from mental health illnesses frequently seek out their parents for support and want their assistance in the process of getting professional therapy.

It is extremely crucial for parents to be able to recognise and treat mental health concerns in their young adults in their early stages. Parents' mental health literacy can be critical

to the early detection and treatment of mental health illnesses in their young adults. A previous study conducted by Bonnano et al. (2021) discussed the relationship between parental mental health literacy and stigmatizing beliefs. According to this research, parental understanding of mental health disorders and their respective treatment options has shown significant associations with several positive outcomes. Specifically, it has been linked to increased rates of seeking treatment, the provision of higher-quality treatment, and improved decision-making regarding treatment options for parents. Studies from various contexts validate this idea. a psychoeducational workshop in Kenya which notably enhanced parental mental health literacy and family relationships, underscoring the significance of addressing this matter (Alemu & Wasanga, 2023). Likewise, a mental health literacy initiative in the UK demonstrated enhancements in mental health knowledge, reduction of stigma, and intentions to seek help, highlighting the beneficial effects of such measures (Grove et al., 2023). Moreover, scholarly research underscores the impact of parental behaviour on shaping mental well-being (Brooks et al., 2023). Insufficient mental health literacy among parents can negatively impact young adults' mental health, leading to delayed help-seeking behaviour, limited access to appropriate treatment, and increased stigma. This impact on mental health outcomes has been reported by many young adults from both cultural backgrounds.

This research highlights the importance of parental mental health literacy in shaping young adults' well-being. Being well-informed about mental health issues and treatment options positively influences children's ability to seek help, access effective treatment, and reduce stigma associated with mental health challenges.

Furthermore, Algerian, and British young adults stressed the age difference between them and their parents, which prevented parents from knowing how to support them in such situations. Disparities in experiences and perspectives, as well as changing societal norms and expectations, play a role in this occurrence. The disparity in age can impede assistance due to

varying mental health encounters and societal standards, resulting in misinterpretations and obstacles in communication between young individuals and their parents (Duby et al., 2022). These misunderstandings and misinterpretations can occasionally arise because of the generational gap, with young adults harbouring distinct viewpoints from their parents. Consequently, there is a deficiency in both support and communication, thereby complicating the process for young adults to feel acknowledged and comprehended. In line with this notion, Dusknicky et al. (2023) stated that the generation gap, ultimately obstructing efficient communication and support. To bridge this gap, it is important for parents to actively listen to their young adults and try to see things from their point of view, not comparing them to other people's experiences and lives. Open and honest communication can help both parties better understand each other and prevent conflicts from arising.

Sub-theme 4b: Religiosity

To understand why young adults are particularly unlikely to access treatment, it is important to determine the specific beliefs and experiences of young adults with mental illness. The result shows that Algerian participants' relationship to God when facing mental health issues was very important in their healing journey. This relationship helped create positive emotions to overcome mental health difficulties. Muslim Algerian interventions incorporate Islamic principles into the therapeutic process, which are derived from the two primary sources of Islamic teaching. The cultural and theological ideas and traditions of Islam have a significant impact on the lifestyles and viewpoints of Algerian young adults in all aspects of their existence, including decision-making, family relations, health practices, and healthcare utilization. The five pillars of Islam - faith, prayer, charity, fasting, and pilgrimage to Mecca - form the basis of these ideas. Contact with religious figures such as religious leaders (imams) were viewed positively by Algerian young adults. One study (Gilat et al., 2010) revealed that

when a member of an Arab family shows symptoms of mental illness, Arabs usually turn first to family practitioners, followed by family members, and then the Sheikh. Only few people turn to mental health practitioners. In most Arab countries, there is no interaction between the medical profession and the traditional healers (Okasha, Karam & Okasha, 2012). Imams are considered the first help point for Algerian young adults who find it difficult to deal with mental health issues and find social support. Religious healers are often the first non-family personnel with whom Algerian young adults prefer to disclose mental illness-related issues due to their private, non-judgmental, culturally familiar approach, and non-stigmatised encounters. Those healers use religious practises such as prayers, reading 'Ruqya' (specific verses from the Holy Quran), or asking the patient to drink and wash their body using water over which verses of the Quran are read. Overall, expanding access to culturally relevant mental health care is critical for fostering well-being and reducing stigma in Algeria.

Different cultural beliefs about mental illness may influence the type of treatment that is sought, addressed, and managed. In the context of the United Kingdom, there exists a distinct approach regarding the utilization of religion in the treatment of mental health conditions. Within Western societies such as the UK, a historical tendency towards ambivalence or dismissal is observed concerning the integration of religious encounters within mental healthcare practices. Influential figures like Sigmund Freud often portrayed religion as irrational, antiquated, and associated with neurosis (Dein, 2010).

Most participants in the UK consider reaching out to friends as the most suitable method to seek assistance, given their similar ages and mutual understanding of each other's challenges. This highlights the importance of considering cultural factors when providing mental health care and the value of social support in managing a mental illness. It also suggests that traditional religious approaches to mental health may not be as prevalent in certain cultures or regions. Although religious beliefs and rituals may yield favourable impacts on well-being universally,

while religious beliefs and practices may have positive effects on well-being across cultures, there has been limited integrating of cultural considerations into research on the relationship between religion and mental health from a Western perspective (Loewenthal & Lewis, 2011).

The result demonstrates that a significant number of young adults in the UK do not stick to religious traditions even if they were raised in religious families, favouring alternative techniques to tackle their mental health issues. This tendency could be attributed to the presence of well-established healthcare system in the UK offering access to mental health experts and resources which are preferred over religious interventions. Within the National Health Service (NHS) of the UK, individuals with mental health conditions have commonly been given therapy mainly through medication following the medical model, rather than integrating religious or spiritual dimensions (Forrester-Jones et al., 2018). Likewise, research indicates that while a significant portion of the UK population identifies with a specific religion (largely Christianity), a minority of psychiatrists in Britain personally embrace religious beliefs, indicating a more secular outlook in mental healthcare provision (Cook et al., 2009). The findings illustrated the existence of general strategies, some rooted in Islamic teachings, that could aid in Algerians individuals' recovery while others highlighting the efficacy of seeking assistance from friends or professionals as a more effective approach in Western British society.

Sub-theme 4c: Support those who exhibit symptoms

Having an awareness of one's mental health difficulties could be a starting point in the process of change and support. It is demonstrated by Evans-lacko et al. (2013) in their research study that knowing someone with a mental health problem or familiarity with mental illness is strongly associated with mental health-related knowledge, attitudes, and behaviour (Corrigan

et al., 2012; Pettigrew et al., 2006). The comparison of the findings between the two groups highlighted that there are different levels of acceptance, awareness, and understanding of mental health issues. These differences may be attributed to various factors such as cultural background, education level, and personal experiences.

Both participant groups were knowledgeable about how to support those who displayed mental health issues. The British participants emphasised the significance of creating a safe and judgement-free environment for people with mental health issues to share their experiences, but the best advice they would give to someone with mental health issues is to follow a formal therapy programme through visiting professionals. The Algerian participants, on the other hand, concentrated on religion and spirituality in their counsel to those suffering from mental health problems, encouraging them to adhere to Islamic religious practises such as being attached to God. Having a “healthy attachment” to God would also be linked to better psychological functioning. A belief in a higher power can help to overcome feelings of helplessness, providing a framework for understanding difficult circumstances and a sense of meaning or purpose (Loewenthal, 2001). Additionally, to the emphasise on the point engaging in religious practice such as prayers that would make Muslims comfortable and released from the stress and mental health issues they face. As a result, Many Muslims acknowledged the importance of prayers and its benefit to health and healing (Padela & Zaidi, 2018). engaging in these rituals can promote mental and emotional well-being.

The result of the study highlights the importance of social support and positive feedback in promoting mental health among young adults of different cultural backgrounds. Traditional healing in Algeria or professional treatment in the United Kingdom has been viewed as having positive effects on individuals with mental health issues. Both are effective in addressing mental health concerns and improving overall well-being, but the approach may vary

depending on cultural beliefs and practises. As a result, both participants gave appropriate and effective support advice that aligns with their cultural beliefs and values.

4.7 conclusion

There were similarities and differences in the way participants approached and sought help for their mental health issues, which may have been influenced by their cultural backgrounds and the availability of mental health resources in their respective countries. The level of awareness was high in the western community and low in the Algerian community, and that returned to the cultural beliefs and traditions of each society. Through this result, the researcher answered the research question: How do young adults experience and express mental health challenges in Algeria and the United Kingdom? And highlighted the importance of considering cultural factors when addressing mental health issues.

Cultural stigmas surrounding mental health were present in both countries, but they differed in their manifestation and severity, with Algerian youth facing more significant barriers to accessing mental health care due to cultural beliefs and practises, while they were similar in the UK but not to the same severity as in Algeria. Seeking help was so important in dealing with mental health issues in this age group, but not all young adults accepted this idea, as some of them were introverted. It is important to note that sports and exercise were found to have a positive impact on mental health in both countries, but this was more widely accepted and encouraged in the UK than in Algeria. Therefore, promoting physical activity as a means of improving mental health may be a culturally sensitive approach to addressing mental health concerns among young adults in both countries. Family and community support in managing mental health was highly valued in both cultures, with many young adults expressing a preference for seeking help from these sources rather than professional services. The availability and accessibility of mental health services varied between the two countries, with the UK having more resources and support systems in place compared to Algeria. Therefore,

it is important for policymakers and healthcare providers in Algeria to prioritise the development and implementation of mental health services and support systems to meet the needs of young adults. On the other hand, traditional healing through religious practises and contact with religious leaders was the best support system in the Algerian community. Incorporating traditional healing practises and religious leaders into mental health services in Algeria could potentially improve the accessibility and acceptability of these services for young adults. This part of the result answered the second research question. How do cultural and societal factors affect young people's mental health?

This study result highlights the importance of raising awareness and providing support for mental health issues globally, especially among young adults who are more susceptible to these challenges. It also emphasises the need for a collaborative effort between different countries to tackle mental health issues and promote well-being. It suggests that a combination of religious and non-religious strategies could be effective in addressing mental health issues among young adults in both cultures. It is crucial to acknowledge that the findings of this study may not be generalizable to other cultures or age groups, and further research is needed to understand the complex interplay between culture and mental health. Additionally, mental health interventions should be tailored to the specific cultural beliefs and practises of each country to ensure their effectiveness and accessibility.

4.8 Section 2: Social media usage and mental health study 01

There are serious obstacles to accessing care, but this does not exclude the need for support and services for young adults with mental health disorders. However, these obstacles may lead young adults to seek alternatives to more traditional means of care. An alternative is to seek information and support online regarding mental health. This part of the study show social media has become a part of the daily life of young people in different communities, and how different platforms enable them to express themselves and communicate with others.

Furthermore, how can social media be a source of emotional support for young people who do not have traditional or professional assistance, or who prefer to seek assistance anonymously? This section answers the research question: This section answers the research question: What role can social media play in communicating mental health challenges of young adults? The result of the study showed that social media platforms offer challenges and opportunities in terms of mental well-being of young adults. It provides a platform for emotional support, but it can also lead to fear, depression, and social isolation due to pressure to constantly compare themselves to others.

Theme 1: Mental health challenges sharing online.

Online interventions are viewed as having great potential for reaching youth in distress, but little is known about how well these interventions fit with young people's own priorities and practices with online support (Gibson & Trnka, 2020). Some participants from both cultures use social media to get mental health information, but they never share their mental health struggles. Listening to their voices helped the researcher understand why they were not sharing their mental health problems online. Participants placed a premium on the concept of introversion in real or virtual life, as well as a desire to keep their personal struggles private, particularly when it comes to mental health. Yet, as stated in the first section of the study, disclosing mental health difficulties online or in person can be a complex decision that may depend on various factors, such as the participant's comfort level and the potential consequences of disclosure. Previous research studies confirmed this idea that most young adults show that seeing positive things on social media helps them to support their mental health difficulties. For example, Considerations such as simplicity, accessibility of information, and privacy can influence young people's decisions to use the internet as a source of support for sensitive issues (Gibson & Trnka, 2020; Pretorius et al., 2019). A young person might prefer

to go online and independently search for professional services so that they can maintain their privacy and control over the information (Frost et al., 2016), rather than, for example, asking their parents for help. For this reason, the internet is considered as an additional source of support in the present study.

Consequently, for many participants, expressing mental health difficulties or experiences online is an open option. On the other hand, some participants articulated the positive potential of using social media to learn about and promote their mental health and offered various implementation strategies. As online services can increase accessibility and provide anonymity, there are concerns about privacy, confidentiality, and trustworthiness of online resources among young people (Kuer et al., 2014). Additionally, due to social media's flexibility, information can be customised to the priorities of its intended users. This highlights the importance of mental health professionals and organisations utilising social media platforms to reach a wider audience and provide relevant information. Although participants primarily discussed their use of social media to share their mental health challenges, search engines, and navigating between professionally produced websites and user-generated content, many of the young adults appeared to value different types of health knowledge coming from various sources. This can help bridge the gap between talking about mental health openly and raising awareness, which can lead to a sense of community and reduce the stigma surrounding mental health issues, especially in Arab communities.

Sub-theme 1a: online mental health communications' impact on social interaction

There is considerable debate regarding the potential connections between the use of social media and mental health disorders. Aligning with the outcomes of the current research study, an earlier investigation asserted that the growing prevalence of internet and social media involvement in the daily routines of young people has resulted in notable effects of social media practices on mental health (Vaingankar et al., 2022). This underscores the ongoing discussion

within the research community regarding the influence of digital platforms on the mental well-being of young adults, emphasizing the necessity for ongoing exploration and comprehension of these intricate relationships. On the one hand, social media may help to avoid mental illness by enabling and promoting social interaction and connection as well as allowing users to reflect components of their identity and express emotion relevant to their lived experience.

The participants in this study offered ideas regarding the possible negative effects of using social media to promote mental health. Findings show that there is a potential for social media to reinforce stigma and trigger negative emotions. Furthermore, the study also revealed that social media may not be an appropriate platform for those who are vulnerable to cyberbullying and online harassment, which could further exacerbate their mental health issues. On the other hand, based on the experiences of the participants, social media facilitate communication and self-expression. Support is not so easily available offline, then online forums have a potentially vital role in the lives of young people who are vulnerable, isolated, or in some way marginalized. Overall, online communication and social media have evolved into effective instruments for connecting with people, sharing personal information, and receiving support from virtual communities. Individuals may now connect and interact with a larger network of people because of the unique properties of anonymity, synchronisation, and accessibility. Additionally, social media has been shown to be beneficial for bridging the loneliness gap and providing young adults with emotional support. As a result, internet communication and social media have become essential aspects of modern life, allowing individuals to communicate with one another.

Therefore, mental health promotion should consider a variety of communication support methods, including in-person interactions. Participants believe that in-person conversation and body contact are essential for resolving mental health difficulties in a caring and sympathetic manner. While there may be cultural variances in how these conversations are

addressed, the significance of personal connection and empathy remains universal. The study found that while online communication can provide a platform for discussing sensitive topics, it should not replace face-to-face interaction as it is crucial for building strong relationships and developing social skills because the lack of visual cues in computer-mediated communication can lead to difficulties in accurately interpreting the emotions of others, which may have significant consequences for effective communication and relationship building.

It is important to be aware of these limitations and to take extra care to clarify and confirm understanding in digital interactions. Young adults can forge stronger connections and steer clear of miscommunications that might impede effective communication by being aware of the limitations of digital communication and taking precautions to ensure clear understanding and that everyone has equal opportunities to receive support and maintain a healthy balance between online and offline social interactions.

Theme 2: Importance of social media

Social media has enabled new ways to develop relationships and remain socially connected but has also caused negative consequences such as virtual communities and a new set of interaction norms. Social networking is a crucial element in protecting our mental health. Both the quantity and quality of social relationships affect mental health, health behaviour, physical health, and mortality risk (Martinsen, 2008), social media has been regarded as both valuable and invaluable among young adults. A few respondents from both cultures felt that their excessive social media engagement have, however, been linked to many mental health issues. Several studies have been conducted on the impacts of social media, and it has been indicated that the prolonged use of social media platforms such as Facebook may be related to negative signs and symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress (Berryman et al., 2018; O'Reilly et al, 2018).

Furthermore, other participants' reflection on social media importance was depending on prioritizing positivity which results in being motivated to embrace positive change and contribute to others' motivation, and it has been identified as important to positive development to create a positive educational environment and increase competence. Aligned with a recent research study by Esam & Hashim, (2016) that Social media encompasses a range of online tools that allow users to share and distribute fresh ideas, thoughts, and information within an interactive and virtual environment.

Promoting positive youth development which can be facilitated by social media interactions, educational messages, and empowerment. The result shows that participants embrace these traits to overcome the negativity found on social media. It lay a foundation for comprehending the role of social media in promoting youth mental health as well as an exploration of the negative social media context and experiences that are frequently linked to mental health issues such as depression and anxiety.

Theme 3: Online Activities

Coping involves a collection of strategies and techniques that individuals use to manage stress, anxiety, and other difficult emotions. These can include exercise, mindfulness practises, talking to a trusted friend or therapist, and engaging in hobbies or activities that bring joy. In line with this result, a previous research study stated that social media has the potential to improve users' mental health by facilitating social connections and peer support (Naslund et al, 2020). In this study, our participants narrated several instances when they felt happy while connecting or using social media to feel happier by building positive activities that helped them progress and overcome their mental health issues. According to research results, three aspects of social media usage may promote positive mental health among youth: connections with friends and family, as similarly mentioned in recent research that highlights its role in providing

opportunities for peer support and solidarity (e.g., Pérez-Sabater, 2021). Social media can have a positive impact on the mental health of young adults, particularly in terms of connecting with others, engaging with positive content, and expressing themselves.

In contrast, it has also been reported negative experiences with social media such as social comparison, which had adverse effects on their mental health and well-being. In line with this result a previous research study social media may function as a source of stress or reinforce negative self-evaluations through social comparisons, and heavier Facebook users are more likely to believe others are happier and have better lives (Nessi & Prinstein, 2015; Chou & Edge, 2012). The result of this study reveal a significant correlation between the act of scrolling through social media news feeds and the phenomenon known as fear of missing out, a form of problematic attachment to social media as discussed in previous research by Altuwairiqi et al. (2019) This behaviour is associated with a range of adverse outcomes, including diminished sleep, reduced life competency, heightened emotional tension, negative impacts on physical well-being, increased anxiety, and impaired emotional control.

In addition to the addictive use of social media by young adult participants in both cultures led them to compare themselves to others on social media that resulted depression, low self-esteem, and feelings of inadequacy. In a recent meta-analysis conducted by Cunningham et al. (2021), it was discovered that the correlation between depressive symptoms and problematic social media use outweighed the impact of the time spent on social networking sites. This result underscores the well-established idea that engaging in social comparisons can have a notable negative effect on self-esteem. This aligns with prior research, which has consistently demonstrated that individuals who frequently engage in social comparison tend to have lower self-esteem, poorer self-perception, and more negative emotional experiences." (Jang et al., 2016). This is because social media frequently displays an idealised portrayal of people's lives.

Theme 4: Online mental health influence and support

Sharing similar mental health experiences on social media has assisted young adults in developing techniques to better understand themselves. Young people have voiced worries about the influence of the internet and social media on their mental health, yet they will seek help online. There is a clear need for leadership and engaging online mental health resources. This emphasises the significance of social media as a forum for mental health assistance as well as the need for more accessible and inclusive tools to help young adults manage their mental health. It also emphasises social media's potential as a tool for mental health advocacy and education.

Social media plays an important role in raising awareness of mental illnesses as users share advice, information, and personal stories to make mental health support more accessible and inclusive. Social media is used in health communication by individuals, health professionals, disease centres, and other health regulatory bodies. The functioning of social networking sites is crucial for promoting young people's overall mental health and well-being by enhancing social connectivity, self-efficacy, general knowledge, and/or life skills. The Internet has also made it simpler for consumers to locate information, contact professionals, and learn about their problems. Social media adds a new dimension to health care by providing a channel for the public, patients, and health professionals to communicate about health concerns, potentially improving health outcomes. In line with this research findings a previous research study in the United Kingdom, social media has become one of the most popular sources of health information among young people (Fergie et al., 2016a, 2016b). In Algeria, Facebook is the leading and most visited social media website, where people share news and moments and express ideas as well. Accordingly, it becomes one of the main sources of information, news, education, and culture (Abainia, 2020). Social media has become a key means to access resources relevant to young adults' health experiences. Although opportunities

for users to contribute health-related content on personal 'homepages' were available previously (Hardey, 2001), As a result, although participants mentioned some negative effects that had a negative impact on their mental health, the findings indicate that social media for young adults offers more benefits and support across cultures than drawbacks. According to the current study, social media can be an effective tool for enhancing young adults' mental health outcomes, especially when used in a positive and supportive manner. Nevertheless, it is critical to keep an eye on how social media affects mental health and to develop plans to counteract any unfavourable outcomes.

4.9 Conclusion

Young adults' experiences with mental health issues were similar in Algeria and the United Kingdom since they were in the same age range and both experienced difficulties dealing with mental health issues. They were both educated and conscious of their mental health challenge, which demonstrates that today's young adults are more eager to comprehend and inform themselves about health issues. However, the cultural and social contexts in which these experiences occur may differ between the two countries, leading to different coping mechanisms and support systems.

This study found that good interactions, social support, and social connectivity on social networking sites were associated with decreased levels of anxiety and depression. Negative interactions and social comparisons on SNS were linked to increased levels of stress and mental health issues. Three aspects of social media usage may promote positive mental health among young people: connection with the community, engagement with social media content, and the value of social media as an outlet for expression. However, there are three components to the negative outcomes of social media: addiction, social comparison, and distraction. To summarise, social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and Instagram facilitate mental health communication and intervention. Yet, these platforms have limits and might

contribute to the spread of disinformation. As a result, it is vital to utilise them appropriately and examine the information provided on them cautiously.

4.10 Summary

There is significant insight to be gained in comparing the different perspectives of British and Algerian young adults on mental health concerns and preferred therapeutic approaches. In the United Kingdom, mental health problems are mainly viewed as individual issues that require self-help, community support, or professional therapy in more severe situations. In this society, religion or spirituality does not often play a large part in the healing process for mental health concerns. Algerian young adults, on the other hand, see mental health difficulties as connected with spiritual issues. They consider mental health difficulties to be spiritual issues, and they feel that a self-healing journey should incorporate traditional therapeutic approaches such as religious treatment and religious practices. In this cultural setting, religion is more prevalent and serves a purpose.

British and Algerian young adults' approach mental health differently, with British young adults emphasising professional treatment and community support and Algerian young adults emphasising religious practises and religious therapy. Both cultures recognise the beneficial and negative impacts of social media on mental health, admitting that social media may increase stress and anxiety while also providing a feeling of connection and support. It is critical to recognise that cultural perspectives and societal norms impact understanding and treatment of mental health disorders, emphasising the need to take cultural aspects into account when establishing mental health support methods and treatments.

Through this research study, another set of research questions has emerged concerning the traditional healing processes within Muslim communities. The researcher has raised questions about how these traditional or religious healing processes manifest among Muslims

and what role imams play in addressing mental health issues within their congregations. Additionally, the study aims to investigate whether imams have sufficient training and knowledge to effectively deal with mental health issues across diverse Muslim cultural backgrounds and societies.

Chapter 05: Findings and discussion study 02.

5.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the findings of our study, which examines the critical role played by imams in addressing mental health issues within Muslim communities in Algeria and the United Kingdom. As trusted religious leaders and guides, imams hold a unique position in the lives of community members, providing not only spiritual guidance but also support for various facets of life, including mental health. This chapter delves into the knowledge, training, and practices of imams concerning mental health issues and explores their collaboration with mental health professionals and referral processes when necessary. By shedding light on these aspects, the researcher aims to gain a comprehensive understanding of the imams' role in promoting mental well-being within the Islamic communities.

5.2 Rational of study

This present study seeks to investigate how imams provide mental health support from an Islamic religious perspective in Algeria and the UK, as well as acknowledge their understanding of mental illnesses and spiritual issues. Given the rapidly growing populations of Muslims in Western societies, it is imperative to develop a better understanding of their psychosocial and spiritual needs and concerns (Rasool, 2016). Furthermore, it focuses on the role of imams in Muslim mental health counselling across cultures and examines the imams' recognition of mental health problems, their consultation experiences, and their opinions about the appropriate type of referral. The benefits of choosing imams from different cultural backgrounds to present the most beneficial treatments, advice, and guidance used by imams to promote Muslims' mental health This study highlights the importance of cultural sensitivity in

mental health counselling in Muslim communities and the need for imams to be trained in cross-cultural communication. It also suggests that incorporating traditional Islamic practises and beliefs into mental health treatment may be beneficial for Muslim patients. It is essential to study the imams' challenges with Muslims with mental health issues, which may include stigmatization, a lack of knowledge about mental health, resistance to seeking professional help, or wrong beliefs about mental health issues.

5.3 Participants

The study's target population comprises imams aged between 30 and 60, all of whom are Muslim men. To identify potential participants in both Algeria and the United Kingdom, we employed a comprehensive approach that combined indirect online methods with face-to-face interactions. Permissions diligently has been obtained from mosque administrators and administrators of various public Facebook groups related to education, religion, and psychology. It's important to note the considerable diversity in the roles of imams within mosques, as revealed by the research findings. These roles encompass Quran teachers, professors of Quranic education, preachers, and Arabic teachers. While most participants hold bachelor's degrees from Islamic institutes, some possess relevant certifications from their respective mosques. The accumulated experience of participants in mosque-related activities ranged from 2 years to 10 years, providing valuable context to their perspectives on mental health within their communities.

5.4 Sample size

The qualitative questionnaires can be structured to add more “qualitativeness” to quantitative data to give the research a richer and more meaningful result especially when such research

involves personal opinions like research investigating the role of imams in two different communities and cultures. Nonprobability sample has been used by choosing Purposive or judgmental sampling, which is a strategy in which specific settings, participants, or events are deliberately chosen to provide important information that cannot be obtained from other options (Maxwell, 1996). It has been decided what information was necessary to have and then searches for individuals who can and are willing to provide it due to their knowledge or experience such as imams in this case study. Furthermore, using snowball sampling increases the sample size of imams because a few cases may help to encourage other cases to participate in the study. This method is best suited for small populations that are difficult to reach due to their closed nature, such as secret societies and inaccessible professions (Breweton and Millward, 2001). This means appropriate cases has been chosen to be in the sample whilst actively excluding others. Consequently, some of the population had a chance of being chosen as participants, i.e. only imams who work in the mosques were included in the study as participants, whilst others will not such as other religious people who are not imams but use Islamic psychotherapy such as Roqia to treat Muslims with mental health and spiritual issues. 30 imams have been chosen for recruiting (15 from Algeria and 15 from the United Kingdom). The previous studies by Bujang, Omar, and Baharum (2018) ; Conroy (2015) ; and Delice (2010) support the sample size of 30 as a minimum desired number for the questionnaire-based survey for reliable analyses outcomes. Therefore, collecting Qualitative questionnaires were considered appropriate to support and strengthen one another. Some of the questionnaire questions were designed to ask quantitative questions while leaving enough space for respondents to fill in their own opinions and that allow the questions to be controlled while also being both closed and open-ended. some questions dealt with ranking the imams' opinions about their experiences with the utilisation of Islamic psychotherapy intervention based on Islamic instructions, teachings for Muslims with mental health issues and their opinions on

challenges treating them and some on ranking their collaborations with mental health services and professionals.

5.5 Data collection

The researcher utilized online social media platforms, particularly Facebook pages, to establish initial contact with Algerian imams. Through this method, the researcher connected with one imam who facilitated the data collection process in Algeria. After explaining the study and outlining the criteria for participant inclusion (only religious leaders working in mosques), the researcher and the imam agreed on a collaborative approach. The imam then distributed the questionnaires to other imams within his network. Once the imams completed the questionnaires, they were collected, scanned, and sent to the researcher via email.

In the UK, the researcher reached out to administrators of mosque pages and groups to enlist their support in disseminating the qualitative questionnaires. The imams involved in the UK phase of the study were from various nationalities but were born and raised in the UK. Initial attempts to communicate with UK imams via email and social media posts went unanswered, prompting the researcher to take a more proactive approach. The researcher personally visited cities in the UK, such as Manchester, Liverpool, and London, where there is a significant mosque presence. This face-to-face strategy ultimately proved to be the most effective for collecting data from imams in the UK. While not all UK imams agreed to complete the questionnaires, many suggested and referred colleagues within their mosques and occasionally to other mosques.

The semi-structured questionnaires were provided in both Arabic and English to give imams the option to respond in the language they felt most comfortable with. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary. Each participant received a brief overview of the research project, which outlined the procedures and explained the implications of their involvement. Participants

were required to read and understand the consent form, ensuring their comfort and security regarding data collection and the study's aims.

To ensure participants fully understood the study before consenting, the research purpose was communicated both orally and in writing to the Algerian and British imams. Once participants expressed their willingness to contribute, invitations and detailed information sheets were distributed. Written consent forms were then sent via email. Participants were informed that there were no costs associated with participation and were given a one-month window to withdraw their consent and request data removal. The researcher's contact information was provided for any inquiries or concerns. In cases where British participants did not respond to emails, consent forms were distributed and explained in person.

Throughout the data collection process, the researcher maintained a neutral stance, creating a comfortable and non-pressured environment for participants to freely express their opinions. Participants were also given the option to decline to complete the questionnaire or skip specific questions if they felt uncomfortable, ensuring that their participation remained entirely voluntary.

5.6 Data analysis

Thematic analysis was employed as the method of choice for data analysis in this research study. Thematic analysis is a systematic approach to identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns within the data, involving steps such as data familiarization, generation of initial codes, theme identification, theme review, definition, and naming, and report production (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Structured inductive thematic analysis was used to examine the open-ended responses, allowing for the identification of common topics, concepts, and patterns within the qualitative data. This approach provided a comprehensive understanding of the data's

complexity and enabled the researcher to uncover meaningful themes and connections among data points, ultimately facilitating a robust analysis of the research findings.

The study involved translating online questionnaires from Algerian imams into English to capture participants' meanings. Word-for-word translation was used for the Qur'anic version, while some British questionnaires were translated into English for Arabic-speaking participants. The coding process involved manually reading each questionnaire and identifying recurring themes or patterns. Codes were assigned to specific segments of text, grouped according to similarities and patterns. These codes were then clustered together to form overarching themes. The key findings of the study provided insight into the similarities and differences in promoting Muslim mental health in Algeria and the United Kingdom. These themes represented the key findings and provided insight into the promotion of mental health in both countries.

5.7 Themes study 02

After conducting a Thematic Analysis, eight themes were generated, each accompanied by its associated sub-themes. The details of these themes and sub-themes can be found in the thematic table below.

Table 5: Table format detailing themes from Thematic Analysis

Themes	Subthemes
1-Imams' role in the mosque	1a- Imams' mental health knowledge 1b- The positive influence of Islamic
2-Role of Islamic religion in supporting mental health	faith on M.H 2a- Description of M.H support in the Holy Quran

3-Muslim Beliefs towards causes and solutions to Mental health.	3a- Imams’ engagement with Muslims with M.H issues
4-Imams’ initiatives in Meeting M.H needs	4a- Imams’ recommendations for Muslims with mental health issues
5-Religious interventions and psychotherapy	/
6-Barriers that prevent Muslims from Accessing M.H services	6a- Imams’ role in reducing stigma in Muslim communities.
7- Professional referrals	7a- Imams’ mental health training 7b- Spiritual treatment effectiveness 7c- Imams professional referrals and collaborations with mental health professionals

To gain a comprehensive understanding of the various aspects of this role, it is essential to explore the key themes associated with how imams engage with and support individuals dealing with mental health concerns. The following themes answered the research questions What it is the imams’ role in counselling Muslims with mental health issues? By providing a comprehensive overview of their responsibilities and approaches in addressing mental health concerns within the Muslim community.

Theme 01: Imams’ role in the mosque

Before delving into questions about mental health, the researcher seeks to understand the diverse interpretations of the term "imam" as offered by imams themselves. Imams provide various nuanced meanings contingent upon the context. In this context, they elucidate the overarching significance of an imam and the roles they fulfil within Muslim communities. According to British imam (1):

Imam is the leader of Muslims in prayers. The religious leader who teaches people recitation and Qur'anic studies. Imam should know all teachings and rules of religion.

I will quote as evidence the hadith of Anas, may God be pleased with him, in the words of the prophet peace be upon him "the imam was appointed to be followed" which means to be followed in his deeds, steadfastness and prayers which is one of the doors of repentance to god. Imam benefits the society with education, spreading the religion, and solving the problems of the society and individuals. Algerian imam (8)

while another Algerian Imam (11) stated that:

Being an imam is considered an honourable profession that involves learning, teaching, and calling people to God. It encompasses encouraging righteousness, urging goodness, and instructing individuals on matters of creed, Sharia (Islamic law), and morals. The imam acts as a guarantor for the believers in their prayers, offering guidance and assistance in matters of spirituality.

The British and Algerian imams explained that Their role is indeed pivotal in guiding and educating their communities on matters of religion. They are seen as leaders to be followed not just in their actions but also in their steadfastness and prayers. Imams are respected as knowledgeable interpreters of the Quran, providing comprehensive religious instruction covering ethics, rituals, and community affairs. While they may not be experts in every aspect of Islam, they possess a deep understanding of its fundamental principles, teachings, and practices. Their primary aim is to offer spiritual guidance and moral direction aligned with Islamic values, aiding their communities in leading righteous and fulfilling lives. This often involves disseminating accurate Islamic teachings and leading prayers in mosques, relying on a strong foundation in Islamic studies. Through their leadership, imams help deepen people's understanding of Islam and its application in daily life, fostering a sense of unity and faith within the community.

While other Algerian and British imams identify it as:

it is the succession of the messenger peace be upon him, He is one of the main guides in building the Islamic community through the pulpit or circles of knowledge and preaching and methodological lessons. (British imams 2)

It is divine message whose banner was carried by the prophets who are the best of human beings, and it is a message to all humanity. (Algerian Imams 2)

Being an imam is the profession of the prophet Muhammad (Peace be upon him) which is the model of Muslims to be followed in his actions and behaviours that benefit the Muslim society

They do so by drawing upon the example and teachings of Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) and by adhering to Islamic principles and traditions.

Some imams mentioned that it is not only about following the prophet (peace be upon him) but imamate was their profession that serves Muslims communities in all times and places.

An Algerian Imam (13) stated:

Imamate is the profession of prophets and messengers, as it combines education, role models and contribution to the service of society, country, and people.

While some may view the role of an imam as primarily a religious and spiritual one, others may emphasize the imam's responsibility as a protector or advocate for the Muslim community.

According to a British Imam (1):

being an imam also could mean protecting society and Muslim community through messages.

Leading a group of Muslims in prayer, advising, solving family and social problems through the teaching of the Islamic religion (British Imam 8)

Being an imam involves addressing social injustices, promoting equality, defending Muslims' rights, and safeguarding their interests. Apart from leading prayers and being spiritual leaders, imams guide the Muslim community through communication, and offer messages promoting societal well-being, striving to support and uplift their communities in various aspects of life based on Islamic teachings.

Another Algerian imam discussed how imams serve as a guarantee for believers' prayers. This means that the Imam's spiritual status has a favourable impact on the community's prayers. Their presence and leadership are thought to increase the spiritual efficacy and acceptability of the prayers behind them.

The virtue of imamate is great because the imam is a guarantor of the believers in their prayers. His job is to urge righteousness and goodness. Where it happened that a man came to the prophet peace be upon him and he said: "tell me something to do" he replied: "be the imam of your people". Algerian Imam (10)

In this incident mentioned by the Algerian imam, when a man sought the Prophet Muhammad for guidance, the Prophet encouraged him to become the imam of his people. This might be seen as a call to take on a leadership position in the community, taking the duty of guiding and directing the people toward righteousness and good deeds.

Being an imam is a Heavy Responsibility according to imams' statements; According to an Algerian imam (12):

The imamate is a great trust and a heavy responsibility that the imam undertakes to achieve the desired social reform and to preserve religiosity in society calling to worship god, preserving worship, educating people, teaching them their religion, achieving their unity and solidarity among themselves.

Additionally, to another British imam (9) who summarised the meaning and the role of imam and think that it is what Muslims need in their life.

The call to righteousness, guidance, education, advice, explanation of legal provisions and other things that Muslims need.

The imam undertakes this responsibility to achieve social reform and preserve religiosity in society.

To summarise, imams are knowledgeable individuals who guide Muslims in their daily lives and provide support in the mosque. They lead congregational prayers, teach, and recite the Quran, offer spiritual guidance and counselling, educate the community about Islamic beliefs, address social issues, and promote unity among Muslims. Imams also deliver sermons, facilitate Quranic study and memorization, and work towards social reform and preserving religiosity in society. It acknowledges that there may be variations in the imam's role influenced by cultural, regional, and individual contexts within the Muslim community.

Sub-theme 1a: Imams Mental health knowledge

Inquiring with imams about the definition of mental health to see if they can identify problems with mental health and grasp risk factors and causes. Imams' awareness and appropriate knowledge of mental health may play a critical role in decreasing stigma, creating awareness, and providing spiritual and emotional support to cope with mental health difficulties.

Someone who is mentally stable and have a good psychological wellbeing. (British Imam 1)

Similarly to another Algerian imam (12):

Mental health means having a good psychological immunity from mental illnesses such anxiety, depression, fear, and obsessive-compulsive disorder.

These definitions align with the general understanding of good mental health as a state of balance, inner peace, and emotional well-being and absence of mental health disorders such as anxiety, depression.

Despite their differing cultural backgrounds, the British Imam and the Algerian Imam have a similar viewpoint on defining mental health. They both highlight the importance of being mentally healthy in dealing with life's problems and preserving psychological balance. According to a British imam (7)

The ability to face psychological problems and be free from mental health illnesses and behavioural deviations.

Similarly, to an Algerian imam (14) who share the same point of view.

A feeling of reassurance and the ability to deal with the various problems and difficulties that a person faces in his life and control stress and not give in to fear and anxiety.

It implies that good mental health enables people to deal with and overcome numerous psychological challenges in their lives. This section shows that imams possess a deep understanding of mental health, they can effectively address the psychological challenges faced by their congregations.

Theme 2: role of Islamic religion in supporting mental health

This theme explains the role of Islamic religion in supporting Muslims mental health in Algeria and United Kingdom. Religiosity and mental health are intertwined, religious beliefs and practices give a clear purpose of life. An Algerian imam (9) stated:

Islam honoured and cared for the soul in its various stages from childhood, adolescence to adulthood.

This participant explained the comprehensive nature of Islam's approach to spiritual development of the human being. which suggests that Islam acknowledges the importance of nurturing and honouring the soul throughout different stages of life, while also recognizing the unique challenges and opportunities for growth in each phase. Islam encourages an ongoing journey of spiritual development and fulfilment, fostering a sense of purpose and well-being at every stage of life's progression.

According to many British imams, Islam is a peaceful way of life that allows people to live in peace and comfort.

Islam is a way of life. It teaches you how to be peaceful with yourself and people around you (British imam 5)

Similarly, to another British Imam:

It plays a role in calming the soul and lifting the spirit and it makes you accept life and not give too much importance to problems (British imam 11)

This could be explained that Islam is more than just a religion or something that you do day by day; it is also a total way of life. This faith encourages people on how to stay calm and relaxed within themselves as well as in relation to others. It helps in achieving inner peace and calmness through this spiritual compass which enables one to encounter tests of life without being overcome by extreme stresses hence enabling one cope better with difficulties.

Islam encourages people to participate in beneficial actions in social circumstances and promotes mental health maintenance via acts of worship.

The Islamic religion promotes mental health by educating oneself on good deeds in social life and urging the preservation of mental health through the practice of acts of worship that spread a sense of comfort and reassurance. (Algerian imam 9)

This can be explained that participating in worship activities not only strengthens Muslims' spiritual bonds with Allah but also provides Muslims with psychological comfort. Consistently engaging in religious practices and contemplation can help alleviate stress and imbue life with a profound sense of purpose and significance. For instance, the act of remembering Allah through religious rituals becomes a source of solace and inner serenity, nurturing mental and emotional equilibrium. This underscores the multifaceted advantages of spiritual devotion in promoting overall well-being, as asserted by an Algerian imam (15).

Prayers, zakat, fasting, pilgrimage, Quran, and supplications and other religious practices, have a great impact in removing mental health issues and improving psychological wellbeing and that by strengthening the psychological system's ability to cope with daily pressures.

Moreover, it is emphasised by many imams from both cultures that prayer can serve as a method of self-reflection and mindfulness, allowing individuals to step back from their daily concerns and focus on their inner thoughts and feelings. This process can foster a greater understanding of oneself, personal growth, and a sense of purpose.

Prayer is a method of psychological treatment, and it is a pillar of religion, and we say in every prayer “Guide us to the straight path” it means guide us, conciliate, and firm.

(Algerian imam 4)

The findings explore the idea that prayers serve to gain insight into oneself and provide a form of self-help, promoting feelings of control and self-assurance. It suggests that prayers have a dual role, functioning not only as a spiritual ritual but also as a psychological remedy, emphasizing the significance of seeking inner equilibrium and resolution.

In addition, reading the Quran is described as a source of spiritual nourishment and solace, especially during tough times.

Protecting Muslims from anxiety and daily life stressors by performing religious practices such as reading Qur’an and praying. (British imam 10)

At the core of this approach lies the belief in the healing power of the Quran, revered as a source of guidance and tranquillity, instilling believers with the virtues of security, confidence, and patience amidst life's adversities and illnesses.

Islam commanded adherence to healthy and preventive behaviours ‘such as purification, directed worship as a method of psychological and physical treatment,

such as prayer, made frequent dhikr one of the causes of comfort and tranquillity of the heart, advice for treatments, guided people on what it is beneficial and to avoid what it is harmful, and indicated what develops psychological confidence and patience, endurance. Guide to what achieves peace of mind *من قوله تعالى: {إِنَّ هَذَا الْقُرْآنَ يَهْدِي لِلَّتِي هِيَ أَقْوَمُ وَيُبَشِّرُ الْمُؤْمِنِينَ الَّذِينَ يَعْمَلُونَ الصَّالِحَاتِ أَنَّ لَهُمْ أَجْرًا كَبِيرًا* “Verily this Qur'an doth guide to that which is most right (or stable), and giveth the Glad Tidings to the Believers who work deeds of righteousness, that they shall have a magnificent reward. (Algerian Imam 3)

This can be explained that the lessons and narratives of the Quran provide insights on resilience and resolve, helping believers to face obstacles with bravery and faith, eventually fostering a more positive and emotionally balanced outlook on life. Muslims should adopt an optimistic outlook on life by expecting God's goodness and learning from the examples of prophets who overcame adversity.

Persistence, psychological balance, patience in time of adversity, optimism, lack of despair, which develops a person's self-confidence. (British imam 8)

Islam cautions against actions that may cause harm and advocates for practices that nurture physical, psychological, and spiritual health.

Islam forbade it from what harms it, so it commanded worship, remembrance of God, kindness to others and upholding the ties with family, and give each person his right including soul right. Islam warned against intolerance, laziness, and worry. (Algerian imam1)

This can be explained by the fact that Islam's teachings include worship, compassion, and familial relationships while also warning against negative behaviours and encouraging believers to take preventative steps for their physical and mental health. The Quran, regarded as a book of healing, instils faith, patience, and security in believers through times of adversity and disease. Prayer is also a strong tool of psychological treatment for direction and stability on the moral path. Overall, Islam's complete framework targets individuals' mental well-being, cultivating inner tranquillity, and balancing their spiritual and psychological wellbeing.

Subtheme 2a: The Positive Influence of Islamic Faith on Mental Health

This subtheme explains how one's religious or spiritual beliefs, practices and relationship with higher power can positively influence and contribute to their mental wellbeing. Imams from both cultures explained the importance of the religious guidance and the sense of purpose of the faith support mental wellbeing. This will be explained through the following thematic map.

Figure 1: Religious coping Strategies

Many British imams believe that faith always helps to be optimistic in life, and that this can be learned from prophet hardships:

It helps to be optimistic and expect goodness from God Almighty, through the Quran, which provides us with several lessons on how the prophets overcame hardship in their lives (British Imam 1)

This can be explained by the fact that the stories of the prophets in Islam are filled with valuable lessons, resilience, and examples of coping with various hardships, and that understanding that even the prophets faced difficulties can provide solace and a reminder that patience is a commendable quality during times of struggle. Another imam shared this viewpoint.:

following prophetic teaching helps in supporting mental health (British Imam 4)

Prophetic teaching may involve encouraging Muslims to believe in their ability to overcome difficulties and learn from their experiences.

Another example of the significance of faith in promoting mental health is being strong and patient in the face of adversity because of the belief that there will always be a bright side and relief following it. According to British Imam (13):

The Islamic religion encourages patience and good faith in God, and promote the idea that with hardship there is ease (British Imam 13)

Similarly to another British imam 12:

Having a strong faith makes people more positive and optimistic (British Imam 12)

Having strong faith strengthen and benefits Muslims in various ways.

The closer you get to God the stronger you get mentally and psychologically (British Imam 6)

This illustrates that Muslims who deepen their faith in God experience increased mental and psychological strength, enabling them to face life challenges with resilience and optimism. As it is mentioned by an Algerian imam (2):

Religious beliefs make a person overcome the crises he is exposed to and those internal conflicts that tire and disturb him.

This emphasizes on the empowering nature of religious beliefs in helping Muslims overcome crises and internal conflicts. However, it is essential to acknowledge that the relationship between faith and positivity may vary from person to person due to unique circumstances they encounter throughout life. Whole faith can undoubtedly play a significant role in bolstering mental wellbeing, external factors, and individual experiences also contribute to shaping how they perceive and respond to life's ups and downs.

In contrast, an Algerian imam has another point of view concerning the how religious beliefs help in treating mental health issues and that there is a potential link between religious or spiritual beliefs and scientific approaches in supporting mental health:

Religious beliefs help religion meet science to serve mental health (Algerian Imam 9)

The statement reflects the Imam's perspective that religious beliefs and practices can align with evidence-based scientific approaches to enhance mental health support.

It is not surprising that religion and spirituality continue to play a vital role in supporting the mental health of Algerian and British Muslims. Self-awareness in one's relationship with Allah, both in heart and mind, is believed to lead individuals toward the straight path of self-knowledge, offering a source of healing for mental health issues.

The straight path, guided by Islamic principles, provides not only a prayer and request but also hope for guidance from Allah. It emphasizes the importance of honesty, integrity, and

goodness, which are central aspects of the Islamic message. As expressed by the Algerian

Imam 15:

The straight path presents us with a prayer and a request and hope from God to guide us to all things through which honesty, integrity of mind, goodness and guidance of mind are the most important aspects of the message of Islam. ﴿أَوْ مَن كَانَ مِنِّي فَأُحْيِيَنَاهُ وَجَعَلْنَا لَهُ نُورًا يَمْشِي بِهِ فِي النَّاسِ كَمَن مَّثَلُهُ فِي الظُّلُمَاتِ لَيْسَ بِخَارِجٍ مِّنْهَا ۚ كَذَلِكَ زُيِّنَ لِلْكَافِرِينَ مَا كَانُوا يَعْمَلُونَ﴾ Is he who was dead (without Faith by ignorance and disbelief) and We gave him life (by knowledge and Faith) and set for him a light (of Belief) whereby he can walk amongst men, like him who is in the darkness (of disbelief, polytheism and hypocrisy) from which he can never come out? Thus, it is made fair seeming to the disbelievers that which they used to do. (Surat Al-Anaam 6:122) (Algerian Imam 15)

The straight path, as embodied by Islamic principles, serves as a moral compass, guiding Muslims toward righteous actions and decisions. The spiritual connection with Allah, therefore, provides solace and comfort during difficult times, promoting resilience and hope.

In conclusion, the contributions of imams from both Algerian and British Muslim communities highlight the significance of religious beliefs and faith in supporting mental health. This inclusion underscores the profound impact a strong connection with faith can have on mental well-being. The emphasis on religious faith suggests that it can serve as an effective coping mechanism for mental health challenges, offering spiritual strength and emotional stability.

Sub-theme 2b: Description of mental health support in the Holy Quran

In this theme, Imams in the UK and Algeria interpret the Quran's teachings as a profound source of healing, encompassing various health concerns, including mental health. They highlight

specific Quranic verses that touch on health matters, illustrating how the Quran offers relief for mental discomfort and supports psychological well-being.

إِنَّ هَذَا الْقُرْآنَ يَهْدِي لِلَّتِي هِيَ أَقْوَمُ وَيُبَشِّرُ الْمُؤْمِنِينَ الَّذِينَ يَعْمَلُونَ الصَّالِحَاتِ أَنَّ لَهُمْ أَجْرًا كَبِيرًا Translation: *Verily, this Quran guides to that which is most just and right and gives glad tidings to the believers (in the Oneness of Allah and His Messenger, Muhammad SAW, etc.) who work deeds of righteousness, that they shall have a great reward (Paradise). (Al-Isra, 09- 283)*

The verse highlights how the Quran offers guidance and morality to readers, leading them towards rational and ethical behaviour. It also brings hope to believers who do good deeds, assuring them of significant rewards.

Believing that the divine words have the power to heal the mind and restore emotional balance. This holistic approach to spiritual care has proven to be effective in promoting overall wellness and improving mental health. Some British and Algerian imams have supported this claim by citing the following Quranic verse:

*فَدَجَاءَكُمُ مِنَ اللَّهِ نُورٌ وَكِتَابٌ مُبِينٌ * يَهْدِي بِهِ اللَّهُ مَنِ اتَّبَعَ رِضْوَانَهُ سُبُلَ السَّلَامِ وَيُخْرِجُهُمُ مِنَ الظُّلُمَاتِ إِلَى النُّورِ بِإِذْنِهِ وَيَهْدِيهِمْ إِلَى صِرَاطٍ مُسْتَقِيمٍ* Translation: *By which Allah guides those who pursue His pleasure to the ways of peace and brings them out from darknesses into the light, by His permission, and guides them to a straight path. There has come to you from Allah a light and a clear Book (Al-Maedah 15-16: 15)*

During difficult circumstances, seeking direction from Allah's light, represented by the Quran, can lead to clarity and comprehension. This spiritual assistance can lessen feelings of despair, hopelessness, and uncertainty, resulting in a more optimistic outlook on life.

Following the Quran's teachings and performing noble actions can build a sense of calm, satisfaction, and resilience in Muslims, eventually contributing to improved mental health. Muslims can discover inner peace, clarity, and a direct route towards a full and balanced existence by seeking Allah's pleasure.

لا تحزن إن الله معنا Translation: *Be not sad (or afraid), surely Allah is with us.*

This clarified the need to put faith in Allah and the fact that he is always there for his followers, even in their darkest moments.

It has been stated by several Algerian and British imams that whatever feelings arise in Muslims' hearts, such as sadness, anxiety, stress, worry, or frustration, remembering Allah via dhikr will always provide a remedy to alleviate them.

الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا وَتَطْمَئِنُّ قُلُوبُهُمْ بِذِكْرِ اللَّهِ أَلَا بِذِكْرِ اللَّهِ تَطْمَئِنُّ الْقُلُوبُ Translation: *Those who have believed and whose hearts are assured by the remembrance of Allah. Unquestionably, by the remembrance of Allah hearts are assured. (Al-Raad 28)*

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا اسْتَعِينُوا بِالصَّبْرِ وَالصَّلَاةِ إِنَّ اللَّهَ مَعَ الصَّابِرِينَ O you who have believed, seek help through patience and prayer. Indeed, Allah is with the patient. (Al-Bakarah 153)

These two verses underline the relaxing effect of remembering Allah. Engaging in acts of worship, such as prayers, supplication, and remembering Allah, can bring peace and tranquillity to the heart and mind.

Another verse was mentioned that demonstrates how the Quran provides spiritual support and encouragement to people who are going through mental and emotional difficulties.

إِنَّ الَّذِينَ قَالُوا رَبُّنَا اللَّهُ ثُمَّ اسْتَقَامُوا تَتَنَزَّلُ عَلَيْهِمُ الْمَلَائِكَةُ أَلَّا تَخَافُوا وَلَا تَحْزَنُوا وَأَبْشِرُوا بِالْجَنَّةِ الَّتِي كُنتُمْ تُوعَدُونَ

Indeed, those who have said, *Our Lord is Allah and then remained on a right course - the angels will descend upon them*, *Do not fear and do not grieve but receive good tidings of Paradise, which you were promised.* (Surah Fussilat, 41:30)

This Quranic passage emphasizes the significant relationship between religion, righteousness, and mental health. It conveys an encouraging message, reminding Muslims that their loyalty to Allah and dedication to living a pure life will be met with divine help and recompense.

Similarly, another passage was mentioned by imams from both cultures that emphasizes patience in challenging situations.

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا اصْبِرُوا وَصَابِرُوا وَرَابِطُوا وَاتَّقُوا اللَّهَ لَعَلَّكُمْ تُفْلِحُونَ. Translation: *O you who have believed, persevere and endure and remain stationed and fear Allah that you may be successful.* (Surah Al-Imran, 3:200)

The verse stresses that having a firm belief in Allah and following His instructions might give one hope for a brighter future in the Eternal Paradise. Muslims are inspired by this concept to lead moral lives to reach Paradise, where they will be rewarded for their good actions.

Another verse explains the concept of patience and resilience during difficult times. It acknowledges that periods of hardship are often followed by relief and ease.

قَالَيْنَ مَعَ الْعُسْرِ يُسْرًا. Translation: *For indeed, with hardship [will be] ease.* (Surah Ash-Sharh, 94:5)

This passage reminds Muslims that challenges are temporary, and those who persevere in patience and faith will always receive Allah's kindness and assistance, offering peace and optimism during hardships.

Furthermore, most imams from both cultures emphasized and mentioned the following verse, which reflects the story of the Prophet Joseph (Yusuf in Arabic), who found comfort in turning to Allah during his trials and tribulations:

قَالَ إِنَّمَا أَشْكُو بَثِّي وَحُزْنِي إِلَى اللَّهِ وَأَعْلَمُ مِنَ اللَّهِ مَا لَا تَعْلَمُونَ Translation: *He said: I only complain of my suffering and my grief to Allah, and I know from Allah that which you do not know.* (Surah Yusuf, 12:86)

Prophet Joseph acknowledges his reliance on Allah in this verse as he deals with challenges and hardships. He seeks comfort and consolation from Allah, knowing that Allah is aware of and comprehends what others may not.

Furthermore, the Quran's teachings encompass a holistic approach to well-being, addressing both spiritual and physical aspects of a person's life. While it offers spiritual guidance and healing for the soul, it also promotes principles of healthy living and physical well-being. For example:

وَنُنزِّلُ مِنَ الْقُرْآنِ مَا هُوَ شِفَاءٌ وَرَحْمَةٌ لِّلْمُؤْمِنِينَ ۖ وَلَا يَزِيدُ الظَّالِمِينَ إِلَّا خَسَارًا. Translation: *and We send down of the Qur'an that which is healing and mercy for the believers, but it does not increase the wrongdoers except in loss.* (Surah Al-Isra 17: 82)

Similarly, Another Qur'anic verse mentioned by Algerian and British imams which shows that Qur'an also heal mental and physical health issues:

يَا أَيُّهَا النَّاسُ قَدْ جَاءَكُم مِّنْ رَبِّكُم مَّوْعِظَةٌ مِّنْ رَبِّكُمْ وَشِفَاءٌ لِّمَا فِي الصُّدُورِ وَهُدًى وَرَحْمَةٌ لِّلْمُؤْمِنِينَ. Translation: *O mankind, there has to come to you instruction from your Lord and healing for what is in the breasts and guidance and mercy for the believers.* (Surah Yunus 10: 57)

These verses of the Quran emphasize its role as a comprehensive guide for human well-being, addressing spiritual, mental, and physical health, as well as its therapeutic value in promoting holistic health and overall wellness.

The Quran, as presented by imams, can serve as a prescription for healing, remedy for suffering, and the best treatment for psychological and mental illness among Muslim believers. It acknowledges that facing mental health challenges is a normal aspect of human life and encourages seeking solace and support from Allah through regular religious practices like prayers, Quranic reading, and dhikr. Recognizing the limitations of human control is crucial for effectively coping with stress and anxiety, while placing faith in Allah's wisdom provides strength and optimism during challenging times.

Theme3: Muslim beliefs towards causes and solutions to mental health problems.

This theme explores imams' perspectives on their community members' perceptions of mental health. The responses of imams differ in ways that correspond to cultural norms and traditional beliefs in diverse Muslim communities.

One of the reasons that illustrates the influence on Muslims' attitudes towards mental health problems is their faith, cultural context, and shared beliefs. The collective knowledge and shared beliefs significantly shape how Muslims perceive, and approach issues related to mental health within their communities. As mentioned by a British imam (1):

every Muslim possesses a certain level of knowledge and beliefs that are intricately connected to their society.

Given the inherent interconnectedness of religious convictions and practices with cultural, social, and geographical elements, it follows that the intricate interplay of these factors within their sociocultural context has a significant impact on Muslims' attitudes and beliefs.

Others have indicated that there is a link between mental health and spiritual issues, and that spiritual aspects or imbalances can have an impact on mental health challenges.

Most of them believe that mental health issues are a part of spiritual issues. (Algerian imam 8)

This can be explained that spiritual factors could play a contributing role in mental health concerns.

Imams highlight the virtues of patience and acceptance as essential aspects of the human experience, given that these trials are an inevitable part of life:

As Muslims, we may not always prioritize mental health issues as much because we understand that they are a part of life's challenges, and we are encouraged to exercise patience and resilience in coping with them. (British Imam 5)

Muslims regard life as a test and believe that having patience is the best way to deal with hardships, such as mental health illnesses, and continue living with it. This viewpoint is consistent with the notion that difficulties and tribulations are a normal part of life and that patience is a virtue valued in Islam.

A lack of faith is regarded as one of the reasons and beliefs among Muslims that is considered responsible for various mental health issues and psychological distress. This notion is attested to by a British imam 11:

Most Muslims do not believe in the existence of mental illnesses, and this is due to different cultural traditions which consider mental illnesses a defect and disgrace, and that person effected by them is merely lacking in religion and faith, and that he should return to the right path for psychological comfort.

This idea is supported by a second Algerian imam, who concurs that having strong convictions offers comfort on both a psychological and spiritual level.

Algerian Muslims prioritize mental health, and Allah remembering is a source of their psychological comfort. Many Muslims find spiritual satisfaction, purpose, and tranquillity in their faith, which can have a significant positive impact on mental well-being (Algerian Imam 10)

Muslims view faith as a powerful strength to protect against mental health challenges and as a coping mechanism. It provides purpose and a hopeful outlook, empowering them through spiritual convictions that guide them through difficulties. This sense of empowerment offers reassurance and purpose amidst adversity.

Sub-theme 3a: Imams engagement with Muslims with mental health issues

The engagement of imams with Muslims facing mental health issues varies depending on factors such as cultural context, and the imam's own training and awareness.

When British imams were asked how often they deal with Muslim mental health issues, most of them (10 from 15) gave the same answer:

Sometimes they deal with Muslims with mental health issues.

Most of British imams repeated use of "sometimes" indicates that British imams have a varied and inconsistent approach to dealing with mental health issues among Muslims. Conversely, when Algerian imams were questioned on their involvement with Muslims facing mental health issues, their responses showcased a spectrum of approaches. These encompassed.

"Never," "Sometimes," and "Always." between Algerian Imams about dealing with Muslims with mental health issues.

This range of responses among Algerian imams reveals a disparity in their approaches to dealing with Muslim mental health issues. Some imams completely avoid discussing mental health issues, while others do so very sometimes, and yet others do it consistently or often.

Overall, the findings show that imams' participation with Muslims' mental health concerns varies across the British and Algerian contexts. British imams have an inconsistent attitude, but Algerian imams participate in a broader variety of activities, from complete non-engagement to periodic or consistent addressing of mental health difficulties in their communities.

Theme 04: Imams' initiatives in meeting mental health needs

Before delving into the exploration of imams' proactive strategies for addressing community mental health needs and examining the challenges they face, the researcher sought to identify the specific age groups that seek help from imams for mental health matters. Understanding the demographics of those reaching out to imams provides crucial context for comprehending the dynamics of mental health support within the community.

Overall, the findings reveal that both British and Algerian imams encounter a mix of age-based groups seeking help. British imams (1, 3, 4,5,7,8,9,10,11,12,14) are approached by:

“Adolescents”, “Young adults”, and “Adults”, as well as “Families” seeking assistance.

On the other hand, Algerian imams (1, 2,3,4,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,15) primarily interact with:

“Young adults” and “Adults” without mentioning specific engagement with “Families”.

It's worth noting that some responses indicate overlapping age groups, suggesting that imams often provide support to multiple age categories, especially young adults, and adults.

British imams (1,2,3,4,5,6,7,9,11,12,14,15) have recognized the challenge of effective communication, with many of them identifying: *Communication skills* as an area of concern. This challenge may arise due to the diverse backgrounds and origins of Muslims in the United Kingdom, which can lead to misunderstandings and difficulties in interpreting the instructions provided by the imams. In contrast, Algerian imams, do not encounter this particular challenge in Algerian culture, where the cultural and linguistic environment may be more homogeneous, making communication smoother and less prone to such misconceptions.

Another significant concern shared by imams in both the UK and Algeria is the challenge they encounter when attempting to provide effective guidance on mental health issues, particularly for certain segments of the Muslim population. Imams from both cultures have identified "Guidance Skills" as their chosen answer. This challenge may stem from cultural perceptions or personal difficulties, which can create difficulties for Muslims in adhering to the guidance provided by imams.

Subtheme 4a: Imams' Recommendations for Muslims with Mental Health Issues

This sub-theme delves into the lessons and perspectives on mental health offered by imams in both British and Algerian contexts, shedding light on how imams' approach mental health issues and provide guidance to their communities.

Among Algerian imams, a predominant response emerged when asked about their recommendations for Muslims with mental health issues:

I would involve mental health issues as spiritual issues and start using Roqya.

(Algerian Imam 9)

I would directly use Roqya. (Algerian Imam 11)

These responses signify the integration of mental health issues into spiritual matters. Algerian imams advocate the use of Roqya, an Islamic spiritual healing practice, to address mental health concerns, recognizing the interconnectedness of mental well-being and spirituality.

However, most British imams recommend:

Recommend seeking help from mental health professionals affiliated with their religious denomination (British Imam 3)

This can be explained by the fact that British imams prioritize seeking professional mental health help first, ensuring that individuals receive appropriate and specialized care. Like British imams, most of Algerian imams encourage:

More intensive prayers. (Algerian Imam 7)

This may be explained by the integration of mental health and spiritual matters in the guidance of British and Algerian imams. British imams prioritize professional mental health support, emphasizing evidence-based treatments while also incorporating certain religious practices, such as prayers, to enhance the overall effectiveness of their approach. Algerian imams, on the other hand, place greater emphasis on spiritual healing practices like Roqya and prayers, believing in the power of faith for holistic well-being. To answer the second research question: What types of referrals do imams offer to Muslims suffering from mental illnesses and how do they provide support? several themes provide relevant answers:

Table 6: Imams' referrals for mental health treatment

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Sub-themes</i>
5. Religious interventions and psychotherapy	/
6. Barriers that Prevent Muslims from accessing Mental health services	6a. Imams' role in reducing stigma in Muslim communities. 6b. Imams' Mental health Training
7. Professional referrals	7a. Spiritual Treatment Effectiveness 7b. Imams Professional Referrals and collaboration with mental health professionals

Theme 05: Religious interventions and psychotherapy

Imams from both cultures express a more varied perspective, acknowledging that religion can be helpful in some cases while recognizing that other situations may require professional treatments. According to a British imam (5):

Being religious is helpful but it is not the only way for mental health treatment.

Similarly to other imams have the same point of view some believe that being religious can be beneficial but is not the sole solution for mental health treatment acknowledging that certain issues require medical intervention and that severe cases may necessitate seeing a therapist or psychiatrist and even require medication.

There are cases when people need to see a therapist or psychiatrist especially severe cases that need medication. (British imam 11)

There are severe mental health issues that need medication, so religion won't be effective in this case. (British Imam 2)

Another Algerian participant presents a nuanced perspective on the idea that religious interventions are fundamental components of psychotherapy and complement medical treatments.

No, religious interventions are one of the basics of psychotherapy and a complement to medical treatment. (Algerian Imam 1)

This viewpoint underscores the integral role of religious practices and beliefs in shaping therapeutic approaches and their significance alongside medical treatments.

In contrary, the following viewpoint significantly differs from that of most Algerians, who agreed that the only practical approach to addressing Muslim mental health issues could be interventions integrating religious principles.

The Islamic religion achieves psychological comfort by renewing the connection with God, this process will inspire hope, optimism, patience, and interaction with society. (Algerian Imam 8)

This could be explained that The Islamic faith offers a framework for psychological well-being by strengthening a connection with God, resulting in positive emotional, mental, and social effects. This comprehensive approach, grounded in religious principles, suggests it could be a holistic intervention for addressing mental health issues.

Imams in the United Kingdom hold varying opinions on the usefulness of religion in mental health therapies, recognizing both its potential advantages and the necessity for professional therapy. Algerian imams typically endorse religiosity's positive influence on mental health, seeing it as an essential component of psychotherapy alongside medical therapies. Some Algerian imams strongly support religiosity as essential for mental health therapy, emphasizing the distinct ways in which cultural and religious settings impact attitudes toward the relevance of religiosity in mental health therapies.

Theme 06: Barriers that prevent Muslims from accessing mental health services.

This theme delves into the path to mental health treatment for Muslims, with a focus on specific circumstances that may serve as barriers to receive such care from the perspective of imams.

This theme shows whether religion can be a barrier to receiving mental health services, as well as other barriers that may prevent Muslims from seeking help from mental health services.

When asking the question of how religion affects access to mental health treatment, all imams from both cultures unanimously agreed on one answer which is:

It does not affect accessing mental health services. (Algerian Imam 9)

Another Algerian imam emphasized the point that religion can serve as a facilitator for treating mental health conditions, emphasizing that it encourages seeking help and treatment for any type of illness. According to an Algerian Imam (13):

On the contrary, religion commands and necessitates treatment and encourages seeking it. Mental health services are nothing but means and innovations that have kept pace with the modern era and have benefited and facilitated treatments.

While another Imam, who holds a different perspective on the role of religious knowledge in healing from mental health issues, stated:

It does not affect [mental health]. If the person is knowledgeable about Quranic verses that address their mental health, they can perform roqya for themselves without the need for Imams or any other treatments. (British Imam 1)

This may imply that Muslims' knowledge of their religion helps them understand it better, including the available treatments in Islam, which are traditional treatments. This knowledge may eliminate the need for alternative therapies or religious leaders who may have more expertise in this area.

The other barriers that were mentioned by imams, who provided multiple answers, as limiting Muslims' access to mental health services and professionals, were identified by both Algerian and British imams as the most prevalent obstacles preventing Muslims from accessing mental health services or seeking help from professionals. These barriers include:

Ignorance and lack of knowledge.

Stigma.

Suspicious and mistrust of therapies.

Another barrier that was frequently mentioned by most British imams was:

Language barriers.

This might be because the UK is home to a diverse range of cultures, and the fear of not being understood by professionals could deter individuals from seeking help.

On the other hand, Algerian imams emphasized the point that was shared by all of them, which includes:

The preference to seek help from traditional healers.

Lack of family support.

This preference may be attributed to cultural beliefs and practices within Algerian communities, where traditional healing methods hold significant importance in addressing mental health concerns.

The findings show that religion has no discernible effect on accessing mental health services. This aspect of the theme highlights the significance of religion in the lives of Muslims but underscores that it does not hinder access to mental health services, according to imams from both cultures. Religion, in fact, plays a role in encouraging people to seek help when necessary.

On the other hand, the barriers that may affect Muslims in Algeria and the UK are largely rooted in cultural and societal factors influencing the mentality of Muslims and their approach to seeking help.

Sub-theme 6a: Imams Role in reducing stigma in Muslims communities.

Imams play a crucial role in reducing stigma within Muslim communities, as highlighted in this theme. The researcher examined the role of imams in reducing stigma in Algerian and

British Muslim communities by asking them how they go about achieving this goal. Some imams from both cultures chose the following answer:

I use qur'anic saying about stigma.

This may suggest that the Quran contains numerous verses that address the issue of stigma, guiding people not to engage in stigmatization and promoting the idea that it is not a desirable behaviour within society, whether among Muslims or non-Muslims.

A few Algerian imams commented on Quranic sayings and specifically mentioned verses that emphasize the prohibition of using stigma: according to Algerian imam (5) and Algerian imam (11):

لا يسخر قوم من قوم Translation: *let not a people ridicule [another] people*

ولا تنابزو بالالقاب Translation: *And do not insult one another and do not call each other by [offensive] nicknames*

These two statements shows that Quran already mentioned that stigma is not an accepted behaviour and should not be existed in the society while other imams from both cultures choose the answer of:

I would deliver lessons about stigma in the mosque.

Addressing stigma in the mosque is a beneficial approach that imams can employ to raise awareness among Muslims and guide them in understanding the importance of not stigmatizing individuals with mental health issues. This initiative can help educate and raise awareness within the community about these issues.

Theme 07: Professional referrals

This theme delves deeper into the training of imams in mental health settings. It aims to assess whether imams are adequately prepared to address the psychological distress and mental health issues faced by Muslims. This evaluation seeks to determine whether imams are better equipped to handle emergency situations and whether they are actively collaborating with mental health professionals when they encounter challenges beyond their scope. Additionally, it explores the importance of recognizing when a problem is rooted in mental health issues that should be addressed by professionals rather than religious leaders.

Before knowing if imams collaborate or refer Muslims with mental health issues to mental health services or professionals, first the researcher wanted to know if imams are trained or have any sources in the mosque that may help Muslims with mental health issues in urgent matters.

Sub-theme 7a: Imams mental health training

When asked about their training, staffing, and available resources for addressing urgent mental health cases within the mosque, the responses from imams varied. Both Algerian and British imams collectively indicated that they had received no training in the field of mental health, as evidenced by their consistent response “No”. The responses regarding the reasons for the lack of training and staffing in the mosque concerning mental health issues differed among the

imams. few imams provided their own unique perspective on why such training and resources were not present.

Few British and Algerian imams provided their own unique perspective on why such training and resources were not present. Some imams stated that mosques serve as places of therapy, providing a sense of comfort to those struggling with mental health issues. They emphasized their lack of formal training and resources within the mosque for addressing mental health concerns: According to a British Imam 2:

No, the mosque itself provides a sense of community and belonging which can be therapeutic for people struggling with mental health issues. Additionally, the spiritual practices and teachings offered in the mosque.

Similarly to an Algerian imam 12:

We first need to implant the concepts that the mosque is not only for prayers, but that one of its roles is promoting positive mental health and treat it.

In contrast, others mentioned that, although they themselves lack formal training, they attend sessions conducted by trained religious leaders who possess more profound knowledge about mental health and its intersection with spiritual treatment:

No, I used to go to help a religious leader in his roqya sessions and learn from him, but I am not trained enough to treat mental health issues of Muslims (British imam 13)

Learning from religious leaders is another important aspect. This finding demonstrates that even though imams may not have received the right formal training, they can acquire knowledge and skills through learning from trained and experienced religious leaders who possess expertise in this domain. By observing and studying under these knowledgeable figures, imams can acquire the essential skills and knowledge needed to effectively guide their communities in matters of spirituality and mental health.

The findings show that the mosque is considered a sacred place where people can seek support from religious leaders, even if they are not formally trained in mental health. Having sufficient knowledge about religious practices and providing guidance to Muslims on various mental health matters can be achieved through expertise in religious matters and a deep understanding of the Quran. It underscores the significance of being well-versed in religion and its teachings to offer meaningful support in the realm of mental health.

Sub-theme 7b: Spiritual treatment effectiveness

This theme examines the standards that imams employ in their traditional spiritual approaches when treating Muslims with mental health issues and assesses the effectiveness of such treatments for Muslim individuals. Many British imams indicated that they do not utilize any specific standards to measure the effectiveness of their treatment methods. For example:

There are no standards I use. (British imam 11)

Conversely, a few imams mentioned that their assessment of treatment effectiveness depended on the attitudes and behaviours of the individuals seeking help. As one imam explained:

I would ask them how they felt after receiving the treatment and observe their behaviours and body language (British Imam 12)

Similarly, another British imam shared a similar approach, stating:

I depend on people's opinions on the treatments we provide, for example, observe their body language and their daily expressions to see if there is any change (British Imam 4)

Some imams believed that providing mental health therapy or roqya (spiritual healing) was not within the scope of their duties in the mosque. For example, British Imam (8) expressed this perspective by stating:

Offering mental health therapy or roqya is not from my duties in the mosque.

Meanwhile, British Imam (2) offered a different perspective, emphasizing the importance of an individual's commitment to the treatment process:

It depends on how a person follows the treatment because sometimes they start the treatment and do not finish it.

This suggests that the effectiveness of spiritual treatment may depend on the willingness of individuals with mental health issues to adhere to the treatment.

On the other hand, Algerian imams provided insights into the standards they use to determine the effectiveness of their spiritual treatments. Some emphasized the importance of

their own knowledge and familiarity with treating individuals with mental health issues. For instance, Algerian Imam (2) mentioned criteria such as

Correct diagnosis, good knowledge and insight based on science and learning, familiarity with knowledge and experiences of specialists, accepting scientific ideas and theories.

Conversely, others underscored the significance of observing the positive changes in an individual's mental health and psychological well-being as indicators of treatment effectiveness. Algerian Imam (6) outlined criteria such as:

The disappearance of stress and anxiety, integration into society, improved interpersonal relationships, contentment, and self-acceptance in all circumstances, contributing to helping others, and experiencing tranquillity and reassurance' as measures of effective spiritual treatment.

This implies that the desired outcome of such treatments is the improvement of mental health and the promotion of overall psychological well-being for the individuals seeking help.

Following the first part of this theme, the duration of treating Muslims with spiritual or mental health issues varies according to several factors. Some imams emphasized that the time required for treatment is contingent on specific circumstances. For example, British Imam (10) stated:

It depends on the severity of the case and the engagement of the patients.

Similarly, Algerian Imam 9 shared a comparable viewpoint, explaining that treatment duration is subject to variation depending on factors such as:

The nature of the dilemmas and diseases, the individual's personality being treated, and the methods and skills available for treatment.

This demonstrates that the duration of treatment is intricately linked to the severity of the case and the level of personal engagement in the treatment process, emphasizing the importance of tailoring treatment plans to individual needs.

Few British imams also specified the timeframe for observing the effectiveness of their treatment. They mentioned that it typically takes:

One week to two months. (British imam 14), One week to one year. (British imam 2)

This can be explained Adequate time is required to assess mental health changes and evaluate treatment effects, ensuring a thorough evaluation of treatment effects.

Sub-Theme 7c: Imams' Professional referrals and Collaboration with professionals

This theme underscores the significance of collaboration between mental health professionals and imams, as imams are often the first point of contact for most Muslims seeking assistance with mental health or other social issues.

For instance, one British imam stated that most of those who approach him only need support to strengthen their faith, so he does not refer them to mental health professionals, saying.

No, because some of them only need some support to strengthen their faith (British Imam 1).

Another reason from an Algerian imam:

No, I have not dealt with advanced cases of severe mental health issues (Algerian Imam 1).

Indeed, some imams believe that recommendations should be made only in extreme cases. According to this point of view, imams' primary job is to provide support and aid to individuals suffering from less severe mental health issues, with referrals kept for cases when these issues more advanced or severe.

Moreover, another statement made by an Algerian Imam highlights a significant challenge in addressing mental health issues within the Muslim community. Trust is a critical factor in seeking help for mental health problems. He said:

No, because people with mental health issues do not trust professionals or mental health services (Algeria imam 3)

This suggests that imams may possess a greater understanding of the attitudes held by Muslims and their preconceived notions regarding professional settings. Trust plays a pivotal role in seeking assistance from professionals, and imams may serve as key referral sources in facilitating this process.

While another British imam expresses concern, stating:

No, there is insufficient support for free health services and the high prices for treatment sessions at private clinics (British Imam 8).

This highlights the challenges of accessing free healthcare services and the financial burden imposed by private clinics, highlighting the need for adequate support and affordability measures.

On the other hand, the lack of collaboration between imams and mental health professionals in Algeria and United Kingdom, as mentioned by some Algerian imams, can be attributed to several reasons. One key reason is the perception that religious institutions, like mosques, operate separately from other health institutions. This perspective is articulated by Algerian Imam 7, who stated,

No, because we are religious institutions and do not affiliate with other health institutions.

Another British imam indicates a lack of collaboration between imams and mental health professionals. While the specific reasons for this lack of contact are not mentioned in the provided statement:

I am not in contact with any mental health services (British Imam 5)

British Imam (9) shares a similar perspective:

I didn't think about it.

This suggests a lack of awareness or interest in such partnerships.

In contrast, there is a range of attitudes and approaches among few Algerian imams regarding collaboration with mental health professionals. Some Algerian imams have positively acknowledged their collaboration with mental health professionals including:

Psychologists, mental health associations, religious leaders specialised in Roqya

(Algerian Imam 10)

This collaborative effort can be seen as a positive step towards promoting mental well-being and providing support to their congregation members.

On the other hand, there are imams who have gone a step further by inviting psychologists to the mosque to provide lessons and guidance on mental health.

Yes, I have brought a psychologist in my session with Muslims in the mosque for some

psychological guidance (Algerian Imam 11)

This proactive approach suggests a willingness to integrate psychological support within the religious community and educate their congregation about mental health.

5.8 Conclusion

Imams serve as the primary point of contact for Muslims dealing with mental health issues, particularly in Algeria. They are regarded as educators, teachers, and advisors, safeguarding the well-being of the Muslim community. In Algeria, imams often view mental health issues as spiritual challenges that require "roqya" (spiritual healing), while many British imams consider professional treatment a necessity when dealing with individuals facing mental health issues.

Imams offer insights into how their respective societies perceive and address mental health and the potential benefits of religious practices in coping with such challenges. The Islamic religion provides Muslims with a comprehensive framework of behaviour, ethics, and social values that assist in developing adaptive coping strategies for managing life's stresses. Notably, Muslims, particularly in Algeria, frequently prefer seeking spiritual treatment through religious leaders and imams, sometimes hesitating to seek professional help for various reasons, as discussed earlier. In some cases, Western Muslims may refrain from seeking professional help to align with their religious beliefs. This research underscores the effectiveness of integrating spirituality and religiosity into psychotherapy and highlights how religious beliefs can influence mental health management plans.

A significant finding is that most imams from both cultures do not routinely refer individuals to mental health professionals. This is due to factors such as a lack of trust in professionals, cost considerations, neglect, or a primary focus on strengthening the faith of Muslims rather than considering mental health referrals. Unfortunately, there is generally limited collaboration between imams and mental health services, as it is not consistently viewed as part of the imams' responsibilities. However, a few Algerian imams have recognized the benefits of collaboration and actively worked to raise awareness within their communities by bringing mental health professionals to the mosque.

In conclusion, this research illuminates the intricate roles of imams in addressing mental health issues, highlighting the contrast in approaches between Algerian and British imams. It emphasizes the importance of integrating spirituality and religiosity into mental health support and underlines how religious beliefs can shape mental health management strategies. Furthermore, it calls attention to the challenges surrounding referrals to professionals and the limited collaboration between imams and mental health services.

5.9 Discussion

This research study chapter examines the role of imams in Muslim communities in promoting mental health concerns in greater detail. This second study addressed the questions: What is the imam's role in counselling Muslims with mental health issues? What types of referrals do imams offer to Muslims suffering from mental illnesses and how do they provide support? How do imams recognise mental health issues from spiritual issues? To know if imams can adequately recognize, treat, and refer congregants with emotional, behavioural, or mental health issues to spiritual or mental health professionals when appropriate. But, before looking at their role in society, to know more about their knowledge and explanation of how they define an imam, as well as their awareness of mental health concerns and their perspective on how Muslims in the Islamic faith obtain care for their mental health difficulties. The second study examined the three layers of Islamic religion to understand the significance of imams as religious leaders: the Quran as the holy text, the belief system derived from it, and the social-religious practices influenced by culture. This exploration highlights how the belief system of Muslims facilitates direct contact with imams for guidance and advice, particularly regarding spiritual matters, including healing and mental health.

Theme 01: Imams' role in the mosque

The study's findings show the roles and responsibilities shouldered by imams in both Algerian and British contexts, delineating the dynamic evolution of their profession. Schmid's (2020) investigation aligns with this paradigm shift, characterizing imams as 'professional function holders' necessitating a diverse skill set to effectively cater to the evolving needs of communities and the broader societal landscape. Primarily, imams from both cultural contexts

are acknowledged as religious leaders at the forefront of guiding Muslim congregations through in their lives. Insights gleaned from Abu-Ras et Al (2008) that imams are not only perceived as spiritual guides but also serve as counsellors, embodying a multifaceted role.

The research outcomes from Algeria and the United Kingdom underscore the important responsibilities entailed in the role of Imamate. Imams are depicted as educators deeply engaged in Quranic studies, imparting knowledge about the Quran and its recitation. In congruence with a wealth of scholarly inquiries, imams emerge as pivotal figures in elucidating and interpreting the Quran and The Hadith, the sacred scriptures of Islam (Ali et al., 2005). Simultaneously, they function as ambassadors of the Islamic faith, tasked with addressing the life challenges faced by Muslim communities, propagating the tenets of Islam, and imparting its principles. Aligned with this research result, it is underscored in the research by Humam et al (2023) that the nexus between religious leaders, including imams, and the provision of religious knowledge to aid Muslims in navigating stressful life events. Aligned with another researcher, exemplified by Maiwada et al. (2018), accentuates the pivotal role of Muslim religious leaders in the socialization of new community members, shaping their values and acclimating them to communal life. Similarly, as cited by Schimed's (2020) conceptualization of imams as 'agents of cultivation' (Tezcan, 2012) which shows the imams' capacity to exert influence in steering Muslim communities. This intricate portrayal underscores the nuanced and influential position of imams, concurrently serving as local community leaders and integral contributors to the broader societal fabric.

Furthermore, the results highlight the correlation between the role of an imam and the profession of prophets, emphasizing the importance of learning from the experiences of prophets. In the specific context of this study and within the broader Islamic framework, Imamate is perceived as a continuation of the prophetic legacy within Muslim communities. This aligns with the findings of a research study of Yazdi (2022), that asserts the Imam not

only acquires knowledge akin to a prophet but does so through a union with the prophet's soul. The Imam, as revealed in the study, shares the laws of the world and the divine legislative will, effectively continuing the prophet's mission of conveying these to people through revelation. This underscores the significant role of the Imam in preserving and transmitting the prophetic legacy.

The study examines imams in Algerian and British contexts, highlighting their role as religious leaders and spiritual guides. Imams are educators, interpreters of sacred scriptures, and ambassadors of Islam. They socialize community members and shape their values, aligning with the prophetic legacy. Imams are influential figures, serving as local community leaders and contributing to broader community needs. Their enduring significance in preserving and transmitting Islamic teachings is emphasized.

The findings of this study elucidate imams' awareness of mental health and their ability to identify concerns within the Muslim community. Regardless of their cultural background, imams consistently demonstrate a satisfactory level of knowledge about mental health. Aligned with this research study result, according to Ali and Milstein (2012) imams on average could recognize someone with a mental illness and showed a willingness to refer out but preferred referral while continuing to provide counsel themselves. Similarly, in line with a study conducted by Humam et al. (2023), religious leaders who comprehend the distinction between mental and spiritual issues should encourage community members to seek professional assistance from individuals outside of their religious leadership. This approach ensures that individuals receive comprehensive care. It underscores that imams' understanding of mental health issues enables them to differentiate between mental health concerns and spiritual matters, empowering them to offer suitable care and guidance to the Muslim community.

Imams from both cultures defined mental health as being mentally stable, possessing good psychological resilience, aligned with the result of this research study the mental health concept according to imam El Ghazali “Mental health is not only limited to the absence of psychiatric disorders in a person, but also a person who has a good personality, physical and psychological development, self-integrity, the unity of view, the endurance of pressures, self-reliance, the perception of reality that is free from deviation, empathy and social sensitivity, as well as the ability to adapt and integrate with the environment” (Hasan and Tamam, 2018) this means that having a good mental health you should have the characteristics mentioned by imam El Ghazali.

The results of interviews with imams showed that mental health means having the ability to cope with life stressors. In line with this result as cited by (Hasan and Tamam, 2018) research A healthy person is a person who is able to face the challenges of life and can accept others as they are to be empathetic and not apriority negating themselves and others (Main, 2013). Which means that coping with life stressors and challenges makes people able to fulfil the demands of life in his social environment, set realistic goals, a decision-maker, capable of accepting responsibilities, able to design the future, accept new ideas and experiences, and satisfied with his work. This uniformity in their definitions is a positive sign, suggesting that imams have a shared understanding of the concept of mental health that transcends cultural differences.

This highlights the importance of imams' mental health awareness and their potential influence on their communities. Imams from diverse cultural backgrounds have a high awareness of mental health, focusing on good mental stability, psychological well-being, and the ability to face life's problems. Mental health is a universal concern that affects individuals from all backgrounds, emphasizing its cross-cultural applicability. By acknowledging the shared importance of mental health, imams can guide their communities towards achieving

balance and resilience, regardless of cultural differences, promoting resilience in the face of life's challenges.

Theme 2: Role of Islamic religion in supporting mental health.

To comprehend the role of imams in promoting Muslim mental health, it is essential to first understand the concept of Muslim mental health and how Muslims coping mechanisms. Furthermore, gaining insight into the role of Islamic religion in assisting individuals with their mental health difficulties is crucial. This aligned with previous research that has been carried out for the last many decades and has identified relationship between mental health and religious convictions; in particular, range of religious practices has been found instrumental in the promotion of mental health. (Ijaz et al,2017). Similarly in another research study, Physical and emotional support is rooted in cultural and religious contexts, i.e. coping strategies, that address young people's psychological issues (Saged et al, 2022) It has been found in other research studies that religion has continued to be a central part of societies and human experience, shaping how individuals react to the environments in which they live (Akinfenwa et al 2014). Similarly, as cited by Papaleontiou-Louca (2020) according to various empirical studies, spirituality, and religiosity, including Islamic practices, can fulfil human needs for meaning in life (Park, 2005), provide mental relief (Exline et al., 2000), and foster emotional bonding (Rowatt & Kirkpatrick, 2002). Additionally, other research studies indicate that spiritual support is a significant predictor of reliance upon religious coping, which is a major contributor to positive outcomes (Jones, 2004). This shows the positive link between religion and mental health.

The work reveals a significant relationship between religiosity and mental health in both Algerian and British Muslim communities. This demonstrates that religious beliefs have

consistently upheld and nurtured the well-being of Muslims at various life stages, fostering a sense of peace in Muslim life. Aligned with there is a growing body of research indicating a connection between mental health and diverse religious practices. Consequently, there is an increasing demand for heightened religious sensitivity among mental health clinicians to better comprehend and leverage the potentially therapeutic aspects of religion (Ibrahim & Whiteley, 2021). Similarly with another research study by Sabry and Vohra's (2013), which concluded that Islam furnishes Muslims with a code of behaviour, ethics, and social values. This code aids them in tolerating and developing adaptive coping strategies to navigate stressful life circumstances. The intersection of religion and mental health can be attributed to Islam's emphasis on soul care and honour.

Imams from both cultures have highlighted several key aspects of how Islam positively impacts the well-being of its adherents. Firstly, peace and comfort result from following the Islamic religion. As articulated by the imams, Islam teaches individuals how to find inner peace and live in comfort by accepting life as it is, with both its positive and negative events. This focus on inner tranquillity and contentment can significantly enhance mental health. This result aligns with the research of Sabry and Vohra (2013), which stated that Islam helps Muslims tolerating and developing adaptive coping strategies to deal with stressful life events. Furthermore, Islam instructs on how-to live-in harmony with others, as exemplified in the Quranic verse. By following these teachings, Muslims can create a harmonious society and contribute to the overall well-being of individuals and communities. as exemplified in the Quranic verse:

وَاتَّبِعْ فِيمَا ءَاتَاكَ اللّٰهُ الدّٰرَ الْاٰخِرَةَ وَلَا تَنْسَ نَصِيْبَكَ مِنَ الدُّنْيَا وَاَحْسِنْ كَمَا اَحْسَنَ اللّٰهُ اِلَيْكَ وَلَا تَبْغِ الْفَسَادَ فِي الْاَرْضِ اِنَّ اللّٰهَ لَا يُحِبُّ الْمُفْسِدِيْنَ

Translation: *Seek the life to come by means of what God granted you, but do not neglect your rightful share in this world. Do good to others as God has done good to you. Do not seek to*

spread corruption in the land, for God does not love those who do this (Quran, 28:77). This not only fosters a sense of belonging and support but also promotes a sense of purpose and fulfillment in life. Secondly, Imams' results indicate that education and the preservation of Islamic principles motivate believers to educate themselves, maintain mental health through faith-based or worship activities, and foster self-awareness and self-improvement. This corresponded with previous research that indicates a positive relationship between mental health and religious activities, also known as religiosity in the social sciences (Hackney and Sanders, 2003). The specific results from Imams' study highlight those practices such as prayer, reading the Quran, and other religious rituals are instrumental in fostering emotional balance. This observation is congruent with the findings of another study that underscores the positive effects of various religious practices, including meditation, centering prayer, and contemplative activities. These practices have been shown to elicit the "relaxation response," associated with improved health outcomes such as reduced sympathetic nervous system activity, decreased muscle tension, lower activity of the anterior pituitary/adrenocortical axis, decreased blood pressure and heart rate, and alterations in brain waves (Benson, 1996). Engaging in religious practices and contemplation can help individuals connect with their spirituality, find solace in their faith, and alleviate stress.

Within the scope of this study, imams have emphasized the paramount importance of two specific religious practices believed to be integral for addressing and healing mental health issues. First, the imams underscored the significance of prayers as a religious practice that have a pivotal role in guiding Muslims through life, offering psychological comfort, and steering them on the righteous path. These findings correlate with the Quranic verse:

يَعْلَمُ مَا أَتْلُو مَا أُوحِيَ إِلَيْكَ مِنَ الْكِتَابِ وَأَقِمِ الصَّلَاةَ لِئِنَّ الصَّلَاةَ تَنْهَىٰ عَنِ الْفَحْشَاءِ وَالْمُنْكَرِ ۗ وَذَكَرُ اللَّهَ أَكْبَرُ ۗ وَاللَّهُ
بِصُنْعِهِمْ عَلِيمٌ Translation: *Recite that which has been revealed to you of the Book and keep up prayer; surely prayer keeps one away from indecency and evil, and certainly the*

remembrance of Allah is the greatest, and Allah knows what you do. (Al-Ankabut 29:45)

Emphasizing that prayer keeps individuals away from indecency and evil, with the remembrance of Allah being paramount. This result also aligns with existing research, exemplified by Henry et al. (2015), which asserts that Islamic prayers possess the capacity to amplify spiritual energy, thereby fostering psychological benefits such as stress reduction and enhanced well-being. According to him, Islamic prayers, known as Salah, yield diverse psychological benefits through the provision of spiritual energy to Muslim individuals ((Henry et al. 2015). As a result, by incorporating prayers, therapists can tap into the spiritual resources of their Muslim clients, allowing for a deeper connection and sense of meaning in the therapeutic journey. Similar research indicated those who pray showed that they are happier and healthier (Hamid et al, 2010).

In the Holy book of Quran, Allah Almighty says in the Quran in Surah Al Baqarah (The Cow 2:186)

وَإِذَا سَأَلَكَ عِبَادِي عَنِّي فَإِنِّي قَرِيبٌ أُجِيبُ دَعْوَةَ الدَّاعِ إِذَا دَعَانِ فَلْيَسْتَجِيبُوا لِي وَلْيُؤْمِنُوا بِي لَعَلَّهُمْ يَرْشُدُونَ

Translation: *When My servants ask you 'O Prophet' about Me: I am truly near. I respond to one's prayer when they call upon Me. So let them respond 'with obedience' to Me and believe in Me, perhaps they will be guided 'to the Right Way.*

As result, through prayers the Muslims gained the spiritual power that is the energy of their souls. This integration can also provide a sense of comfort and support, promoting a holistic approach to healing that addresses both psychological and spiritual well-being.

Secondly, the imams emphasized another crucial religious practice — the profound impact of the Qur'an on mental health. this was aligned with a research study that shows Yet for the Muslim, the Qur'an and Sunnah are ultimately the fundamental sources of healing and,

as religiosity and mental health are inextricably linked, faith is a necessary component of healing and recovery for Muslims. (Umarji and Islam 2022). The Qur'an stands out as the definitive and authoritative scripture for Muslims globally, providing guidance and solutions for health-related concerns. This result aligns with existing research, particularly the study by Alhouseini et al. (2014), suggesting that listening to specific verses, such as Yasin Surah, yields psychological benefits by fostering calmness and tranquillity. Evidence from confirm this showing that various verses in the Holy Quran directly or indirectly address aspects of mental health. For instance, the Quran contains many verses about achieving tranquillity. For example, Allah says in the Quran,

الَّذِينَ ءَامَنُوا وَتَطْمَئِنُّ قُلُوبُهُمْ بِذِكْرِ اللَّهِ أَلَا بِذِكْرِ اللَّهِ تَطْمَئِنُّ الْقُلُوبُ Translation: *Be aware that the remembrance of Allah calms the hearts* (AL-Raad, 13: 27-28).

The Qur'an emerges as a potent resource, assisting Muslims in coping with, resolving, and overcoming life's adversities. The imams show in the study findings that This assistance extends beyond practical guidance, encompassing the cultivation of virtues like optimism, self-confidence, and patience. The result shows that the Quran significantly contribute to psychological resilience, fostering a state of peace of mind.

In conclusion, Islam's teachings, transmitted by imams, not only offer practical guidance but also promote virtues like optimism, self-confidence, and patience, enhancing psychological resilience. The religion's emphasis on soul care and respect highlights the connection between religion and mental health. It encourages seeking help and guidance from others during difficult times, fostering psychological resilience and overall well-being within the Muslim community. This holistic approach to well-being, including spiritual and psychological components, demonstrates the ongoing impact of the Muslim community on mental health.

Sub-theme 2a: The positive influence of Islamic faith on Mental health

The results of this study underscore the positive influence Islamic faith has in how Muslims navigate and address mental health concerns. Imams, as spiritual leaders, actively advocate for specific techniques aimed at supporting psychological resilience within the Muslim community. This then aligns with previous research by Benty et al. (2021), emphasizing that faith significantly shapes the conceptualization of psychological well-being, response to emotional distress, and patterns of help-seeking behaviour. Similar to previous research given faith’s centrality in understanding and coping with psychological distress, the primary source of relief is often through seeking counsel from the Imam, reliance on religious practices, and turning to Islamic principles (e.g., Ai et al., 2005). Imams, in the present study, focused on elucidating the positive impact of Islamic faith on Muslims facing mental health challenges, detailing the various ways individuals draw upon their faith to effectively cope with and manage such issues. This consistent thematic resonance with existing literature reinforces the notion that religious beliefs, particularly within the Islamic context, serve as a potent resource for individuals grappling with mental health issues. The table below summarizes the imams' findings on how Islamic teachings can provide good mental health to Muslims.

Table 7: The effect of Islamic teachings on mental health

Islamic teachings to overcome M.H. I	The result of following Islamic teachings
Following Prophets hardship	Optimism
Learning from prophets’ teachings	Overcome crises
Patience	Ease after Hardship
Connection to God	Strong psychological resilience

Imams in both communities underlined the necessity of following prophets' hardships and learning from them to discover answers to present mental health difficulties, as many prophets had comparable? emotional struggles. The acknowledgment of lessons drawn from the lives of prophets who confronted and triumphed over adversity is notably highlighted by imams from both Algeria and United Kingdom. This relationship resonates with the findings of prior research by Sabry and Vohra (2013) The Prophet Muhammad, peace be upon him, highlighted the significance of mental health and acknowledged it in different facets of his teachings. One of these elements is the focus on patience, which is stated over 200 times in the Quran and can be a valuable aid to those dealing with mental health issues. Following stories of prophets and learning from them helps Muslims filled with resilience and coping strategies offer valuable insights that provide comfort, which resulted in optimism and encouragement during challenging times to overcome crises.

The focus of imams on patience as a positive therapy in the Islamic context results in the recognition of patience as an admirable quality aiding Muslims in connecting with Allah (SWT) and enduring hardships with strength. This aligns with the findings of Achour et al. (2016), who assert that Muslims believe ease and comfort typically follow hardship and difficulties, leading them to exert maximum effort to reach a stage of relief through patience. The implications of patience in coping with life stressors are significant, extending the endurance of Muslims during challenging times and strengthening reactions to anxiety. There is an underlying belief that God loves patient individuals and supports them, as echoed in research by Ilyas (2020), explains patience as a form of therapy for curing illnesses as described in the Qur'an. This suggests great benefits, such as building the soul, strengthening personality,

and increasing strength in dealing with various problems and burdens of life. This highlights that patience is a way of life for Muslims, and having the knowledge that strong faith in God during hardship will result in ease afterward helps them avoid losing hope and succumbing to despair. These concepts underscore the potential of Islamic faith to instil positive and optimistic attitudes, promoting mental resilience in the face of difficulties. The belief in the temporary nature of challenges and the assurance of eventual relief serves as a powerful coping mechanism, fostering hope and preventing despair.

Further to this, it suggests that deepening one's faith, learning from prophets' hardships, and establishing a strong connection with God can lead to comfort, psychological resilience, and healing. Adhering to the straight path and religious principles can enhance mental and psychological strength. Aligned with this common cultural treatment for mental illness include servanthood, prayer (salah), invocation (dua), recitation of Quran (al-Ruqyah), Prophetic Medicine (Tibb-i Nabavi), remembrance of Allah (dhikr), charity (sadaqah), working with spiritual leaders, engaging in rituals, nightly prayers, joining spiritual conversation circles known as halaqah, focusing on diet, and muraqaba (i.e., one's striving to examine their spiritual heart and striving to develop their insight), to name a few (Tanhan & young, 2022). Similarly, as highlighted in the verse:

And whosoever fears Allah...He will make a way for him to get out (from every difficulty) and He will provide him from (sources) he does not expect (Qur'ān El-Talaq 65:2-3).

A robust faith and connection to Allah can empower individuals to confront life's challenges with a positive.

Sub-theme 2b: Description of Mental Health support in the Holy Quran

The exploration of Quranic teachings as a means of mental health care by Imams in the United

Kingdom and Algeria, referencing specific verses that address mental health support, underscores the profound impact of the Quran on the well-being of believers. In line with this research, a previous study highlights that Muslim scholars have not extensively delved into the formulation of interpretations within Islamic practices and traditions. The conventional method of interpretation tends to focus more on linguistic aspects (Putra et al., 2023). This is grounded in a socio-cultural understanding of the Quran, where its interpretation imparts meaning to the Muslim community. It also emphasizes the techniques employed in integrating these interpretations into their daily lives as a practical approach to addressing and overcoming mental health challenges.

Through the Quranic verses mentioned by Imams from both Algeria and the United Kingdom, it is evident that the Quran serves as a comprehensive handbook covering not only mental and emotional well-being but also physical well-being. The result of this study shows that Quran is regarded as a guide that addresses all elements of human health. This aligns with a previous research study by Ali (2015), which posits that the moral system outlined in the Quran provides an understanding of the nature of Man, World, God, and Hereafter, and is significant for self-realization. Additionally, one of the most well-known verses regarding Allah's support is found in Surah Al-Baqarah (2:286): "Allah does not burden a soul beyond that it can bear...". The results, as disclosed by the Imams, demonstrate that the Quran offers guidance for Muslims facing difficult and challenging times. The emphasis is on the belief in the presence of Allah, asserting that Allah is always with believers, even during challenging moments and seeking the direction of Allah, as outlined in the Quran.

The verses highlighted by the imams emphasize the Quran's encouragement for believers to endure challenges with patience and prayer, underscoring the belief that Allah is present with those who demonstrate patience. This emphasis promotes mental resilience and strength during adversity. Notably, the Quran contains numerous verses conveying different

messages to make the believers know more about mental health and that it is something existed before, such as

Indeed, mankind was created anxious (Quran 70:19)

And

We will surely test you with something of fear, hunger, a loss of wealth, lives, and fruits, but give good tidings to the patient (Quran 2:155).

Through these hardships Muslims can learn patience and understand that Allah's kindness and assistance will eventually manifest. The Quran, recognized as a remedy for mental health issues, addresses states of stress, anxiety, sadness, or depression. Indeed, the Quran is described as a healing guidance in the verse:

Say, 'It is, for those who believe, a guidance and cure (Quran 41:44).

Allah says:

O mankind! There has come to you good advice from your Lord, and healing of that which is in your breasts, - a guidance and a mercy (Qur'an, 10: 57).

Furthermore, Allah says:

And We send down of the Qur'an that which is healing and a mercy to those who believe, and it increases the wrongdoers (Zālimūn) nothing but loss (Qur'an, 17: 82).

Reciting and reflecting on its meanings can enhance one's emotional state, provide a deeper understanding or reframing of one's situation, and contribute to alleviating mental health issues. This aligns with previous research by Loukas et al. (2010), which highlights the Quran's detailed descriptions of medical remedies, anatomical structures, and even surgical procedures. specific Quranic verses were mentioned by imams, each highlighting the Quran's ability to provide guidance and support for mental health issues. Various studies were aligned with this result. For example, with findings from Al-Houseini et al. (2014), who emphasized that existing literature supports the idea that reciting Quranic verses can effectively reduce daily stress and

promote a lasting sense of tranquillity. Numerous other verses of the Holy Qur'an reveal insights into treatments of physical and mental diseases and mental health (Aboul-Enein, 2016; Damian et al., 2016). Similarly, Babamohamadi et al. (2015) stated that The Holy Qur'an describes the purposes and obligations of Muslims throughout its chapters and verses, which seek to educate and transform readers through recitation. The Qur'an refers to itself as a book of healing:

We have sent down in the Qur'an that which is healing and a mercy to those who believe
(Qur'an, 17:82).

Additionally, to another study, after retrieving 229 articles on the subject and eliminating those with unrelated content, we selected 19 articles for this review. Five sets of diseases and conditions—stress, anxiety, and depression; cancer; pain, including pain during childbirth; heart disease; and coma were identified, and the Qur'anic intervention showed significant improvement and amelioration of these incapacitating conditions. (Abdekhoda & Ranjbaran, 2022). It's important to note that previous studies haven't consistently specified criteria for selecting verses, indicating the Quran's broad and adaptable therapeutic potential for enhancing the mental well-being of Muslims.

Moreover, the Imams emphasized the Quranic encouragement to learn from prophets' hardships, citing the story of Prophet Joseph (Yusuf) as an illustrative example. This aligns with a qur'anic verse that declares:

Indeed, in the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) you have a good example to follow (Qur'an, 33: 21).

It's worth noting that there are various other stories, not explicitly addressed in the study, depicting the hardships faced even by prophets, encompassing instances of mental health challenges and periods of sadness.

the Quranic verses discussed by Imams in the study demonstrate that the Quran offers a therapeutic approach to addressing mental health challenges. Emphasizing the significance of faith, patience, and a strong connection with Allah as fundamental elements for achieving mental and emotional balance. The profound insights found in the teachings of the Quran provide a comprehensive framework for understanding and addressing mental health challenges.

Theme03: Muslims beliefs towards causes and solutions to mental health issues.

The result of the study demonstrates that, despite variations in culture and context between Algerian and British Muslim communities, there exist shared perspectives among imams regarding the causes and solutions of mental health issues. This commonality in ideas may arise from the unifying influence of Islamic principles and teachings. This finding aligns with a prior research study by Riley (2011), which asserted that, despite the heterogeneous nature of Muslims in terms of cultural, ethnic, linguistic, and sociological backgrounds, they are connected by common Islamic themes. The common thread in Islamic faith and behaviour may be influential in shaping various cultures' perspectives and approaches to mental health. This might include perspectives on getting help from others, finding tranquillity in faith, or doing Islamic rituals that enhance mental health.

Several key points were highlighted by Algerian and British imams concerning their perspectives within Muslim communities regarding their beliefs, attitudes, causes, and solutions for mental health issues. The first point highlighted by both imams from both cultures is that the level of knowledge of mental health and faith is connected to the cultures and societies. This can be aligned with a previous research study by Padela et al. (2011) which asserts that religious values and beliefs are intricately intertwined with cultural norms and practices. These elements shape patients' concepts of health and illness, impact expectations in

the doctor-patient relationship, guide adherence to doctors' recommendations, influence medical decision-making, and affect health outcomes (Fukuhara et al. 2003; Geertz 1983; Johnson et al., 1999; Nehra & Kulaksizoglu, 2002; Nielsen et al., 2003). Another study aligned with the results by Collins et al. (2004) although various barriers have been identified at different levels, religion was considered only as a component of culture, which, in turn, was only contemplated at the individual level. The collective knowledge and shared beliefs and culture within a Muslim community can influence how individuals perceive and address mental health challenges.

Secondly, the results show that imams consider spirituality as a potential cause of mental health issues. This study explores the connection between mental health and spirituality from two distinct perspectives. Firstly, it is suggested that Muslims with a weaker spiritual connection, often resulting from detachment from their religion and reduced interaction with God, may be more vulnerable to experiencing mental health issues. On the other hand, an alternative viewpoint posits that mental health challenges can be interpreted through a spiritual lens. In line with a previous research study by Subu et al. (2022), global studies have shown that many people believe mental illnesses are "spiritual illnesses" caused by demonic or spirit possessions, witchcraft, or the effects of the evil-eye (Karanci, 2014; Ross et al., 2013; Stefanovics et al., 2016; Tajima-Pozo et al., 2011). This perspective suggests that the difficulties Muslims in Algeria and United Kingdom face in their mental well-being may stem from spiritual conflicts, imbalances, or internal unrest.

Thirdly, the solution underscored by Imams highlights the significance of virtues such as patience and acceptance. The findings from Imams indicate that their Muslim communities perceive mental health challenges as tests from God and advocate for the virtues of patience and acceptance. This perspective harmoniously aligns with a broader view of psycho-spiritual well-being, directly linked to an individual's ability to fulfil their inherent spiritual purpose.

This alignment is consistent with the research of Ibn Qayyim al-Jawziyyah (1997), which emphasizes a crucial aspect of Islam that should accompany formal rituals, du'a, and dhikr constant remembrance of Allah and continuous connection with the Divine. Developing a genuinely Islamic attitude of patience enables individuals to navigate life's challenges, as Muslims consider life to be a test, and the values of patience and acceptance are highly esteemed in Islamic teachings.

Fourthly, Faith Deficiency as a Contributing Factor: Some Muslims may perceive a lack of faith as a potential cause of mental health issues. This viewpoint suggests that mental illnesses might be overlooked due to cultural traditions that stigmatize them, portraying those affected as deficient in religion and faith. Numerous studies align with this research finding. For some individuals, mental illness is seen as an opportunity to address a disconnection from religion or a deficiency in faith through regular prayer and a sense of personal responsibility (Padela et al., 2012; Youssef and Deane, 2006). Another research study supports this perspective, explaining how the absence of faith could contribute to mental health issues. This category comprises three subcategories: the first (i) subcategory views mental health issues as a test, the second (ii) subcategory involves the influence of supernatural entities (jinns, shaytan meaning evil, nazar or al-ayn meaning evil eye, and black magic), and the third (iii) subcategory emphasizes that a lack of or weak faith, or the failure to practice it, might lead to mental health issues. This last subcategory underscores the importance of a balanced life, incorporating a biopsychosocial spiritual perspective (Tanhan, 2017, 2019). The imams from both Algeria and the United Kingdom highlighted these three categories in the preceding paragraphs.

The final point emphasizes that strong faith is considered a coping mechanism and solution for overcoming mental health issues within Muslim communities. As previously mentioned, the Islamic religion is viewed as a source of psychological comfort and strength for many Muslims. This aligns with previous studies, including Koenig et al. (1989), which suggest

that religion plays a significant role in influencing individuals' responses to psychological treatment. Research by Padela and Curlin (2013) supports the notion that religious beliefs, values, and practices impact the health behaviours of diverse Muslim groups in two keyways: Muslims use a God-centered framework to comprehend health, illness, and treatment options, and they turn to Islamic ethic-legal guidelines when deciding the permissibility of medical treatments. In summary, strong spiritual convictions provide guidance during difficulties and empower individuals to confront adversity.

In summary, Imams' perspectives on mental health in Muslim communities are shaped by personal experiences, cultural backgrounds, and religious beliefs. Some see faith as strength, while others stigmatize mental health issues, attributing them to lack of faith. Emphasizing acceptance and patience is common. Understanding diverse viewpoints is crucial, requiring a nuanced approach within cultural and religious contexts.

Sub-theme 3a: Imams' engagement with Muslims with mental health issues

The findings indicate that imams frequently engage with Muslims in their communities on significant mental health issues, and this involvement is notably influenced by their cultural background and training. This active engagement underscores the importance of imams in establishing connections with community members and addressing mental health challenges. The study's results illuminate how imams can effectively support and provide resources for the mental health of Muslim communities through their culturally informed and well-trained participation.

The findings of this study the importance of the role of imams in addressing mental health issues within Muslim communities. Consistent with these research outcomes, a previous study posited that a diverse array of religious teachers, spiritual guides, and scholars, situated in mosques, community centres, and educational establishments, may be approached by members of the Muslim community grappling with psychological difficulties (Pilkington,

Msetfi, & Watson, 2011). The recurrent usage of the term "Sometimes" by British imams, when questioned about their involvement with Muslims facing mental health issues, may indeed signify an inconsistency in their approach to addressing these concerns. Aligned with the present study, a prior research effort by Meran and Mason (2019) indicated that British Muslims habitually resort to their faith leaders in response to the onset of mental ill-health. This suggests that imams intermittently engage with individuals confronting such challenges. However, the inconsistency in their engagement patterns could be ascribed to various factors. The varied cultural composition of the Muslim population in Britain plays a crucial role. This community is ethnically and culturally diverse, consisting of individuals from different backgrounds and experiences. In line with the findings of a previous study conducted by Hough et al. (2021) on Western European Muslim communities, there is a concentrated effort to preserve the traditions, norms, cultures, and practices of their countries of origin rather than emphasizing integration into European societies. Consequently, imams may face a broad spectrum of mental health needs within their congregations. Addressing mental health issues becomes challenging due to this diversity, making it impractical to adopt a one-size-fits-all approach. Secondly, the findings may also indicate an evolving awareness and training among British imams regarding mental health. Consistent with the results of this research, a study by Ali and Milstein (2012) utilized a vignette-based survey illustrating an individual displaying symptoms of depression to assess imams' beliefs regarding the aetiology of mental illness, their views on helpful interventions, as well as their practices in referrals and counselling experience. Their primary discovery was that imams acknowledged the severity of serious mental illnesses and the necessity of some form of intervention for recovery. The findings suggest that some imams may be better equipped to handle these issues due to their access to resources, education, and training, while others may still be in the process of gaining a deeper understanding of mental health concerns. Consistent with a prior research study by Ali et al. (2005) despite

having minimal formal training in counselling, imams are often called upon to assist congregants dealing with mental health and social service issues. Imams require more support from mental health professionals to effectively fulfil a potentially crucial role in improving access to services for minority Muslim communities, where there currently appear to be unmet psychosocial needs.

In contrast, the responses from Algerian imams present a spectrum of approaches, with some indicating "Never." This lack of formal training could explain why some Algerian imams might avoid discussing mental health issues. In line with this research result, a prior study highlighted that despite dedicating significant time to "counselling" congregants, many imams rarely have formal training in addressing mental health issues (Ciftci, 2012). The diversity of responses suggests a broader range of attitudes and practices among Algerian imams. The Algerian context introduces unique factors, where cultural attitudes toward mental health and awareness of these issues may differ from those in Britain. Nevertheless, the results indicate that others may be more open to addressing these concerns through the "Always" and "Sometimes" responses, reflecting a strong cultural value placed on community support and the role of religious leaders in addressing various challenges.

The observed variations in imams' engagement with mental health issues between different contexts underscore the importance of considering cultural and contextual factors when engaging with Muslims with mental health issues. The results highlight the essential recognition that imams play a significant role in providing spiritual and emotional guidance to their congregations, and their approach to mental health issues can profoundly impact individuals seeking help.

This theme underscores the imperative of acknowledging the diversity of attitudes and practices among imams in addressing mental health issues. It highlights the necessity for culturally sensitive and context-specific approaches to mental health support within Muslim

communities. Recognizing the unique perspectives and needs among imams is crucial, emphasizing that a personalized approach is essential for effective mental health interventions within this demographic.

Theme 4: Imam's initiatives in meeting mental health needs

Before exploring the imams' initiatives in addressing the mental health needs of their Muslim communities, the study examined the age groups that have substantial contact with imams and the specific challenges they face in fulfilling their mental health requirements.

The identification of overlapping age groups in the responses indicates that imams from both Algeria and the UK frequently find themselves providing support across multiple categories, particularly for young adults and adults as well as families. Ibrahim and Mojab (2023) imply that imams effectively engage and provide support to a diverse range of age groups, from younger members to adults and families. The diversity of age groups seeking help from imams suggests that the challenges faced by these communities are intricate and multifaceted. Imams are actively addressing a wide range of issues, reflecting the intricate nature of societal and individual needs. Aligned with this result (Hamid, 2013) stated that Imams can provide culturally appropriate psychosocial support services, especially for younger members of the community.

The recognition that imams' roles extend beyond religious and spiritual matters to encompass various dimensions of individuals' lives, including social, psychological, and well-being aspects, is significant. Imams utilize effective managerial strategies to improve the well-being of the community. They strive to embed authentic Islamic principles and management techniques within Islamic societies, facilitating Muslim individuals and their families to

achieve prosperity in diverse areas such as family life, commerce, governance, and the political landscape of Muslim nations (Khichi & Razavi, 2021).

Understanding the distinct age groups seeking help from imams is crucial for tailoring the support and services they offer to meet the specific needs of their congregants. This information holds valuable insights for policymakers and community leaders working to promote well-being and address the challenges faced by these communities.

Effective communication skills are essential for cultivating comprehension and cooperation among imams and their diverse congregations in the multicultural society of Britain. Imams in Britain encounter a challenge in improving their communication abilities, as highlighted by Mukadam et al. (2010), who reference concerns raised by the Muslim council of Britain regarding the insufficient advancement of local imams and inadequate training. Individuals graduating from British seminaries frequently lack proficiency in communication, leadership, and cultural awareness. Western European Muslim communities may have tended to prioritize the preservation of their nations of origin's traditions, norms, cultures, and practices over actively seeking integration into European societies. Consequently, there has been a historical reliance on importing Imams from outside of Europe (Hussain & Tuck, 2014), leading to potential misunderstandings that hinder the effective dissemination of guidance, thus reducing community engagement and interaction (Halder et al., 2023). Moreover, the diverse backgrounds present within the British Muslim community could pose challenges in discussing how religious beliefs impact decision-making, consequently impacting the management of chronic conditions and exacerbating health disparities.

British Imams or British Muslims from different backgrounds who lack communication skills may encounter challenges in addressing these intricate issues proficiently in their examination of cultural competence among mental health professionals (Lewis et al.,

2018). Strengthening the abilities of religious leaders is essential for addressing and alleviating a wide range of psychosocial needs among Muslims with diverse backgrounds. This is particularly important because individuals in these communities often place great faith and trust in their cultural institutions, heavily relying on them for psychosocial support (Ibrahim & Mojab, 2023). Therefore, there is an immediate need for training and development to improve communication skills between imams and their congregations, particularly in relation to mental health care, to ensure effective support and engagement. Providing support for their capacity and equipping them with tools to enhance their knowledge in counselling, awareness of available resources, language proficiency, and active communication with healthcare services, law enforcement, and social services will ease their work, reduce barriers, and increase access to services for vulnerable communities (Ibrahim & Mojab, 2023).

In contrast, Algerian imams operate in a more homogeneous cultural and linguistic environment, reducing such communication hurdles. Nevertheless, both British and Algerian imams grapple with the challenge of offering effective guidance on mental health issues, particularly for certain segments of their communities. The identification of "Guidance Skills" as a common concern underscores the importance of continuous skill development for imams in both contexts. This recognition signifies their dedication to better serving their diverse communities, adapting to their evolving needs, and fostering cultural sensitivity. In a world where mental health issues are increasingly prevalent, the role of imams as mental health allies and community leaders is becoming increasingly vital. Their commitment to enhancing their communication and guidance skills is instrumental in helping Muslims navigate the complexities of mental health while preserving their cultural identities.

It is noteworthy that existing studies have not specifically addressed the age groups of individuals seeking assistance from imams for their mental health issues, nor have they

explored the challenges imams face when dealing with Muslims experiencing mental health challenges. This gap in the literature leaves a significant knowledge void regarding the intersection of age and the support-seeking dynamics within the Muslim community. Further research in this area would be instrumental in gaining a more nuanced understanding of the diverse challenges faced by imams when providing mental health guidance across different age groups.

Sub-Theme 4a: Imams' recommendations for Muslims with mental health issues

The results underscore the divergent recommendations offered by Algerian and British imams concerning mental health issues, illustrating the intersectionality of cultural, religious, and healthcare perspectives. The findings emphasize the role of imams as mental health care providers, utilizing Quranic scriptures and practices such as Roqya as references to alleviate the distress of Muslims. The contrast in recommendations suggests the influence of cultural and contextual factors on the guidance provided by imams, highlighting the importance of considering diverse perspectives in addressing mental health within the Muslim community.

In the Algerian context, it is evident that imams often perceive mental health issues through a predominantly spiritual lens. They emphasize the application of Roqya, an Islamic spiritual healing practice, to address concerns related to mental health. This perspective aligns with research findings asserting that healing constitutes a central component across religious systems, aiming to restore health, wholeness, and alleviate suffering (Dein, 2020) according to him "religious healing," often used in social science literature, is mentioned without a clear definition, and is frequently employed interchangeably with "faith" or "spiritual" healing, further emphasizing the interconnectedness of spiritual and mental well-being (Dein, 2020). In parallel with these ideas, another study notes that Roqyah is a spiritual treatment process

aligned with various religious practices, including prayer and zikr (divine remembrance) (Afifuddin & Nooraini, 2016). Similarly with another research study that emphasizes that "Ruqyah" serves as a healing method based on the Quran and hadith, involving recitation, seeking refuge, remembrance, and supplication to treat sickness and other problems, reading Quranic verses, Allah's names, and attributes, or praying in an understood language (Ahmed et al., 2016). Consequently, this research underscores the prevalence of ruqyah shar'iyah as a favoured mode of spiritual healing among Algerian Muslims for depressive illnesses, employed by imams in addressing mental health challenges within the Algerian community. This approach is grounded in the belief that spiritual interventions play a significant role in fostering healing and overall well-being. The application of ruqyah syar'iyah by Algerian imams for treating mental health issues holds the potential to emerge as a novel alternative to contemporary treatments on a local and global scale.

On the contrary, British imams recommend seeking assistance from mental health professionals associated with their religious denomination. According to the findings of this study, a previous research investigation indicated that imams may be uniquely positioned to positively influence individuals at various stages of seeking mental health help, from recognizing existing issues to deciding to access formal services (Humam et al., 2023). This approach underscores the importance of evidence-based mental health care provided by professionals trained to understand the cultural and religious sensitivities of those seeking help. The results emphasize the recommendation for British imams to separate mental health care from religious or spiritual practices. Simultaneously, it suggests that mental health professionals should possess knowledge about the Muslim religious background for successful therapeutic treatment. It becomes evident that imams, serving as religious leaders, may benefit from enhanced counselling skills. Additionally, the complex tapestry of cultural and religious

diversity in these communities underscores the importance of mental health professionals who can navigate and respect these unique aspects when providing support.

In the broader context of mental health, the endorsement of more intensive prayers as a recommendation by both British and Algerian imams underscores the idea that mental health support can be multifaceted, incorporating both evidence-based care and faith-based practices. It emphasizes the importance of respecting individuals' beliefs and preferences in their mental health journey while ensuring access to appropriate and specialized care when needed. This convergence of perspectives ultimately underscores the complexity and diversity of approaches to mental health support within various cultural and religious contexts. Aligned with this research, a previous study stated that those who prayed moderately, but not daily, experienced less depression (Nathensen, 2012). Similarly, several reports on the application of prayers in psychotherapy illustrate positive outcomes for individuals exhibiting pathological symptoms such as tension, anxiety, depression, and antisocial tendencies (Abdullah et al., 2012). Practicing intensive prayers as a religious activity can also serve as a source of emotional and psychological support for individuals facing mental health challenges.

The disparities in recommendations between these two groups of imams mirror the wider range of mental health viewpoints among the global Muslim community. It is essential to acknowledge that there is no one-size-fits-all strategy to managing mental health difficulties, and that individuals may pick a path that is consistent with their values and cultural background.

Theme 05: Religious interventions and psychotherapy

The contrasting perspectives of British and Algerian imams regarding the role of religion in mental health interventions underscore the intricacies of therapy, which are shaped by cultural, religious, and medical factors. The findings shows that The British imams acknowledged the

potential benefits of religious beliefs and practices in enhancing mental well-being, they also recognize that religion is not the sole solution for mental health treatment. Emphasizing the importance of seeking help from therapists or psychiatrists and, if necessary, utilizing medication in severe cases. Aligns with previous research as mentioned in a study by Ayvaci (2017), patients' tendencies to use religion when coping with mental health-related problems, combined with the involvement of a nonclinical party, can result in a complex model of mental healthcare delivery. The British imam's perspective underscores the need for medical and professional treatments in severe cases, emphasizing a comprehensive approach to mental health care.

On the contrary, Algerian imams present a nuanced viewpoint. They consider religious interventions to be essential components of psychotherapy, serving as complements to medical treatments. A prior research study has affirmed that the integration of religious elements into psychotherapy can enhance the therapeutic relationship, strengthen adherence to treatment, and improve an individual's ability to cope with suffering (Martins and Moreira-Almeida, 2018). In alignment with another study supporting these findings, the recent Position Statement on religiosity and spirituality from the World Psychiatry Association suggests a careful consideration of clients' religious beliefs and practices, irrespective of the professional's own beliefs (Moreira-Almeida et al., 2016). Consequently, Algerian imams emphasize the importance of regularly and systematically assessing and addressing religiosity in psychotherapy, emphasizing its complementary role.

In contrast to a few Algerian imams who highlight that the Islamic faith provides a robust framework for achieving psychological well-being. Aligned with this research result, a prior study underscored the substantial impact of faith on the conceptualization of psychological health, emotional pain, and subsequent help-seeking behaviour (Bentley et al., 2021). These imams comprehend that engaging in religious rituals and connecting with God

may significantly enhance psychological well-being. This comprehensive, faith-based approach, encompassing both religion's role and religious interventions, presents a holistic strategy for addressing mental health issues. Such a viewpoint aligns with a more traditional understanding of religion's role in mental health, underscoring the significant influence of Islamic culture on attitudes toward mental well-being.

The variation in views among British and Algerian imams underscores the importance of integrating religious perspectives into mental health treatment and stresses the significance of respecting diverse outlooks. Culturally and religiously sensitive mental health services are crucial, recognizing that individuals may uphold different beliefs and attitudes regarding the role of religion in mental health. This aligns with the findings of a previous study by Skinner (2010), which demonstrated that when clients and healers share similar understandings of mental disorders, better therapeutic outcomes are achieved. Mental health professionals need to acknowledge these variations and design services that can accommodate diverse perspectives. These differing viewpoints are indicative of the broader societal and cultural contexts within which imams operate.

In conclusion, the integration of religious and spiritual components into psychotherapy equips mental health professionals with a more comprehensive understanding of the Muslim experience, enabling them to tailor treatments to the Muslim belief system. This approach serves as a valuable paradigm for addressing issues of identity, purpose, and meaning in both Arab and Western cultures within the framework of the Muslim faith.

Theme 06: Barriers that prevent Muslims from accessing Mental health services.

The exploration of the pathway to mental health care for Muslims and the potential barriers, particularly from the perspective of imams, offers valuable insights into the intricate dynamics

of religious, cultural, and societal factors. The theme primarily revolves around the identified obstacles that hinder Muslims' access to mental health services.

Firstly, it is unanimously agreed by imams from both Algerian and British contexts that religion does not serve as a hindrance to mental health service utilization. Instead, religion is regarded as a facilitator that encourages individuals to seek professional help when faced with mental health issues. Aligned with this research result, a previous study on The Bio-Psychosocial Health Model by Koenig (2001) emphasizes the therapeutic effects of belief in religion, religious practices, and societal support. The significance of religious knowledge is highlighted, particularly among British imams, as a potential facilitator for mental health treatment. This underscores the role of religious knowledge in guiding Muslims to understand and utilize available treatments within the Islamic tradition. Specific emphasis is placed on the knowledge of Quranic verses addressing mental health, empowering individuals to perform traditional treatments like Roqya. In line with this result, a previous research study stated that the Qur'an is the quintessential authoritative scripture for practicing Muslims worldwide, offering guidance for medical solutions and health problems (Aboul-Enein, 2016). Similarly, another study supports this idea by confirming that within the Quran and Hadith are descriptions of medical remedies, anatomical structures, and surgical procedures (Loukas et al., 2010). This suggests that well-informed Muslims may have the tools to address their mental health concerns within their religious framework.

Nevertheless, despite the positive impact of religion, imams from both Algeria and the United Kingdom recognize the existence of cultural and societal barriers hindering Muslims from accessing mental health services. Consistent with this research finding, a previous study highlighted that cultural factors significantly influence service utilization through their impact on structural aspects, beliefs, stigma, and perceptions of mental health services (Nwokoroku et al., 2022). Barriers identified include ignorance, lack of knowledge, stigma, suspicions, and

mistrust of therapies, echoing the broader challenges confronted by individuals seeking mental health care. In alignment with this research outcome, a separate study by Basit & Hamid, (2010) reported various barriers faced by many Muslims when attempting to access mental health support: (a) misconceptions about mental illnesses and insufficient awareness of their prevalence in Muslim communities; (b) language barriers; (c) a preference for seeking help from traditional healers; (d) concerns related to stigma and family honour; (e) being unfamiliar with the concepts of counselling and psychotherapy. Similarly, another research study addressing barriers to help-seeking encompassed factors such as stigma, issues of privacy and confidentiality, trust, mental health literacy, language, logistics, and culturally rooted obstacles (Khatib, Alyafei, Shaikh, 2023). These barriers are deeply rooted in cultural and societal factors, reflecting the broader challenges faced by Muslims seeking mental health care in Algerian and British Muslim communities.

British imams emphasize the presence of language barriers in the culturally diverse landscape of the UK, attributing this challenge to both imams and the Muslim community. This linguistic obstacle is rooted in the fear of not being comprehended by either professionals or religious leaders. Consistent with this viewpoint, a research study, which includes a previous investigation by Al Shamsi et al (2020) affirms the notion that language barriers in healthcare result in miscommunication between medical professionals and patients. This miscommunication, in turn, diminishes satisfaction for both parties and compromises the quality of healthcare delivery and patient safety. Consequently, language barriers and a lack of cultural and linguistic sensitivity in existing mental healthcare services may pose difficulties for Muslims dealing with mental health issues in receiving professional support services. This circumstance can make it challenging for them to effectively communicate their mental health concerns and obtain appropriate treatment.

On the other hand, in Algeria, significant barriers are linked to traditional healing methods. This preference is shaped by cultural beliefs and practices within Algerian communities, where traditional healing holds substantial importance in addressing mental health concerns. Aligned with this research result, a previous study highlights concerns about certain traditional healers causing harm, notably by imposing a considerable financial burden on the unwell. Despite these challenges, the unavoidable reality is that traditional healers outnumber biomedical providers and play a particularly vital role in mental health, as emphasized by (Patel, 2011). This underscores the impact of cultural norms on help-seeking behaviours and reflects the broader context of healthcare practices in the region. The lack of family support is identified as another barrier by Algerian imams, possibly stemming from a reserved culture that inhibits open discussions about mental health issues within families. Aligned with this result, a previous research study stated that the absence of family support can have negative psychological consequences, leaving members susceptible to threats and pressures (Swartzman, Sani, Munro, 2017). The results of this study indicate that family support is considered a crucial aspect of the healing journey. Without such support, there can be an impact on the family member, influencing their adoption of appropriate help-seeking behaviour.

In conclusion, the results highlight the multifaceted nature of barriers that impede Muslims from accessing mental health services. While religion is generally considered a positive influence, cultural and societal factors exert a more significant role in shaping attitudes toward mental health care and help-seeking behaviours. The identified barriers contribute to the underrepresentation of Muslims in mental health help-seeking behaviours and attitudes within their communities, necessitating further efforts to facilitate access to mental health support for this minority group in the UK and Algeria

Sub-theme 6a: Imam's role in reducing stigma in Muslim communities.

As previously stated in the previous theme result, if an imam is familiar with the signs of mental health, they will have a better awareness of mental health, which will help reduce the stigma associated with mental health concerns in their community. Their knowledgeable approach can promote open and tolerant discussions regarding mental health. There is a limited support research studies that exploring the potential role of imams in reducing stigma against mental illness in their communities. This study result explores more about imams' strategies in destigmatising mental health issues in Arab and western communities namely Algeria and the United Kingdom.

In both Algeria and the UK, imams seem to select answers that are most fitting for their roles in the mosque. Imams in Algeria and the United Kingdom, as indicated by this study, implement two key measures to combat stigma in their communities. The first measure involves leveraging Quranic teachings, seen as a potent tool by these leaders. This aligns with a previous research study highlighting the Quran's potential as a significant means for culturally competent public health practitioners, particularly in diverse populations like Muslim communities, to promote and sustain healthy behaviours (Aboul-Enein, 2016). The results reveal that the Quran contains numerous verses stressing compassion, empathy, and the prohibition of ridiculing or insulting others. Drawing upon these verses, imams can underscore the moral and ethical basis against stigmatizing individuals, especially those facing mental health challenges. This strategy resonates with Islam's fundamental principles, fostering a more empathetic and understanding community.

The second approach employed by imams to reduce stigma within their Muslim communities involves educating and imparting lessons on the subject in the mosque. The study findings indicate that the mosque can serve as a central hub for education and awareness, extending beyond congregational prayers and community gatherings. Consistent with these

findings, research suggests that religious engagement and attendance at the mosque play crucial roles in Muslims' recovery from mental illness, correlating with reduced rates of depression and enhanced social functioning (Eltaiba & Harries, 2015; Abdel-Khalek, 2007). Similarly, another study emphasizes the importance of embedding mental health interventions within mosque communities for more effective and enduring treatment outcomes, leading to a decrease in mental health disparities (Basit, 2010; Killawi et al., 2015). By delivering lessons on stigma and mental health within the mosque, imams can effectively reach a broad audience and establish a secure environment for open discussions. These educational initiatives not only promote awareness but also contribute significantly to destigmatizing mental health issues, fostering improved understanding and support for individuals and families grappling with such challenges.

In conclusion, imams have a vital role to play in reducing stigma within Muslim communities, particularly concerning mental health. Their use of Quranic teachings, educational initiatives, can lead to more informed, compassionate, and supportive communities. This theme emphasizes the importance of spirituality, education, in addressing the mental health challenges faced by Muslim communities.

Theme 07: Professional referrals

The findings of this study underscore the level of expertise possessed by imams in addressing mental health concerns among Muslims in their communities. Additionally, the study sheds light on the services that mosques offer in critical mental health situations. The primary focus of the research was on the training of imams. Since mosques are often the exclusive spaces where Muslims gather collectively, imams play a pivotal role in establishing connections within Muslim communities. Consistent with earlier studies, which emphasized imams as crucial sources of support and guidance for the public, regardless of ethnicity (Shah &

Culberston, 2011). This research underscores the significance of imams' direct engagement with their communities.

Sub-Theme 7a: Imams' mental health training

The study reveals a significant disparity in the training received by imams in Algeria and the United Kingdom when it comes to addressing mental health issues within the Muslim community. Many imams from both cultural backgrounds lack the necessary skills to effectively support urgent cases struggling with mental health problems. Consistent with the findings of this study, a prior research study indicated that a majority of imams are inadequately trained to meet the needs of young second- and third-generation Muslims (Hafiz, 2014). The reason imams often lack sufficient training is rooted in the perception that the mosque itself serves as a therapeutic space, negating the need for imams to undergo specific training. This perception arises from the belief that the lessons and spiritual practices within the mosque release individuals from mental health issues and crises.

Consistent with these results, a previous research study confirms the notion that every mosque worldwide has the common purpose of being a source of guidance, benefits, and peace for all those who enter it (Jehangir, 2018). A mosque is expected to be welcoming to the community regardless of their faith and belief, providing guidance and acting as a source of inner peace through the spiritual upliftment of human hearts. From an Islamic perspective, all activities promoting goodness and virtue are to be conducted within the premises of a mosque. The study's findings underscore that mosques serve as purposeful and serviceable components and facilities, playing a vibrant and effective role in the Muslim community. This is succinctly expressed in the Quranic verse:

The mosques of God shall be maintained by such as believe in God and the Last Day, establish regular prayers, and practise regular charity, and fear none (at all) except God. It is they who are expected to be on true guidance (Qur'an 9:18).

The discussion and details presented in this research result make it clear that the role of a mosque is far more comprehensive than merely being a place of worship. Similarly, the role of an imam extends beyond leading prayers inside the mosque. The findings also reveal that while imams may possess knowledge, some British imams acknowledge their efforts to learn from other trained religious leaders to better address spiritual issues, albeit more than mental health issues. Consequently, the study emphasizes that if imams lack sufficient training, it becomes challenging for them to recognize mental health issues. Even though imams in this study demonstrated knowledge about mental health issues, the lack of specific training remains a significant gap. Importantly, the study underscores that their knowledge alone may not be sufficient to effectively address and support individuals grappling with mental health challenges.

These findings support the urgent need for targeted training programs and increased resources to ensure that imams are better equipped to address the mental health needs of their communities. The study establishes that imams, while not providing counselling for the mental health-related needs of their congregants, face limitations due to inadequate training, staffing, and resources at their mosques.

Sub-Theme 7b: Spiritual treatment effectiveness

The findings of this study delve into the criteria utilized by imams in their conventional spiritual methods to address mental health concerns among Muslims and evaluate the effectiveness of these treatments. Insights from British and Algerian imams reveal a noteworthy contrast. The data indicates that most British imams lack specific standards to gauge treatment effectiveness, indicating a potential gap in assessing and quantifying the impact of their spiritual interventions. Conversely, some British imams employ observational and behavioural

indicators, encompassing individuals' feelings, attitudes, and body language, to evaluate treatment effectiveness. Although subjective, this approach enables imams to assess the impact of their spiritual interventions through the perspective of those seeking help. On the other hand, a few British imams believe that providing mental health therapy or spiritual healing falls outside their duties within the mosque, highlighting variations in imams' perceived roles and responsibilities regarding mental health. The findings also suggest that imams' standards for treatment effectiveness depend on individuals' faith levels in following the treatment.

In contrast, Algerian imams offer insights into the standards they employ to assess the effectiveness of their spiritual treatments. These standards include factors such as accurate diagnosis, knowledge, familiarity with specialists' experiences, and acceptance of scientific ideas and theories. Additionally, they emphasize positive changes in an individual's mental health and psychological well-being as measures of treatment effectiveness, underscoring a strong focus on the holistic improvement of an individual's mental health and overall well-being.

Regarding the treatment duration for Muslims with spiritual or mental health issues, the findings reveal variability influenced by several factors. The severity of the case and the level of patient engagement play pivotal roles in determining the duration. The nature of dilemmas and diseases, the individual's personality, and the available methods and skills for treatment also influence the treatment duration. Some British imams provide specific timeframes for observing treatment effectiveness, ranging from one week to one year. The researcher focuses on duration in future research to explore potential effects on Muslims' mental health and their help-seeking behaviour.

The adaptability of treatment duration depends on a combination of factors, including the severity of the case, patient engagement, and the nature of the issues. This outcome sheds

light on the diverse approaches and perceptions of imams concerning the treatment and assessment of mental health issues within their communities.

Sub-Theme 7c: Imams’ professional referrals and collaboration with mental health professionals

This outcome outlines the types of referrals employed by imams, underscoring the importance of collaboration between mental health professionals and imams. It highlights the complexities involved in addressing mental health issues within Muslim communities. The key points and discussions related to this theme include. To summarize, the following table outlining the types of referrals that imams may offer for mental health treatment:

Table 8: Imam Types of Referrals and collaboration with professionals

Type of Referral	Description
1. Spiritual Counselling	Imams provide spiritual guidance and advice based on Islamic principles. They offer emotional support through religious teachings and encourage individuals to turn to faith for solace and strength.
2. Referral to Mental Health Professionals	Imams recognize the need for specialized care and may refer individuals with severe mental health issues to Professional for evaluation and treatment.
3. Integration of Faith-Based Practices	Imams may incorporate faith-based practices, including Roqya as part of the therapeutic process to provide comfort and healing to those experiencing mental distress.

4. Creating a Supportive Community	Imams foster a sense of community support by organizing sessions that address mental health issues and raising awareness, reducing stigma, and providing valuable support to those in need. These initiatives help create a supportive environment for individuals dealing with mental illnesses.
5. Collaboration with Mental Health Services	In some cases, imams collaborate with mental health professionals and services to offer comprehensive care. This collaboration may involve bringing mental health experts to the mosque or establishing partnerships with local mental health organizations.

This table encompassing a range of approaches that combine spirituality, professional care, and community support.

The research findings indicate that British imams have diverse perspectives on the timing and necessity of referring individuals to mental health professionals. The findings reveal that not all imams engage in referrals for Muslims dealing with mental health issues, citing various reasons, including specialization in religious guidance and limited experience with severe cases that would warrant a referral. Some imams advocate for referrals only in extreme cases, showcasing their awareness of their roles as both support providers and gatekeepers to mental health services. In accordance with this result there is a previous qualitative UK-based study, Watts, Murray, and Pilkington (2014) performed a phenomenological analysis of the experiences of six imams, all of whom saw providing counselling and pastoral care as a core part of their role and acted in a manner analogous to central diagnostic practitioners: directing those with medical ailments to doctors, and those with jinn difficulties to a spiritual expert.

This emphasizes the crucial role of imams in facilitating access to professional mental health services and underscores the importance of their understanding of the attitudes and challenges faced by Muslims seeking assistance. Furthermore, concerns have been raised about financial barriers obstructing access to professional mental health services, highlighting challenges related to affordability and the availability of free healthcare services. This underscores the need for implementing adequate support and affordability measures to ensure that individuals can access the necessary care.

Additionally, Algerian imams have recognized a lack of trust in mental health professionals and services as a significant barrier, leading to reluctance among people with mental health issues to seek professional help. Acknowledging imams as trusted community figures, it becomes evident that they can play a pivotal role in bridging this trust gap and encouraging individuals to seek professional assistance when needed.

Furthermore, the study reveals a lack of collaboration between imams and mental health services or professionals in both Algeria and the UK. This is attributed to several reasons outlined by the imams. Firstly, mosques or religious institutions operate independently from medical or mental health services. Moreover, in the case of the few imams in the UK, there is reported to be no communication between the imams and mental health services. Mosques and religious institutions operate separately from medical and mental health services, highlighting a clear division between these two realms. This lack of integration results in a lack of coordination between imams and mental health services, creating challenges for individuals seeking mental health care. The disconnect may limit imams' ability to effectively address mental health challenges within their communities. To address this, fostering collaboration between religious and healthcare sectors is crucial. By working together, imams and mental health professionals can offer a comprehensive approach to mental health care, incorporating spirituality and evidence-based interventions. This collaboration can help reduce stigma,

promote inclusivity, and ultimately improve mental health outcomes within religious communities.

In contrast, a significant number of Algerians have declared their collaboration with mental health services and professionals, including religious leaders who specialize solely in spiritual guidance. Supporting these findings, a prior research study noted that while some imams expressed a willingness to collaborate with mental health professionals, actual consultation practices were infrequent in their communities (Ali, Milstein, 2012). Another study by Abu-Ras et al. (2008) emphasized the pivotal role of imams in promoting mental health, serving as individuals whom people could turn to for both religious guidance and counselling. Imams can also contribute to the education of mental health professionals on how to incorporate religion into an individual's treatment plan. Therefore, it is crucial for mental health professionals to offer service users the option of integrating religious beliefs into therapeutic work (El-Awaisi et al., 2021). Similarly, a survey of imams in the United States conducted by Ali et al. (2005) strongly suggested a need for mental health professionals to support imams in their vital role of improving access for members of the Muslim community to mainstream mental health services. This underscores the significance of collaboration and communication between imams and mental health professionals to enhance overall mental health support within the Muslim community.

The study emphasizes the importance of imams as spiritual guides and influential figures in the Muslim community, particularly in promoting trust and access to mental health services. Imams' understanding of Islamic teachings and spiritual support can help destigmatize mental health issues and encourage individuals to seek professional help. By collaborating with mental health professionals, imams can bridge the gap between religious and clinical approaches, creating a holistic support system that addresses the unique needs and challenges faced by Muslims in accessing mental health services.

5.10 Conclusion

In conclusion, this qualitative study significantly advances our comprehension of the pivotal role imams play in addressing mental health issues within diverse Muslim communities in Algeria and the United Kingdom. The study reveals imams as influential figures, acting as local community leaders and contributing to broader communities toward achieving balance and resilience, transcending cultural differences, and promoting resilience in the face of life's challenges.

By exploring the intricate interplay between religion, culture, and mental health, the research highlights the positive influence of religious practices and spirituality on individuals facing mental health challenges. Valuable insights into traditional and alternative treatments, such as reading the Quran, underscore their benefits in helping Muslims understand and overcome mental health issues. Additionally, the practice of roqya, guided by imams, underscores their pivotal position in bridging the gap between cultural beliefs and professional mental health services.

The findings also illuminate the existence of stigmatization related to mental health conditions within Muslim communities. Imams deploy strategic measures to foster awareness and combat stigma. However, a notable observation is the clear division between mosques/religious institutions and medical/mental health services, indicating a lack of integration and coordination between imams and mental health professionals.

The implications of this study extend to the development of targeted interventions that recognize and integrate the unique role of imams. Collaboration between religious leaders and mental health professionals is essential to create a comprehensive framework integrating spiritual practices, community support, and professional mental health services for addressing

mental health challenges within Muslim populations. Imams, leveraging their roles in mosques, can bridge the gap between religious practices and mental health services, offering a holistic approach to treat mental health issues in the community.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

This study delves into the implications of comprehending mental health challenges in Algeria and the United Kingdom, along with their encounters with mental health issues in various

cultural settings. This research emphasizes a favourable link between the mental health experiences of youth and their cultural backgrounds, emphasizing a noteworthy utilization of religiosity in mental health care as a distinguishing element. The initial investigation scrutinizes the extent of knowledge within the youth demographic and its impact on their recognition of mental health symptoms. This assessment appraises the mental health literacy of young individuals, aiming to pinpoint deficiencies in knowledge, beliefs, and behavioural intentions (Dias, Campos, Almeida & Palha, 2018). To demonstrate that individuals employ a mix of self-care, cultural, and professional interventions to address the way they handle their mental health challenges, incorporating various psychological, social, and practical strategies.

Moreover, the current study presents a comparative analysis of the Pathways utilized in selecting appropriate coping mechanisms and seeking assistance, which are contingent on the cultural and geographical contexts. An examination of the data reveals that anxiety emerges as the predominant mental health issue encountered by most young individuals in both the Algerian and British populations. These societies employ interventions that have been adjusted to suit their respective cultural frameworks. The initial study (1) illustrates that numerous mental health difficulties experienced by young adults from Algeria and the United Kingdom may be either unreported or unattended to, rendering it challenging to pinpoint the most widespread issues. Cultural beliefs, particularly within the Algerian society, play a significant role in shaping the approach towards self-coping strategies. This aspect underscores the distinctions in addressing mental health concerns within the two cultures Algeria and the UK. It is pertinent to note there were differences in Remedies that were classified into religious (incorporating religious rituals and traditional remedies) in Algeria, biomedical (involving professional medical assistance and mental health services) in the UK, and self-care (embracing nature, physical activities, meditation, and social networking platforms) in both Algeria and

the UK. The perceived aetiologies of mental illnesses were evaluated through the lens of the participants' perspectives and were divided into a "traditional explanation" (e.g., spirit possession, malevolent gaze, envy) or a contemporary medical interpretation (professional therapeutic interventions). As stated by Heider (1958), individuals function as 'naïve scientists', striving to identify patterns and consistency within their social environment; hence, the patterns of acknowledgment and conduct concerning mental health matters are no anomaly. Despite the similarities in experiencing mental health issues during this age period and acknowledging them, there were more differences in how they were dealt with.

In an increasingly globalized world, it is not sufficient to have all the same treatment and healing approaches. The first research study demonstrates the importance of the utility of digital media like social media platforms in supporting mental health. Young people in both Algeria and the United Kingdom are increasingly turning to online resources, such as internet searches, health websites, and online discussion forums, to find information and support for their mental health. However, there are concerns about the credibility and reliability of some online sources, which can be a barrier to effective help-seeking (Pretorius et al., 2019). This thesis shows both positive and negative sides of social media use in supporting mental health issues and recommends average use and time to support mental health in a balanced way. Social media can provide a platform for individuals to connect with others, seek support, and find resources for their mental health issues, including online communities, mental health professionals providing advice, and people sharing their experiences.

Study (1) reveals both Algerians and British young adults prefer using informal support through different activities contacting family, friends. However, there is a difference in their willingness to utilize this support. This emphasize the significance of initial mental health aid, placing the responsibility on family and friends who are often the first to recognize and acknowledge the onset of mental health issues, thereby aiding in the recovery process. The present study aligns

with the concept of mental health literacy and awareness, which is rooted in the mental health beliefs of different cultures, enabling young adults to seek professional help when necessary. This underscores the argument that mental health literacy of individuals empowers professionals to respond more effectively by offering suitable support, making referrals, and coordinating care for individuals facing mental health challenges (Murphy, Klug & Kasimatis, 2023). The validation of culturally informal interventions from family and friends underscores the reliance of Algerian and British young adults on these support systems, leading individuals to lean towards seeking professional support when needed.

The study 1 reveals a greater openness and awareness regarding mental health literacy in the United Kingdom, attributable to the availability of services and the individualistic nature of the culture. It was observed that the most preferred course of action for seeking assistance after interactions with family and friends is to seek professional help, given their expertise in psychological matters. This inclination stems from the fact that Western populations tend to possess greater medical knowledge of mental disorders compared to non-Western populations (Altweck et al., 2015). The comfort and transparency in engaging with mental health or utilizing mental health services within one's cultural context were notably emphasized within British society. However, there were also negative outcomes observed within Western communities concerning the utilization of mental health services. Broader challenges such as the cost and accessibility of mental health care, including high out-of-pocket expenses and long wait times for services (Baker & Kirk-Wade, 2024), may contribute to disparities in who can access and utilize mental health support. This underscores the complex interplay between the cultural landscape in delivering mental health services and the reception of mental health concerns within the British community.

In contrast, there is a noticeable reticence on the topic of mental health within Algerian society. The reliance on informal mental health support also demonstrates a negative impact on help-

seeking behaviours. This preference for informal support in Algeria and other Arab cultures can be attributed to factors such as low mental health literacy, stigma, and the significant role of family and society in Arab culture when it comes to addressing psychological issues (Al-Shannaq & Aldalaykeh, 2023). Algerian society exhibits significant stigma towards mental health issues, where traditional cultural beliefs about the causes of mental illness, such as possession by spirits (Jinn), evil eye, jealousy, heavily influence how individuals perceive and approach such challenges. This stigma and lack of acceptance of mental illness within the society have resulted in the neglect of mental health problems. Mental illness stigma acts as a major barrier to seeking help in Algeria, primarily due to the influence of religion and traditional beliefs. Previous research by Ihsan al-Issa has indicated that cultural factors, including the Muslim religion and social changes, are correlated with the rates and symptoms of mental illness in Algeria, with traditional beliefs about causes like spirit possession playing a significant role (Al-Issa, 1990). This underscores the necessity for modern, destigmatized approaches to mental health care in Algeria. Cultural and spiritual explanations for mental health problems may be more prevalent in the Algerian context, with religion playing a crucial role in the pathway to mental health care. The first research study makes a compelling case for culturally competent mental health care by providing a comprehensive understanding of the cultural perspectives affecting mental health care among young adults in Algeria and the UK. Despite an increasing awareness of the importance of spirituality in mental health Algerian contexts, there exists a 'religiosity gap' in the United Kingdom, where the value placed on spirituality and religion differs among British young adults. There is a disconnection between religiosity and spirituality and its relation to mental health issues among British young adults and their society. This gap may stem from a lack of understanding about the complex ways people connect with spirituality within contemporary society and mental health contexts, potentially resulting in the neglect of people's spiritual needs.

Study one highlights the contrasting approaches to mental health services between Algerian collectivist culture and British individualistic culture. It emphasizes that the key distinction lies in the utilization of professionals versus traditional healing methods, particularly through religious practices. In Algeria, the role of religious leaders in treating mental health issues is significant, whereas in the UK, individuals are more inclined to seek help from mental health professionals due to a culture of openness. This difference is attributed to the cultural characteristics of individualism and collectivism, which significantly influence people's psychological thoughts and actions. British young adults prioritize seeking professional help outside their immediate social circles, while Algerian culture places importance on family unity in addressing mental health issues, leading individuals to seek guidance from religious leaders rather than mental health professionals.

Study 2 investigates the widespread acceptance of non-professional treatment recommended by religious leaders in both the United Kingdom and Algeria. It examines the belief systems within Muslim communities, specifically regarding Islamic traditions related to mental health and how individuals seek assistance from religious leaders across various cultures through imam's lens. It emphasizes on the role of western British and Arab Algerian imams and their perspectives about the Islamic therapy and that to shed the light on the Islamic psychotherapy between Muslims in the west and Arab cultures. The study offers new perspectives on the contribution of Islam to mental health support, particularly through insights from religious leaders in Algeria and the United Kingdom, an area that has not been extensively explored in previous research. Within Algerian and British Muslim communities, religious support plays a significant role, encompassing practices such as Quranic recitation, prayers, and Ruqyah (Islamic spiritual healing). Religious leaders are involved in providing guidance for treatment, with these practices often incorporating Quranic verses as integral components in addressing mental health issues. The study underscores the importance of translated Quranic verses in

offering mental health guidance, highlighting the integration of religious teachings with mental health support and the Quran's central role in promoting overall well-being among Muslims. This help reduce the information gap in the west and Islam even in the Arab culture which open opportunities of research and cooperation between Muslims and Arabs Islamic psychotherapists and psychologists thus enhancing the global understanding and cooperation.

The study 2 highlights the multifaceted role of imams within both Algerian and British Muslim communities, which extends beyond their traditional religious duties. Imams are regarded as community leaders and actively engage in addressing various social and personal issues, including mental health concerns. Study (2) reveals a disparity in training between Algerian and British imams regarding mental health issues. Both Algerian and British imams exhibit a lack of training in this area. As Algerian imams tend to connect mental health issues directly with spiritual matters, favouring methods like Roqyah Shariya for treatment. In contrast, British imams they prefer not to deal with mental health issues who prefer encouraging their Muslim community members to seek professional help for mental health concerns.

Study 2 provides a comprehensive examination of Islamic psychotherapy by imams, emphasizing its association with mental health in Algerian and British societies. The proficiency of Algerian imams in utilizing spiritual therapy underscores their adeptness in addressing mental health issues among Muslims. The study reveals that Islamic therapy has predominantly led to positive outcomes in the mental well-being of Muslims, contrasting with British imams who exhibit a lack of familiarity with evaluating the effectiveness of Roqya, as it is not a primary focus in their mosques. This investigation emphasizes the incorporation of religious therapy into psychotherapy, showcasing divergent viewpoints between Algerian and British imams. British imams typically adopt a professional approach towards mental health problems, integrating religion where applicable but referring severe cases to specialized professionals, acknowledging that religion alone may not suffice in such instances. Conversely,

Algerian imams advocate for Islamic psychotherapy as the primary intervention for mental health concerns, seamlessly integrating it into psychotherapeutic practices. The research highlights the significant impact of Islamic psychotherapy in conferring meaning and direction to life in Algerian culture when compared to the British Muslim culture, which predominantly adheres to Western medical practices regardless of religious convictions. This duality in approach can present challenges and opportunities in accessing mental health services, contingent upon whether religious leaders perceive such issues as solely mental health-related or as spiritual dilemmas. The divergence in treatment strategies for mental health problems among religious leaders within their respective communities indicates varying levels of treatment effectiveness. Islamic psychotherapy is not contradictory to modern methodologies but rather can complement psychotherapy particularly in Algeria. While in the British Muslim community professionals must comprehend the religious and spiritual dimensions of patients' requirements, while religious leaders should also grasp Muslim diagnoses to ensure suitable referrals. It is advisable to have a comprehensive understanding of both the medical and religious perspectives of individuals among religious leaders and healthcare professionals.

Study 2 further endorses the partnership between religious figures in society and mental health professionals to incorporate it into their healing and treatment programs. The study highlighted differences between Algeria and the United Kingdom, with the UK offering more mental health services compared to other countries (WHO, 20011). This availability of services plays a crucial role in recognizing culturally competent services from non-Western backgrounds, which is essential for effective and fair service delivery, especially in healthcare settings (Lau & Rodgers, 2021). Cultural competence refers to a set of consistent behaviours, attitudes, and policies that converge in a system, agency, or among professionals, enabling them to work effectively in cross-cultural situations (Cross, 1989). It involves the capacity of systems to

provide care to patients with diverse values, beliefs, and behaviours, while customizing delivery to meet their social, cultural, and linguistic needs (Btancourt, Green & Carrillo, 2002). Study 2 indicates that religion does not hinder seeking treatment for mental health issues; instead, it encourages Muslims to seek help, as the Quran contains numerous verses advocating seeking help when needed. Moreover, imams in mosques play a role in raising awareness about mental health and reducing stigma through lessons. Collaborating with professionals during imams' sessions in the mosque could be beneficial in such scenarios. Addressing a challenge identified in the UK, a recent study involving twenty-two psychiatrists (Durà-Vilà et al., 2011) revealed that none of them routinely integrated religious aspects into mental health assessments. Although UK professionals may not possess extensive knowledge about Islam and its practices in mental health treatment, they should consider the narratives and interpretations of mental health issues from Muslim perspectives, as personal faith is integral to understanding their experiences. It is crucial for mental health services and professionals, to acknowledge and respect Muslim religious and cultural beliefs. On the other hand, Algerian religious leaders should be more accessible to professionals in Algeria to facilitate referrals and help their community access appropriate mental health care, thus combating the taboo surrounding discussions on mental health. Consequently, mental health professionals in both Algeria and the United Kingdom must be mindful of maintaining clear boundaries in therapeutic relationships while addressing religious matters. Collaborative initiatives between religious leaders and mental health professionals have the potential to enhance access to existing mental health services and streamline the help-seeking process, ultimately boosting future service utilization. A potential outcome of this study could involve training professionals and religious leaders in both religion and mental health care across various settings, including mosques and mental health services.

6.1 Contribution to the Field and Directions for Future Research:

To the best of my knowledge, no prior research has been conducted in Algeria to investigate the diverse experiences of young adults dealing with mental health difficulties in two distinct cultures (Arab and Western) in the digital era. The research on mental health experiences of young adults in Algeria is mostly based on very limited literature and data. In 1990, Ihsan El Issa was from the few researchers in Algeria who spoke about mental illness and its relationship to culture. He reviewed the association between cultural factors and symptoms of mental illness in Algeria. Two major sociocultural factors related to mental illness was emphasised in his research: the Muslim religion and social changes during both the colonial and post-colonial eras. However, most of the previous research on mental health has given priority on the effect of colonialism on mental health after the independence of Algeria 1962 and in the period of black decade between (1989-1999). There have not been extensive epidemiological studies in Algeria, but many psychiatrists have conducted local or regional investigations on different themes like depression, suicide, psychosis, and anxiety (Benmebarek, 2017). However, more work is needed to reform mental health research in Algeria. Future research can focus on mental health education and support among parents and teachers to show them how to help children and young people with mental health issues (this can be done via questionnaires or face-to-face interviews if all participants agree). Additionally, to how integrative care can improve education, mental and physical health, as well as social interaction for children and adolescents.

To understand the adolescents and young adults' mental health challenges in Algerian and British cultures there should be rich mine of information in future research. It is important not to make too many generalizations from the results. The results are specific to young adults aged between 18 and 24, in different cities in two different geographical areas, and should not be extrapolated out to include the whole country. There are too many variables: all provinces,

cities, characteristics, social norms and even languages. It is recommended different cities of Algeria and United Kingdom to be included in any future research. To the best of my knowledge, no prior research has been conducted comparing the role of religious leaders in providing Islamic psychotherapy in both Algeria and the United Kingdom. This research would explore the importance and utilization of Islamic psychotherapy, which shares common principles in both Western British and Islamic Algerian communities. It would also examine differences in cultural context, approaches to mental health, the role of religious leaders, and the importance of integration with formal services, shaping the practice and delivery of Islamic psychotherapy in each setting.

Such a study could help prioritize mental health research in both Western and non-Western societies, thus enabling society to better support individuals with mental health problems. Research in mental health saves lives by improving our entire society and contributing to the alleviation of severe distress, ultimately enhancing overall quality of life.

6.2 Recommendations in religious and professional mental health care system:

- Despite some strides in infrastructure, resources, and legislative efforts, mental health in Algeria remains overlooked in public health policies due to inadequate service coverage.
- The promotion and management of mental health demand a significant shift in practices and attitudes, necessitating a multidisciplinary and coordinated approach.
- Urgent attention is needed for extensive epidemiological research and studies on mental health in Algeria. Similarly, further investigation into the role of religious leaders in providing Islamic-based mental health support is essential in the UK.
- It is imperative to assess the knowledge and capabilities of religious leaders in addressing mental health issues among Muslims from various cultural backgrounds.

- Comprehensive mental health education and training should be provided to community religious leaders, such as imams, in both Algeria and the UK. This training would enable them to collaborate effectively with mental health professionals and expand beyond traditional healing methods.
- Improving access to religious support services within mental health care systems is critical in both countries which can facilitate existential recovery and foster stronger connections between religious communities and mental health services, overcoming cultural and religious barriers to care.
- Western mental health professionals should receive training in engaging with diverse communities to enhance cultural competence. This training would familiarize them with Muslim beliefs about mental health and ensure accurate diagnoses without overlooking the significance of religion in patients' lives.

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Appendices List

Appendix A: Interview Study 01

Title of Project: Young adults' mental health experiences in different cultures in the digital age: Case of Algeria and United Kingdom.

Ethics Approval Number: 13922

Researcher name: NADIA BENGHAFFOR

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

PART01: Culture and mental health experiences

- 1) What does mental health mean to you?
- 1) Could you mention three signs of mental health issues you know?
- 2) How could you know that you have a mental health issue? How would you face it?
- 3) What are the coping strategies you do to handle your mental health problems?
- 4) How do you seek help when you have poor mental health wellbeing?
- 5) How would you describe dealing with mental health problems in your society?
- 6) How might the experience of mental health issues differ between individuals in Arab countries and Western countries, if at all?
- 7) What is your opinion about stigmatisation in your society against people with mental health problems?
- 8) What is the advice do you hear usually when you have an overwhelming mental health problem?
- 9) What beliefs and perceptions do you think play a significant role in supporting mental health within your society?

10) What actions would you take to help someone who's exhibiting signs and symptoms of mental health issues?

PART02: Social media and mental health

- 1) How do you generally share your mental health challenges with others? Why?
- 2) How important is social media in your life?
- 3) What is the difference between communicating about mental health issues online and in person? Justify your response.
- 4) Identify an online activity that you do on a regular basis: What emotions does it elicit in you? What makes you feel that way?
- 5) Think about your own social media use. What activities do you do which supports your mental health?
- 6) How does using social media platforms affect your mood?
- 7) How does online communication influence your interactions in real life?
- 8) How would you describe social media's impact on your mental health?
- 9) How frequently do you post about your mental health issues on social media?
- 10) How do you perceive the role of social media in relation to your mental health?

الجزء 01: الثقافة وخبرات الصحة النفسية

(1) ماذا تعني لك الصحة النفسية؟

(1) هل يمكنك ذكر ثلاث علامات لمشاكل الصحة العقلية التي تعرفها؟

(2) كيف تعرف أن لديك مشكلة تتعلق بالصحة العقلية؟ كيف ستواجهها؟

(3) ما هي استراتيجيات المواجهة التي تقوم بها للتعامل مع مشكلات الصحة العقلية؟

- (4) كيف تطلب المساعدة عندما تكون صحتك النفسية سيئة؟
- (5) كيف تصف التعامل مع مشاكل الصحة العقلية في مجتمعك؟
- (6) هل تعتقد أن هناك فرقاً بين المعاناة من مشاكل الصحة النفسية في الدول العربية والمقاطعة الغربية؟ إذا كان الجواب نعم ، ما هو الفرق؟
- (7) ما رأيك في وصم مجتمعك للأشخاص الذين يعانون من مشاكل نفسية؟
- (8) ما هي النصائح التي تسمعها عادة عندما تكون لديك مشكلة صحية نفسية؟
- (9) ما هي المعتقدات والتصورات الأكثر أهمية في مجتمعك لدعم الصحة النفسية؟
- (10) ما الإجراءات التي يجب أن تتخذها لمساعدة شخص تظهر عليه علامات وأعراض مشكلات الصحة العقلية؟

الجزء 02: وسائل التواصل الاجتماعي والصحة العقلية

- (1) كيف تشارك تحديات صحتك العقلية مع الآخرين بشكل عام؟ لماذا؟
- (2) ما هو الدور الذي تلعبه وسائل التواصل الاجتماعي في حياتك؟
- (3) ما الفرق بين التواصل مع مشاكل الصحة العقلية عبر الإنترنت وفي الحياة الواقعية؟ برر جوابك.
- (4) حدد نشاطاً عبر الإنترنت تشارك فيه بانتظام: ما هو شعورك؟ لماذا يجعلك تشعر بهذه الطريقة؟
- (5) فكر في استخدامك لوسائل التواصل الاجتماعي. ما هي الأنشطة التي تقوم بها والتي تدعم صحتك العقلية؟
- (6) كيف يتغير مزاجك عند استخدام منصات التواصل الاجتماعي؟
- (7) كيف يؤثر الاتصال عبر الإنترنت على تفاعلك في العالم الحقيقي؟
- (8) كيف يمكنك وصف تأثير وسائل التواصل الاجتماعي على صحتك العقلية؟
- (9) كم مرة تشارك مشاكل الصحة العقلية الخاصة بك على وسائل التواصل الاجتماعي؟
- (10) كيف يمكن أن تساعدك وسائل التواصل الاجتماعي في دعم صحتك العقلية؟

Appendix B: Participants recruitment letter

Dear (Participant name),

I hope my email finds you well. I am Nadia, a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland. I am conducting research that discusses "Young adults' mental health experiences in different cultures in the digital age: Algeria and the United Kingdom".

The proposed study aims to explore the cultural differences in experiencing and expressing mental health issues among Algerian and UK young adults. Moreover, this research project seeks to gain a better understanding of the role social media plays as a potentially viable intervention for those struggling with poor mental health by understanding how young people talk about their mental health through social media. In addition, understanding how they might use social media as a means of peer support could provide significant input into developing tools to improve mental health outcomes in this population.

For this reason, I am kindly requesting you to participate in an interview to answer some of the questions related to the objective. the interview would take 30 to 60 minutes.

for further information, please read the participants' information sheet.

If you have any questions let me know

if you feel that you are interested in taking part in this research, please sign the consent form and send it back to me.

Thank you very much,

Nadia BENGHAFFOR

Appendix C: Consent form study 01

Title of Project: Young adults' mental health experiences in different cultures in the digital age: Algeria and United Kingdom.

Ethics Approval Number: 13922

Researcher name: NADIA BENGHAFFOR

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

This is a consent form for a PhD research project entitled: Young adults' mental health experiences in different cultures in the digital age: Algeria and United Kingdom. It is a research project at the University of the West of Scotland carried out by the principal investigator (Nadia Benghaffor). By completing this form and agreeing to give your full consent, you agree that you have read and understood the participant information sheet and understand what is being asked of you in this study.

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm your agreement:

	Initial below:
I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet and instruction sheet for the study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time up to one month after completing the study without giving any reason.	
I understand that the information I give is confidential and any publication resulting from this work will not identify me personally.	
I consent to the processing of my personal information (<i>age, sex, and contact details</i>) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.	
I agree to have my voice/likeness digitally recorded.	
I freely agree to participate in this study.	

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals):

Name of researcher (block capitals):

NADIA BENGHAFFOR

Date:

Date:

Signature:

Signature:

نموذج الموافقة المستنيرة للبحث

عنوان المشروع: تجارب الصحة العقلية للشباب في ثقافات مختلفة في العصر الرقمي. الحالة: الجزائر والمملكة المتحدة.

رقم الموافقة الأخلاقية: 2020-

أسماء المحققين: نادية بن غفور

البريد الإلكتروني للباحث: [REDACTED]

هذا نموذج موافقة لمشروع بحث دكتوراه بعنوان: تجارب الصحة العقلية للشباب في ثقافات مختلفة في العصر الرقمي: حالة الجزائر والمملكة المتحدة. هو مشروع بحثي في جامعة غرب اسكتلندا نفذته الباحثة الرئيسية (نادية بن غفور). من خلال إكمال هذا النموذج والموافقة على منح موافقتك الكاملة ، فإنك توافق على أنك قد قرأت وفهمت ورقة معلومات المشارك وفهمت ما هو مطلوب منك في هذه الدراسة.

يُرجى قراءة العبارات التالية ، وإذا وافقت ، فقم بوضع الأحرف الأولى في المربع المقابل لتأكيد موافقتك:

الأولي أدناه:	
أؤكد أنني قد قرأت وفهمت ورقة معلومات المشارك وورقة التعليمات الخاصة بالدراسة. لقد أتيت لي الفرصة للنظر في المعلومات وطرح الأسئلة وأجابت على هذه الأسئلة بشكل مرض.	
أفهم أن مشاركتي طوعية وأني حر في الانسحاب في أي وقت لمدة تصل إلى شهر واحد بعد إكمال الدراسة دون إبداء أي سبب	
أفهم أن المعلومات التي أقدمها سرية وأن أي منشور ناتج عن هذا العمل لن يحددني شخصياً.	
أوافق على معالجة معلوماتي الشخصية (العمر والجنس وبيانات الاتصال) للأغراض الموضحة لي. أفهم أنه سيتم التعامل مع هذه المعلومات وفقاً لجميع تشريعات حماية البيانات المعمول بها.	
أوافق على تسجيل صوتي / تشابهي رقمياً.	
أوافق بحرية على المشاركة في هذه الدراسة.	أوافق

اسم الباحث (الأحرف الكبيرة):

التاريخ:

التوقيع:

اسم المشارك (الأحرف الكبيرة):

التاريخ: 14/09/2021

التوقيع:

Appendix D: Ethical approval Letter

04/08/2021

Dear Nadia Benghaffor,

Your application 16636: Young adults' mental health experiences in different cultures in the digital age: Algeria and United Kingdom., submission 13922, has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study, you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them. The following comments made by reviewers are intended to improve the study: Naturally the content of the interviews will be emotive, but so long as the participants are happy to engage with such topics this will be fine. The only potential element raised by this reviewer, is the suggestions for mental health support in the debrief. The researchers need to provide a few suggestions of official organisations that provide information and or support regarding mental health for participants of both countries / languages.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Iain McPhee

Appendix E: Study 01 Information sheet

Title of Project: Young adults' mental health experiences in different cultures in the digital age: Algeria and United Kingdom.

Ethics Approval Number: 13922

Researcher name: NADIA BENGHAFFOR

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of this study is to explore how mental health challenges is experienced and expressed by young adults in different cultures. Moreover, to shed the light on the role of social media play in promoting a good psychological wellbeing.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are a young person (late adolescence 18-24 years old) that may experience symptoms of poor mental health, but do not have a diagnosis. We aim to interview youngsters from different cultural background (Algeria or the United Kingdom.).

Do I have to take part?

No, participation in this study is voluntary. It is up to you to decide whether to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. You are still free to withdraw, but you should let the principal investigator know that you want to withdraw without any pressure. You have up to one-month post-interview to ask your data to be withdrawn. You will be given time to ask questions and address any concern in the interview process. You will be asked to withdraw at any point in the interview questions if the questions affect your emotional health status or cause any psychological or physical harm. The participant sheet information will be provided in both Arabic and English languages.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you decide to take part, you will be asked to answer questions in an individual interview regarding your personal experience in your society while having a mental health problem including difficulties in expressing or sharing challenges you faced with mental health. Furthermore, to break the taboo around mental health issues and opening up your struggles which make others also feel less alone and encourage them to speak about their mental health issues in turn, it also helps by allowing yourself ask for and accept help and you have the opportunity to be open minded speaking about psychological wellbeing and issues related to mental health. The study will take around 30 to 60 minutes.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

While we hope that your experience will be pleasant, there are no obvious disadvantages of taking part in the study. However, asking about your mental health issues experiences may make you uncomfortable, at any time in the interview you can choose to withdraw.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

As a participant, you will help the researcher to identify how experiencing and expressing mental health problems among young adults vary from culture to another and how social media could be a source of help in the digital age. You will help the research in identifying questions that may be missed or not prioritise. Involving you in the research study can help you to bridge the gaps of speaking about mental health openly. Furthermore, the experience may be life enhancing for example it may help with personal development including increase of confidence and self-esteem and the belief that your views matter and can bring a change to the society.it can help researchers to stay mindful of young people perspectives on the research agenda and process.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Emma Cockrow and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project. If we are able to anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data, you provide we will undertake this and will endeavour to minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible. Or we will anonymise or

pseudonymise the personal data you provide by the first week of the study and all data will be anonymised when analysed. If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

If you agree to participate in this project, once the data will be collected it will be analysed and written as a UWS PhD thesis. The researcher will Share research findings with the participants at the end of a study which will proves feedback to participants on the outcome of the research to which they have contributed. Furthermore, the thesis version will be published online to facilitate its use for future research. All data will remain anonymous.

Who has reviewed the study?

ESS Ethics Committee

Contact for further information.

If you require any further information, please contact:

Researcher: Nadia BENGHAFFOR
University of the West of Scotland,
High Street,
Paisley,
PA1 2BE
UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Research Supervisor: Lucy TROUP
University of the West of Scotland,
High Street,
Paisley,
PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Thank you for taking part in this study.

Appendix F: Debrief sheet Study 01

Title of Project: Young adults' mental health experiences in different cultures in the digital age: Algeria and United Kingdom.

Ethics Approval Number: 13922

Researcher name: NADIA BENGHAFFOR

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

Thank you for participating in my research.

This research study is a part of my doctoral research at the University of the West of Scotland. Thank you for your valuable time. I greatly appreciate your willingness to meet with me for an individual interview and to share your thoughts about your experiences. Your contributions and responses will offer valued information which will be extremely useful and helpful to improve knowledge for all of us.

Culture influences mental health in various ways and constrains how emotions are felt and expressed in a given cultural context. This research has tended to understand how young people experience mental health challenges in Arab and western countries especially within the rise of social media as a result of the digital revolution. Furthermore, it aims to explore how social media help improve mental health of young adults.

The information you will provide in the interview will be held anonymously. As outlined in the information sheet, if you have any questions or comments for more clear explanation please feel free to contact me: [REDACTED]

Again, thank you so very much for your participation for your time and efforts that made this research study possible.

Contact Information:

Principal Researcher: Nadia Benghaffor
University of the West of Scotland,
High Street, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Contact Information of Mental health services in Algeria and UK:

United Kingdom:

Samaritans: Available 24 hours a day to provide confidential emotional support for people who are experiencing feeling of distress, despair, or suicidal thoughts.

Website: www.samaritans.org

Location: 116 123 (free to call from within the UK and Ireland)

Email: [REDACTED]

Algeria (Algiers):

Cabinet Meriem Hamia Psychologue

Psychologist: Meriem Hamia

Location: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Website: <https://web.facebook.com/meriemhamia>

Appendix G: Questionnaire Study02

Dear Sir

I would like to ask you for a few minutes of your time to fill out the questionnaire, which will be anonymous and used only for research purposes. Your answers are a valuable source of information and useful to investigate the role of the imam in promoting mental health among Muslims in Arab and western cultures. I would like to thank you for your availability and valuable collaboration. At the same time, I would like to notify you that I will be pleased to inform you of future initiatives to disseminate or present the results of the research that will be promoted after the survey. Please write the appropriate response in front of each question.

Demographic information:

Title.

Name:

Age:

Current Position:

Ethnicity:

Status:

- Married:
- Children:
- Single:

Education:

What is your level of education?

- Bachelor
- Master
- PhD
- Other Certificate:

Where did you study?

- Mosque
- University
- Other: (please extend your answer)

Do you hold a degree in Islamic studies? If so, could you please name it?

- Yes
- No

How many years you have been an imam?

- Less than 1 year
- 1 year
- 2 years
- 3 years
- More: (mention)

Do you offer mental health support in the mosque?

- Yes
- No
- If yes, could you please name your lessons:

Do you have another Career rather than an Imam?

- Yes
- No
- If yes, could you please mention it:

.....

Where is your mosque located? Could you please tell me what it is named?

.....

Knowledge:

What does be an imam mean to you?

.....
.....
.....

What does the word mental health mean to you?

.....
.....
.....

Can you identify a Surah or Ayah that describes mental health in the Quran? Can you please list it here?

.....
.....

Do you think religious beliefs can use to help support mental health? If so, can you describe how?

.....
.....
.....

What is your role in the mosque?

- Muslim guidance
- Salah (Prayers)
- Teach people about Quran
- Spiritual therapy
- Other:

What is the role Islamic religion plays in supporting mental health?

.....
.....

.....
.....

Experiences:

According to you, what do Muslims believe about mental health?

.....
.....
.....
.....

How often have you dealt with Muslims with mental health issues?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

How often do you deliver lessons about mental health in khutbah el Jummuha?

- Once a week
- Once a month
- Twice a month
- Few times every few months
- Seldom
- Never
- Other (mention):

Which of these groups seeks mental health advice?

Groups	Women	men
Adolescents		
Young Adults		
Adults		
Families		

What kind of issues do you usually receive from your community? (You can choose more than one answer)

- Social Issues
- Family issues
- Personal issues
- Material issues
- Psychological distress
- Spiritual issues
- Religious issues
- Others: (mention)

Are you familiar with mental health issues types and symptoms?

- Yes
- No

What were the types of mental health issues you dealt with?

- Depression
- Anxiety
- Paranoia
- Other: (Mention)

What were the symptoms you observe in mentally ill Muslims who approach you? (You can choose more than one answer)

- Feeling sad or down
- Overthinking
- Excessive stress
- Physical illness
- Excessive fears or worries, or extreme feelings of guilt.
- Withdrawal from social life
- Low energy or problems sleeping.
- Other: (Mention)

What are the challenges you face as an imam with people with mental health issues?

- Communication skills
- Leadership skills
- Guidance skills

What would you recommend for Muslims with mental health issues? (You can choose more than one answer)

- I would directly use Roquia
- I would recommend visiting mental health professional affiliated with our religious denomination
- I would reassure you if it is mental health issues or spiritual issues
- I would encourage them for more intensive prayers
- I would involve mental health issues as a part of spiritual issues and start using Roqia
- I would recommend practising sport
- Prescribing herbs
- Other:

Treatment Effectiveness

How do you solve Muslim Dilemmas?

- Quranic passages and hadith
- Sharing personal experiences
- Sharing prophets’ stories
- Encourage self-solving problems

What would you do to convince Muslims with mental health issues when they refuse to go to mental health professionals? You can choose more than one answer.

- Turning to Allah in prayer and supplication
- I would advise reading and listen to the Quran
- Seeking community support
- Engaging in prosocial behaviour (i.e. helping others)
- I would reassure them that the psychologist is more aware of the symptoms they face than me.
- I would recommend involving Sports activities and healthy habits
- I would recommend not involving mental health issues in a spiritual one
- Other:

Do you think that religiously integrated interventions are the only effective way of treating Muslims with mental health issues?

- Yes
- No

Please explain your choosing answer

.....
.....

Professionals' referral

What standards do you use to determine whether the treatment you provide to Muslims suffering from mental health problems is effective?

.....
.....
.....

How long does it take you to treat Muslims who have mental health or spiritual problems?

.....
.....

Did all who approach you refer you to a mental health professional?

- Yes
- No

If no (explain the reason why):

.....

Are you currently collaborating with professionals or mental health services?

- Yes
- No

If yes, could you please mention the name of the services you are collaborating with?

.....
.....

If not, could you please mention why?

.....
.....

Barriers to accessing mental health services

What is the central role of religiosity in Muslim mental health?

.....
.....
.....

According to you, how religion affects access to mental health services?

.....
.....
.....

Do you have any adequate training, stuffing, or resources about mental health in the mosque for urgent mental health cases?

- Yes
- No

Please explain your answer:

.....
.....

According to you what are the barriers that prevent Muslims with mental health issues access mental health services? (You can choose more than one answer)

- Ignorance and lack of knowledge
- Lack of family support
- Languages barriers
- Stigma
- Suspicions and mistrust therapies
- Wrong beliefs about professional mental health treatments
- Preferences to seek help from traditional healers
- Other: (mention)

How do you reduce the stigma against mental illness in your society?

- I would deliver lessons about stigma in the mosque
- I do not speak about stigma in my lessons.
- I use Quranic sayings about stigma.
- I do not know what is stigma

Thank you

استبيان

سيدي

أود أن أسألك عن بضع دقائق من وقتك لملء الاستبيان ، والذي من الواضح أنه سيكون مجهول الهوية ويستخدم فقط لأغراض البحث. إجاباتك هي مصدر قيم للمعلومات ومفيدة في تقصي دور الأئمة في تعزيز الصحة النفسية بين المسلمين في الثقافات العربية والغربية. أود أن أشكركم على توافركم وتعاونكم القيم. في الوقت نفسه ، أود أن أبلغكم أنه يسعدني أن أبلغكم بالمبادرات المستقبلية لنشر أو تقديم نتائج البحث الذي سيتم الترويج له في ختام الاستبيان

المعلومات الديموغرافية

عنوان:

اسم:

سن:

العمل:

عرق:

الحالة الاجتماعية

• متزوج :

• أطفال :

• غير مرتبط :

تعليم

ما هو مستواك التعليمي؟

• بكالوريوس

• درجة الماجستير

• دكتوراه

• شهادة أخرى :

• أين درست؟

• مسجد

• جامعة

• غير ذلك: (يرجى تمديد إجابتك)

هل تحمل شهادة في الدراسات الإسلامية؟ إذا كان الأمر كذلك ، هل يمكنك تسميته؟

• نعم

• لا على الإطلاق

• كم سنة كنت إماماً؟

• أقل من 1 سنة

• سنة 1

• سنتان

• سنوات 3

• المزيد: (أذكر)

هل تقدمون دعم الصحة النفسية في المسجد؟

• نعم

• لا على الإطلاق

• إذا كانت الإجابة بنعم ، فهل يمكنك من فضلك تسمية دروسك:

هل لديك مهنة أخرى غير إمام؟

• نعم

• لا على الإطلاق

• إذا كانت الإجابة بنعم ، هل يمكنك ذكر ذلك من فضلك :

أين يقع مسجدك؟ هل يمكن أن تخبرني من فضلك ما اسمه؟

معرفة

ماذا يعني لك الإمام؟

.....
.....
.....

ماذا تعني لك كلمة الصحة النفسية؟

.....
.....
.....

هل يمكنك تحديد سورة أو آية تصف الصحة النفسية في القرآن؟ هل يمكنك إدراجها هنا من فضلك؟

.....
.....
.....

هل تعتقد أن المعتقدات الدينية يمكن أن تساعد في دعم الصحة العقلية؟ إذا كان الأمر كذلك ، هل يمكنك أن تصف كيف؟

.....
.....
.....

ما هو دورك في المسجد؟

• الهداية الإسلامية

• صلاة

• تعليم الناس القرآن

• العلاج الروحي

• آخر :

ما هو الدور الذي يلعبه الدين الإسلامي في دعم الصحة النفسية؟

.....
.....

خبرة

حسب رأيك ، ما رأي المسلمين في الصحة النفسية؟

.....
.....

كم مرة تعاملت مع المسلمين بمشاكل نفسية؟

• أبداً

• بعض الأحيان

• عادة

• دائماً

كم مرة تقوم بإلقاء دروس حول الصحة النفسية في خطبة الجمعة؟

• مرة في الأسبوع

• مرة في الشهر

• مرتان شهرياً

• عدة مرات كل بضعة أشهر

• نادراً

• أبداً

• أخرى (أذكر)

أي من هذه المجموعات يسعى للحصول على مشورة الصحة العقلية؟

مجموعات	النساء	الرجال
المراهقون		
شباب		
الكبار		
العائلات		

ما نوع المشكلات التي تتلقاها عادة من مجتمعك؟ (يمكنك اختيار أكثر من إجابة واحدة)

- القضايا الاجتماعية
- مشاكل عائلية
- مشاكل شخصية
- القضايا المادية
- الضائقة النفسية
- القضايا الروحية
- القضايا الدينية
- أخرى:

هل أنت على دراية بأنواع مشاكل الصحة النفسية وأعراضها؟

• نعم

• لا على الإطلاق

ما هي أنواع مشكلات الصحة العقلية التي تعاملت معها؟

• كآبة

• قلق

• جنون العظمة

• أخرى:

ما هي الأعراض التي لاحظتها عند المسلمين المصابين بأمراض عقلية الذين يقترّبون منك؟ (يمكنك اختيار أكثر من إجابة واحدة)

• الشعور بالحزن أو الحزن

• التفكير الزائد عن اللازم

• الإجهاد المفرط

• مرض جسدي

• مخاوف أو مخاوف مفرطة ، أو الشعور بالذنب الشديد

• الانسحاب من الحياة الاجتماعية

• انخفاض الطاقة أو مشاكل النوم

• أخرى: (أذكر)

ما هي التحديات التي تواجهك بصفقتك إمامًا مع الأشخاص الذين يعانون من مشاكل نفسية؟

• مهارات التواصل

• مهارات القيادة

• مهارات التوجيه

بماذا تنصح المسلمين الذين يعانون من مشاكل نفسية؟ (يمكنك اختيار أكثر من إجابة واحدة)

• سأستخدم الرقية مباشرة

• أوصي بزيارة أخصائي الصحة العقلية المنتمين إلى طائفتنا الدينية

• أود أن أطمئن إذا كان الأمر يتعلق بقضايا الصحة العقلية أو القضايا الروحية

• أشجعهم على تكثيف الصلاة

• أود أن أشرك قضايا الصحة العقلية كجزء من القضايا الروحية وأبدأ في استخدام الرقية

• أوصي بممارسة الرياضة

• وصف الأعشاب

• آخر :

فعالية العلاج

كيف تحل معضلات المسلمين؟

• الآيات القرآنية والأحاديث النبوية

• تبادل الخبرات الشخصية

• مشاركة قصص الأنبياء

- التشجيع على حل المشكلات ذاتيًا
- ماذا ستفعل لإقناع المسلمين بمشاكل الصحة العقلية عندما يرفضون الذهاب إلى أخصائيي الصحة العقلية؟ يمكنك اختيار أكثر من إجابة؟
- الرجوع إلى الله في الصلاة والدعاء
- أنصح بقراءة القرآن والاستماع إليه
- السعي للحصول على دعم المجتمع
- الانخراط في سلوك اجتماعي إيجابي (أي مساعدة الآخرين)
- أود أن أطمئن إلى أن الأخصائي النفسي أكثر وعياً بالأعراض التي يواجهونها مني
- أوصي بإشراك الأنشطة الرياضية والعادات الصحية
- أوصي بعدم إشراك الروحانيات في قضايا الصحة العقلية
- آخر :
- هل تعتقد أن التدخلات الدينية المتكاملة ليست سوى وسيلة فعالة لعلاج المسلمين الذين يعانون من مشاكل الصحة العقلية؟
- نعم
- لا على الإطلاق
- يرجى توضيح اختيارك للإجابة

إحالة المتخصصين

ما هي المعايير التي تستخدمها لتحديد ما إذا كان العلاج الذي تقدمه للمسلمين الذين يعانون من مشاكل نفسية فعالاً؟

.....

.....

ما هي المدة التي تستغرقها في علاج المسلمين الذين يعانون من مشاكل نفسية أو روحية؟

.....

.....

هل قام كل من اتصل بك بإحالة أخصائي الصحة العقلية؟

•نعم

•لا على الإطلاق

:إذا كانت الإجابة بلا (اشرح السبب)

هل تتعاون حالياً مع متخصصين أو خدمات الصحة العقلية؟

•نعم

•لا على الإطلاق

إذا كانت الإجابة بنعم ، هل يمكنك ذكر اسم الخدمات التي تتعاون معها؟

إذا كانت الإجابة "لا" ، هل يمكنك ذكر السبب من فضلك؟

حواجز الوصول إلى خدمات الصحة النفسية

ما هو الدور المركزي للتدين في الصحة النفسية للمسلمين؟

.....

.....

حسب رأيك ، كيف يؤثر الدين على الوصول إلى خدمات الصحة النفسية؟

.....

.....

هل لديك أي تدريب أو موارد كافية حول الصحة النفسية في المسجد لحالات الصحة النفسية العاجلة؟

•نعم

•لا على الإطلاق

يرجى توضيح إجابتك:

حسب رأيك ، ما هي العوائق التي تمنع المسلمين الذين يعانون من مشاكل الصحة العقلية من الوصول إلى خدمات الصحة النفسية؟

(يمكنك اختيار أكثر من إجابة واحدة)

•الجهل وقلة المعرفة

- عدم وجود دعم الأسرة
- حواجز اللغات
- وصمه عار
- الشكوك وعدم الثقة في العلاجات
- المعتقدات الخاطئة حول علاجات الصحة النفسية المهنية
- تفضيلات طلب المساعدة من المعالجين التقليديين
- أخرى: (أذكر)
- كيف تقلل من وصمة العار ضد المرض النفسي في مجتمعك؟
- سأقوم بإعطاء دروس عن وصمة العار في المسجد
- أنا لا أتحدث عن وصمة العار في دروسي
- أستخدم أقوالاً قرآنية عن وصمة العار
- لا أعرف

شكرًا لك

Appendix H: Participants recruitment letter Study 02

El Salam Alaykum,

I hope my email finds you well. I am Nadia, a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland. I am conducting a study about "Imams' Roles and Experiences in Promoting Muslims' Mental Health: The Case of Algeria and the United Kingdom."

The proposed study aims to investigate how imams provide mental health support from an Islamic religious perspective in Algeria and the UK, as well as acknowledge their understanding of mental illnesses and spiritual issues.

For this reason, I am kindly requesting that you participate in completing a questionnaire to answer some of the equations related to the aforementioned objective. The questionnaire would take 20 to 45 minutes.

For further information, please read the participants' information sheet.

If you have any questions, let me know.

If you feel that you are interested in taking part in this research, please sign the consent form and send it back to me.

PS: I would be grateful if you could kindly pass the questionnaire on to any imams that may be interested in participating.

Thank you very much,

Nadia BENGHAFFOR

Appendix H: Consent form Study 02

Title of Project: Imams' roles and experiences in promoting Muslims mental health:
Algeria and the United Kingdom

Ethics Approval Number: 16234

Researcher name: NADIA BENGHAFFOR

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

This is a consent form for a PhD research project entitled Imams role and experiences in promoting Muslims mental health in different cultures: Algeria and United Kingdom. It is a research project at the University of the West of Scotland carried out by the principle investigator (Nadia Benghaffor). By completing this form and agreeing to give your full consent, you agree that you have read and understood the participant information sheet and understand what is being asked of you in this study.

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm your agreement:

	Initial below:
I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet and instruction sheet for the study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time up to one month after completing the study without giving any reason.	
I understand that the information I give is confidential and any publication resulting from this work will not identify me personally.	
I consent to the processing of my personal information (<i>age, sex, and contact details</i>) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.	
I agree to have my voice/likeness digitally recorded.	
I freely agree to participate in this study.	

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals):

Name of researcher (block capitals):

NADIA BENGHAFFOR

Date:

Date:

Signature:

Signature:

نموذج الموافقة المستنيرة للبحث

عنوان المشروع: دور الأئمة وخبراتهم في تعزيز الصحة النفسية للمسلمين في مختلف الثقافات: الجزائر والمملكة المتحدة.

رقم الموافقة الأخلاقية: 2020-

أسماء المحققين: نادية بن غفور

البريد الإلكتروني للباحث: [REDACTED]

هذه استمارة موافقة لمشروع بحث دكتوراه بعنوان دور الأئمة وخبراتهم في تعزيز الصحة النفسية للمسلمين في مختلف الثقافات: الجزائر والمملكة المتحدة. هو مشروع بحثي في جامعة غرب اسكتلندا نفذته الباحثة الرئيسية (نادية بن غفور). من خلال إكمال هذا النموذج والموافقة على منح موافقتك الكاملة ، فإنك توافق على أنك قد قرأت وفهمت ورقة معلومات المشارك وفهمت ما هو مطلوب منك في هذه الدراسة. يُرجى قراءة العبارات التالية ، وإذا وافقت ، فقم بوضع الأحرف الأولى في المربع المقابل لتأكيد موافقتك:

الأولي أدناه:	
أؤكد أنني قد قرأت وفهمت ورقة معلومات المشارك وورقة التعليمات الخاصة بالدراسة. لقد أتيت لي الفرصة للنظر في المعلومات وطرح الأسئلة وأجابت على هذه الأسئلة بشكل مرض.	
أفهم أن مشاركتي طوعية وأنني حر في الانسحاب في أي وقت لمدة تصل إلى شهر واحد بعد إكمال الدراسة دون إبداء أي سبب	
أفهم أن المعلومات التي أقدمها سرية وأن أي منشور ناتج عن هذا العمل لن يحددني شخصياً.	
أوافق على معالجة معلوماتي الشخصية (العمر والجنس وبيانات الاتصال) للأغراض الموضحة لي. أفهم أنه سيتم التعامل مع هذه المعلومات وفقاً لجميع تشريعات حماية البيانات المعمول بها.	
أوافق على تسجيل صوتي / تشابهي رقمياً.	
أوافق بحرية على المشاركة في هذه الدراسة.	

--	--

اسم الباحث (الأحرف الكبيرة): NADIA BENGHAFFOR

التاريخ:

التوقيع:

اسم المشارك (الأحرف الكبيرة):

التاريخ:

التوقيع:

Appendix I: Ethical approval letter Study 02

27/01/2023

Dear RESCHED1 Nadia Benghaffor,

Your application 21078: Imams' roles and experiences in promoting Muslims mental health: Algeria and the United Kingdom, submission 16234, has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study, you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them. The reviewers have made some suggestions that you might want to discuss with your supervisor before data collection commences.

Dr, Lucy Troup

Appendix J: Information sheet study 02

Title of Project: Imams' roles and experiences in promoting Muslims mental health: Algeria and the United Kingdom

Ethics Approval Number: 16234

Researcher name: NADIA BENGHAFFOR

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of this research is to investigate the role of imams in promoting mental health, as well as their knowledge and experiences with Muslims who have mental health issues in two different cultures (Algeria and the United Kingdom).

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are an imam aged between (30 to 60 years old) to explore your role in promoting mental health among Muslims and your knowledge and experiences treating people with mental health issues. We intend to question imams from various cultural background (Algeria or the United Kingdom.)

Do I have to take part?

No, participation in this study is voluntary. It is up to you to decide whether to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. You are still free to withdraw, but you should let the principal investigator know that you want to withdraw without any pressure. You have up to one month to ask your data to be withdrawn. You will be given time to ask questions and address any concern during the process of answering the questions. You will be asked to withdraw at any point if the questions affect your

emotional health status or cause any psychological or physical harm. The participant sheet information will be provided in both Arabic and English languages.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you decide to take part, you will be asked to fill out questionnaires about your role and personal experience in your society with treating Muslims with mental health issues, as well as the difficulties that Muslims face when dealing with mental health challenges that they consider spiritual issues. Furthermore, to break the taboo around professional and opening up struggles which make others also feel less alone and encourage them to speak about their mental health issues in turn. It also helps by allowing you as an imam to collaborate with professionals and mental health services. The study will take around 15 to 30 minutes.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

While we hope that your experience will be pleasant, there are no obvious disadvantages of taking part in the study. However, asking about your mental health issues experiences may make you uncomfortable, at any time in the interview you can choose to withdraw.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

As a participant, you will help the researcher to identify how experiencing and expressing mental health problems among Muslims vary from culture to another and how social media could be a source of help in the digital age. You will help the research in identifying questions that may be missed or not prioritise. Involving you in the research study can help you to bridge the gaps of speaking about mental health openly. Furthermore, the experience may be life enhancing for example it may help with personal development including increase of confidence and self-esteem and the belief that your views matter and can bring a change to the society. It can help researchers to stay mindful of young people perspectives on the research agenda and process.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Emma Cockrow and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project. If we are able to anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provide we will undertake this and will endeavour to

minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible. Or we will anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provide by the first week of the study and all data will be anonymised when analysed. If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

If you agree to participate in this project, once the data will be collected it will be analysed and written as a UWS PhD thesis. The researcher will Share research findings with the participants at the end of a study which will proves feedback to participants on the outcome of the research to which they have contributed. Furthermore, the thesis version will be published online to facilitate its use for future research. All data will remain anonymous.

Who has reviewed the study?

ESS Ethics Committee

Contact for further information.

If you require any further information, please contact:

Researcher: Nadia BENGHAFFOR
University of the West of Scotland,
High Street,
Paisley,
PA1 2BE
UK

Telephone: (+44) [REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Research Supervisor: Lucy TROUP
University of the West of Scotland,
High Street,
Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Thank you for taking part in this study.

Appendix K: Debrief sheet study 02.

Title of Project: Imams' roles and experiences in promoting Muslims mental health:
Algeria and the United Kingdom

Ethics Approval Number: 16234

Researcher name: [REDACTED]

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

Thank you for participating in my research.

This research study is a part of my doctoral research at the University of the West of Scotland. Thank you for your valuable time. I greatly appreciate your willingness to participate in my research study and to share your thoughts about your experiences. Your contributions and responses will offer valued Information, which will be extremely useful and helpful to improve knowledge for all of us. This study has tended to provide a clear understanding of imams' mental health knowledge and collaborations with mental health services and professionals, particularly in Arab and Western countries. It also intends to investigate the role of imams in promoting mental health in Muslim communities. This study gave voice to imams who serve Muslim community in many facets and roles.

The information you will provide in the questionnaires will be held anonymously. As outlined in the information sheet, if you have any questions or comments for more clear explanation please feel free to contact me: NADIA BENGHAFFOR [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

Again, thank you so very much for your participation for your time and efforts that made this research study possible.

Contact Information:

Principal Researcher: Nadia Benghaffor

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Contact Information of Mental health services in Algeria and UK:

United Kingdom:

Samaritans: Available 24 hours a day to provide confidential emotional support for people who are experiencing feeling of distress, despair, or suicidal thoughts.

Website: www.samaritans.org

Location: 116 123 (free to call from within the UK and Ireland)

Email: [REDACTED]

Algeria (Algiers):

Cabinet Meriem Hamia Psychologue

Psychologist: Meriem Hamia

Location: [REDACTED].

Telephone Number: [REDACTED]

Website: <https://web.facebook.com/meriemhamia>

ورقة استخلاص المعلومات

شكرا لك على المشاركة في بحثي!

هذه الدراسة البحثية هي جزء من بحث الدكتوراه الذي أجرته في جامعة غرب اسكتلندا. شكرا لك على وقتك الثمين. أقدر بشدة رغبتك في مقابلي في مقابلة فردية ومشاركة أفكارك حول تجاربك. ستقدم مساهماتك وردودك معلومات قيمة ، والتي ستكون مفيدة للغاية ومفيدة لتحسين المعرفة لنا جميعًا. تميل هذه الدراسة إلى توفير فهم واضح لمعرفة الأئمة في مجال الصحة العقلية والتعاون مع خدمات الصحة النفسية والمهنيين ، لا سيما في الدول العربية والغربية. كما تعترم التحقيق في دور الأئمة في تعزيز الصحة النفسية في المجتمعات الإسلامية. أعطت هذه الدراسة صوتًا للأئمة الذين يخدمون المجتمع المسلم في العديد من الجوانب والأدوار.

سيتم الاحتفاظ بالمعلومات التي ستقدمها في الاستبيانات دون الكشف عن هويتك. كما هو موضح في ورقة المعلومات ، إذا كان لديك

أي أسئلة أو تعليقات للحصول على شرح أكثر وضوحًا ، فلا تتردد في الاتصال بي: نادية

بن غفور NADIA BENGHAFFOR

لوسي تروب LUCY TROUP

مرة أخرى ، شكرًا جزيلًا لك على مشاركتك لوقتك وجهودك التي جعلت هذه الدراسة البحثية ممكنة.

معلومات للتواصل:

الباحثة الرئيسية: نادية بن غفور

جامعة غرب اسكتلندا

هاي ستريت ، بيزلي ، PA1 2BE ، المملكة المتحدة

هاتف:

عنوان البريد الإلكتروني:

معلومات الاتصال بخدمات الصحة النفسية في الجزائر والمملكة المتحدة:

المملكة المتحدة:

Samaritans: متاح على مدار 24-ساعة في اليوم لتقديم الدعم العاطفي السري للأشخاص الذين يعانون من الشعور بالضيق أو اليأس

أو الأفكار الانتحارية.

• www.samaritans.org

• 116123 (اتصال مجاني من داخل المملكة المتحدة وأيرلندا) .

• البريد الإلكتروني:

الجزائر (الجزائر):

مجلس الوزراء مريم حمية علم النفس

أخصائية نفسية: مريم حمية

المكان: ريزيدنس الأندلس فيلا 98 الجزائر.

رقم الهاتف: 98 20 52 0559 (213 +)

الموقع: <https://web.facebook.com/meriemhami>